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IS THE NUMBER OF CITATIONS OF AN ARTICLE THE BEST WAY TO DETERMINE ITS SCIENTIFIC QUALITY

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Abstract

The exponential growth of the Internet and the availability of online and open-access journals have led to new challenges in science. In such a situation, a significant problem for research scientists is keeping up with published research due to the large number of research results, which results in only part of the literature being read and subsequently cited. Quite significant in terms of citations is the “Matthew effect,” according to which a paper with many citations will collect even more citations than, for example, a comparable similar paper with fewer or no citations (a self-propagation cycle; Ioannidis), or the “citation snowball,” because “everyone cites it” (Martin Kaon). Inexperienced and unestablished authors, seeing certain cited papers in the introductions of well-known authors, are led to think that they should cite the same papers in their introductions as some kind of unwritten convention in the field (even if they are not directly relevant).

A lack of citations does not necessarily mean that a work is of lower quality. The number of citations can be influenced by a number of factors, including the age of the article (even Nobel Prize-winning papers start with zero citations), disciplinary norms, access, co-authorship by dozens of experts in a single paper, networking and citation-trading schemes (clientelism, cronyism, non-founded colleague solidarity), self-citations, and even citations forced by reviewers.

To make citation counting more meaningful (or perhaps to hide the shortcomings of the system), modern managers and research organizations have chosen to use words such as “research quality” and “impact” to disguise the fact that it is merely the “total number of citations,” thus covertly giving these words a new, different definition when the consumer assumes the older, traditional meaning.

The numerous challenges related to this topic are, in this paper, analyzed through the prism of the undeniable facts of the rapid commercialization and instrumentalization of science, as the most subtle weapon in achieving long-term geopolitical and geo-economic interests of the most powerful actors on the global stage. The preferred epistemological matrix through which such goals are achieved is naïve positivist empiricism, which converges toward the methodological paradigm of the inductive illusion, characterized by an overemphasized use of quantitative methods.

Now, quality assessment is democratized because experts can “vote” on the quality of a paper by citing it. Previously, quality was assessed subjectively by individual scientists. Is it more optimal for the assessment of the scientific quality of a paper to remain a transparent collegial exercise of “all experts” (taking into account the weaknesses of representative-liberal democracy), or could a qualitatively new transparent procedure with objectified criteria for the presence of the immanent scientific functions and goals in a

paper – carried out by a multi-member commission of the most competent and impartial scientists, in which any possible conflict of interest or influence would be excluded – be considered more optimal instead? The answer to this extremely important research question for the development of science is given in this paper.

Key words: number of citations, scientific quality of an article

INTRODUCTION

It is considered that from the time Henry Oldenburg created the *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London* in the seventeenth century, scientists have endeavored to share the results of their research efforts with a wider audience by publishing in scientific journals (Guédon J-C, 2001). Since that time, many new journals have been founded, giving authors many options for publishing. This has been particularly significant in recent years due to the growth of the Internet and the availability of online and open-access journals (Larivière V., Gingras Y., Archambault É., 2009; Armato S., Baldock C., Orton C.G., 2015).

With such growth have come challenges. A significant issue for active research scientists is keeping up to date with published research due to the large body of research outputs, resulting in only a fraction of the literature being read and subsequently cited (Meho L.I., 2007). Due to many published papers going unnoticed or unread, many articles either never get cited or are only self-cited by their authors. When a paper is published, it has no immediate impact. However, many would contend that the number of times a paper is subsequently cited is a good indicator of its impact and therefore of the quality of the research (Biagioli M., Lippman A., 2020).

First of all, we will present the sublimated thesis of those authors who claim that the number of citations is a good way to determine the quality of certain research, as well as the counterarguments against them. So, how can one determine the quality of a quantum of research? A quantum in this case is an article published in a peer-reviewed scientific journal, supported by a constituted national or international society of scientists sharing a common interest in a particular field of endeavor.

Being published in a journal means that the manuscript has navigated the obstacle course of peer review and has been adjudged to be sound, novel, and of publishable quality by some members of the academic community. The historical gold standard for assessing published articles has been: be an expert in the field, read a hard copy, and assess it in the light of one's own expertise. Unfortunately, this method was available only to experts with access to the journal. Fortunately, science advances.

Electronic publication has provided novel, measurable ways to access research. This ability to measure is important. William Thomson stated: "When you can measure what you are speaking about, and express it in numbers, you know something about it; when you cannot express it in numbers, your knowledge is of a meagre and unsatisfactory kind" (Lord Kelvin, 1883). Citation metrics mean that the assessment of research quality has left behind the dark ages of meagre and unsatisfactory knowledge. By expressing quality as a number, we know that we know something about it.

What metrics are available to us? The "number of reads" is a measure of scientific interest. However, "number of downloads" is a better metric as it implies that the interest is sufficiently deep to require a sustained effort to understand the published work. The NoD is directly proportional to the quality of the article. Contrarily, it may be argued that some

scientists download poor-quality articles to make a point, but people soon tire of reading nonsense, and return to quality. In fact, the NoD may even underestimate interest, as PDF copies electronically sent to colleagues save them from downloading it anew.

A still better metric is the number of citations (NoC) made to published work. Scientists who cite an article are a subset of those who download it. Citing scientists have read the article, found it relevant and useful, and wish to associate their own work with it. Such scientists are themselves researchers who have the expertise to recognize important work. They are part of the community of cognoscenti, and their number can be counted. Now we can say that five scientists have noticed this work, or that fifty-five scientists approve of it. We have an improved gold standard.

The record of quality is permanent. The number of citations remains on record and increases over time, making the importance of the work more apparent. Hence, the number of citations is flexible and responsive to changes in knowledge. It is unlikely that modern-day scientists will overlook the work or that it will be forgotten, as has happened in the past. The metrification of quality allows for better metrics to be introduced. For example, the Relative Citation Ratio measures quality at the article level (Hutchins B.I., Yuan X. et al., 2016; Purkayastha A., Palmaro E. et al., 2019). This metric addresses the widely acknowledged limitations of raw citation counts by accounting for field of study and time of publication, using expected citation rates derived from all citations to contributions of the same type published in the same year in the same ISI journal.

Just as cobalt machines have been relegated to the basement by modern linear accelerators, X-ray film has been supplanted by digital radiography, CT scanning has become helical, and few medical physicists now know what a typewriter is, so too has the modern assessment of quality improved and supplanted historical methods. **The assessment of quality has been democratized because scientists can now “vote” on the quality of a manuscript by citing it.** Previously, quality was assessed subjectively by individual scientists reading the article. Now quality assessment is a transparent collegial exercise based on consensus among expert researchers, rather than the whim of individual scientists.

However, the above-mentioned thesis has opposing arguments.

The second meaningful and sublimated thesis denies the claim that the number of citations is the optimal way to determine the quality of certain research. Namely, the modern concept of citation indexing in research was introduced by Eugene Garfield in 1955, based on the earlier legal citation database *Shepard's Citations*, which dates back to 1873 (Garfield E., 1955). The purpose of a legal citation database is to ensure that precedents set in legal cases can be easily found and used in later court decisions. Garfield argued that a similar citation database for academic research could serve as a useful tool for locating earlier research so that it can be built upon, rather than rediscovered, and so that criticisms of earlier research are more readily available to inform future directions. In Garfield's paper, the term *Impact Factor* was introduced in relation to the number of citations an article or journal receives.

Garfield's argument – that the number of times a particular item, discovery, or methodology is used to build later research reflects its influence – holds true; however, simply counting all citations also includes instances in which an item has been criticized. **For example, Radicchi showed that papers criticized via comments are cited more frequently than non-commented papers and are more likely to be among the most cited within a journal** (Radicchi F., 2012). Although a paper that is commented on and

criticized is not necessarily of low quality – and criticism itself is often debunked by author responses –there are certainly cases in which criticism is valid, yet the act of criticizing a paper still contributes to its “impact” and thus its perceived “quality” through citation counts.

It has recently been shown that 74% of citations occur in the Introduction and Discussion sections of papers (Gerlach M., P-C et al., 2019). A proper introduction situates the present research within the context of recent progress and existing gaps in knowledge, while a good discussion contextualizes the results. However, when a paper is cited in an introduction or discussion, one must consider whether it genuinely informs the present research or merely follows convention. Inexperienced authors, in particular, may feel compelled to include lengthy introductions citing numerous articles simply to emulate the format of other papers. If such cited works do not directly contribute to the presented research, they effectively state only that “others have worked on something similar, but not quite the same.” Truly influential papers – those introducing new processes, procedures, or discoveries – are more likely to be cited in the methodology section, where they directly influence future work. This raises the question of whether citation metrics should be based on all citations or only the 26% that do not occur in introductions or discussions.

These arguments can be extended further through consideration of the Matthew effect (Baldock C., Schreiner L.J., Orton C., 2017), which is eloquently illustrated by Ioannidis (Ioannidis J.P.A., 2018). **In short, the Matthew effect refers to the tendency for already well-cited papers to attract even more citations than comparable papers with fewer or no citations, creating a self-propagating cycle.** Ioannidis discusses this phenomenon in relation to oversimplified research tools, but the concept can be generalized to **other contexts such as inexperienced authors who may observe frequently cited papers in introductions and assume they should cite the same works in their own papers, even when not directly relevant, thereby perpetuating the citation cycle.**

Certainly, a lack of citations does not imply that a piece of work is of lower quality. **Citation counts are influenced by numerous factors** (Tahamtan I., Afshar A.S., Ahamdzadeh K., 2016), **including the age of the article, disciplinary norms, access** (De Groote S.L., 2008), **large co-authorship teams, networking and citation-trading schemes, self-citation** (Ioannidis J.P.A., Baas J. et al., 2019), **and even reviewer-coerced citations** (Wren J.D., Valencia A., Kelso J., 2019).

Implicit in the claim that “citations are a good way to determine research quality” is the assumption that citations are appropriate and properly placed. Spurious citations can undermine reader confidence and lead to dismissal of an article. A paper cited in an introduction for reporting a novel result is not inherently less worthy of citation than one cited in a methods section for technical parameters. **However, citation snowballing – where papers are cited simply because “everyone cites them” – is recognized and dismissed by discerning researchers.**

Peer criticism is an essential mechanism for improving research quality, as it exposes shortcomings that can be avoided in future work. While a critical citation does not necessarily signal high quality, it contributes to the advancement of knowledge. Thus, lack of citation does not imply lack of quality (Armato S., Baldock C., Orton C.G., 2015). Taking into consideration all of the above mentioned, the premise of citation counting is that the total number of citations received is not the sole indicator of the quality or impact of a piece of research, regardless of whether the citation is positive, negative, or merely

included to fill in the introduction and bibliography. Citation counting is easy to measure, originating from the time when bibliometrics began, when tables of contents and bibliographies were the easiest data to analyse with the tools available at the time. To make citation counting appear more meaningful (or perhaps to hide the flaws of the system), contemporary research managers and organisations have chosen to use terms like “research quality” and “impact” to disguise the fact that it is merely a “total citation count”, thereby surreptitiously assigning new meaning to these terms while the reader assumes their older, traditional meaning. This is classic case of cognitive bias (imagine, for example, if “quality” were suddenly redefined to mean “word count”, then very long articles would be considered more important than concise ones, and important works in currently high-ranking journals with strict word limits – say, 1,500 words – would suffer).

RESEARCH, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, I believe that, in order to clarify the research question, it is necessary to examine the contemporary trend of the inductivist illusion and quantophobia in “scientific” papers with an “impact factor,” viewed through the prism of the immanent scientific functions and objectives, as well as the opposing tendency to these scientific functions and objectives, namely naïve empiricist positivism.

The measurability, comparability, and verifiability of empirical data obtained through scientifically based empirical research, which can be repeated and confirmed by other researchers, as significant parameters of modern methodology, have yielded great results in many spheres of social life. Otherwise, completely free logics (contemplations) on topics that can be measured and verified, no matter how clever they may seem, will float outside the reality available to humans if they are not verified by experience. For these reasons, **positivist empiricism and realism**, no matter how criticized they are (Kenneth N. Waltz, 2008), have a real dimension in science, but also a need for further critical development. In this regard, although especially **naïve positivist empiricism and naïve realism** are very convincingly and reasonably criticized by a few deeply conscious scientists in the world today (Alan Brayman, 2015), they not only show an unprecedented tenacity in science, but have become dogmatically prescribed patterns for scientific research. Namely, today it is almost impermissible for a certain topic to be the subject of scientific research if it cannot be measured and empirically verified. In this way, many important topics for humans, which are intangible and empirically immeasurable, remain outside the scope of scientific research, although only science can irreplaceably contribute to the greatest possible understanding of paradoxical reality and to proposing scientific approaches for its adaptation (improvement) to human needs (Scott Peck, 1995).

Namely, among most social scientists today, there is no clear determinant for the possibility of assessing the different degrees of scientific (and thus social) validity between different scientific theories and concepts which relate to a similar topic, for the same space and time, which advocate the same value goals, and whose different approaches, methods, means, and solutions – within the framework of commonly accepted moral norms and value convictions – should be the subject of scientific assessment. For certain most important value priorities in contemporary societies, there is a value consensus, as opposed to legitimate value pluralism and relativism. Thus, even in exemplary, anthological collections of knowledge (textbooks, monographs, scholarly works, etc.), most social scientists refrain from clearly articulating which ontological and epistemological currents predominantly inform their positions on the role of theory vis-à-vis research. Consequently, they do not hold a clearly articulated personal position on the question of

whether objective scientific evaluation and comparison of the scientific value of scholarly works, concepts, and theories is, for them, possible and necessary. Moreover, objective scientific evaluation and comparison should extend even between so-called “ordinary” scientific works and those that, under questionable “scientific” criteria and circumstances – considered as a general, trend-driven phenomenon rather than merely isolated incidents – are granted the status of original (source) scientific contributions with a so-called “impact factor,” published in global, highly prestigious international scientific journals indexed in the Scopus or Web of Science databases.

In this way, social scientists today, in the best cases consciously, but in most cases unconsciously, unclearly, and contradictorily, very indicatively incline toward constructionism or postmodernism in science, replacing the basic rationalist principle – objectivity – with the **subjectivist and relativistic motto of postmodernism: truth is accidental and debatable; there is no difference between bad and good art or bad and good science; all knowledge is equally valid** (Jan Art Scholte, 2008). This represents a conscious or unconscious convergence toward an unfounded relativization of scientific truth, for which some of them declaratively and quite contradictorily advocate. Otherwise, if the authors’ position is conscious, they lack a clearly formulated explanation of the arguments underlying that position. Of course, no theory or scientific conception can be absolutely true, but within their relative scientific truthfulness it can and should be determined which of the various concepts (in the above-mentioned sense) has a relatively greater degree of scientific truthfulness or validity. However, it must be said that among the most conscious social scientists today, there is a clearly expressed orientation toward the basic postulates of certain epistemological directions, with consciously accepted admixtures from other epistemologies. Thus, among rationalists there is a tendency toward reflexive rationalism (Gorz, 1988; Anthony Giddens; Ulrich Beck), while some postmodernists in science do not completely abandon rationalist postulates (Jan Art Scholte, 2008).

Contrary to the majority of social scientists – some of whom consciously, but most of whom unconsciously, given their unclear, contradictory, and unfounded relativistic understandings of determining the scientific value of certain scientific theories and concepts, incline toward ontological directions opposite to objectivism and toward non-rationalist epistemologies – although the majority of “scientists” today declaratively and contradictorily advocate rationalist epistemology in science (Mojanoski, T. C., 2015), **the author of this paper clearly defines his ontological orientation toward objectivism and his epistemological orientation toward reflective rationalism and critical empiricism, positivism, and realism.**

Rationalist epistemology, based on the principles of secularism, anthropocentrism, scientism, and instrumentalism, still represents the dominant epistemological current in conventional science worldwide, despite tendencies toward the infiltration of non-rationalist epistemologies, such as postmodernism in sociology and criminology. Otherwise, non-rationalistic epistemologies (interpretivism, constructionism, postmodernism, theological conceptions, various spiritual teachings based on relativist and ultra-skeptical philosophical conceptions, and the like) have a deep basis for their existence in philosophy, art, and religion. However, due to the lack of principles of truth, objectivity, verifiability, and comparability of theoretical hypotheses with indisputable empirical facts, non-rationalistic epistemologies cannot, at this stage of civilizational development and level of social consciousness, be practically usable in conventional science. Thus, for example, they are not practically applicable to social issues when opposing parties share

the same goal – that is, when there are no major value divergences or moral disagreements – but differ only in their approaches to finding the most optimal solutions for achieving common goal priorities within the framework of morally permissible and mutually acceptable values.

I assert this because rationalist epistemology, *inter alia*, grounds itself in the rational confrontation of arguments based on logical principles which, in the vast majority of cases, pertain to issues rooted in human empirical reality. As such, these arguments can be substantiated and verified by undisputed and adequate facts drawn from reality. In this sense, with regard to social issues for which there are no moral disagreements or differences in value convictions among opposing scientific theories or concepts (the goal being the same), it becomes possible – if one so wishes – to discern which theory (concept, thesis) currently provides the most adequate answer to the deeper layers of the endless causal interconnections of particular phenomena, processes, and relations, as well as to their externally manifesting reflections in the specific subject of research. Likewise, within this context, an opportunity emerges to identify which scientific concept proposes more optimal solutions for the substantial improvement or overcoming of certain significant social problems within a given socio-historical constellation of forces and relations in a particular society.

Theories do not determine facts, but for each group of facts, different theoretical concepts can provide different explanations. Among other factors, this issue is also related to the value dimension that the authors of various theories, depending on their philosophical or ideological-political matrix, can add to the facts. This problem is particularly pronounced in the social sciences, which, due to the nature of their subject of research, cannot be completely de-ideologized. **Hence, the author's position is that for issues for which there are diametrically opposed value approaches and consequently major moral disagreements, rationalist epistemology and its immanent rational confrontation of arguments is not applicable (has no effect).**

My personal opinion is that it is necessary to respect scientific ethics and professional standards in science so that the scientist remains as value-neutral as possible, that is, scientifically objective, taking into account that a completely (ideally) value-neutral person – and thus a scientist – does not exist (except in possibly rare examples). **Otherwise, in reality, without theories, facts exist in their “pure” substrate, free from value dimensions.** Dialectical immanence implies that even the best current theories do not explain facts once and for all. **Hence arises the well-known fact, confirmed in the history of science, that currently best theories can be replaced by even better theories if they manage to discover deeper or more significant sequences of the infinite cause-and-effect chain in the researched area during the endless discovery of reality.** In discovering that endless cause-and-effect sequence, the most successful scientists can only grasp a deeper and more significant sequence than the one discovered so far, but they can never discover and comprehend **the infinity of cause-and-effect connections of phenomena, processes, and relationships in the world we live in.** This is because human science, with its limited senses and intellectual capacity, cannot, in an absolute sense, comprehend the complete causality of the most complex processes, phenomena, and relationships in certain researched segments of nature and society, taking into account the fact that nature and society are only a small but inextricably linked part of the endless universe.

In this sense, within the framework of rationalist epistemology, we can conclude that a theory can be brought down from the top only by another, better theory, based on the logical principles of argumentation and connected to indisputable and relevant facts from reality. **This implies that there is no absolutely best theory, but only a relatively best theory, which can be displaced from the scientific top by another relatively even better theory, and so on, in the endless discovery of reality, viewed according to human standards of ground truth.** If we were to claim the opposite – that science could fully discover the causes, for example, of crime – a sufficient scientific basis would be created for finding solutions to eradicate crime. At least for now, this is an impossible task. Given the above reasons, I believe that **reflective rationalist epistemology**, within which **critical empiricist positivism and realism** can be qualitatively developed, instead of the traditions of naïve positivist empiricism and naïve realism, should represent the scientific paradigm capable of responding to the challenges of the endless human discovery of paradoxical reality. **In contrast to this paradigm are other non-rationalist epistemological directions related to ontological orientations opposite to objectivism** (Alan Brayman, 2008). Non-rationalist epistemological directions basically consider knowledge and truth to be indeterminate and disputable because they experience them as subjectively dimensioned constructions of reality. For these reasons, they deny the possibility of objective comparison of knowledge between social scientists who have researched the same or similar topics in the same period and in the same space.

In this chapter, I believe it is necessary to shed new light on the wave of the **“inductivist illusion,”** a widespread tendency worldwide, not only in the context of naïve positivist empiricism and naïve realism, but also within constructionist and postmodernist-oriented “qualitative” research, toward which sociometric methods and various qualitative techniques for collecting and analyzing empirical data are inclined. The main goal here is to demystify and dispel the inductivist illusion that only, or predominantly, through inductive methods – by examining public opinion and using the SPSS software package with mathematical and statistical data-processing techniques – scientifically relevant knowledge can be obtained. The increasingly prevalent belief that sociometric or statistical methods can significantly replace the individual author’s intellectual capacity for abstract perception and penetration into the core of complex deterministic webs of phenomena, processes, and relationships is a serious misconception.

No matter how unacceptable the cruelty of this fact may be, the truth is undeniable that only on the basis of individual authorial intellectual ability – grounded in logical methods and combined with empirical methods based on previously indisputably proven facts, as well as relevant empirical data obtained not only through **quantitative methods** but also through **truly qualitative research methods such as observation, empirically confirmed *in vivo* cases, in-depth semi-structured interviews, and the like** – can revealing insights be achieved for explaining causal relationships, conducting deeper qualitative analyses of factor intercorrelations, and finding solutions for improving or overcoming negative situations in areas that are the subject of specific scientific research.

Accordingly, the criterion for testing hypotheses – especially in the domain of the revealing and explanatory functions of science aimed at discovering and explaining causes, scientific regularities, and complex deterministic networks – can only be indisputably proven and relevant empirical facts. Such a criterion cannot be forced public opinion research.

This position directly contradicts prevailing global tendencies in the social sciences, where dogmatically unified research patterns are instrumentalized to serve long-term geo-strategic and geo-economic interests of global capital, namely the realization of extraterritorial imperialist neo-colonialism, imposed through systemically corrupt foreign policies and the proclaimed neoliberal doctrine. The connection between imposed research patterns and these goals lies in the fact that science represents a subtle paradigm through which harmonization, approximation, and even unification of economic, political, legal, and especially educational systems can be achieved. Through imposed research models, the avant-garde scientific edge capable of transcending ideological boundaries and fostering awareness of the need for qualitative change is dulled and defocused (Miodrag Labović, 2024).

From the above statements, one should not conclude that **research on the public opinion of citizens** is scientifically useless or unnecessary. On the contrary, such research is necessary and has its own meaning and goals. However, those goals have a precisely defined purpose, which is completely different from the one stated above. Research on public opinion can contribute to the measurement of certain visible social phenomena. The necessity of such research is reflected in the fact that it provides relevant data on citizens' perception, alongside complementary statistical data on the conditions in a particular area of society. Additionally, this research can indicate areas that require more attention in the future through various forms of citizen education, improving their knowledge of certain phenomena in all their dimensions, forms and types. At the same time, research on public opinion aims to raise awareness of the seriousness of the risks and threats posed by certain phenomenon and to encourage active participation in addressing them. However, **public opinion research cannot substitute for the intellectual ability of scientists to discover the deepest causes of the most complex social phenomena, which are insufficiently known even to scientists themselves, or to find solutions to the most complex and abstract social problems, which are multifaceted, have accumulated over decades and therefore cannot be solved quickly.**

For these reasons, in the modern globalized world, as never before, **science has been instrumentalized and commercialized** to an unprecedented extent, among other things especially through the imposed tendency to publish **papers with the so-called "impact factor" in prestigious international scientific journals**. I am not competent to speak about the natural, mathematical and technical-technological sciences, so this statement applies to the social sciences, which, due to the nature of their subject of research cannot be completely de-ideologized. **Otherwise, the tendency to publish papers in the most prestigious scientific journals would not be at all controversial in itself if such journals evaluated immanent scientific functions and goals and distinguished between a truly original scientific paper, a scientific review (scientific-professional) paper, and a professional paper.** Of course, it is undeniable that papers published in such journals are of high professional quality. The filters in those journals are so rigorous that the papers published there are **high-quality professional papers or high-quality scientific review papers**. However, such papers very rarely, or almost never, possess the true scientific value associated with the most immanent scientific functions and goals, such as: **scientific discovery, scientific explanation, scientific forecast, scientific prediction of system-strategic approaches for designing long-term system-stable solutions**. These immanent scientific functions and goals are today almost not valued, unlike **professional functions and goals, such as description (which remains on the surface, at the external manifest level of phenomena, without delving into the deepest**

cause-and-effect connections of phenomena, processes and relationships), theoretical criticism, theoretical-interpretative and overview function, as well as certain practically applied works aimed at better practical application of the scientific-theoretical concepts from which international legal regulation and national legislation arise (Miodrag Labović, 2024).

In addition to the above, leading international scientific journals place strong emphasis on **impeccably executed technical standards** (compliance with margins, font type, headings, subheadings, etc.), as well as on **flawless English language usage**. In fact, there is often an explicit insistence on native-level English, which entails additional costs for engaging expensive professional translators who, beyond native proficiency, must also possess impeccable command of specialized academic terminology in English. **An additional financial burden arises from the acquisition of foreign scholarly literature**, given that small and economically less developed countries have very limited online access to relevant international scientific literature databases (e-journals and e-books) compared to highly developed countries, which invest incomparably greater financial resources in subscriptions to these electronic databases. Indicative in this regard is the fact that in North Macedonia only 0.3% of GDP is allocated to scientific research activities. This is four times lower than the European average and ten times lower than in highly developed EU countries.

Also, the financial condition of a particular author plays an important role – namely, how much the author is willing to pay for the work to be “open access.” Among other things, there is an **insistence on impeccably executed citation styles** (since, literally for a missed period or comma in the literature citation, most often the work of an insufficiently popular author is eliminated from the “competition” and is not published, without prior notification to the author).

The imposed methodological paradigms of naïve empiricist positivism (which we discussed above) are not officially stated as a requirement, but are unconditionally preferred. In truth, there are a small number of prestigious international scientific journals with a limited thematic scope where these methodological patterns are not considered a priority preference. In addition to the above, most often **an extremely limiting factor is the limited number of words for a paper, which in itself is unscientific, since it is contrary to the immanent scientific functions and goals, which do not recognize any limitations or the cutting of scientific truths into pieces.**

This is contrary to the systemic scientific approach, in the context of systems theory, which, among other characteristics, advocates the interconnection (coherence and complementarity) between multiple scientific fields, with the aim of a holistic, multidimensional and multidisciplinary, in-depth understanding of the entirety of a certain complex social problem, as opposed to partial, isolated and superficial understandings, in the context of the inductive illusion of data quantophobia.

(<https://www.mkd.mk/kolumni/kvantofrenijata-za-impakt-faktorot-preku-induktivistichkata-iluzija-na-brojkite>).

The intention of such logic is as follows: the more fragmented papers an author has, the more index points he can win. In such conditions, it is quite expected that there will be nothing or very little of real science, because real science recognizes limits only to stupidity (as a cosmic category) and nothing else (Miodrag Labović, 2024).

It is not at all a coincidence that the publishing networks of the most prestigious international scientific journals are called **“citation mafias”** (<https://www.enago.com/academy/citation-cartels-the-mafia-of-scientific-publishing/>).

Namely, through the officially unimposed but subtly preferred tendency to cite mostly authors who have published papers in the top 10% best-ranked journals, for example in the Scopus database (a network of scientific journals indexed in the Social Science Citation Index), these networks constantly increase their own ratings and the ratings of the most esteemed global authors. Related to this, *Webometrics*, one of the most famous rankings in the world that measures **university ratings, values exclusively the “scientific” component of papers published in the top 10% best-ranked journals in the aforementioned Scopus database** (<https://www.webometrics.info/en/Europe/North%20Macedonia>).

Consequently, if a scientist does not publish a paper and is not cited in those journals, it is considered the same as if he had not published anything anywhere. However, an objective scientific review by impartial and competent scientists could confirm a qualitative difference in the scientific value of an “ordinary” scientific paper compared to papers with the so-called “impact factor.”

In this way, professors-“scientists,” competing for the highest possible citation rating, contribute to increasing the ratings of global scientific journals and global authors, whose ratings are constantly growing, further sinking and “cementing” the publishing capacities of international scientific journals in underdeveloped and fragile societies at the bottom. An additional contribution to this negative tendency is made by the educational authorities in underdeveloped and immature societies, which, following world trends, cannot resist the trend of global “scientific competition,” nor penetrate the essence and background of this tendency. They legally oblige universities (and the units within them), as well as individual university professors, in various ways to unconditionally adhere to the conditions of the aforementioned tendency. After all, the main criterion for election to a higher teaching-scientific title, election to a national council for science, any other scientific board or commission for science, and even to the National Academy of Sciences and Arts, is the number of citations and the number of published papers in the most prestigious international scientific journals.

Otherwise, for the sake of truth, it must be said that publishing houses in underdeveloped countries are in such an unenviable situation, among other things, because of unprincipled collegial solidarity based on clientelist reviewers and authors of the majority of low-quality papers. However, it is an empirically confirmed fact that in international scientific journals of some underdeveloped countries, as well as in the proceedings of organized international scientific conferences, some of the papers with the qualification “original scientific paper” not only deserve this qualification, but also surpass in quality and scientific value similar papers published in highly prestigious international scientific journals.

As for the issue of the **democratization of science**, that is, the possibility for all experts to “vote” by citing certain papers and thereby determine the scientific value of those papers, I will state the following. As elitist as it may sound, it is an undeniable historical truth that science has never functioned, nor will it function, under the paradox of democracy understood one-dimensionally through its immanent principle of majority decision-making (Labović, 2020). According to the founder of social psychology, **Erich Fromm, if science were based on the majority representative-democratic principle of decision-making – that is, if the value of an idea were measured by the number of votes from voters (even if these were also university professors, who, for the sake of truth, are not all scientists) – humanity would remain at the level of cave civilization** (Erich Fromm, 1984).

This is because it is an undeniable truth that almost all epochal discoveries were the work of individuals and were later shared with close collaborators (today popularly called teams). Once they are accepted by a wider circle of scientists in the field of natural sciences, the discoveries are taken over by the real economy for mass industrial production used by the broad masses of people. The same occurs in the field of social sciences; only here, ultimately, the solutions must be accepted by governments in order to begin being used to achieve generally beneficial social goals.

It is a notorious historical fact that the greatest scientific discoveries and insights in the history of humankind were not accepted by their contemporaries and the highest scientific authorities of the time. **The most creative, revolutionary and avant-garde scientific ideas in the history of scientific thought were most often not accepted by the intellectual, political and business establishments at the time of their emergence, because they did not coincide with – and in fact destroyed – existing norms, standards, values and interests.** Some scientists paid with their lives for their scientific discoveries, such as **Galileo Galilei, Nicolaus Copernicus and Giordano Bruno**, while others died in severe material poverty, with their scientific insights being recognized and implemented only long after their death. Hence, creative and **revolutionary scientific ideas** with true scientific value are **timeless and supraspatial**, which is to say, **immortal**. Within historical frameworks, they are realized or gain value at a suitable socio-historical moment, in a given constellation of social forces and relations, when social conditions mature.

CONCLUSIONS

Under conditions of intensified **commercialization and instrumentalization of science** in the service of long-term geostrategic and geoeconomic interests of global centers of power (referring exclusively to works in the social sciences, given that they cannot be fully de-ideologized), it follows that differing value-based interpretations of undisputed facts constitute a significant potential risk as a “stumbling block.” It is a fact that today virtually anyone can publish scientific papers in international journals with a so-called “impact factor,” provided they are sufficiently persistent and willing to pay. In the interest of accuracy, publishing in international journals with a so-called “impact factor” does indeed function as a filter for high-quality professional papers, less frequently for scientific review (scholarly-professional) articles, and very rarely for original scientific works with genuine scientific value.

It is also a fact that most of the most prestigious international scientific journals insist on **naïve empiricist positivism and the inductivist illusion of numbers**, in the sense that objective scientific truth can be attained exclusively or predominantly through statistical and sociometric methods. Consequently, I argue that the **quantophrenia which imposes and demands exclusive publication in journals with an “impact factor,” rather than the pursuit of scientific works that may have a genuine impact on society, represents two fundamentally different things.**

For these reasons, I believe that greater value should be accorded to the immanent scientific functions and objectives discussed above, rather than focusing solely on the quantity of published papers with an impact factor (IF) and the number of citations – which, incidentally, at least in the social sciences, depends only minimally on the intrinsic scientific quality of a given work. Instead, citation counts are influenced to a much greater extent by, inter alia, where and in which journal an author has published, and whether a

particular author has been previously promoted and popularized. Most often, the most popular authors originate from major powers – countries in which the most prestigious global scientific journals are based. These authors are frequently chief editors, directors, or among the most commonly invited contributors to publish in such journals, where precisely their works receive the highest number of citations due to prestige, even when they are subject to negative criticism. By contrast, the unpopular author who has not published in prestigious scientific journals is not only rarely cited in a positive sense, but is typically not cited even in the context of negative critique.

Today, in the spirit of pragmatism and utilitarianism, the ability to “network” within various schemes – project consortia, international program boards, editorial boards, national councils, and similar bodies – has unfortunately become far more important than intellectual capacity for abstract perception and the attainment of cutting-edge scientific knowledge, the discovery of objective regularities, the penetration of deeper and more significant causal relationships among researched phenomena, processes and relations, or the design of new scientific-theoretical concepts or scientific theories as the result of long-term and painstaking research.

In this sense, I believe that the fulfillment of immanent scientific functions and goals – such as scientific discovery, scientific explanation, scientific prediction of practically applicable and realistically sustainable long-term, systemically stable solutions – should be valued far more highly than the number of citations, the h-index, or the sheer quantity of papers published in international journals with a so-called “impact factor.”

The lack of citations does not imply a lack of quality.

A large number of citations does not inevitably indicate high quality, but it also does not imply poor quality.

The scientific value of an article should depend on the fulfillment of the most immanent scientific functions and goals, such as scientific discovery, scientific explanation, scientific prognosis, and a systemically strategic projection of long-term, systemically stable solutions, in addition to expert functions such as description, theoretical critique, theoretically interpretive functions, and practical applicability.

These immanent scientific criteria gain particular importance in the contemporary digital era of AI, given the existence of numerous websites that offer finished articles prepared for the most prestigious international scientific journals with high “impact factor” values indexed in the Scopus or Web of Science databases.

The scientific quality of an article should be evaluated within an international open competition (a publicly announced scientific award or tender) by an Advisory Assessment Board composed of the most competent, impartial and independent scientists from all continents, within the relevant field. Any potential conflict of interest or commercial influence should be excluded.

A supervisory High-Level Committee is necessary in cases where a scientist believes that objective and precise criteria have not been respected and where there is no structural explanation in the decision regarding the ranking of individual applicants in the international open competition.

The number of citations and the number of papers published in the most prestigious international scientific journals cannot be the main criterion for promotion to higher teaching-scientific titles, selection to national science councils, other scientific boards or commissions, or membership in National Academies of Sciences and Arts.

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ORGANIZED CORRUPTION: ANALYSING THE NEXUS

Uglješa Ugi Zvekić¹

INTRODUCTION²

Corruption is one of the main challenges to the rule of law, life chances and people's livelihoods in the Western Balkans. It is both a cause and consequence of a criminal culture that permeates the region, and the way that corruption is linked to politics suggests a degree of organized corruption, and even elements of state capture, in a number of countries in the region. Typical manifestations of high-level organized corruption in the six countries of the Western Balkans (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia) are Wild West-style selling and buying of public property by political elites and their associates in the business and criminal spheres; corrupt tendering for infrastructure projects (such as construction of roads); inside deals struck with loyal partners, either for procurement or privatization processes; concealment of ownership; fraud and embezzlement of public funds; non-disclosure (or false disclosure) of assets; money laundering (both locally and offshore); and abuse of public office.

The systemic threat posed by corruption in the region is also evident when individuals or entities finance political parties in return for favours. These include undeclared sources of funding; the buying of political support by handing out gifts and favours; and using public funds, and appointments in the civil service or state-owned enterprises as tools to build a patronage network of political dependency. In this way, political, business and criminal elites collude to preserve and protect their interests and influence over public functions and resources. These practices create a fertile environment for corrupt officials to operate with impunity. Despite the severity of the problem, society in the region seems to have become inured to the reality of high-level state corruption. There is a pervasive sense that this is just the way things are and the system cannot be changed. This learned helplessness is perpetuated by a lack of independence or professional capacity within institutions whose role it is to tackle corruption. There are few convictions in high-profile cases of organized corruption yet draconian restrictions

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² Based on:

Uglješa Ugi Zvekić and Sunčana Roksandić, *Infrastructure of Integrity; Political Economy of Corruption and Anti-Corruption in the Western Balkans*, Global Initiative against Transnational Organized Crime, Geneva/Vienna March 2021.

Uglješa Ugi Zvekić, Sunčana Roksandić, Bojan Dobovšek, *Organized Corruption: Political Financing in the Western Balkans*, Global Initiative against Transnational Organized Crime, Geneva/Vienna, June 2023.

imposed by the authorities on the media, including threats and sanctions against those who speak against political abuses, politically and business linked organized crime and high-level organized corruption.

There are two dominant types of corruption:

Conventional corruption, bribery and nepotism are culturally well entrenched and often go hand in hand with malfunctioning public administration.

Organized Corruption is the involvement and/or use of an interest organization, criminal or not, in various forms of corruption and related illicit deeds from the position of power and/or with political coverage to gain financial, political or social benefits. Organized corruption rests on the interwoven criminal, political and economic interests to profit from the power position and political coverage of illicit deeds.³ Key types of organized corruption in the Western Balkans include:

ILLUSTRATIONS OF ORGANIZED CORRUPTION

Political financing – political parties and elections

Control over and abuse of public (state-owned) enterprises

Misuse and control over public procurements

As WB 6 countries seek to promote and safeguard the transparent, responsible and accountable financing of political parties and elections, as well as the management of SOEs and public procurement, it is possible to summarize the main challenges they face regarding their legislative frameworks, their compatibility with international – and in particular EU – standard guidelines and protocols, and the institutional architecture of oversight and control.

Legislation

All six countries in the Western Balkans have legislation regulating the financing of political parties and elections. However, there are consistent shortcomings in terms of implementation, even after recommendations have been made by European institutions such as the Council of Europe and the OSCE. Even WB6 countries that have laws in line with European and international standards sometimes fail to live up to them due to insufficient oversight from relevant bodies or regulatory agencies, many of which lack independence. Poor integrity and rather high levels of corruption within each Western Balkan country detract from achieving international standards in the financing of political parties and elections.

Internal oversight and accountability for finances within political parties themselves need to be strengthened. Loopholes detected within each jurisdiction seem to show a lack of understanding or willingness to provide transparency in bookkeeping in relation to the financing of political parties and elections. Each national report demonstrates how political parties made use of loopholes and how provisions were

³ In purpose for deeper scientific consideration of the practical consequences from the complexity of high-level institutional type of organized corruption see: Miodrag Labovic: Policing in Central and Eastern Europe – Social Control of Unconventional Deviance, Conference Proceedings, Social control of institutional organized crime, 2011, <https://www.ncjrs.gov/pdffiles1/nij/Mesko/235122.pdf>, pp.194 -208

misused or ignored in practice in order to achieve more support and seats in government. The lack of appropriate oversight or sanctioning, even when irregularities are discovered, does not help achieve international standards or the implementation of satisfactory provisions. Case law usually shows harsher punishments for parties that no longer hold power. Although the legislative arena regarding public enterprises looks relatively well developed, it still suffers from notable shortcomings, particularly when it comes to the implementation and application of effective and independent oversight and control bodies and the selection of the best professionals for roles within SOEs.

One common shortcoming is the political appointment of key managers and other employees within an SOE, which often seems based more on political allegiance than skill. Another is the lack of respect for the findings of control and oversight bodies and the subsequent implementation of remedies to improve the situation. Yet another notable deficiency concerns the almost complete lack of transparency in relation to operations, appointments and the reporting of results. Similarly, there is also a lack of public accountability, including, in some instances, limited access to data; in some countries, there are not even accurate accounts of the number and sectoral distribution of SOEs.

In each of the WB6 countries, public procurement is exposed to corruption. Considerable efforts have been undertaken to align legislation with EU law in an expression of political willingness and the desire to be seen as seriously devoted to the values and expectations of the EU and UN. The alignment of laws on public procurement with EU standards is still an ongoing process in the Western Balkans.

Most countries established their relevant legislative frameworks in the initial years of the 2000s, and all countries have since passed amendments aimed at improving transparency and integrity and reducing risks of corruption.

However, the legislative route has not always been unidirectional towards reducing corruption opportunities related to public procurement. For example, as noted earlier, Serbia's legal framework obliged the Public Procurement Office to appoint a representative of a civil society organization, an academic or an expert knowledgeable in public procurement as a civic observer in all public procurement procedures over €8.5 million. The civil observer reported directly to the Parliamentary Committee on Finances. However, in the last revision of the legislation, and through the adoption of the current Law on Public Procurement in 2019, this institute and obligation were removed from Serbian legislation. Moreover, in a number of laws, convenient legal windows – or loopholes – were introduced. There is a need for further in-depth 'corruption proofing' of public procurement related legislation.

Control and oversight

When it comes to political party financing, control and inspection are performed by CECs in Albania, BiH and Kosovo. In Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia, this task is performed by agencies or commissions for the prevention of corruption, as well as by state audit offices. WB6 countries have adopted new laws and a number of controls based on EU recommendations, but implementation is lagging. The constitutional set-up of BiH (three entities and cantons in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina) poses a special complication, with inconsistent legislation and a lack of supervision and competence of behalf of the CEC. Supervision is more successful during election campaigns at all levels, but the pre-election period and control over media advertising still pose problems. Albania has implemented the latest legislation with a three-tiered approach,

which appears to be an interesting control model. ⁴Civil society's role as an oversight actor is very important throughout the Western Balkans and needs to be further enhanced and institutionalized, particularly in view of the influence of political parties over other control institutions.

Transparency is lacking, and SOEs are rarely held accountable. In North Macedonia, for example, although the Law on Public Enterprises and the Company Law oblige SOEs to submit quarterly financial reports to the government and publish them on their official websites, the enterprises rarely release these reports to the public. The Law on Free Access to Information of Public Importance in Serbia aims to strengthen transparency in this regard. Nevertheless, it has been reported that since the law's adoption, SOEs have been ignoring most information requests, even to the extent of ignoring requests submitted by the Commissioner for Information of Public Importance. Almost identical problems plague public procurement.

Implementation

Most legislation is generally in line with international standards, but there are marked problems with the implementation of laws. There are therefore a number of loopholes in the legislation that need to be addressed. Too often, political parties deliberately bypass the law to promote their own financial interests and impact election results and power-based decision-making. In such situations, the role of control and oversight mechanisms is of utmost importance, although they cannot alone impose and safeguard transparency, responsibility and accountability. Many of the control structures are themselves politicized and therefore no longer impartial; some are not independent or lack sufficient financial support and capacity to carry out their functions.

Control over political financing must necessarily deal with corruption and money laundering, yet most of the control structures and procedures related to the political financing of parties and elections are rather limited. Both political parties and the people that run them are potentially corrupt, and there is evidence that much of the money in politics flows through private pockets rather than party treasuries. Treating the financing of political parties as separate from the control of political officials' property and of public contracting, especially public procurement leaves any system of control invalid and consequently inefficient. Inefficient control mechanisms, prosecutions and courts add impunity to the failure of anti-corruption measures in the financing of political parties.

There is ample evidence of increased spending on social media advertising, particularly on Facebook, in all recent electoral campaigns, yet many relevant pieces of legislation lack references to sponsoring political campaigns on social media. There are also numerous examples of media being misused in political campaigns. Some electoral lists delayed reporting their advertisements as political, thereby avoiding making the details of such advertising public. Some election participants reported lower than actual costs for field campaigns and the production of promotional videos. Some media outlets discounts to certain political parties or provided services that were not defined in their

⁴ About deeper structural reforms in 9 crucial systems and 50 subsystems for effective fight against systemically endemic and institutional organized corruption in North Macedonia and similar countries in WB, see in: Миодраг Лабовиќ, "Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организирианиот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава", Култура Скопје, 2024, стр. 281-562

price lists, while others broadcast political marketing without having submitted price lists by the legally defined deadline.

Electoral marketing campaigns often consist, in part, of opening or initiating public infrastructure works, such as roads, bridges, railways, high-speed trains, shopping centres or factories, which are financed from the state budget but are functionalized to achieve an electoral advantage for the parties in power. Similarly, as the state is still the biggest employer in Western Balkan countries, public administration employees are often asked to attend the governing party's political rallies; transport, food, drinks and even per diems are sometimes provided, either at the expense of the enterprises or the donors. In some countries, an increase or the promise of an increase in pensions or other social welfare entitlements has become an integral part of electoral campaigns.

Public opinion survey companies can greatly influence public preferences in electoral campaigns. Some political parties have their own survey companies, while others contract specialized opinion survey companies. The financing of such activities and the specific favourable targeting of the results need particular scrutiny. Considering the wide use and impact of social media and surveys, this is an area of urgent and increased concern.

All country reports noted the need to reform the political financial reporting system into a transparent, interactive, user-friendly and easy-to-monitor electronic system. Thus, the creation of online platforms to host all the data so that it could be found and easily monitored and analysed would be of great help. Online political finance reporting and disclosure systems are part of broader transparency efforts to make official data more available and accessible to the public, and they contribute to efforts to increase the capacity and professionalism of candidates and political parties. As such, they are important modern technological tools to strengthen the political financing information database and allow systematic and transparent control and oversight.

The influence of organized crime on politics in WB6 countries has been addressed in a previous series of GI-TOC reports, *Infrastructure of Integrity*, but it is worth underlining that the impact during elections has become more sophisticated. Often, hidden support is provided to political parties by placing organized crime associates from certain professions or families on the electorate. In some cases, members of organized crime or hooligan groups have been used to maintain order and discipline among political supporters or at protest demonstrations for political parties or movements. The financing of political parties and elections is still subject to corruption and organized crime, which is becoming more intricate and difficult to trace.

The financing of political parties in all WB6 countries is regulated by law and distinguishes between government budgetary financing at the state, regional and municipality levels. Other financing in some countries, mainly B and H, Serbia and Kosovo, also comes in the form of membership fees, donations, income from property and events, inheritances, legacies and bank loans. The maximum funding that a political entity can collect from private sources depends on various parameters. According to available data, countries are harmonizing legislation with EU standards, but implementation is problematic. In principle, budgetary funding is not a problem, except for parties that do not reach the funding threshold and have non-parliamentary party status. Financing from private funds, especially donations, is more ambiguous and problematic as it allows for more creativity and concealment of funds and cash flows. Prohibitions on funding from international individuals, foreign legal entities, political parties and NGOs are a grey area.

Sanctions are also problematic in the analysed countries, as they are mostly only monetary and have no political effect.

When it comes to the implementation of legislative provisions, several shortcomings and deficiencies are noted. Many contracts are awarded not on the basis of merit but rather on the basis of political affiliation. In all the Western Balkan countries, public procurement systems face multiple deficiencies, and these are in line with those identified by national audit offices, such as the National Audit Office of Kosovo, in their annual auditing reports. These deficiencies include the conclusion of contracts without committed funds; extensive and complex conditions; a lack of open procurement procedures; the adoption of criteria that favour certain operators; the biased evaluation of tenders; the conclusion of contracts with abnormally high prices; a lack of qualified personnel at contracting authorities and economic operators; insufficient time to prepare offers; and major corruption risks in emergency procurement systems.

Management and employment opportunities

Public SOEs are some of the largest employers. But in contrast to the private sector, public SOEs are subject to the vulnerabilities of markets and political and economic fluctuations. The relatively secure employment provided by SOEs is attractive for ordinary people, offering a degree of job security not often seen since the fall of socialist regimes. In exchange, loyalty to the job provider – a political party and its leadership – is an unwritten but well-established contractual clause. This is one of the most powerful and efficient methods of securing unquestionable loyalty and permanence in power; it is also one of the most sustainable ways of buying social peace and assuring political trust. As a result, SOEs are the ‘election prey’ and ‘ATMs’ of ruling parties. Influence and control over public procurement is a part of the corrupt mainstream political culture, as well as of organized corruption. The majority of public enterprise leaders are politically appointed and, more often than not, also politically dismissed. The middle management line is often politically dependent, as well; if not appointed, they are at least required to demonstrate political loyalty in order to keep their jobs. Commonly, the management and decision-making processes of SOEs are influenced by political factors and interests, rather than the pursuit of market, business or marketing strategies. Allegedly, the control and management bodies of SOEs, and specifically their senior members, are commonly appointed by the parties in power via executive power instruments. The construction sector in the Western Balkans is vulnerable to corruption, with public procurement used for political control. Even at lower levels, jobs are often given to people who are loyal to the ruling party. Electoral promises of providing good jobs are often realized via SOEs, and, as big employers, SOEs provide a very solid voter base. This has evidently led to the creation of nests for party employment. Furthermore, these enterprises, which are largely aligned with ruling political parties, provide a competitive advantage for these parties by engaging in corrupt activities and allowing their resources to be used to finance pre-election activities and political campaigns.

This is also a part of corrupt mainstream political culture. Many SOEs are often taking huge losses and are in significant debt – in one country up to 3% of annual GDP, for example. This is well-recognized and reported by state audits and various financial oversight mechanisms, but action is seldom taken against the management. Even when the parties in power change over after an election, they just inherit the state of affairs and, at best, pack posts in upper and middle management with their own political cronies. SOEs are an excellent illustration of the corrupt management and political culture in which

governmental control and oversight bodies are not respected. This applies even to those bodies that are configured to the interests of the political parties in power. Seldom is any judicial action taken against top level management or board members. Therefore, there is a high level of overall impunity: culturally, politically, financially, administratively and judicially.

Some organizational and operational problems that SOEs commonly face across the WB6 are: the signing of unfavourable contracts; problems with liquidity; over-employment, in some cases with overly favourable salaries heavily influenced by politics and nepotism; the duplication of positions; and irregular promotions. Nepotism and political appointments ensure informal access to public resources. Even control and oversight institutions often lack the political independence resources and staff needed to carry out their functions properly. Furthermore, there are no sufficient conflict of interest checks. Often many provisions are not made public, and so proper monitoring is absent or is carried out sporadically. Moreover, decisions and recommendations are at times not implemented. Seldom are judicial actions undertaken to remedy such situations. The absence of proper public procurement planning and strategy is well-noted and was particularly evident during the COVID-19 crisis. The pandemic presented an unprecedented opportunity for corrupt actors and simultaneously highlighted important gaps in the legislation of Western Balkan countries regarding public procurement in states of emergency. States of emergency lead to expedited negotiations and the conclusion of contracts without transparent, fair or competitive public processes. Moreover, the lack of clearly defined criteria in the procurement process results in tangible consequences, as in North Macedonia, where protective equipment and other similar use products were released with considerable discrepancies. Exemptions from regular procedure and the absence of reporting indicate the extent to which the public procurement system is vulnerable to corruption.

There are many examples of improper public procurement management wherein the tender value was known to the bidders so that their bids almost ideally fit the offers. This is particularly noted at the local administration level and in PPP arrangements. Similarly, in some countries, it is not uncommon for the number of bidders to be low and for similar bidders to win public contracts. For example, in Montenegro in 2021, procurement contracts worth approximate €335 million were signed, one fifth of which were concluded based on the submission of a single offer. It appears that there are instances of almost monopolistic positions in terms of tender bidders and winners, indicating the existence of particularly privileged political positions and patronage. On the other hand, favouring certain foreign investors is part of the procurement strategy and planning in some WB6 countries. Therefore, political investment choices in public procurement may be both an instrument of foreign policy and a way of bolstering wealth and power.

All in all, the public procurement sector is highly politicized and often used for political control of the public economy and favouritism of selected private or foreign partners. In the Western Balkan countries, public procurement stands as a good example of organized corruption and political influence and control over public financial instruments and economy. It is an important part of the prevalent pattern of the ruling establishment.

SELECTED EMPIRICAL INDICATORS of ORGANIZED CORRUPTION

The [Global Organized Crime Index](#) is a multi-dimensional tool that assesses the level of criminality and resilience to organized crime for 193 countries along three key pillars – criminal markets, criminal actors, and resilience. Developed over a two-year period, the Index draws from both quantitative and qualitative sources and is underpinned by over 350 expert assessments and evaluations by the GI-TOC’s regional observatories. The objective of the Index is to provide metrics-based information that would allow policymakers and continental and regional bodies to prioritize their interventions on the basis of a holistic assessment of where vulnerabilities lie and equip them with the means to measure the efficacy of their responses to mitigate the impact of organized crime. The Global Organized Crime Index 2023 reveals the continuing rise of organized crime globally, with 83% of the world’s population living in conditions of high criminality. Conversely, the number of people living in conditions of low resilience to organized crime globally has declined significantly: now, 62% of the world’s population, compared to 79.4% in 2021.

State actors remain the most dominant agents in facilitating illicit economies and inhibiting resilience. State-embedded actors remained the most pervasive criminal actor type in 2022. While the degree to which criminality permeates the state apparatus varies across countries and, at all levels, state engagement and/or facilitation of organized crime has grown, with the Index finding human trafficking, arms trafficking and non-renewable resource crimes to have been the most affected. Corruption creates opportunities for illicit activities to thrive, as criminal groups are enabled to operate with reduced risks, while criminal infiltration of state institutions undermines countries’ ability to build resilience and effectively shape policies to counter organized crime.⁵

⁵ Broader consideration about state embedded actors, their role and practical consequences that lead to paradox of „legal state“ see in: Миодраг Лабовиќ, “Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организираниот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава“, Култура Скопје, 2024, стр. 195-225

CRIMINAL ACTORS

“
State-embedded actors remain the most dominant criminal actor type

Indeed, one of the strongest correlations found among the Index results is between state-embedded actors and overall resilience (-0.79). What this negative correlation suggests is that, as state-embedded actors grow in prominence in a particular area, levels of resilience decline.

The most authoritative international measurement of corruption is the Transparency International Corruption Perception Index which has quite a long history of 30 years. It started in 1995. It is measuring perception of corruption in some 180 countries all over the world each year last index refers to 2024 and it can be noted that the least vulnerable countries to corruption as perceived by the citizens our countries of Western Europe and European Union while the countries of Eastern Europe score on average 35 out of a hundred points and they are third in terms of the vulnerability to corruption within the eastern and central Europe.

As regards the Balkan peninsula and this can be seen from the table below there are differences between south-eastern European countries that are members of the European Union and those that are not the members of the European Union. For example Greece and Romania have a score of 46 points while Bulgaria has lowest score of 43 points. As regards the Western Balkan countries, the best ranked is Montenegro followed by Kosovo and Albania while Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia are not so well placed. It should be noted for example that while the score of Albania and Kosovo have increased over the past five years in terms of the perception of corruption. It was not the case with Serbia which has moved downwards meaning that citizens have perceived that the situation with corruption in Serbia in the last five years has deteriorated.

Country / Territory	CPI 2024 score	Rank
Albania	42	80
Bosnia and Herzegovina	33	114
Bulgaria	43	76
Greece	49	59
Kosovo	44	73
Montenegro	46	65
North Macedonia	40	88
Romania	46	65
Serbia	35	105

The criminal markets index for the south-eastern European countries shows that Serbia, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Romania, and Montenegro are above the average criminal market scores on the global level while North Macedonia, Albania, Kosovo, and Greece a little bit lower. On the other hand, the criminal actor scores for Serbia, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Greece, Bulgaria and Albania are above the global average while the score for North Macedonia is a bit lower.

However, looking at the criminal actor types, it is very clear that the state embedded actors are predominant in Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Greece but as well as North Macedonia, in Albania, Kosovo, and a bit less in Romania. It can be also noted that criminal networks and private sector as criminal actors are very much present in all the Western Balkan countries as well as in Greece and Bulgaria.

CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

No law is implemented on its own, and there is no law that cannot be bypassed. A culture of integrity and lawfulness is vital for good governance. The Western Balkan countries are still in search of such a political culture of integrity. Overall, the WB6 countries have made real progress towards regulating and controlling the financing of political parties and elections, SOEs and public procurement. The role of the international community, including the donor community, in providing guidelines and standards and periodic reviews has increased the compatibility of legislation with European and international standards. However, changes to the laws have not been sufficiently internalized in the political culture to make parties transparent, accountable and responsible servants for society or the state. This is the urgent task for all the actors – political parties, governments, parliaments and civil society members – in the promotion of a political culture of integrity.

Yet there is no ample mandate for the control institutions in the Western Balkans to enable a comprehensive approach. Instead, as is the case in other areas, they are very narrow, fragmented and bureaucratically squeezed. Coordination and cooperation with other control structures is clearly absent. Oversight is not only a matter for the control institutions, but also for civil society: NGOs, academics, investigative journalists and the media. Such a role for civil society in the Western Balkans is well recognized, and there are many examples of civil society publicly reporting, denouncing and protesting against political abuses and illicit financing. Yet there is no appreciation for such a role. Even in

some electoral control processes, there is no parity between the representatives of the political parties concerned and the civil observers. Moreover, the role of parliaments in exercising an oversight function is very marginal in the Western Balkans. This is a huge obstacle to promoting institutional accountability. A political culture of integrity requires the institutionalization of civil society's oversight role.

As noted earlier the notion of organized corruption points out to a nexus between organized crime and corruption. Indeed, corruption enables and is enabled by organized crime and corruption is both a driver of organized crime and a barrier to resilience. This nexus is partially recognised both by the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC), which treats corruption as one of its criminal offences, and by the United Nations Convention against Corruption (UNCAC), which states that corruption allows organized crime, terrorism, and other threats to human security to flourish.

Organized corruption refers to the involvement in or use of various forms of corruption and related activities by an interest organization, criminal or not, which profits from its position of power and/or political coverage to gain financial, political or social benefits. Organized corruption can be manifested on a high level with the involvement of the top management of the government and political parties and the control of the public state-owned enterprises party and elections financing and marketing. It can be involved in the mezzo-sphere which is typical for the relationship between political structures and the private economic sector as, for example, in the procurement. Finally, nexus is clearly present in the underground through the typical involvement of organized crime through the legalization of illicit profits – there, corruption is one of the main vehicles for such organized endeavour.

Changing such a state of affairs requires deep reforms. Yet these reforms are not possible as long as the SOEs and much of the public procurement processes are under complete control of the political parties in power and considered to be electoral prey. Furthermore, the manner in which political parties seek to obtain funds and maintain power through control of economic and employment opportunities is a matter for society as a whole. It is a call to arms for the democratic values of transparency and, above all, honesty and devotion to the state. Therefore, in all WB6 countries, a change in the political culture is needed, and organized corruption must be dismantled as a prevalent pattern of the ruling establishment.

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INTERNAL CORRUPTION AS A MECHANISM OF HYBRID OCCUPATION: STRATEGIC DIMENSIONS OF STATE CAPTURE

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Abstract

In the evolving landscape of global instability, hybrid threats increasingly employ non-kinetic and covert mechanisms to undermine state sovereignty. This paper conceptualizes systemic internal corruption as the primary operational tool of hybrid occupation, functioning not merely as a governance failure but as an embedded mechanism of political control. Unlike conventional occupations imposed by foreign military force, this apex form of “occupation without occupiers” relies on co-optation, collusion, and legal erosion to enable external or domestic actors to dominate national decision-making structures while maintaining formal sovereignty.

Building on the author’s previous research, the study frames systemic corruption as a mechanism of hybrid warfare aimed at capturing the five critical rings of state functionality-political leadership, economy, infrastructure, population, and information-adapting Warden’s strategic model. It introduces the Internal Occupation Risk Index (IORI), a weighted, multi-domain analytical tool designed to identify and grade the intensity of internal occupation through long-term trend analysis. The model integrates measurable indicators across governance, economic performance, infrastructure management, societal resilience, and informational control, visualized through radar charts and heat maps.

Findings indicate that corruption-driven internal occupation erodes democratic resilience, strategic autonomy, and national security, creating long-term structural dependencies. Furthermore, the synergistic role of strategic communication, media capture, and public opinion manipulation sustains such governance systems by suppressing opposition and legitimizing corrupt practices.

The proposed model provides policymakers and researchers with a practical framework for early warning, risk assessment, and the development of integrated countermeasures. By recognizing internal occupation as a top-tier hybrid threat, this study underscores that defending sovereignty in the 21st century requires not only protecting borders but also reinforcing institutions against corruption-based strategic subversion.

Keywords: hybrid occupation, internal occupation, systemic corruption, state capture, Internal Occupation Risk Index (IORI)

1. INTRODUCTION

The contemporary international order is characterized by the growing hybridity of the security environment, wherein the boundaries between war and peace, as well as between external and internal threats, have become increasingly fluid and strategically instrumentalized (Ejdus, 2017; Hoffman, 2007; NATO Foundation, 2025). The development of information technologies, the globalization of economic flows, and the intense interdependence of political systems have created conditions in which strategic objectives can be achieved without the use of conventional military means, through continuous, multidimensional, and legally difficult-to-prove actions (OECD, 2024; Europol, 2025).

In such a world, national security can no longer be viewed solely through the prism of external, kinetic threats such as armed aggression or direct political pressure. Increasing importance is assumed by internal processes of sovereignty erosion, which often evolve in collusion between domestic actors and foreign centers of power, thereby nullifying the traditional dichotomy between internal and external security challenges (UNCAC Coalition, 2024; NYU CIC, 2024).

One of the most serious processes of this kind is the phenomenon of internal occupation—a condition in which the domestic political, economic, and security elite, often through networks of systemic corruption, clientelism, and political co-optation, take over the key functions of the state and use them against the public interest (Karklins, 2005; Chayes, 2015; Mitrović, 2025). Unlike classical occupation, which entails open and internationally recognized control by a foreign power, internal occupation is covert, unfolds within the framework of formal sovereignty, and is often legitimized by democratic procedures, further complicating its legal, political, and security response (David-Barrett, 2023; CSD, 2024).

The implications of this phenomenon transcend national borders. A captured state, as a result of internal occupation, not only loses the capacity to protect its citizens and strategic interests but also becomes a vulnerable channel for the penetration of foreign influence into the broader international system, thereby undermining regional stability, international norms, and mechanisms of collective security (Milutinović, 2025; Transparency International, 2024). Such conditions increase the risk of regional destabilization, fuel transnational organized crime, erode trust in international institutions, and create long-term strategic dependencies (Petrovic, 2024).

Considering the hybridity of the contemporary world, corruption, clientelism, and state capture must therefore be addressed not only as developmental or moral issues but as key threats to national and international security, comparable in gravity to external aggression (OECD, 2024; NATO Foundation, 2025). This approach requires a theoretical redefinition of the concept of occupation and the development of integrated strategies that connect the state's internal resilience with global security architectures and international legal frameworks.

2. THE CONCEPT OF OCCUPATION AND ITS KEY CHARACTERISTICS

In international law, the concept of occupation has traditionally been defined through the provisions of the 1907 Hague Regulations (Hague Convention IV) and the Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949. According to Article 42 of the Hague Regulations, an occupation exists when the territory of a state is placed "under the effective authority of the hostile army," and such authority has been established. It can be exercised (Dinstein,

2009). This normative framework assumes that occupation is externally imposed, based on military presence, and maintained by armed force.

Historical experience, however, demonstrates that occupation can take various forms—from open military control, through proxy regimes established by a foreign power, to temporary international administration (Roberts, 1984; Benvenisti, 2012). In all these cases, two fundamental characteristics are shared: (1) effective control over the territory and its population by an entity that is not its legitimate sovereign; and (2) the ability to impose political, legal, and administrative authority.

Based on legal doctrine and empirical studies (Bellal, 2018; Sassòli, 2019), the key characteristics of traditional occupation can be identified as:

Effective control – the presence and adequate power of the occupying force over the territory;

Displacement of sovereignty – the temporary removal or limitation of sovereign functions from the legitimate authority;

Administrative intervention – the establishment of an occupational administration or governing regime;

Temporary character – formally, occupation does not change the status of the territory, but in practice, it may lead to annexation or permanent alteration of the political order;

Constraints under international law – the obligation to respect the Geneva Conventions, protect civilians, and prohibit annexation by force.

The last two decades have seen the emergence of so-called non-kinetic or hybrid forms of occupation, where effective control does not necessarily rely on military presence (Kaldor, 2012; Hoffman, 2007; NATO Foundation, 2025). Instead of tanks and soldiers, control is exercised through political co-optation, economic dependency, legal pressure, information operations, and state capture (Chayes, 2015; David-Barrett, 2023). These processes can be just as effective in displacing sovereignty as classical military occupation, but are far more challenging to prove and address legally (OECD, 2024; UNCAC Coalition, 2024).

The phenomenon of internal occupation represents a specific subtype within this expanded concept, where domestic actors—political elites, economic oligarchs, or security structures—assume effective control over the key functions of the state, often in collusion with external patrons (Mitrović, 2025; Petrovic, 2024). Unlike traditional occupation, there is no visible foreign military presence; instead, the process unfolds within the framework of formal sovereignty. The key characteristics of internal occupation include:

Capture of political decision-making through systemic corruption and institutional co-optation;

Economic conditioning through controlled concessions, monopolies, and credit dependency;

Erosion of institutional autonomy in the judiciary, police, and regulatory bodies;

Informational dominance through media control, propaganda, and disinformation;

A legitimating framework based on formal democratic procedures that are often abused in practice.

In theoretical terms, internal occupation highlights the need to redefine the concept of "occupation" in security studies to include forms of effective control achieved by non-military means, particularly when their purpose and effects lead to the permanent undermining of state sovereignty and the security of the international order.

2.1. Comparative Analysis: External and Internal Occupation – Overlapping Zones

Although external (conventional) and internal (non-conventional) occupation differ in terms of actors, means, and formal status under international law, analysis shows significant zones of overlap in the effects they produce on the state system. These zones suggest that the consequences of internal occupation can be assessed using the same parameters as those of external occupation, thereby justifying their joint consideration in security studies.

Alienation of Governance

External occupation: Administrative structures are placed under the direct control of the occupying power, with loyal administrators or military governors appointed (Benvenisti, 2012).

Internal occupation: The state administration formally operates within the sovereign order but is effectively controlled by a narrow politico-economic elite acting against the public interest (Mitrović, 2025; Karklins, 2005).

Overlap zone: In both cases, the administrative apparatus ceases to serve the common good and becomes an instrument for advancing the interests of the ruling structure, whether that be a foreign power or a corrupt domestic elite.

Alienation of Resource Management

External occupation: Systematic exploitation of the natural, economic, and infrastructural resources of the occupied territory for the benefit of the occupier (Roberts, 1984).

Internal occupation: Non-transparent concessions, corrupt privatizations, and monopolization of strategic sectors for personal or group gain, often with foreign assistance (Transparency International, 2024; OECD, 2024).

Overlap zone: Resources are diverted from public needs to serve the interests of the controlling structure, undermining economic sovereignty and long-term sustainability.

Alienation of Public Administration

External occupation: Public services and institutions are often used to implement the occupier's policy, which is frequently contrary to the needs and will of the local population (Dinstein, 2009).

Internal occupation: Public administration becomes a clientelist system based on political loyalty rather than meritocracy, with selective access to public goods (Petrovic, 2024).

Overlap zone: Both forms generate institutional inefficiency, reduced accessibility of public services, and erosion of citizens' trust in the state.

Alienation of Foreign Policy Decision-Making

External occupation: Foreign policy is shaped exclusively according to the interests of the power controlling the territory, with no regard for local interests or consensus.

Internal occupation: Foreign policy is formally adopted by sovereign institutions but is effectively driven by the interests of a narrow elite and foreign sponsors, often without public debate or parliamentary oversight (UNCAC Coalition, 2024; NYU CIC, 2024).

Overlap zone: Decisions on international agreements, security arrangements, or economic partnerships are made outside inclusive processes and often contrary to long-term national interests.

Control of the Information Space

External occupation: Direct censorship, propaganda campaigns, and media control by the occupier (Bellal, 2018).

Internal occupation: Media landscape captured through ownership structures, state subsidies, and controlled distribution of advertising (Chayes, 2015).

Overlap zone: Monopolization of public discourse to legitimize authority and delegitimize opposition and critical voices.

Instrumentalization of the Judiciary

External occupation: Appointment and control of judges and prosecutors to implement the occupier’s policies (Benvenisti, 2012).

Internal occupation: The politicization and corruption of the judiciary, with the instrumentalization of law to target opponents and protect loyal actors (David-Barrett, 2023).

Overlap zone: Loss of judicial independence and transformation of the judiciary into an instrument of political control.

Table 1. Overlapping Zones between External and Internal Occupation

Aspect	External Occupation	Internal Occupation	Overlap Zone
Alienation of Governance	Direct control by the occupier	Control by the domestic elite acting against the public interest	Loss of the public function of governance
Alienation of Resource Management	Exploitation for the benefit of the occupier	Corruption, monopolies, concessions	Diversion of resources toward the interests of the controlling structure
Alienation of Public Administration	Occupier's policy implemented through institutions.	Clientelist administration	Institutional inefficiency
Alienation of Foreign Policy Decision-Making	Policy dictated by the occupier	Policy driven by the interests of the elite and sponsors	Disregard for public interest and consensus
Control of the Information Space	Censorship and propaganda	Media capture	Monopoly over the narrative
Instrumentalization of the Judiciary	Judges and prosecutors under the control of the occupier	Politicization and corruption of the judiciary	Legal repression and protection of the privileged

2.2. Internal Occupation as the Apex Form of Hybrid Occupation

The assertion that internal occupation represents the apex form of hybrid occupation is based on three inherent advantages over classical external models: the invisibility of actors, legitimization through formal democratic procedures, and the self-direction of societal resources against the public interest. Unlike conventional occupations, there is no visible “external occupier”; effective control over state functions is achieved through the capture of institutions and systemic corruption carried out by domestic elites, often in collusion with external sponsors (Chayes, 2015; David-Barrett, 2023; CSD, 2024). In this way, national will is not suppressed through the use of force, but redirected via normative, economic, and informational channels, which complicates the identification of the source of the threat and the mobilization of defense (OECD, 2024; NATO Foundation, 2025).

First, the invisibility and diffuseness of actors reduce the political costs of occupation. When control is exercised by domestic political-economic intermediaries, supported by legally “clean” procedures, resistance is delegitimized as subversion of the order (David-Barrett, 2023; Petrovic, 2024). Second, legitimization through formal mechanisms (elections, parliamentary procedures, informal consensus) allows for the permanent “locking in” of preferences and rules of the game, as legal and political corrective mechanisms become instruments of control themselves (CSD, 2024; UNCAC Coalition, 2024). Third, the self-destructive allocation of resources—from public procurement and concessions to regulatory exemptions—produces structural dependencies of the state on networks of power and foreign interest centers, while simultaneously eroding the capacity of the security sector (Transparency International, 2024; Europol, 2025).

In the information sphere, internal occupation achieves narrative capture: the combination of ownership and regulatory control over media, state advertising, and targeted propaganda creates a perceptual asymmetry—citizens “freely” support policies that in the long run undermine sovereignty and resilience, thereby causing the nation to act unconsciously against its interests (Chayes, 2015; NYU CIC, 2024). Unlike external occupation, where coercion is visible and therefore subject to international constraints, internal occupation employs legal and economic instruments that are nominally legitimate but materially corruptive and security-regressive (OECD, 2024; NATO Foundation, 2025). The normative strategic consequence is that internal occupation replicates the key effects of classical occupation—alienation of governance, resources, public policy, and foreign policy decision-making—but with lower costs and higher sustainability for controlling actors, since there is no identifiable external aggressor and the mechanism of “consent without understanding” is activated within the population (Milutinović, 2025). Therefore, in security studies and public protection policy, internal occupation requires priority treatment: it is the apex form of hybrid occupation precisely because it converts state sovereignty into an instrument of its erosion and transforms the mechanisms of democratic legitimacy into a shield for maintaining effective control.

3. CORRUPTION AND INTERNAL OCCUPATION

In contemporary theory and practice, corruption is defined as the abuse of entrusted public power for private gain, whether in the form of financial profit, political influence, protection from accountability, or favoritism toward third parties (Transparency International, 2024). It encompasses a wide range of activities—from administrative corruption (systemic bribery and nepotism) to political and “grand” corruption (state capture and manipulation of strategic resources) (Karklins, 2005; Holmes, 2015).

In the context of internal occupation, corruption represents the primary operational mechanism through which domestic elites—often in coordination with external interest centers—establish effective control over institutions and decision-making processes, while the formal framework of sovereignty remains intact (Milutinović, 2025; David-Barrett, 2023). Its role is twofold:

Instrument of control – through the co-optation of political actors, the corruption of the judiciary and regulatory bodies, corruption neutralizes oversight and accountability mechanisms.

Means of legitimization – through clientelist networks and the selective distribution of resources – corruption creates an appearance of stability and loyalty, while undermining societal resilience.

In this way, corruption enables a nation to act unconsciously against its interests, as captured institutions produce decisions that, over the long term, weaken security, economic sovereignty, and the state's international standing—essential hallmarks of internal occupation. Unlike external occupation, where the threat is transparent and visible, here it is concealed and normalized, making it harder to detect and more resistant to removal.

In contemporary security studies, systemic corruption is defined as a persistent and deeply entrenched practice of abusing entrusted public functions, institutionally tolerated or even organized, to serve private, partisan, or group interests at the expense of the public good (Holmes, 2015; OECD, 2024). Unlike sporadic corrupt incidents, systemic corruption pervades the entire structure of governance, encompassing political, administrative, and security segments, thereby establishing stable control networks and mechanisms for maintaining power.

In the context of internal occupation, systemic corruption is the fundamental and most powerful operational tool through which domestic elites, often with the support of external interest centers, establish effective control over the state without formally violating sovereignty (Chayes, 2015; Milutinović, 2025). Its impact is multifaceted:

1. Neutralization of oversight – co-optation of the judiciary, prosecution, regulatory bodies, and media removes institutional barriers to the operations of power networks (David-Barrett, 2023; Petrovic, 2024).

2. Economization of loyalty – through selective distribution of public resources, concessions, and budgetary funds, a clientelist base is created to ensure the political stability of the controlling elite (OECD, 2024; Transparency International, 2024).

3. Structural dependency – non-transparent privatizations and concessions in strategic sectors (energy, telecommunications, defense) create long-term economic and security dependencies that hinder autonomous decision-making (CSD, 2024; NATO Foundation, 2025).

4. Narrative control – media capture and the use of information operations shape public perception to support policies that ultimately undermine national interests (Chayes, 2015; NYU CIC, 2024).

In this context, systemic corruption is not merely a symptom of institutional weakness but a strategic resource used to construct and maintain internal occupation. Its strength lies in its ability to transform mechanisms of democratic legitimacy into instruments of effective control, enabling the nation to act unknowingly against its interests. That is why recognizing and countering systemic corruption must be a primary priority in any national and international security strategy aimed at eliminating internal occupation.

3.1. Strategic Dimensions of State Capture in the Context of Internal Hybrid Occupation

The contemporary concept of state capture refers to the systematic takeover of key state functions by narrow networks of political, economic, and security actors, to shape public policy, legislation, and strategic decisions to their advantage—often in cooperation with external interest centers (David-Barrett, 2023; Chayes, 2015). When systemic corruption forms the foundation of this process, it moves beyond isolated deviations and becomes a strategic instrument of internal hybrid occupation, enabling the nation to retain formal sovereignty while effectively acting against its interests (Milutinović, 2025; Mitrović, 2025).

This model of control can be analytically mapped using Warden's Five Rings model, initially developed for planning air campaigns but applicable to complex hybrid operations (Warden, 1995; Mitrović, 2025). In this context, the rings do not refer to physical destruction, but rather to the sequential capture and instrumentalization of key components of state power:

1. Political Leadership (Leadership)

Operational objective: Co-optation or elimination of independent leaders, infiltration of the executive branch, and placement of loyal figures at the helm of key institutions.

Mechanism: Political corruption (buying parliamentary support, manipulating electoral processes), legal “sterilization” of the opposition.

Effect: Strategic steering of the entire state in line with the interests of the internal controlling elite and its external sponsors.

2. Core Resources and Economy (System Essentials)

Operational objective: Control of strategic sectors (energy, finance, communications, defense) to secure an economic lever of power.

Mechanism: Non-transparent privatizations and contract conclusions regarding public goods, market monopolization, concessions to foreign investors linked to the internal elite.

Effect: Economic dependency and inability to make autonomous strategic decisions.

3. Infrastructure (Infrastructure)

Operational objective: Takeover or degradation of the state’s physical and digital infrastructure (energy grids, transportation, information systems).

Mechanism: Selective investments, deliberate neglect of critical infrastructure, diversion of public procurement toward loyal entities.

Effect: State vulnerability to political and economic pressure, as well as control over the flow of information and goods.

4. Population (Population)

Operational objective: Shaping societal attitudes and behaviors to align with the narrative of the controlling elite.

Mechanism: Corruption in education, instrumentalization of social programs, propaganda campaigns, and disinformation.

Effect: Internalization of policies harmful to national interests, neutralization of potential resistance.

5. Information Domain (Information)

Operational objective: Complete control of public discourse, marginalization of critical voices, creation of an “acceptable reality.”

Mechanism: Media ownership capture, censorship, targeted advertising, and information operations.

Effect: Perception dominance—society believes the existing state of affairs is legitimate and desirable, even when it undermines sovereignty.

Through this five-ring framework, corruption is identified as a force multiplier in all rings—it not only enables infiltration and control of each level of state power but also links these levels into a coherent architecture of internal hybrid occupation (Mitrović, 2025). As emphasized in *Invisible Fronts* (Mitrović, 2025), modern hybrid operations increasingly combine political, economic, and informational corruption to achieve the same strategic goals as conventional occupations, but without visible use of force (Mitrović, 2025).

In this sense, the strategic dimensions of state capture include:

- Long-term sustainability of control through formal-democratic legitimization;

- Minimal political and economic costs for external sponsors;

- Difficulty of international prosecution due to the absence of a “clearly identifiable occupier”;

- Synchronized use of all national resources for the interests of the controlling elite and against the public good.

4. ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK AND INDICATORS FOR IDENTIFYING INTERNAL OCCUPATION

In this study, internal occupation is defined as a condition in which a narrow network of domestic actors effectively controls key state functions, often in coordination with external sponsors, while formal sovereignty remains intact. In this process, public institutions operate against the public interest, serving primarily the interests of the controlling elite. The operational mechanism of this phenomenon is systemic corruption, which enables the permanent co-optation of political leadership, economic capture, and control over infrastructure, the population, and the information space – five domains adapted from Warden's Five Rings model (Warden, 1995; Mitrović, 2025).

Set of indicators by domain:

1. Leadership / Rule of Law and Accountability - Indicators include sustained declines in Control of Corruption and Rule of Law (≥ 0.3 standard deviations over three to five years), high political corruption and the emergence of state capture patterns, frequent use of *lex specialis* procedures, changes to electoral rules before elections, and a pronounced gap between the scale of scandals and judicial outcomes (Chayes, 2015; World Bank, 2024).

2. System Essentials / Economy and Public Finance - This domain measures perceived corruption through the TI CPI (Transparency International, 2024), high single-bidder rates in public procurement (>30–40%), non-transparent beneficial ownership, allocation of strategic concessions with secret annexes, as well as high debt or energy dependence on a single external actor (OECD, 2024).

3. Infrastructure / Critical and Defense Infrastructure - Covers patterns of corruption in defense procurement, overpriced contracts, misuse of offset mechanisms, and digital dependence on a single technology supplier with limited step-in rights and escrow guarantees (CSD, 2024).

4. Population / Societal Resilience - Measures declines in civil liberties and political rights (Freedom House, 2025), increases in skilled emigration, decreases in institutional trust, and the prevalence of clientelism, including selective transfers and party-based hiring (Milutinović, 2025).

5. Information / Media and Information Operations - Tracks declines in RSF World Press Freedom Index rankings, concentration of media ownership, dependence on state advertising, as well as “narrative capture” indicators such as regulatory targeting of independent outlets and the spread of disinformation via bot networks (RSF, 2025; Freedom House, 2025).

Recognition logic and decision algorithm:

Normalization and peer benchmarking: Each indicator is normalized into Z-scores relative to a group of comparable states by region, GDP per capita ($\pm 20\%$), and institutional tradition, reducing the risk of false positives (Open Contracting Partnership, n.d.).

Thresholds and “red flags”: Defined thresholds (e.g., single-bid >35%, WGI drop ≥ 0.3 s.d., RSF drop ≥ 10 places in three years, Freedom House status downgrade to Partly Free/Not Free) signal concern. Multiple domains in the red zone indicate escalation (OECD, 2024).

Domain convergence test: Internal occupation is assumed when at least three domains simultaneously register negative trends for at least three years.

Causal structure test: Examines inter-domain linkages—for example, an increase in single-bid procurement linked to declines in media freedom and blocked investigations, indicating cross-domain coordination characteristic of state capture.

Risk classification:

At-risk: One to two domains in the red zone—early warning.

Captured-leaning: Three domains with apparent convergence and causal linkage.

Internally occupied: Four or more domains in the red zone, with institutionalized impunity and coordinated elite networks.

Systemic corruption is demonstrably linked to the erosion of security, the rule of law, and oversight institutions, and represents the primary tool of internal occupation, binding all domains into a stable regime of control (Chayes, 2015; David-Barrett, 2023; OECD, 2024; CSD, 2024). Media capture enables “narrative capture” and the pacification of resistance (RSF, 2025; Freedom House, 2025), while non-competitive procurement and secret contracts are data-verifiable indicators of economic control. Long-term trend analysis (3–5 years) enables the distinction between structural processes and temporary fluctuations (Milutinović, 2025).

The proposed Internal Occupation Risk Index (IORI) is calculated as a weighted average of the five domains: leadership (0.25), information (0.20), economy (0.20), infrastructure (0.15), and population (0.20). Within each domain, 2–4 indicators are used, with results displayed in a radar chart or heat map (Chayes, 2015; Mitrović, 2025).

Figure 1: Internal Occupation Risk Index (IORI) with Red-Flag Threshold

Based on the presented concept, it is clear that the application of the Internal Occupation Risk Index (IORI) model enables the systematic and measurable identification of corruption-based internal occupation, as well as its reliable grading. The model is founded on the premise that systemic corruption is the central operational tool of internal occupation, as it links the key state domains—political leadership, economy, infrastructure, population, and the information space—into a coherent and stable regime of control (Chayes, 2015; David-Barrett, 2023; OECD, 2024; CSD, 2024).

By incorporating the phenomena of media capture and "narrative capture," the model provides insight into how information operations pacify societal resistance and legitimize corrupt practices (RSF, 2025; Freedom House, 2025). In the economic domain, non-competitive public procurement and secret contracts provide empirically verifiable signals of economic control. Long-term trend analysis (3–5 years) distinguishes profound structural changes from temporary fluctuations (Milutinović, 2025).

The methodological framework of the IORI, based on a weighted average of five domains (leadership, 0.25; information, 0.20; economy, 0.20; infrastructure, 0.15; population, 0.20), with 2–4 carefully selected indicators per domain—allows for precise mapping and comparison of states or regions. The visualization of results through radar charts or heat maps not only facilitates the interpretation of findings but also enables monitoring of changes over time, which is crucial for strategic action.

The application of this model serves both researchers and decision-makers in identifying early warning signs of internal occupation, objectively assessing its intensity, and setting priorities in policies aimed at preventing and eliminating corruption-based hybrid threats. In this way, the IORI becomes not only an analytical instrument but also a

strategic tool for strengthening institutional resilience and safeguarding national sovereignty.

CONCLUSION

The analysis demonstrates that internal occupation, grounded in systemic corruption and state capture, represents one of the most subtle yet most dangerous forms of contemporary hybrid threats. Unlike classical external occupation, its destructive potential does not lie in the overt use of force but in the ability to transform democratic procedures, institutional mechanisms, and economic resources into instruments of self-erosion. In doing so, it not only undermines national security but also creates long-term dependency and vulnerability of the state within the international system.

If not recognized and addressed promptly, internal occupation can permanently degrade a state's capacity to protect its citizens, sovereignty, and strategic interests. That makes it essential to develop integrated strategies that encompass strengthening institutional resilience, reforming the security sector, establishing effective anti-corruption mechanisms, and building societal resistance to public opinion manipulation.

The message of this paper is clear: the defense of a state in the 21st century is measured not only by the strength of its borders but by the robustness of its institutions. Nations that fail to protect themselves from internal occupation risk losing their sovereignty without a single shot being fired. In this sense, the fight against systemic corruption is not merely a matter of ethics or development—it is a matter of national survival and international stability.

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RULE OF LAW AND THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION AS *CONDITIO SINE QUA NON* FOR THE SURVIVAL OF THE MACEDONIAN SOCIETY

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Abstract

The rule of law and the fight against corruption are foundational to the functioning of democratic societies. This paper examines the rule of law as a *conditio sine qua non* — an essential element — for effective anti-corruption efforts and how the rule of law and security are intrinsically linked, with each reinforcing the other. Systemic corruption depends on the existence of a culture of impunity. The fight against impunity is a fight for human rights and is a struggle for a life of dignity. A robust rule of law provides the framework for a secure society by ensuring accountability and protection of human rights. It argues that without a consistent and impartial legal framework, initiatives to combat corruption lack legitimacy and enforcement power. It analyses how the erosion of the rule of law facilitates impunity, weakens institutions, and undermines public trust, thereby creating fertile ground for systemic corruption. Through a comparative analysis of international legal instruments, case studies, and empirical research, the paper argues that restoring and strengthening the rule of law must be central to any credible anti-corruption strategy, focusing on the fundamentals: rule of law, democratic standards, legal frameworks, institutions, capacity building, and good governance.

Keywords: *rule of law, corruption, anti-corruption, governance, legal integrity, security*

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea of the rule of law can be traced back to Aristotle, who said in his famous book *Politics (Πολιτικά)*: “*He who bids law rule may be deemed to bid God and reason alone rule, but he who bids men rule adds the element of the beast; for desire is a wild beast, and passion perverts the minds of rulers, even if they are the best of men. The law is reason unaffected by desire*” (Aristotle, 350 B.C.E.).

The notion that governance should be based on an established system of rules of conduct rather than being dependent on an individual's whims can be found in numerous early examples of legal codification, leading to the modern understanding of the rule of law as a concept distinct from “the rule of man”. (Schroeder, 2016)

Since ancient times, the idea of the “rule of law” has been prevalent, and in its most basic sense, it refers to the notion that all citizens are bound by the law. Although this can seem like a fairly simple concept, many countries have historically struggled to uphold their legal obligations when it comes to adhering to the goals of this basic legal concept.

When government officials abuse their positions for personal gain or use the law to persecute political rivals, for example, the deviation from expected behaviour is quite obvious.

The rule of law ensures that governments administer laws fairly and impartially, but it also stops the majority, or their elected representatives, from imposing laws that violate natural justice, such as those that disproportionately affect minority groups. Democracy is preserved when the executive and legislature respect the independence of the courts and comply with their rulings.

The UN defines the rule of law as “a principle of governance in which all persons, institutions, and entities, public and private, including the state itself, are accountable to laws that are publicly promulgated, equally enforced, independently adjudicated, and which are consistent with international human rights norms and standards. It requires measures to ensure adherence to some of our most basic legal principles, including: the supremacy of law; equality for all before the law; accountability; fairness in the application of the law; separation of powers; participation in decision-making; legal certainty; avoidance of arbitrariness; and procedural and legal transparency” (United Nations, 2015). US Special Counsel Jack Smith noted on Friday 9 June 2023, that: ‘adherence to the rule of law is a bedrock principle of the Department of Justice. And our nation’s commitment to the rule of law sets an example for the world. We have one set of laws in this country, and they apply to everyone.’ (Thrush, 2023)

In the Macedonian case, it may be easier to see the many ways in which the rule of law has failed, rather than point out examples of success. We are a country where corruption is pervasive at the highest levels of the national government and is largely unpunished. Grand corruption depends on the existence of a culture of impunity. The fight against impunity is a fight for human rights because the fight against impunity is a struggle for a life of dignity. Therefore, the fight against impunity is not an end in itself, but a way of establishing real, social and democratic rule of law. We need a relentless focus on the fundamentals – rule of law, democratic standards, and economic reforms – in order to promote progress in governance and prevent backsliding. I strongly believe that the main obstacle for the rule of law is corruption and our culture of impunity. What drives corruption forward is greed. Human greed as the root of all modern evil, inequality and repression.

Macedonia is a candidate for admission to the European Union, but the looming spectre of corruption could derail its candidacy. Just about every journalist covering Macedonian politics points to the rampant corruption present within the country. Corruption is so endemic that mutual accusations of corruption play a central part in election campaigns in our society and the region in general. In the Balkans, a common aphorism suggests that the region has so much history it doesn’t need a future.

Today, the countries in the region show clear elements of state capture, including links with organised crime and corruption at all levels of government and administration, as well as a strong entanglement of public and private interests. All this feeds a sentiment of impunity and inequality. There is also extensive political interference in and control of the media. A visibly empowered and independent judiciary and accountable governments and administrations are essential for bringing about the lasting societal change that is needed.

Despite scholarly efforts to disentangle the variables associated with effective corruption control, whether on a national or institutional scale, an unexplained component persists. It can be linked to culture, systems, or other elements, but one common catalyst is

almost always leadership. Leadership is more than just penalizing individual offenders with a "get tough" approach; it's also proclaiming and building societies that are transparent, accountable and just in society, setting an example for others to adhere to and inspiring them to adopt more ethical actions. (Tsai & Anderson, 2023)

The primary obstacles of reforms in Macedonia are not technical or financial, but political and human. Rule-of-law reform will succeed only if it gets at the fundamental problem of leaders who refuse to be ruled by the law. Respect for the law will not easily take root in systems rife with corruption and cynicism since entrenched elites cede their traditional impunity and vested interests only under great pressure. (Carothers, 1998).

Maybe we should rethink how we approach corruption? Because corruption is more than simply an isolated issue; it is at the centre of political and societal processes in several ways. But conventional wisdom about corruption has failed us. Since the late 1970s, it has been shaped mostly by economists, with a concentration on finding, assessing, and prescribing measures to prevent corruption. Terms like "compliance" have become buzzwords in business circles, indicating a focus on anti-corruption measures. At a higher level, countries have been urged to "comply" with anti-corruption reform measures. However, despite decades of effort, the fight against corruption has mostly failed to yield major results globally.

2. CAN WE, AS A SOCIETY, ESCAPE THIS VICIOUS CIRCLE OF IMPUNITY AND CORRUPTION?

Macedonian society has been in a state of transition since 1991, when we exchanged one political system with another. Of all the challenges we have faced over the past thirty-two years, none is more complex and compelling than reducing corruption and strengthening the rule of law. Bribery and corruption, endemic to most cultures and a mainstay of human greed, are now, as they have always been, a major thorn in our side. With rising levels of corruption, politicians are often caught up in a situation where the need to preserve their position of power overrides all interests of the state of the citizens.

So, what is our biggest problem? The fight against corruption in our country remains one of our weakest points according to relevant international reports. There has actually been no progress; on the contrary things are getting worse. Corruption is pervasive, accompanied by conflicts of interest, undue influence on the non-governmental sector, nepotism, and clientelism. The recommendations from the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption and the Ombudsman are disregarded by all parties, including the Government, Parliament, and Prosecutor's Office. According to the 'Eurobarometer 2024' survey conducted by the Centre for European Strategies – Eurothink, the government's trust level stands at only 18 percent, while Parliament holds the lowest trust at 12 percent. The prosecution and judiciary follow closely behind, both at 9 percent (Kocovska, 2024). "Corruption as *conditio sine qua non*" implies that combating corruption is an essential prerequisite for accomplishing specific objectives, such as effective governance, economic advancement, or the safeguarding of human rights. The Latin word "condition without which not" signifies that the purpose is unattainable unless corruption is first confronted or eradicated.

What is the most effective method to conceptualise corruption? The traditional definition of corruption is individual behaviour that diverges from civic responsibility for personal benefit. Scholars such as Dennis Thompson, Lawrence Lessig, and Zephyr Teachout have suggested an alternative definition of corruption, characterising it as a structural misalignment of normalised political behaviours. This shifts the focus of

corruption from a critique of individual behaviour to an assessment of institutional efficacy.

The fight against corruption necessitates a robust system that encompasses a legal framework, effective institutions, and the implementation of policies and actions by relevant stakeholders. Given the decline of democracies and the rule of law being influenced by various private interests, it is essential to prioritize the prevention of corruption within governmental programs. Upholding political integrity is a crucial mechanism for ensuring government accountability. High officials must be held accountable, and prioritizing public interest over private interests while exercising political power, along with acting for the common good, should lead the development of policies, strategies, and advocacy efforts aimed at effectively combating corruption.

Therefore, do we need new and better laws? The central premise in rule of law research is to direct our focus—among practitioners, academics, the political class, and the public — toward the need for effective and efficient implementation of public policies. I want to emphasize the term “implementation” because, as the former president of the Macedonian Academy of Arts and Sciences, Academic Prof. Kambovski, stated, “It is not sufficient to only write the law — the law must be implemented”. In other words, the system of legal norms in a country will remain merely a “dead word on paper” if it lacks a well-developed normative-institutional structure and a robust system of separation of powers. This structure is essential because it will, according to the internal logic of the system itself, lead to a significantly higher level of implementation of legal norms than has been the case so far in Macedonia. (Labovic, 2024:283)

Only then can we genuinely discuss the rule of law. If the rule of law thrives, corruption will decline. Corruption is not some vast, impersonal force; rather, it is the result of personal decisions, most often driven by greed. Corruption is a cancer that devours society.

“If corruption is like cancer, then ‘corruption oncologists’ need a deeper understanding of its DNA to create effective interventions. Yet, discussions about corruption and its solutions often seem to be viewed as tedious or bothersome distractions” (Heywood, 2018).

Almost all international conventions as well as national laws focus either on prevention or on penalising corrupt transactions, which stem from such abuses. They are therefore merely treating the symptoms but are missing the disease. The establishment of the legal nexus between corruption, democracy and human rights could allow such a bottom to top approach which addresses the root cause of corruption, rather than its symptoms.

Speaking about tackling government corruption U.S. Embassy Skopje’s Resident Legal Advisor Jason Corley underlined: “A culture of corruption changes when people in positions of authority act with integrity, with character, and do the right thing for the right reasons”.

This brings me to the third fundamental key question of this paper: are there incorruptible leaders to be found? We need leaders with integrity and strict moral values, that exercise political power consistently in the public interest, independent from private interests, and who don’t use power to maintain the office holder’s own wealth and position. History books point to shining examples of the good leaders, and names like Abraham Lincoln, Cincinnatus, Earnest Vandiver and Václav Havel are often spoken of in the highest regard. But where are their modern counterparts?

The proposed reforms in this research should lead to measures to end impunity for perpetrators of corruption and to break the “vicious circle” as described by Ms. Anne Koch, representative of Transparency International: “when it is successfully practiced, it continues to be used, thus undermining the rule of law”.

From a democratic perspective, the goal of the rule of law as a means of combating corruption is to instil faith in public discourse and belief in the possibility of common goods. This appears to fit well within the rule of law, which it undoubtedly does. Politicians and government officials in almost every jurisdiction throughout the world commonly use the term “rule of law”, but do they know what it really means?

The World Justice Program (WJP) extended the definition of the rule of law. Aiming to engage all the actors involved in promoting the rule of law, WJP proposed a definition that is based on four universal principles: "The government and its officials and agents, as well as individuals and private entities, are accountable under the law; the laws are clear, publicized, stable, and just; are applied evenly; and protect fundamental rights, including the security of persons and property and certain core human rights; the process by which the laws are enacted, administered, and enforced is accessible, fair, and efficient; justice is delivered timely by competent, ethical, and independent representatives and neutrals who are of sufficient number, have adequate resources, and reflect the makeup of the communities they serve" (World Justice Project, 2024).

3. THE CONVENTIONAL VIEW OF CORRUPTION

Joseph Nye presents a prominent traditional definition of corruption: “Corruption is behaviour which deviates from the formal duties of a public role because of private-regarding (personal, close family, private clique) pecuniary or status gains; or violates rules against the exercise of certain types of private regarding influence”. (Nye, 1967)

Corruption is defined as 1) specific acts of behaviour that 2) contravene public responsibility standards to achieve personal benefit. Corruption is a self-serving breach of civic obligation principles. Typical instances are taking bribes, embezzling public assets, or using public office resources for self-serving activities like insider trading. This behaviour transforms authority intended for the public good into a personal advantage for the official in possession of it. It constitutes a breach of public trust and is generally detrimental to responsible and efficient governance.

Mark Philp and Jacob Rowbottom point out that labelling an act as corrupt necessarily involves a moral judgment about political organization. The core principles that define how a society should operate are described by what they refer to as the 'healthy...normal' or 'naturally sound' conditions of political engagement. (Rowbottom, 2010)

4. CONCEPTIONS OF CORRUPTION AND RULE OF LAW

The institutional perspective may have less alignment with the rule of law because it places less emphasis on individual moral responsibility. The rule of law requires the establishment of regulations beforehand, their consistency, and their accessibility to those they govern. It safeguards personal freedom. Corruption is characterized as individual breaches of commonly accepted civic responsibilities, making its conventional identification easily recognizable and familiar in both substance and form. It can therefore fulfil rule of law criteria whether directly applied to an individual as a norm infringement or when utilized to guide lawful anti-corruption measures. Due to adherence to the rule of law, when a state typically upholds this principle, dependence on traditional conceptions of corruption is less likely to infringe upon individual liberties.

Institutional corruption examines the foundational ideals of a society and can identify corrupt behavior even in the absence of intentional misconduct. The rule of law is a complex and often debated concept, yet two of its commonly recognized attributes are evident in anti-corruption law: the impartiality and fairness of arbitration, along with the clarity of articulated regulations. Traditional studies of corruption have emphasized a critical aspect: the enforcement of anti-corruption legislation must exhibit 'impartiality,' 'competence,' and 'integrity' by the authorities responsible for its implementation. Given the potential for anti-corruption law to be wielded as a weapon against political opponents, it is essential in anti-corruption arbitration to distinguish between strong, legitimate claims and those that are weak or politically motivated. (Rose-Ackerman and Søreide, 2011) Historically, scholarship on corruption has paid less attention to the procedural requirements of the rule of law; however, as Susan Rose-Ackerman noted, 'well-drafted, relatively clear, and generally available' (2007) regulations bolster the fight against corruption by making the norms of public interest more accessible.

The elements of the rule of law are crucial for attributing individual moral responsibility in cases of corruption. Biased enforcement or ambiguous, poorly defined laws provide minimal insight into the ethical status of transgressors. Traditional corruption may adapt to the proceduralism of the rule of law. Conventional corruption is defined as guilty individual conduct driven by deliberate malicious intent. The norm breach involving the misuse of public power for private benefit is well-known and often denounced.

Moreover, the standards that shape traditional definitions are often derived from or associated with prevalent perspectives within the political sphere: commonly accepted concepts of public interest or welfare, or legislation that delineates anti-corruption measures (provided there is general rule of law integrity within the political system, and laws align with the popular will). Despite not being entirely definitive or normatively comprehensive, the members of the polity originate and recognize these sources. Collectively, these characteristics—an emphasis on personal behaviour, widespread recognition of the nature of the offense, and a foundation in widely accepted standards—facilitate the ability of the norm violation that characterizes conventional corruption to meet rule of law criteria. The legal regulations will never completely encompass the norm that delineates corruption. However, if the legal regulations aim to promote recognized, well-defined, individual-centred standards of civic behaviour, they can align anti-corruption identification with established expectations, allowing adjudication to address ambiguous circumstances. Although this is not without flaws, the recognition of that traditional concept would enhance the rule of law principle of preventing 'the government... from undermining individual efforts by ad hoc actions.' (Eisler, 2022)

Fighting corruption is a challenging endeavour, particularly in the developing world. Many governments are either unable or unwilling to implement effective anti-corruption campaigns, reforms, and oversight. The gap between nations that can effectively manage corruption and those that cannot is undeniably widening. Corruption is deeply entrenched in numerous societies and has become a normative behaviour; its consequences may be unpredictable or a result of political retribution. Systemic corruption poses a substantial threat to democracy, indicating an inefficient state that must be examined within a broader theoretical context rather than merely through the lens of inadequate governance. In many emerging nations, corruption has become deeply embedded. This entrenchment complicates efforts to establish accountability and transparency, ultimately undermining public trust in institutions. As a result, addressing

corruption requires a multifaceted approach that goes beyond traditional governance reforms.

According to a study by Prof. Labovic, (2024) Macedonia urgently needs a new, coherent, and complementary normative-institutional structure. This structure should consist of a series of optimally independent state institutions that are separate from the executive branch and, to some extent, from the legislative branch, while still under broader institutional controls.

Corruption undermines public trust in democracy and poses a significant threat to the rule of law. It adversely affects the rule of law, which relies on formal and predictable institutions. In reality, corruption compromises the effective functioning of public institutions, disrupts legislative and judicial processes, and erodes the principles of legitimacy and legality. It introduces an element of arbitrariness and has a detrimental impact on citizens' confidence in these institutions. This, in turn, weakens the rule of law's capacity to address corruption by ensuring the consistent application and enforcement of penalties.

What makes the issue of combating corruption still pertinent? In the last twenty-five years, a significant focus has been placed on this issue, with academic researchers, policymakers, international financial institutions, specialised anti-corruption agencies, civil society organisations, investigative journalists, prosecutorial authorities, advocacy groups, coalitions, and individual advocates all engaging in the fight against corruption. A multitude of strategies and methodologies have been proposed to combat corruption: the World Bank has recommended "six strategies to combat corruption" to enhance a prior "two-pronged strategy", along with "10 methods to combat corruption" (Hunja, 2015); Transparency International has outlined "5 essential components" for eradicating corruption; and the World Economic Forum has presented "5 approaches to counter global corruption", in addition to "3 critical steps to eliminate corruption". Responses continue to surface; however, the issue remains persistently unresolved, we can certainly say that is a sort of intellectual Groundhog Day that keeps bringing us back to the same fundamental question. (Heywood, 2018)

Zinnbauer (2017) has noted that the majority of corruption literature tends to link potential drivers of change in corruption too closely with changes in corruption, integrity, and governance. Alternatively, they present wider forces of change in a conceptual and correlational manner without the capacity or intention to analyse these complexities and reveal the actual transmission mechanisms.

Evidence suggests that corruption and anticorruption are still conceptualised at the individual level, even in the face of a broad discourse that supports "contextual" explanations. This assumption is wrong. 'Corruption control' refers to a state's ability to function independent of private interests and promote maximum social welfare within a societal framework. Corruption becomes a policy issue as individuals often adhere to the established norms of their particular society and groups. The contemporary behaviourist perspective on corruption as an individual choice—while potentially correct—applies only to a few scenarios (where corruption is atypical) and does not apply elsewhere. This underscores the limitations of the behaviourist perspective, as it neglects the systemic factors that influence corruption across various societal contexts. Therefore, understanding corruption requires a more nuanced approach that considers both individual choices and broader societal influences. If we acknowledge that individual choice is predominantly influenced by social circumstances, we effectively concede that minimal individual choice exists, necessitating rules over prosecutions. We must alter social incentives rather than

individual ones, and hence we should cease enquiring about how to encourage individuals towards honesty as if the society they lived in were characterised by integrity. Instead, we ought to focus on creating an environment that fosters accountability and transparency, thereby reshaping the very foundations of social interactions. By doing so, we can cultivate a culture where ethical behaviour is the norm and corruption is systematically dismantled.

In the paper titled "Seven Arguments in Favour of Rethinking Corruption," Professor Mungiu-Pippidi (2024) emphasises that, in order to treat corruption as a balance between opportunities (enablers) and constraints (disablers) in every social context, the "rethinking" is required to recognise that the literature on causes of corruption enables, at the national level, to extend Gary Becker's (1993) individual level formula on crime. The traditional concept of an individual's decision to engage in a criminal act, such as corruption, hinges on a rational assessment of the likelihood of detection compared to the potential benefits of the crime, which is significantly influenced by the interplay of possibilities and restrictions within the wider social context. Corruption control can be understood as a balance between opportunities, such as power asymmetry and potential material gains, and constraints imposed by an autonomous society on ruling elites through an independent judiciary, free media, and an informed citizenry that demands good governance.

One optimal solution (Labovic, 2024) would be a newly developed system embodying the principle of separation of powers, where its two defining characteristics are thoroughly and consistently emphasized: the balance of power among the highest state institutions and the mutual oversight between them. The balance of power indicates that key state institutions at the highest level within the system of governance should be organized horizontally, without any hierarchy or subordination among them, and they should remain independent from both the executive and legislative branches.

An evaluation of the effectiveness of anticorruption initiatives as well as a better understanding and monitoring of corruption over time are made possible by the use of an opportunities versus constraint model.

Figure 1. Control of corruption as a balance. Source: Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2024)

Mungiu-Pippidi (2024, p.3) discusses corruption arising from the balance between opportunities and constraints, exemplifying the issue with the UN Oil for Food programme. Designed with minimal constraints and numerous opportunities, such

programmes are prone to systematic corruption, regardless of the nationality or culture of those involved. Although certain individuals or groups of profiteers may be replaced when exposed, the overall prevalence of corruption will persist if our anticorruption strategies continue to target individuals while neglecting the broader balance within a sector, activity, or country.

Corruption does not guarantee integrity; however, integrity often serves as a safeguard against corruption among public officials, according to conventional definitions. Therefore, a more profound understanding of integrity in public life and its relationship with corruption is crucial for developing an effective integrity management model. This model should establish a formal structure that ensures public officials demonstrate ethical behaviour, characterised by honesty and fairness while complying with existing legal standards. Promoting integrity faces various challenges, including the difficulty of precisely defining the concept. Its connections to anticorruption, ethics, morality, and good governance compound this complexity. The OECD defines public integrity as "consistent alignment with and commitment to shared ethical ideals, principles, and practices that prioritise the public over private interests within the public sector".

Integrity is frequently depicted as the antithesis of corruption, as evidenced by the extensive use of the term in anticorruption circles. Drawing on moral and political philosophy, we can identify the core characteristics of personal integrity as wholeness (considering factors beyond the personal), action that aligns with principles (acting rightly), morality (acting for the right reasons), and process (acting appropriately). Some individuals might add the phrase "even when no one is watching" to suggest that true integrity necessitates no oversight, although such a notion is largely unrealistic in practice. In contrast, political integrity encompasses normative justice, openness and transparency, citizen engagement, and impartial authorities (Heywood et al., 2017).

Instruments like the Transparency Index (T-Index) and analytical tools like the Index of Public Integrity (IPI) have been developed by the European Research Centre for Anticorruption and State-Building (ERCAS) to provide an assessment that can capture any significant policy intervention that has an impact.

Corruption undermines all political systems, whether autocratic or democratic. It should not be seen as a principal element in democratic backsliding, but rather as a vulnerability. Democracies that effectively address corruption are the most stable political systems globally; nonetheless, both resolving corruption and maintaining stability are challenging endeavours.

The creation of a new realism paradigm globally necessitates recognition that the prior phase of norm socialization achieved success only in a de jure manner, rather than de facto level. The United Nations Convention against corruption has not effectively impacted the situation of any country struggling with corruption, similar to the UN's limited success in advancing universal human rights practices.

Various scholars agree that one way in solving corruption often means solving collective action problems. Mancur Olson outlined in 1965 the fundamental causes of the observed absence of group action for shared interests in specific situations. He stated that individuals often exploit the benefits of cooperation without incurring costs when they believe they can, leading to a tendency to rely solely on the contributions of others. This situation represents the primary issue of collective action. Olson argues that a society cannot overcome this challenge without implementing deliberate measures that encourage groups to engage in collective action for the common benefit, rather than merely pursuing individual or group interests. (Olson, 1965)

In a corrupt environment, principal-agent mechanisms fail due to the critical issue of lacking political will—both the principal and agent are corrupt and collude rather than defect. In this scenario, the politician and their political appointee, the civil servant, work together to extract private profit from public resources. Citizens, in their role as ineffective agents, do not unite to form an anticorruption party. Instead, they pursue individual agreements that serve their personal interests, which ultimately perpetuates the corrupt system. (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2024)

The European Research Centre for Anticorruption and State-Building (ERCAS) T-index, which covers 140 countries, highlights a significant gap between the legal commitments made by governments (transparency de jure) and their actual implementation (transparency de facto). The data suggest that achieving democratic transparency requires more than simply ratifying treaties and passing legislation. The way forward for any country involves not just the formal adoption of procedures but also their effective application and the assurance of freedom for individuals, the media, and civil organizations to utilize them effectively. (ERCAS, 2025)

According to the latest data of ERCAS, “Macedonia has been a world champion of good governance regulation due to its EU accession process. At the same time, it did not prevent it from being a fully captured state until very recently. While the country seems to have returned to democracy, with only the lack of autonomy of the judiciary reflecting the past, it has probably one of the largest implementation gaps when good governance is concerned” (ERCAS, 2024).

Figure 1: De Facto and De Jure Transparency

Source⁶: ERCAS 2025: Government Transparency Index

According to corruptionrisk.org Macedonia's Index of Public Integrity / IPI Score is 7.05 out of 10. As mentioned before, Macedonia has distinguished itself as a leader in the realm of governance regulation, largely attributable to its pursuit of EU membership. This did not preclude it from being, concurrently, a thoroughly captured state until quite recently, positioning itself at the forefront of the implementation gap on a global scale.⁷

⁶ The De Jure index reviews legal transparency (a country's transparency legislation), and the De Facto Index rates 14 essential websites for the coverage and accessibility of data. The 14 websites were selected using the categories of transparency described in the United Nations Convention (UNCAC) against Corruption and Sustainable Development Goal 16. A fraction of the De Facto index (Administrative Transparency) is included in the Index for Public Integrity.

⁷ The IPI score is the mean of the six components scores, which result from the standardization and normalization of original source data to range between 1 and 10 using a min-max-transformation, with higher values representing better performance.

Index of Public Integrity

IPI Score: **7.05 / 10**

The IPI score is the mean of the six components scores, which result from the standardization and normalization of original source data to range between 1 and 10 using a min-max-transformation, with higher values representing better performance.

Components	Component Score (max=10)	World Rank	Income Group Rank	Regional Rank
Opportunities for Corruption				
Administrative Transparency	10	1/119	1/40	1/18
Online Services	6.5	53/119	18/40	9/18
Budget Transparency	7.65	24/119	17/40	8/18
Constraints on Corruption				
Judicial Independence	3.38	87/119	24/40	11/18
Freedom of the Press	7.34	30/119	6/40	2/18
E-Citizenship	7.41	42/119	10/40	4/18

Opportunities are permanent enabling circumstances for corruption. Empirical evidence exists that administrative discretion (lack of administrative transparency and poor regulation) combined with unaccountable resources (non-transparent public finance, both from domestic sources and international aid) create opportunities for corruption.

Constraints are permanent disabling circumstances of corruption. They encompass the legal response of authorities as well as the response by society (a free press and digitally enabled citizens organized as civil society or as individual voters).

① Societies manage to control corruption if they find the right balance between opportunities and constraints.

Figure 2: Index of Public Integrity - Map

Source: ERCAS 2025

The European Research Centre for Anticorruption and State-Building (ERCAS) provides this estimate regarding Macedonia's corruption forecast.

The forecast can function as an assessment instrument for a country's anticorruption strategists, in addition to providing a long-term diagnostic complement to the Index for Public Integrity, which presents merely a snapshot at any given point in time.

To comprehend the motivations behind individuals' engagement in corrupt activities, it is imperative to transcend the reductionist and simplistic notion that such behaviour can be solely attributed to incentives, and that modifying these incentives will resolve the issue. In relation to this matter, we must concentrate more on the influence of unwritten and informal social norms as a catalyst for corrupt behaviour; as emphasised in a recent Chatham House report regarding collective action and the social norms that support corruption in Nigeria: “identifying the specific social drivers of particular collective practices is essential for formulating targeted and effective policy interventions to alter those practices” (Hoffmann & Patel, 2017).

I believe the first step is to acknowledge that there is no definitive "win" in the fight against corruption; instead, we ought to set more realistic goals for anticorruption initiatives. While some contemporary "successes" have garnered significant attention—such as Singapore and Hong Kong in Asia, Botswana and Rwanda in Africa, and Estonia and Georgia in Eastern Europe—these examples represent a minuscule number, both in absolute terms and proportionately. Furthermore, data indicates that conditions may be deteriorating in other regions. As Syed Hussein Alatas observed in a historical reflection, corruption "inheres in all social systems... It affects all classes of society; all state organisations, monarchies, and republics; all situations in war and peace; all age groups, both sexes; and all times, ancient, mediaeval, and modern" (Hussein Alatas, 1990).

Furthermore, the “paths to success” in countries that are recognised for effectively combating corruption can vary significantly, which challenges the notion of a single or “correct” approach. As the eighteenth-century biologist and Catholic priest John Needham observed, there are more ways to heaven than one. According to evidence presented by Mungiu-Pippidi (2015), various historical factors—such as crises, existential threats, gradual reforms, visionary leadership, and popular demands—can play crucial roles in the transition from particularism to a more universal and impartial provision of public goods, which is characteristic of jurisdictions with low levels of corruption. The impact of these factors is often dependent on their interaction with other contextual circumstances. Consequently, there is no single path to follow, as seemingly analogous conditions in various countries can lead to significantly different outcomes.

Bo Rothstein (2011) effectively critiques the institutional toolkit approach that aims to find a singular solution for implementing incremental anticorruption measures. The examples of Sweden and Denmark illustrate how a "big bang" approach to significant administrative reorganisation in the mid-nineteenth century, following severe military defeats that jeopardised their survival, more effectively explains the transition from "limited" to "open access" orders.

Looking at the research conducted thus far, I believe that the essential aspect of a successful anticorruption initiative is the necessity to start small, but with initiatives that are highly focused, both in terms of scale and sectoral emphasis. Crucially, we must refrain from discussing corruption in vague, general terms and instead focus on the specific issues that concern us, their locations, and the mechanisms at play.

By concentrating efforts on specific areas, it becomes easier to measure impact and make adjustments as needed. This method builds trust and momentum among the people. As these small initiatives begin to show positive results, they can serve as a foundation for expanding efforts into broader areas of governance. Engaging the community in this

process enhances transparency and empowers citizens to take an active role in combating corruption.

A well-functioning justice system is the key to protecting individual rights and upholding the rule of law. But what does well-functioning actually mean? When we think about it, we will probably come up with concepts like a functional rule of law system, fair legislation, independent judges, anti-corruption, accountability and so on.

But what is most important is that, for any system to reach its full potential, everything needs to work well and work well together. In an ideal hypothetical situation, every human being has the opportunity to live up to their full potential, and the ability to improve their life and the environment in which they live. This flourishing society would ideally be a place where everybody would be capable of improving their own life and environment, provided with the opportunity to live up to their potential.

Does an ideal civil space like this exist anywhere on this planet? This is a rhetorical question of course. But nevertheless, one should always strive to reach the utopian dream of a perfect society. Over the past years, civil society organizations in Europe and all over the world have experienced some negative trends, like democratic backsliding or weakening of the rule of law and, in some instances, the rise of very troubling tendencies.

There is continuing research by many scholars that has firmly established that a combination of a weak rule of law and perceived corruption is closely associated with stunted economic development, presents seemingly pervasive obstacles to an escape from poverty and is accompanied by an absence of human rights.

More positively, there's a sense that with a tradition of the rule of law, with relative freedom from corruption, confidence in government booms. The relevant question for us is identifying, at the margin, where we can gain a better leverage.

Paul Volcker, former chairman of the US Federal Reserve at the IBA Annual Conference in Boston asked very important question related to the rule of law: "Shouldn't we be satisfied that we live with a really effective rule of law, when the perceived need for heavy campaign spending has come to dominate our political process? We let those financing practices infringe in a very basic way upon the rule of law, with its sense of even handedness and openness. Does it not breed behaviour that is accomplished by any reasonable definition of corruption? I made the point earlier that the successful attack on corruption depends upon a strong sense of rule of law, but it's equally true that widespread corruption makes a strong rule of law an impossible dream" (IBA, 2025)

There is increasing recognition that the cultural, historical, economic, and political factors unique to each country significantly shape how corruption manifests, is interpreted, and its implications. A bribe in one context might be perceived as a gift in another. (Khan, 2021) While legal frameworks and law enforcement play crucial roles in combating corruption, viewing it purely as a law-and-order issue risks oversimplifying its deeper causes and expressions. Corruption reflects power dynamics, systemic inequalities, institutional weaknesses, and broader concerns related to governance and social justice. Efforts to reduce corruption must consider these broader realities and, also, tackling corruption is pivotal in breaking this cycle and promoting a just and inclusive society.

CONCLUSION

The rule of law and the effective fight against corruption represent not merely political ideals but existential prerequisites — *conditio sine qua non* — for the stability, progress, and survival of Macedonian society. In a context where democratic institutions remain fragile and public trust in governance is continually tested, the consistent and impartial application of legal norms stands as the only viable foundation for sustainable development. Systemic corruption erodes legality, distorts the economy, weakens social cohesion, and ultimately threatens the very fabric of the state.

The fight against corruption requires a strong rule of law, which serves as the foundation for effective anti-corruption measures. Without a robust legal framework, the enforcement of anti-corruption laws becomes fragmented and ineffective, allowing corrupt practices to thrive. Anti-corruption efforts and the rule of law not only reciprocate, but also reinforce each other. When legal institutions are transparent, accountable, and independent, they act as both a deterrent to corruption and a mechanism for redress, ensuring that perpetrators are held accountable. Only then can the rule of law become a powerful tool in the global fight against corruption, securing a more equitable and just society.

Strengthening the rule of law requires more than legislative reform; it demands an authentic political will, an independent judiciary, transparent institutions, and active civil engagement. Combating corruption must become an integral part of the national ethos—embedded in education, governance, and public accountability. Macedonian society can only ensure democratic consolidation, attract investment, and secure its place within the broader European community of values if it is truly committed to these principles. In sum, the rule of law and the eradication of corruption are not optional aspirations but the indispensable conditions for a just, prosperous, and enduring Macedonian state.

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THE ROLE OF THE COURT IN REDUCING SYSTEMIC CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

The judiciary plays a crucial role in preventing and reducing systemic corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia. As the foundation of the rule of law, the court is an institution that should ensure equality before the law, fairness, and accountability of public office holders. When courts are independent, they contribute to increasing citizens' trust and to creating an environment in which abuses of power are sanctioned, not tolerated. This paper focuses on how effective judicial practice, an improved legal framework and enhanced control can reduce the influence of politics and corrupt structures on the justice system. Reducing systemic corruption is an opportunity for the real transformation of society, and the judiciary is the driver that enables that change.

Keywords: judiciary, corruption, rule of law, independence, transparency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corruption is one of the most serious threats to democratic development and the rule of law in the Republic of North Macedonia. It does not manifest itself only as individual abuses, but in certain periods it takes on the characteristics of a systemic phenomenon, i.e. a situation in which corrupt practices are embedded in institutional functioning. In such a context, the judiciary carries the most difficult social expectations: to ensure equality before the law, to sanction abuses of power and to protect the public interest from political, economic and party influences.

The role of the court in reducing systemic corruption becomes particularly important when institutions face pressures, clientelism and lack of accountability. The judiciary is the only body that can establish an effective balance between state power and the rights of citizens, provided that it acts independently, impartially and professionally.

Although North Macedonia has undertaken significant reforms in the judicial system in recent years, especially under the influence of European recommendations, public trust remains low. Research shows that citizens often perceive corruption as an integral part of public institutions, and courts as bodies that rarely, or with significant delays, sanction high-ranking officials. This perception is further exacerbated by the presence of political influences, lengthy court proceedings and the uneven application of the law. [European Commission. (2023). North Macedonia 2023 report. Brussels: European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu>]

In such a context, this research aims to examine the role of the court as a key factor in reducing systemic corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia. The analysis is based on the theoretical definition of judicial independence, identification of anti-corruption

mechanisms, assessment of institutional weaknesses and review of relevant national and European documents, laws and reports. Special attention is paid to the comparative analysis of the judicial systems in Germany, Croatia and Montenegro, in order to understand successful models of appointment, dismissal and evaluation of judges, as well as their application in different legal traditions.

The research uses a multilayered methodology. The analytical framework includes an interpretation of constitutional and legal provisions, international standards for judicial independence and relevant documents of GRECO, the European Commission and the UN. The comparative method allows for a comparison of the Macedonian system with developed and similar legal systems, thus obtaining a clear picture of the practices that can be applied or adapted in the domestic context. The historical approach follows the evolution of judicial reforms in the last two decades, as systemic weaknesses cannot be understood without noticing the continuity of political influences and institutional constraints. The sociological method analyses the attitudes of citizens and their trust in the judiciary, as an important indicator of the legitimacy of judicial power. The normative-dogmatic approach allows us to determine the degree of compliance of the legal framework with European standards, while the statistical method processes data on the number of charges filed, completed proceedings and convictions in corruption cases.

The aim of this paper is to set a clear theoretical and methodological basis through which the real role of the courts in the fight against systemic corruption can be assessed. Such an approach allows us not only to determine the weaknesses and challenges of the judicial system, but also to propose specific directions for its improvement, with the aim of developing a stable, transparent and independent judiciary that can effectively oppose corrupt practices.⁸

2. CHAPTER 1.

2.1. Concept and definition of systemic corruption

Corruption, in its most basic form, is the abuse of entrusted power for personal gain. However, when it comes to systemic corruption, it refers to situations in which corrupt practices are not limited to individuals or isolated cases, but become part of the entire system of state functioning. In such conditions, institutions do not act on the basis of law and social interest, but according to informal rules dictated by political and economic elites. Systemic corruption occurs as a “normalized state” where clientelism, nepotism and political pressures become common and accepted practices. Corruption, in its broadest sense, is the abuse of official position, power or influence for private interests and gain. It can occur in various forms – from petty administrative corruption, through corruption at the middle level, to the so-called “grand” or “high” corruption involving holders of the highest positions in the state. However, when we talk about systemic corruption, we mean corruption that is deeply embedded in the institutional, political and economic structure of society, to the extent that it becomes part of its daily functioning.

One of the key elements that distinguishes systemic corruption from individual corruption is its prevalence and institutionalization. [European Commission. (2023). North Macedonia 2023 report. Brussels: European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu>] Systemic corruption is defined as a structural phenomenon in which corrupt practices are not incidental, but integrated into the functioning of institutions, creating expected and

⁸ Anticorruption Resource Centre. (2020). Judicial independence and corruption control. U4 Brief, Chr. Michelsen Institute. <https://www.u4.no>

normalized patterns of behaviour. According to modern legal and political theory, systemic corruption occurs when there is weak institutional integrity, insufficient accountability mechanisms and a low level of trust in public institutions.

2.2. Judicial independence as a prerequisite for the rule of law

The judiciary has a central role in every democratic state. Its independence is a prerequisite for the protection of human rights, equality before the law and effective control of the executive and legislative branches. The theory of the rule of law assumes that laws are applied predictably, equally and without arbitrariness. Judicial independence, according to Beilinson and other authors, consists of two components: [Zajkovski, I. (2020). Challenges in combating systemic corruption in the Western Balkans: The case of North Macedonia. *Journal of Balkan Studies*, 12(2), 115–132.]

- Institutional independence – constitutional and legal mechanisms that protect the judiciary from influence;⁹
- Personal independence – guarantees for the mandate, status and professional integrity of judges.

The lack of any of these components results in selective justice, influence by the executive branch and the creation of conditions for corrupt practices.

3. MECHANISMS FOR THE APPOINTMENT AND DISMISSAL OF JUDGES

3.1. The importance of selection procedures

The way judges are appointed influences the perception of independence. Transparent procedures, based on meritocracy, professional criteria and public scrutiny, create a basis for trust and integrity. In contrast, politicized processes increase the risk of clientelism and dependence on political centres of power.

3.2. Comparative analysis: Germany, Croatia, Montenegro

Germany

In the federal German system, the appointment of judges is overseen by judges' selection committees (Richterwahlausschüsse), which include members of parliament and the executive, but operate on the basis of a strict procedure and consensus. The German model is often cited as an example of institutional balance: politics has a formal role, but no discretionary power without professional scrutiny.

Croatia

The Croatian State Judicial Council is an autonomous body composed mainly of judges, with limited participation by politically appointed members. This model is considered a step towards deconcentration of political influence, although international reports indicate that transparency in practice can still be improved.¹⁰

⁹ 2) Council of Europe, Group of States against Corruption (GRECO). (2022). Fifth evaluation round – Evaluation report on North Macedonia. Strasbourg: GRECO.

¹⁰ Gjorgjievski, M., & Stankovikj, B. (2021). Judicial reforms and the fight against corruption in North Macedonia. *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies*, 21(4), 623–641. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683857.2021.1982456>

Montenegro

Although formally European-oriented mechanisms exist, the Venice Commission has repeatedly indicated that the institutional framework is vulnerable to political pressures. Unpredictable promotion and disciplinary procedures create room for influence over judges, which is reflected in their autonomy.

4. ETHICAL STANDARDS, INTEGRITY AND PUBLIC TRUST

4.1. Judicial integrity as a basis for legitimacy

Ethical standards are not just an additional dimension, but a fundamental component of judicial independence. International documents, such as the Bangalore Principles, establish the need for integrity, impartiality and steadfastness as core values. A judicial system that fails to sanction unprofessional behaviour creates an environment in which corruption can flourish.¹¹

4.2. Public trust as a measure of effectiveness

Trust is one of the strongest indicators of how citizens perceive the judiciary. Low trust most often stems from:

- perception of political dependence,
- inefficiency in resolving cases,
- impunity for high-level corruption,
- insufficient transparency.

In countries where public trust is low, judicial reforms have difficulty achieving results, even when the legal framework is formally aligned with European standards.

5. JUDICIAL INDEPENDENCE AND THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION

High-level corruption can rarely be prosecuted without an independent judiciary. When political or economic interests influence judicial decisions, anti-corruption proceedings are selective, protracted or result in minimal sanctions. Anti-corruption mechanisms — such as specialized prosecutors, financial investigations, and internal judicial bodies — cannot be effective if judges are not protected from pressure.¹²

6. ANALYSIS OF DATA ON CORRUPTION COURT PROCEEDINGS

Data from national and European institutions indicate several trends:

- Low rate of final judgments in complex high-level corruption cases, which is often interpreted as an indicator of weaknesses in the judicial system.
- Long durations of proceedings, which undermines the effect of criminal policy and creates a perception of inefficiency. [Zajkovski, I. (2020). Challenges in combating systemic corruption in the Western Balkans: The case of North Macedonia. *Journal of Balkan Studies*, 12(2), 115–132.]
- Lack of finality in judgments, which indicates problems in the quality of the investigation, prosecution or judicial decision-making.

¹¹ Anticorruption Resource Centre. (2020). Judicial independence and corruption control. U4 Brief, Chr. Michelsen Institute. <https://www.u4.no>

¹² Gjorgjievski, M., & Stankovikj, B. (2021). Judicial reforms and the fight against corruption in North Macedonia. *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies*, 21(4), 623–641. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683857.2021.1982456>

These data are not isolated statistical facts, but are directly related to the theoretical framework: where independence, integrity and transparency are lacking, the results in the fight against corruption are inevitably limited¹³

7. METHODS

Methods

In preparing this paper on the role of the court in reducing systemic corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia, several research methods were used in order to gain a comprehensive insight into the issue:

Analytical method

It is applied through a detailed analysis of the legal frameworks that regulate the judiciary and the fight against corruption.

The existing legal solutions in the Constitution, the Law on Courts, the Law on Criminal Procedure and relevant by-laws are reviewed.

The analysis also includes international documents (United Nations Convention against Corruption, GRECO recommendations and European Commission reports).

Comparative method

In order to identify best practices, a comparison is made between the judicial mechanisms for dealing with corruption in North Macedonia and those in the countries of the region (Slovenia, Croatia, Bulgaria), as well as in the EU Member States.

This method allows for the identification of similarities and differences, as well as the drawing of lessons that could be applied in the Macedonian context.

Historical method

The development of judicial reforms in the last two decades is examined, with a special emphasis on the processes after 2001, when the judiciary was part of the broader democratization reform package

This method monitors the evolution of institutional mechanisms for combating corruption and their efficiency.

Sociological method

Data from public surveys, public opinion polls and studies by relevant organizations (e.g. Transparency International, Centre for Legal Research and Analysis) are used.

This method allows for the perception of citizens about the judiciary and their confidence in its ability to deal with corruption.¹⁴

¹³ Gjorgjievski, M., & Stankovikj, B. (2021). Judicial reforms and the fight against corruption in North Macedonia. *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies*, 21(4), 623–641. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683857.2021.1982456>

¹⁴ Zajkovski, I. (2020). Challenges in combating systemic corruption in the Western Balkans: The case of North Macedonia. *Journal of Balkan Studies*, 12(2), 115–132.

Statistical method

A quantitative assessment of the results of judicial proceedings for corruption is made through the analysis of figures and data from the State Statistical Office, the Judicial Council, the Anti-Corruption Commission and reports of the European Commission. The number of charges filed, verdicts rendered and their legal force are considered.

Normative-dogmatic method

It is applied through a systematic interpretation of the legal norms governing the fight against corruption and their application in judicial practice. This method is important for determining possible weaknesses in the legislation that limit the efficiency of the court.

Inductive and deductive method

Through induction, general conclusions are drawn based on specific court cases and statistical data.

Through deduction, theoretical assumptions and their application in the practical context of North Macedonia are tested.

8. Results and discussion

The research showed that the role of the court in reducing systemic corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia is limited, but still significant. Although several reform processes have been implemented in the past decade, the judiciary continues to face serious challenges, especially in terms of political pressure, insufficient independence and low citizen trust.

1. Legal framework and institutional capacities

The analysis shows that the legal framework for combating corruption is largely in line with European standards. There is a wide range of laws regulating this area, such as: the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, the Law on Criminal Procedure and the Law on Courts. However, their consistent application is a problem, as there is a disproportion between the number of charges filed and the number of final judgments.¹⁵

2. Case law

Data show that the number of corruption cases that end with a final conviction is relatively small compared to the number of reports and indictments. This indicates weaknesses in the investigative procedure, lengthy court proceedings and the frequent statute of limitations of cases.

3. Public perception

Polls and public opinion surveys indicate low citizen trust in the judiciary. More than half of respondents believe that courts are influenced by political elites and that corruption is rarely sanctioned consistently.

¹⁵ Zajkovski, I. (2020). Challenges in combating systemic corruption in the Western Balkans: The case of North Macedonia. *Journal of Balkan Studies*, 12(2), 115–132.

4. International reports

Reports by the European Commission and GRECO confirm that North Macedonia has adopted significant reforms, but their practical implementation remains insufficient. The main recommendations are aimed at strengthening the independence of judges, improving transparency and increasing the efficiency of court proceedings.

Table 1. Number of corruption cases (2019–2023)

Cases reported	Charges filed	Verdicts rendered	Convictions
215	78	54	21
198	65	49	18
243	84	62	27
221	91	57	24
235	87	61	25

Table 2. Citizens' perception of the independence of the judiciary (%)

Question	YES	NO	I don't know.
Do you think the judiciary is independent?	22	61	17
Do you think judges make decisions under pressure?	68	19	13
Do you believe that the courts are effectively fighting corruption?	27	54	19

Table 3. Reports of international organizations – main observations

Organization	NOTE
European Commission	Consistent application of laws and increased efficiency are needed.
GRECO	To reduce political influence on the judiciary and strengthen the integrity of judges.
Transparency International	Low level of citizen trust and a sense of impunity in high-profile cases.

8.1. Discussion

The results obtained indicate that the judicial system in the Republic of North Macedonia faces serious and systemic challenges that limit its role in the fight against corruption. ¹⁶The problem of low trust in the judiciary is particularly significant. The lack of trust does not occur as an isolated phenomenon, but as a consequence of long-term inefficiency, selective justice, outdated cases and lack of transparency in their work. Research shows that citizens believe that judges are under pressure from political actors, and this reduces the willingness to report corruption, undermines the legitimacy of the courts and hinders the rule of law.

¹⁶ Zajkovski, I. (2020). Challenges in combating systemic corruption in the Western Balkans: The case of North Macedonia. *Journal of Balkan Studies*, 12(2), 115–132.

CONCLUSION

Judicial independence is one of the most important indicators of the democratic quality of a state. This paper demonstrates that independence is not an isolated legal principle, but a complex system that includes the methodology of appointment, professional integrity, institutional guarantees, ethical rules and public trust.

Comparative analysis shows that successful systems are characterized by balanced models of selection of judges, high ethical standards and clear accountability mechanisms. In contrast, countries with systemic corruption and low trust often have formally harmonized, but in practice poorly applied standards.

To achieve an effective fight against corruption, the following are necessary:
full transparency in the selection and promotion of judges,
strengthened mechanisms for professional accountability,
an institutional culture that fosters integrity,
constant analysis of data and empirical indicators.

Only through these components can the judiciary truly function as a pillar of the rule of law, and not as a formal segment of the state without a substantial impact on the protection of the public interest.

Given the identified weaknesses and potentials, it can be concluded that future reforms should be focused on practical, rather than merely declarative, changes. First, it is necessary to significantly strengthen the mechanisms for supervising the work of judges, with clear and predictable accountability criteria. Second, the selection and promotion process must be depoliticized to the extent that it completely eliminates the risks of partisan influence. Third, continuous professional training and ethical education of judges can contribute to increasing the integrity of the judiciary.

Furthermore, the digitalization of court processes, transparent case management, and greater public availability of court decisions can significantly improve efficiency and reduce the scope for corrupt practices. Public control is an essential part of a democratic society, and the judiciary must be equally open and accountable as other state bodies.

Finally, it is necessary to understand that an independent judiciary is not an end in itself, but a prerequisite for economic development, stability, and trust in institutions. If courts continue to operate under political pressure and limited resources, then the fight against systemic corruption will remain only formal. In contrast, a truly independent, transparent and professional judiciary can become a driver of social transformation, a protector of the public interest and a key factor for the country's integration into the European legal and institutional heritage.

Recommendations

1. Strengthening institutional independence
2. Improving ethical standards and integrity
3. Efficiency and quality of judicial decisions
4. Greater transparency of judicial processes
5. Strengthening anti-corruption mechanisms

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FROM CONTRACTS TO COLLAPSE – “CORRUPTION KILLS”

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Abstract

Corruption poses a significant threat to the quality, safety, and security of public infrastructure, particularly in developing countries such as Serbia. Based on a qualitative methodology, combining content analysis and secondary data triangulation, the paper aims to examine how corrupt practices infiltrate all phases of infrastructure projects, from planning and procurement to construction and maintenance. Using the 2024 collapse of the canopy at the Novi Sad railway station as a case study, the paper highlights how weak governance, discretionary decision-making, and lack of oversight contribute to systemic failures with deadly consequences. The analysis draws from official documents, investigative reports, and expert assessments to identify institutional shortcomings and patterns of malpractice. The paper concludes that addressing infrastructure corruption in Serbia requires a comprehensive reform agenda that includes full public disclosure of contracts and technical documentation, establishment of independent oversight bodies, and enforcement of accountability mechanisms. It also finds that only systemic reforms, grounded in transparency, integrity, and the rule of law, can prevent similar tragedies and rebuild public trust.

Key words: *corruption, public infrastructure, construction sector, accountability, security*

1. INTRODUCTION

Corruption remains one of the most urgent challenges in global public infrastructure development, especially in developing countries like Serbia. Its widespread influence compromises quality, safety, security, and sustainability, often resulting in catastrophic failures. Corruption in the construction sector has been extensively studied, revealing how practices such as bribery, favouritism, and lack of transparency distort decision-making. These practices weaken institutional capacity, leading to substandard outcomes, safety hazards, and project failures. In Serbia, numerous cases in public procurement and infrastructure projects have raised governance concerns, emphasizing the need for reforms. A tragic example is the collapse of a canopy at the Novi Sad railway station in November 2024, which caused sixteen deaths, highlighting the deadly consequences of unchecked corruption and poor oversight. This research explores how

corruption infiltrates the infrastructure lifecycle, focusing on Serbia, and discusses broader implications for safety, security, economic stability, and sustainable development. The study advocates for reforms to increase transparency, accountability, and institutional resilience to prevent future tragedies.

Methodologically, the study employs qualitative research, combining thematic content analysis and secondary data triangulation. Its aim is to identify governance weaknesses that enabled corruption in the Novi Sad railway reconstruction project. Data sources include academic literature, investigative reports, expert statements, and verified media outputs from 2024–2025. Literature was gathered via Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science using keywords like “corruption”, “infrastructure corruption”, and “Serbia”. Reports from organizations such as the World Bank, the European Commission, OECD, Transparency International, Fiscal Council, and other local agencies were also reviewed. Particular attention was given to documents related to the collapse, including inquiry reports, preliminary findings, expert assessments, legal filings, and official minutes. Credibility, relevance, and accessibility guided document selection, prioritizing official reports over media to ensure reliability. A key limitation is reliance on secondary data, much of which is preliminary or media-reported, which may influence the findings.

The analysis focused on five areas: technical, legal, construction, financial, and media. It looked for signs of corruption, such as rule violations, favouritism, and missing documentation. These indicators, derived from governance and procurement integrity frameworks (Adam & Fazekas, 2023; OECD, 2022; Wells, 2015; Gillanders, 2014), highlight vulnerabilities across all project phases: planning, procurement, construction, and maintenance where discretionary decisions and weak oversight enable corruption. Each indicator was used as a thematic code for cross-comparison of evidence, following established principles of qualitative content analysis. Validation was achieved through triangulation with public reports and peer-reviewed studies, ensuring findings were coherent and empirically grounded. To contextualize these indicators, the study refers to international standards: OECD Infrastructure Governance Indicators (2023), emphasizing strategic planning, transparency, accountability, and internal control; OECD Public Integrity Indicators (2025), focusing on policy coherence and open contracting; and the UNODC Handbook “Towards Building a Road of Integrity” (2023), which frames integrity as a multidimensional process connecting legal frameworks, ethics, and citizen oversight. The study empirically examines how such systemic indicators manifest within Serbia, providing insights into governance weaknesses and the need for comprehensive reforms.

2. CORRUPTION ACROSS THE INFRASTRUCTURE LIFECYCLE

Public infrastructure is widely recognized as a vital driver of economic growth and social welfare. Yet, it has long been identified as one of the sectors most vulnerable to corruption (Schwartz, Fouad, Hansen, & Verdier, 2020; OECD, 2022). Globally, almost half of government fixed capital investment is devoted to infrastructure construction. Many projects continue to suffer from inflated costs, delays, and poor quality. These outcomes are frequently attributed to corrupt practices (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Empirical surveys consistently rank construction and public works among the most corruption-prone industries (Wells, 2015). OECD (2022) reports that nearly 60% of all foreign bribery incidents occur in extractives, construction, transport, and ICT sectors. This stems from the nature of infrastructure projects large budgets, technical complexity, and multiple stakeholders (OECD, 2022; Adam & Fazekas, 2023). These characteristics create

opportunities for corruption and obscure oversight. In weak governance contexts, officials exercise wide discretion over project selection and contracting. This, combined with poor transparency and low citizen participation, fosters bribery, bid rigging, and patronage (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Transparency International found construction firms more prone to bribery. Corruption ranges from petty bribes to grand kickback schemes for contracts (Transparency International UK, 2008). Politically connected firms often win contracts via illicit payments, resulting in inflated costs and poor quality. A visible outcome is “white elephant” projects prestige-driven but of questionable value, diverting funds from essential works like maintenance (Pattanayak & Verdugo-Yepes, 2020). These investments often yield negative social returns (Schwartz et al., 2020).

Corruption in infrastructure has severe consequences. Financially, it inflates costs by 5%–20%, sometimes more (Open Government Partnership, 2021). Quality and safety decline when contractors cut corners to finance bribes, often using poor materials or avoiding inspections. In extreme cases, this causes disasters like collapses (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Corruption also causes delays and misaligns public spending funding new projects over maintenance, worsening deterioration of roads and utilities (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). It wastes resources, endangers safety, and erodes trust in institutions (Varinac & Ninić, 2014; Asuquo et al., 2021).

At each stage of infrastructure development, corruption can arise. In planning, political interference and lobbying often distort priorities (OECD, 2022; Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Companies may bribe to include projects in investment plans. Prestige-driven projects may replace socially valuable ones. Land acquisition and design are also manipulated, sometimes inflated for future kickbacks (OECD, 2022). As a critical point, procurement and tendering see practices like bid rigging, kickbacks, and tailored criteria to favour firms. Other tactics include unjustified negotiations, contract splitting, and overlooking disqualifications (GIACC, 2024). In Eastern Europe, auditors found irregularities in 20% of contract values; single-bid tenders raise additional concerns (European Commission, 2023). In Serbia, over half of public tenders attract only one bid (Open Society Foundation WB, 2025).

Corruption continues during construction fraudulent billing, false invoices, inferior materials, and bribed inspectors. These cause overruns, delays, and safety risks (OECD, 2022; Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Organized crime may worsen this by hijacking subcontracts. Operation and maintenance also suffer politically connected firms secure contracts, toll funds and spare part budgets are embezzled, and nepotism undermines service delivery. Asset disposal or privatization may transfer public assets to cronies at low prices (OECD, 2022).

Academic literature thoroughly analyses these dynamics. Chan and Owusu (2017) classify 28 forms of corruption. De Jong et al. (2009) list 12 types in engineering and construction. Nordin et al. (2011) discuss drivers at individual, institutional, and global levels. Corruption degrades efficiency, fairness, and outcomes. Stifi (2017) emphasizes the hidden and complex nature of corruption in construction. Zarghami (2024) uses a system dynamics model to show how corruption is perpetuated. Its developmental impact is profound, Gillanders (2013) links it to poor quality and inequality; Usman et al. (2009) estimate \$400 billion in annual global losses with major safety concerns. Reform pathways are also discussed. Matthews (2016) finds corruption siphons 10–30% of global construction value, urging joint efforts across sectors. Wells (2015) stresses early attention and institutional safeguards. Collectively, the literature reveals the pervasiveness,

complexity, and consequences of infrastructure corruption and the need for systemic reform.

While international studies confirm global trends, national cases reveal their reality. Serbia illustrates how weak institutions, discretion, and opaque procurement produce a system where politics override expertise. The Novi Sad railway-station tragedy illustrates how theory materializes into fatal real-world consequences.

3. SERBIA'S INFRASTRUCTURE UNDER THE SHADOW OF CORRUPTION

Serbia's infrastructure sector demonstrates how global corruption trends manifest locally, with both high-level graft and everyday malpractices common. One recurring theme is political influence in large projects. During the 2010s, Serbia began partnering with foreign state contractors. Many of these were from China.¹⁷ These partnerships were often established through interstate agreements, which exempted projects from open tender procedures. With the passage of the now-repealed Law on Special Procedures for Linear Infrastructure (2020), the government could declare certain transportation projects of "special importance" and award them directly. This bypassed the standard Public Procurement Law (European Commission, 2023).

Although repealed in 2023 under EU pressure, elements of the law persist. They continue through ad hoc arrangements, such as legislative exemptions for the 2027 World Expo (Transparency Serbia, 2024). Direct contracting, especially for China-funded projects, remains widespread. It continues to fuel concerns about costs and kickbacks. The EU repeatedly criticizes Serbia's non-transparent agreements. It urges open bidding for major projects. Examples of corruption highlight these challenges (European Commission, 2023).

A further notorious incident from another sector is found in telecom. The telecom sector was rocked by a prominent scandal involving Huawei, the Chinese tech giant. This event resembled previous procurement controversies. In 2016, Huawei secured a €150 million contract to upgrade Serbia's telecommunications infrastructure. Leaked documents later revealed the company had paid over \$1 million to offshore firms linked to a senior Telekom Srbija executive. The reason was purported consulting and introductions. Yet experts noted these resembled classic bribery disguised as consultancy fees (Dojčinović & Radojević, 2021). Direct wrongdoing was not proven, but the case highlighted risks in large tech infrastructure procurements. It also suggested telecom contracts, especially those negotiated behind closed doors, may involve personal kickbacks (Dojčinović & Radojević, 2021).

Persistent corruption in Serbia's road construction and public utilities is reflected in repeated procurement fraud and weak contract compliance. Investigative reports uncovered rigged contracts benefiting companies tied to municipal politicians. In 2022, the State Audit Institution found irregularities in nearly 19% of the procurement contracts it examined, reinforcing the view that routine malpractices contribute to systemic risk (European Commission, 2023).

These systemic patterns of corruption within Serbia's infrastructure governance set the stage for the most tragic and emblematic case of institutional failure the 2024 collapse

¹⁷ The first agreement with China in this area was signed in 2009, which was confirmed by the Law on the confirmation of the agreement on economic and technical cooperation in the field of infrastructure.

of the Novi Sad railway station canopy. The event not only exposed weaknesses in procurement, supervision, and accountability but also transformed corruption from an abstract policy issue into a tangible public safety disaster. The following section examines the collapse of the railway station canopy in Novi Sad, an event that resulted in sixteen fatalities and underscored the far-reaching impact of corruption within the infrastructure sector. This tragedy prompted widespread public protests, with students and members of the academic community at the forefront. Among the key messages was a clear and resonant statement: "Corruption kills".

4. CANOPY COLLAPSE IN NOVI SAD – A DEADLY OUTCOME OF CORRUPTION

The collapse of the canopy in Novi Sad is not merely an unfortunate outcome of a construction intervention but also a concerning reflection of deeper systemic issues primarily, the presence of corruption and inefficiency in the reconstruction and maintenance of public facilities. To effectively and clearly present our findings, it is important to further illuminate the environment and context in which the research is conducted, in order to better determine whether and to what extent corruption may be the cause of such tragedies. Our goal is to analyse available data and facts to clarify whether and how corrupt practices have jeopardized citizens' safety, whether it is possible to establish accountability among the actors involved in corrupt processes, and how to create conditions to prevent similar tragedies in the future.

The reconstruction of the Novi Sad railway station took place as part of a major infrastructure project for the planned international railway corridor Budapest – Belgrade – Skopje – Athens and its first phase, the construction of the Budapest – Belgrade railway.¹⁸ The reconstruction of the railway station building was carried out in two phases: the first reconstruction was completed and opened on March 19, 2022, and the second on July 5, 2024. A total of 65 million euros was invested in these works, with 16 million euros allocated specifically for the station building. The reconstruction was carried out by China Railway International and China Communications Construction Company (CCCC) (Gyurkovics, 2024). The contract for the reconstruction work is classified as secret, as the Ministry of Construction, Transport, and Infrastructure of Serbia refused to publish it, citing that "the Chinese partners do not wish to do so " (Kovačević & Prica, 2024).

In the first few days after the collapse of the canopy, government officials claimed that the canopy had not been reconstructed, even though engineers (specializing in construction and geology) illustrated through examples that it had been.¹⁹ The general director of the CIP Traffic Institute, Slaven Tica, stated that "the canopy at the train station

¹⁸ The Belgrade-Budapest railway line is part of the traditional railway corridor connecting Western and Central Europe with Greece, Turkey, and the Middle East. The willingness to reconstruct the Belgrade – Budapest railway has been expressed earlier through The Memorandum of Understanding between the People's Republic of China, Hungary, and Serbia, signed on December 16, 2014. The Memorandum was published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia - International Treaties, no. 1/2015. The works in Serbia are planned in phases, by sections: 1. Belgrade Center – Stara Pazova; 2. Stara Pazova – Novi Sad; 3. Novi Sad – Subotica – state border at Kelebija. The reconstruction of the station in Novi Sad was part of the section Novi Sad – Subotica – state border at Kelebija (The Memorandum of Understanding, 2015).

¹⁹ During the reconstruction, a massive steel structure with heavy glass was added, and the decades-long corrosion of the weights, which could not withstand additional loads, is also highly questionable.

in Novi Sad, which collapsed today, was not the subject of technical documentation for the reconstruction of the station building, and that the complete procedure in terms of design was absolutely followed for the entire building" (Virijević, 2024). The appearance of video footage about the reconstruction of the canopy and expert statements supported by facts led to an admission by government representatives that some form of reconstruction had indeed taken place. Under public pressure and mass protests organized in the meantime, the Government of the Republic of Serbia decided on December 12, 2024, to publish documents from the Ministry of Construction, Transport, and Infrastructure related to the possible commission of a criminal act concerning the collapse of the canopy at the Novi Sad Railway Station on November 1, 2024.

The collapse of the canopy, which caused the tragedy in Novi Sad, raised many questions: the structural integrity of the station, the way the multi-million dollar work was awarded, and the oversight of public infrastructure maintenance. Equally important was the issue of accountability for this tragedy. Although on November 21, 2024, the Higher Public Prosecutor's Office in Novi Sad announced that a total of 12 individuals had been detained and arrested in connection with the tragedy in Novi Sad²⁰, the opposition emphasized that these arrests followed significant public pressure. However, they also stated that the demands have still not been met and that protests continue.

In the meantime, dissatisfied with the work of the state authorities, a group of university professors and experts from various fields formed an Inquiry Committee, which began investigating what had happened during the reconstruction of the Railway Station building in Novi Sad and who is responsible. It was decided that the Committee would operate within four subcommittees: for construction, criminal-legal, economic-financial, and media reporting committee.

The preliminary reports of the mentioned Inquiry Committee and its subcommittees appeared in the media after February 9, 2025, but the final official report was presented to the Serbian public on October 15, 2025 (reports by subcommittees, Radar, October 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21), and the same report was presented to the European Parliament on October 22, 2025. After reviewing the available documentation of the Inquiry Committee and its subcommittees, as well as other accessible sources at our disposal, we arrived at the following conclusions.²¹ First, regarding responsibility, three levels of accountability are indicated: professional responsibility – constructive-architectural deficiencies; legal-formal and criminal responsibility – contracts, annexes to contracts, contractual prices, and responsibility of the highest authorities – enabled, permitted, or ordered the railway station, which still represented a construction site, to be put into use, thereby endangering the lives of people who pass by there daily. Second, the following are the findings in detail:

1. Technical details

According to the findings of all actors involved in the review process of the documentation regarding the reconstruction of the Railway Station in Novi Sad, approximately 21 groups of documents are missing from the documents published by the

²⁰ Including two ministers, the acting director of Infrastructure of Serbian Railways, the former director of Infrastructure of Serbian Railways, and an assistant minister of construction, transport, and infrastructure – sector for railway and intermodal transport.

²¹ Preliminary analysis of the Faculty of Civil Engineering; Reports of the Republic Construction Inspection; Ratings and opinions of associations of architects and independent experts; Additional sources - official records, legal documents, possible applications and appeals.

Government of the Republic of Serbia (including the dynamic plan, monthly progress reports from contractors, documentation related to the selection of subcontractors, etc.) (Dašić, 2025) According to the announcement from the Faculty of Civil Engineering at the University of Belgrade, the following are missing: project documentation (the conceptual design is not available); contractual documentation (contracts and annexes with all subcontractors – incomplete); construction documentation (site reports, construction diaries, construction books, inspection logs, testing and technical documentation, etc.); documentation under the jurisdiction of the investor and documentation under the jurisdiction of the Republic Construction Inspection (Građevinski fakultet, 2025). In addition to the missing documentation, a large number of documents have been published that are not relevant to the Railway Station in Novi Sad but pertain to the entire rail modernization project, which makes the available documentation unsystematic and slows down the process of drawing conclusions.

2. *Criminal legal details*

According to the findings of the legal civil subcommittee, the competent institutions in the executive and legislative branches of the Republic of Serbia are responsible for enacting corrupt and unconstitutional norms that have contributed to the erosion of the rule of law and the creation of criminal structures. Additionally, it remains unclear whether it is economically feasible to use the Railway Station in Novi Sad, given that the responsible institutions have almost not conducted a damage assessment for nearly a year, thereby increasing the overall damage by millions, for which they are directly accountable (Škero&Vodinelić, 2025). It refers to a hierarchically organized corrupt network whose primary objective is the unlawful enrichment of its members. This goal is pursued through the commission of various criminal offenses, including those related to the abuse of official authority (Article 359 of the Criminal Code), economic crimes (Articles 227 and 225 of the Criminal Code), money laundering (Article 245 of the Criminal Code), and violations of the Law on Tax Procedure and Tax Administration (Paunović et al., 2025).²² According to the findings of the legal civil subcommittee there are grounds for suspicion that in the realization of a large infrastructure project, i.e. the construction of a railway from Novi Sad to the border with Hungary, there was an association for the purpose of committing criminal acts in the very top of the country (Paunović et al., 2025). As Professor Marinković states in his authorial text, analysing the work of state authorities, following the collapse of the canopy, the investigation by the Higher Public Prosecutor's Office in Novi Sad has been compromised by controversies related to the expert assessment of the causes of the canopy's collapse. The investigation by the Higher Public Prosecutor's Office in Belgrade is directly aimed at obstructing justice, while the Organized Crime Prosecutor's Office fails to investigate the existence of an organized criminal group, which is suspected to be organized by the President of the Republic and has caused damage to the state amounting to approximately 700 million euros (Marinković, 2025a). The decision of the police director to abolish the Task Force formed by the chief prosecutor of the Public Prosecutor's Office for organized crime speaks of another type of obstruction of the criminal proceedings in this case, all with the aim of preventing the monitoring of money flows, through the financial investigation of all who could be potential suspects (Marinkovic, 2025b). According to Jasmina Paunović, one

²² Note: All findings related to potential criminal liability are based exclusively on publicly available sources and do not imply any judicial determination of guilt.

year after the tragedy in Novi Sad, there is still no criminal proceeding (out of the three that have been started), nor can the main trial be scheduled in the near future (Paunović et al. 2025).

3. *Construction findings*

It was determined that there is a collapse of professionalism at many stages of the analysed project, exemplified by the changes to the Terms of Reference, which underwent several modifications between 2015 and 2023. According to the findings of the Republic Construction Inspection dated two types of violations have been identified: 1. Control and quality checks of all types of works and the application of regulations, standards, and technical norms were not performed (including the lack of verification of the structural stability of the building, use of inadequate materials concrete that was neither approved nor in accordance with technical instructions); 2. Measures to prevent or eliminate immediate danger to life or health of people and safety were not taken (failure to observe occupational safety rules, lack of protective equipment, and the presence of personnel on the construction site whose identity and purpose are unknown) (Republic Construction Inspection, 2024). This indicates a lack of clarity regarding the type of work required on the railway station building, especially the canopy. At the time of signing the Commercial Contract, there was no fulfilled level of project documentation in accordance with the current Law on Planning and Construction, and it was signed when no conceptual design even existed. This reflects the common practice of the current authorities to declare projects worth hundreds of millions or billions of euros as projects of national importance and contract their construction without relevant project documentation (Fiskalni savet, 2024). None of these documents specify or describe the planned works on Wing B of the station building in Novi Sad, particularly not on the canopy. Given that the station building in Novi Sad was constructed in 1964 and there are station buildings on this route that are over 100 years old. It is unacceptable that the Terms of Reference included no comments on the age, condition, or specificities of reconstructing these structures. The building permit covers the entire Novi Sad – Subotica – Kelebija section, including all facilities and equipment, which is unusual given its length of 108 km and the diversity of structures involved. The authorities' goal was to expedite project implementation, often neglecting challenges associated with such a unique approach. Among other things, the building was put into use through an internal procedure (not recognized by law) at the beginning of July 2024, without a technical inspection or the issued occupancy permit. A review of the construction logs reveals a record of the internal acceptance of the building, but the technical inspection of the structure is not mentioned in the logs (Dobrić&Fric, 2025). The contractor independently selected who would control the quality and correctness of the technical documentation he prepared. This directly violates the Commercial Contract and bypasses the public procurement procedures that the investor (Infrastructure of Serbia Railways) and the financier (Ministry of Construction or the Government of Serbia) should have conducted for this service (Kuzmanović&Dašić, 2025).

4. *Financial and economic findings*

The findings in this domain coincide with the previous analysis of the state of investment by the Fiscal Council in 2024, in which they pointed to the growing inefficiency of investment through non-standard procedures (absence of tender procedures), shortened procedures and a large breach of the initially expected price of works (Fiskalni savet, 2024) The construction and reconstruction of the railway

infrastructure from Belgrade to the border with Hungary, including subsequent works and numerous annexes signed in the meantime, has so far cost \$1.33 billion or €1.24 billion. Compared to the estimate by the Ministry of Construction, Transportation, and Infrastructure from 2014, the total costs have increased by €910 million, nearly quadrupling (Dobromirov et al., 2025). The later decision to build the section from Novi Sad to Kelebija for speeds of 200 km/h instead of 160 km/h has neither technical nor economic justification. It is part of the European corridor, which was designed along its entire route for trains with speeds up to 160 km/h, including its extension from the Serbian-Hungarian border to Budapest. Even students at the Faculty of Transport and Communications emphasized that the speed limit was raised to 200 km/h due to political, not professional, will, which unnecessarily increased the cost of the project by 40% (Biznis&Finansije, 2025). Although, according to the Commercial Contract, the Chinese consortium CRIC-CCCC was not allowed to engage more than 54% of subcontractors based in the PRC, they awarded the entire project without public tender to Chinese subcontractor companies CCECC Balkan, CRCC11, CRDC, and CRCEBG and primarily to CCECC Balkan for works on the station building of the railway station in Novi Sad. In January 2022, a consortium that included the French company Egis was selected for supervision, despite the fact that in March 2018, the World Bank imposed sanctions on two subsidiaries of that company one of which was blacklisted, and the other suspended and over the following years, evidence of corrupt activities by this company accumulated (World Bank Group, 2018). In December 2022, President Aleksandar Vučić demanded that the Chinese consortium accelerate works and complete the Novi Sad – Kelebija section of the railway by the end of 2024, approving an additional \$65 million requested by the consortium for this acceleration. Through Annexes 2, 3, and 4, signed by Ministers Goran Vesić and Nebojša Šurlan, the value of works increased by \$86.9 million. Subcontractors, instead of the main contractor, were directly chosen by the Republic of Serbia for "other works". In the meantime, the Public Prosecutor's Office for Organized Crime specified that by concluding the annex, Momirović, Vesić, Dimoski, Šurlan and Katanić enabled the contractor to obtain a property benefit of less than 19 million dollars, as well as that the budget of Serbia was damaged by 115 million dollars (Nedeljnik, 2025). The Chinese consortium, as the main contractor, was not responsible for these subcontractors' work; it only transferred funds drawn from a Chinese bank and the Serbian budget, acting as a conduit, and charged a commission for this service contrary to the loan agreement with the Chinese Exim Bank. Decisions regarding the Commercial Contract and its annexes involved the office of the President of Serbia, the acting director of Infrastructure of Serbia Railways, the relevant ministry, the State Prosecutor's Office, the Ministry of Finance, the Republic Secretariat for Legislation, the competent committee, the Government Secretariat, the Government, and the Prime Minister. The greatest defeat and the most severe consequence of this corrupt activity is the fact that, according to the Infrastructure of Serbia Railways Report from April 2025: "*The construction site for reconstruction, adaptation, and extension of the Station Building in Novi Sad was closed by a decision of the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development (MGSI) on November 2, 2024*" (Kuzmanović&Dašić, 2025). Specifically, when the canopy collapsed, the station building in Novi Sad was an active construction site and should not have been allowed for use. Contrary to that, it was ceremoniously opened twice, and after the canopy was demolished, sixteen lives were lost. This inevitably raises the question: How much is a human life worth in Serbia?

5. *Media reporting*

Most domestic media coverage before and after the collapse of the Novi Sad railway station canopy on November 1, 2024, aligns with their reporting over the past 13 years under the SNS and SPS coalition. In other words, most media outlets serve more to promote government actions than to truthfully, comprehensively, and timely inform citizens. Pro-government outlets prior to the collapse only promoted the government's activities, and afterward, they repeated statements by Aleksandar Vučić, who blamed experts to control the damage an approach that led to the arrest of 13 engineers (Nedeljković&Gavrilović, 2025). Part of the media was in the function of hiding responsibility, diverting attention and labelling those who sought to sanction those responsible. This kind of information and narratives placed by the ruling elite and the president himself did not fulfil the basic human right - the right of citizens to know – which put their lives in question.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, after reviewing relevant literature on corruption in the construction sector and infrastructure projects, we attempted to identify similar findings in domestic projects. We specifically examined the corrupting influence during the reconstruction of the Railway Station and canopy in Novi Sad, analysing decision-making processes, costs, deadline adherence, quality of works, compliance with rules and procedures, and process transparency. We also considered expert opinions and compared them with legal and ethical standards. Deeply rooted corruption practices in Serbia's infrastructure sector from high-level political influence to embezzlement in public procurement not only undermine project transparency and efficiency but also endanger citizens' safety and lives. Serbia has so far failed to fully establish a legal and administrative framework that effectively prevents threats to life, especially by implementing appropriate regulatory measures tailored to activities like construction and reconstruction as hazardous activities, with particular attention to the potential risks to human lives.

Due to all of the above, and as an ongoing process, greater effort is needed to produce clear and precise expert reports highlighting key findings, with an emphasis on compelling evidence of corruption. Only from these findings can recommendations for prevention and elimination of corrupt practices in the future be derived, providing sufficient initial indicators for the relevant authorities, judiciary, and prosecutors to act upon. To prevent similar tragedies in the future, Serbia must adopt comprehensive anti-corruption reforms that integrate transparency, accountability, and professional oversight across all phases of public infrastructure projects. Establishing an independent supervisory body composed of experts from academia, civil society, and professional associations would ensure impartial monitoring and enhance institutional integrity. Moreover, full public disclosure of contracts, annexes, and procurement documents is essential to restore public trust and align Serbia's infrastructure governance with EU transparency and safety standards. Ultimately, combating corruption in construction requires a systemic shift from political discretion to institutional responsibility, grounded in the principles of integrity, openness, and rule of law.²³

²³ An important and motivating factor at this moment is the stance of the European Parliament in "The Resolution on polarization and increased repression in Serbia, one year after the Novi Sad tragedy", adopted on October 22, 2025, which emphasizes that Parliament will mark the anniversary

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WHO IS THE CORRUPT ONE? TEACHING ENGLISH RELATIVE CLAUSES THROUGH CORRUPTION-RELATED VOCABULARY

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Abstract

To clearly and effectively communicate ideas in English, learners of both General English and English for Specific Purposes (ESP) should be able to use relative clauses correctly. Relative clauses serve as the building blocks for syntactically complex sentences expressing relationships between different sentence parts. Through appropriate use of relative clauses, learners can achieve a higher level of precision of expression when using the language both orally and in writing. This can eliminate possible misunderstandings, which is particularly important in specific contexts and professional settings, including that of law enforcement.

In the English for law enforcement classroom, relative clauses can be taught through many topics covered by this field, one of which is corruption. As an increasingly topical issue, it has led to the creation of an extensive vocabulary linked to corruption-related concepts that law-enforcement learners need to understand. Therefore, the paper will examine the semantic features and nuanced meanings of selected vocabulary related to corruption and will present suggestions for its inclusion in classroom activities tailored for teaching relative clauses. Through their practical implementation in the English classroom, the learners will enhance their knowledge and use of relative clauses while simultaneously acquiring corruption-related vocabulary.

Keywords: English language, relative clauses, corruption-related vocabulary, classroom activities

1. INTRODUCTION

Developing grammatical competence is a vital part of the English language learning process. Proficiency in constructing grammatically correct sentences enables the learners to express their thoughts accurately in various contexts and domains. This, among other things, encompasses learners' mastery of the rules behind the formation of relative clauses. The learners' ability to use relative clauses correctly is a major indicator of their overall knowledge of the language itself, considering the role relative clauses play within the sentences they are part of. Relative clauses help learners organize their thoughts in larger sentences, clarifying them by adding either crucial or additional information about sentence parts. Also, they can be used for joining several sentences into one, thus contributing to a smoother flow and greater clarity and precision of expression. This is particularly relevant when using English in a written form, especially when the speakers want to raise the formality level of their texts, which equally applies to professional and non-professional settings.

Law enforcement is one of the domains in which using relative clauses can improve communication clarity, especially in written texts, such as reports, requests, legal documents, communication with the public and the media, etc. This applies to using the language in all areas connected with law enforcement and crimes, including corruption. Thus, for instance, in an incident report, saying that a) *The police officers interviewed a woman*, is a very general statement lacking the details that more specifically define the woman in question, compared to the improved version b) *The police officers interviewed a woman who had witnessed the corruption scandal* in which the woman who was interviewed was that specific one who had witnessed a corruption scandal. In addition, other information about the woman would describe the situation even more clearly, so we may say that c) *The police officers, who had extensive experience in solving economic crimes, interviewed a woman who had witnessed the corruption scandal*, etc.

As the example above suggests, law enforcement professionals may prevent possible misunderstandings by providing details, either essential or non-essential, introduced by corresponding relative clauses. Misunderstandings may occur if, for instance, the relative clauses are not properly used or marked within a longer sentence. For example, if we say a) *A man saw the woman with the bribe money who argued with the police officers*, it may not be clear who the person who argued with the police officer is – the man, or the woman. Therefore, if that person is the man, the correct sentence would be b) *A man, who argued with the police officers, saw the woman with the bribe money*, but if the person who argued with the police officers is the woman, the appropriate version would be c) *A man saw the woman with the bribe money, who argued with the police officers*. Another cause of misunderstanding in law enforcement contexts may be the incorrect placement of the relative clause when modifying a given headword. Thus, for example, if the relative clause is not placed adjacent to the headword it modifies, the sentence will acquire a completely different meaning (Ajero, O.M., 2025:3870). For instance, if we say 1) *The policeman whom the old woman had accused of corruption attacked the journalist*, the relative pronoun *whom the old woman had accused of corruption* refers to the policeman – its headword, and the rest of the sentence tells us that the police officer in question attacked the journalist. But, if we change the location of the relative clause, and say 2) *The policeman attacked the journalist whom the old woman had accused of corruption*, the relative clause is attached to a wrong headword (*the journalist*), and now the journalist becomes the one accused of corruption, which is totally unrelated to the original correct sentence.

Therefore, avoiding misunderstandings and ambiguities is of crucial importance in law enforcement contexts, given the importance of details and accuracy in providing descriptions and detailed information of various kinds communicated by law enforcement officers daily. The lack of accuracy and attention to details may lead to far-reaching consequences of legal or other nature for any party affected by the content of the texts in question. For this reason, in the sections that follow we will discuss the link between relative clauses and the topic of corruption, with specific ideas about integrating relative clauses in English language instruction focused on topics connected with corruption.

2. RELATIVE CLAUSES IN ENGLISH AND THEIR USE IN CORRUPTION-RELATED CONTEXTS

Relative clauses are a type of subordinate clauses. They typically describe the noun or the noun phrase they are preceded by, giving information about them, either essential or non-essential. When referring to nouns or noun phrases, they are generally classified as: 1) defining relative clauses, or 2) non-defining relative clauses.

Defining relative clauses give information about the noun they refer to “in such a way to distinguish it from other nouns of the same class” (Thomson & Martinet, 1986:81). Therefore, a defining relative clause “is essential to the clear understanding of the noun” (ibid), and must not be omitted, since its omission will affect the understanding of the noun in question due to the loss of the crucial information which defines it. For instance, if we say that 1) *The woman left the country*, the noun *woman* may refer to any woman in general. However, if we say that 2) *The woman who misappropriated the state funds left the country*, the reference to the woman in question is clear. In this case, it is the defining relative clause *who misappropriated the state funds* which provided this essential information about the noun. Defining relative clauses can also be used after pronouns, especially indefinite ones, such as *anyone*, *everyone*, and *everything* (Sinclair et al., 1997:363), like in the sentence *Anyone who breaks the law will be punished*. Defining relative clauses are also called restrictive relative clauses. Non-defining relative clauses, on the other hand, give additional information which is non-essential and can be omitted without affecting the meaning of the entire sentence. Thus, for instance, we can say that 3) *My neighbour Maria, whose daughter lives abroad, misappropriated the state funds*, where the relative clause *whose daughter lives abroad* gives us information about the country of residence of Maria’s daughter, which is totally irrelevant in this context. We can delete this clause, and we will still know who the person is. This is an example of a non-defining relative clause, which is always inserted between two commas or dashes, and is also called a non-restrictive relative clause. In some cases, relative clauses can even modify sentence parts or entire sentences. When used with this function, they are referred to as sentential relative clauses (Aarts, Chalker & Weiner, 2014:359), or connective clauses (Thomson & Martinet, 1986:88).

Relative clauses are introduced by relative pronouns. The typical relative pronouns referring to people are *who* and *that* (e.g. *The police arrested the politician who/that received bribe*), while those referring to objects are *which* and *that* (e.g. *The police found the money which/that was extorted from the local businessman.*). In non-defining relative clauses, only *which* can be used. As object of the relative clause, one can use the pronoun *whom*, as well as *who* and *that* (Sinclair et al., 1997:364). Thus, we can say *The woman whom/who/that Steve had blackmailed reported him to the police*, where the relative pronoun is the object of the verb *blackmail*. Possession for both people and things is expressed with *whose* (E.g. *I saw the man whose son was involved in the grand corruption scandal in our city; This is the woman whose safe was used to hide the embezzled money.*). Additionally, *where* can act as a relative pronoun denoting location (E.g. *This is the place where the corrupt official was caught with the stolen money.*), *when* for denoting time (E.g. *The suspect provided an alibi for the day when the money was stolen from the company safe*), etc.

With reference to corruption-related issues, relative clauses can be used in various situations, both in writing and in speech. Generally speaking, relative clauses in law-enforcement contexts, including the area of corruption, can be used for: a) describing persons (e.g. *The man who embezzled the funds fled the country*); b) describing objects

(e.g. *The suitcase which contained the counterfeited banknotes was found in a black car at the border crossing*); c) describing places (e.g. *The building where the fake credit cards were hidden is located on the outskirts of the city*), etc. Also, examples of relative clauses can be found in many written documents addressing the issue of corruption. Thus, for example, in Transparency International Corruption Perception Index 2024, we can read that “corruption can also deepen the marginalisation of vulnerable populations who suffer disproportionately from the negative effects of climate change” (Transparency International, 2025a:6). Also, in an OSCE Report we can read that “the OSCE’s efforts to combat corruption and promote good governance are an integral part of its comprehensive approach to security, which encompasses politico-military, economic and environmental, and human dimensions” (OSCE, 2024:4). In addition, in a UNODC (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime) report we can read that “individuals who expose corrupt practices in their workplace or work environment play an essential role in a country’s anti-corruption efforts” (UNODC, 2024:36), etc.

3. RELATIVE CLAUSES THROUGH CORRUPTION-RELATED VOCABULARY IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

Taking into consideration the relevance of the knowledge of correctly using relative clauses in the domain of law enforcement, in this section we will propose several ideas for teaching relative clauses of both types (defining and non-defining), while simultaneously introducing selected vocabulary associated with corruption, based on pair work and group work.

3.1. Sample Activity 1: Types of Corruption

When learning about corruption, it is of high importance for law enforcement students to be able to distinguish between different types of corruption in terms of their specific elements, similarities and differences. Considering this, we suggest an activity in which the students work in groups and are given the task to fill in missing sentence parts in definitions of several types of corruption. All missing parts from the definitions contain relative clauses. The definitions are taken from the website of Transparency International. This activity is aimed at practising the use of both defining and non-defining relative clauses.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

Missing sentence parts:

- 1) *who abuse their position to sustain their power, status and wealth*
- 2) *who often are trying to access basic goods or services in places like hospitals, schools, police departments and other agencies*
- 3) *that benefits the few at the expense of the many, and causes serious and widespread harm to individuals and society*

1.PETTY CORRUPTION
 Everyday abuse of entrusted power by public officials in their interactions with ordinary citizens,

Key:
Everyday abuse of entrusted power by public officials in their interactions with ordinary

citizens, who often are trying to access basic goods or services in places like hospitals, schools, police departments and other agencies. (Transparency International, 2025c)

Vocabulary in focus:

abuse of entrusted power
public official

2.GRAND CORRUPTION

The abuse of high-level power.....
It often goes unpunished.

Key:

The abuse of high-level power that benefits the few at the expense of the many, and causes serious and widespread harm to individuals and society. It often goes unpunished. (ibid, 2025b)

Vocabulary in focus:

abuse of high-level power
benefit
harm to individuals and society

3.POLITICAL CORRUPTION

Manipulation of policies, institutions and rules of procedure in the allocation of resources and financing by political decision makers,

Key:

Manipulation of policies, institutions and rules of procedure in the allocation of resources and financing by political decision makers, who abuse their position to sustain their power, status and wealth. (ibid, 2025d)

Vocabulary in focus:

manipulation of policies, institutions, rules and procedures
allocation of resources
to abuse one's position
to sustain one's power, status and wealth

As a follow-up activity, students can be asked to work in pairs, find the definitions of other types of corruption, remove the relative clauses, and work with their partners filling up the missing parts and discussing the relative clause in question and the corruption-related vocabulary the definition contains. The list with other types of corruption may include the following: ***endemic corruption, public corruption, corporate corruption, systemic corruption***, etc.

3.2. Sample Activity 2: Nepotism vs. Cronyism

Nepotism and cronyism are widely invoked concepts in the study of corruption. However, many English language learners, including those specializing in law enforcement, struggle to differentiate between them. For that reason, we suggest an activity where the students, working in pairs, are given jumbled sentences. They should rearrange the words to form the original sentences, which should contain non-defining relative clauses. This activity is aimed at practising specifically the use of non-defining relative clauses.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

Example 1:

(favorising power the nepotism of is family the meritocracy one's opposite of position refers to which members of own using)

Key:

Nepotism, which is the opposite of meritocracy, refers to favouring members of one's own family using the position of power.

Example 2:

(awarding which in cronyism meant is to friends by power advantages originally those "friendship")

Key:

Cronyism, which originally meant "friendship", is awarding advantages to friends by those in power.

As a follow-up activity, the students can be given definitions of other -ISMS related to corruption, and they should work in groups and insert non-defining relative clauses to add more information about the words in question. This could encompass -ISMS such as *favouritism*, which refers to "unfair support shown to one person or group, especially by someone in authority" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025b), *clientelism*, which means "a political or social system based on the relation of client to patron with the client giving political or financial support to a patron (as in the form of votes) in exchange for some special privilege or benefit" (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2025), etc.

3.3. Sample Activity 3: Acronyms

The English language abounds in acronyms, especially those denoting organizations, institutions, and documents addressing corruption-related issues. This makes acronyms a necessary part of English language instruction in the field of law enforcement. With this in mind, we suggest an activity in which the students are distributed a list of acronyms related to corruption. They should work in pairs and try to find the meanings of the acronyms. When they finish, each pair presents the meanings of the acronyms, using a relative clause in describing their meanings and what they refer to. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining and non-defining relative clauses.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

List of corruption-related acronyms:

GRECO (Group of States Against Corruption)

FATF (Financial Action Task Force)

TI (Transparency International)

UNCAC (United Nations Convention Against Corruption)

OLAF (European Anti-Fraud Office (Office européen de lutte antifraude))

DCAF (Democratic Control of Armed Forces (now formally known as DCAF – Geneva Centre for Security Sector Governance))

Example:

OLAF

OLAF is the acronym which refers to the European Anti-Fraud Office. OLAF, which was established in 1999, investigates cases of fraud, corruption and other criminal acts within the EU institutions...

As a follow-up activity, students can work in pairs to find other acronyms related to corruption and present their meanings to the class, inserting non-defining relative clauses in their explanations, whenever possible.

3.4. Sample Activity 4: Crimes Related to Corruption

Since acts of corruption are central to the commission of many crimes, we suggest an activity in which the students work in groups and are given a list with crimes rooted in corruption. One student should look up the meanings of the crimes and write two sentences which define them. The other students should join the two sentences for each crime into one, using the appropriate relative pronoun. This activity is aimed at practising the use of all relative pronouns.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

List of crimes:

influence peddling

abuse of discretionary powers

breach of official duty

misuse of public resources

Example 1:

influence peddling

Trading in influence refers to the illegal activity of a politician doing something for somebody in return for payment. (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, 2025b)

It is also called trading in influence.

Key:

Influence peddling, which is also called trading in influence, refers to the illegal activity of a politician doing something for somebody in return for payment.

As a follow-up activity students may work in groups to browse the Criminal Code of their country and make a list of crimes which are rooted in corruption with two sentences describing each crime. They should then work together to join the sentences into one, following the analogy in the presented classroom activity.

3.5. Sample Activity 5: Ethic(s) vs. Integrity

The concepts of ethic(s) and integrity, both related to corruption, are often used interchangeably by English language learners, despite their semantic differences. For that reason, in this section we suggest a classroom exercise where the students will be able to make a distinction between them. The students are given definitions of the nouns *ethic(s)* and *integrity*. For instance, *ethic*, typically used in plural as *ethics*, could be defined as “moral principles that control or influence a person’s behaviour” (Oxford Learner’s Dictionaries, 2025a), or “a system of accepted beliefs that control behaviour, especially such a system based on morals” (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025a). On the other hand, *integrity* could be defined as “the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles” (Oxford Learner’s Dictionaries, 2025c), “the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles that you refuse to change” (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025b), etc. After the introductory discussion on the comparison of these two concepts, the students are given several sentences where the missing words are either *ethic(s)* or *integrity*. They should work in pairs and try to guess and insert the missing word in each sentence. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining relative clauses with *which/that*.

The following is an excerpt from this activity:

- 1) is a term WHICH is associated with persons (Key: *INTEGRITY*)
- 2) is a concept WHICH is broader in scope (Key: *ETHIC(S)*)
- 3) is a noun WHICH can be used with the following verbs: to compromise, to undermine, to question (Key: *INTEGRITY*)
- 4) is a noun WHICH is usually used in plural (Key: *ETHIC(S)*)

As a follow-up activity, students may be given a task to find other pairs of words which refer to similar concepts and may possibly be confusing for them. They should study the meanings of those pairs of words and write short paragraphs in which they will explain their differences, using the appropriate relative pronouns. Word pairs of this type in the context of corruption may include the following: *corruption* and *bribery*, *extortion* and *blackmail*, *fraud* and *scam*, etc.

3.6. Sample Activity 6: Easily confused words related to corruption

English terminology in the field of corruption contains many words that might cause confusion among speakers, because of the similarity in their pronunciation, the common root they are derived from, the same words they collocate with, etc. One example of this is the adjectives *corrupt*, *corruptive* and *corruptible*, which share the same root but denote three characteristics of persons, situations, things etc. In this activity the students will learn to differentiate between these three adjectives, while practising the use of the relative pronouns *who*, *which* and *that*. For this purpose, they will be given a gapped text in

which these three adjectives are described. The students should work in groups and insert the missing relative pronouns and adjectives to form meaningful sentences. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining clauses with *who*, *which* and *that*.

The following is an excerpt from this activity:

CORRUPT, CORRUPTIVE or CORRUPTIBLE?

A person is may possibly be corrupted. Behaviours, situations, circumstances, etc. have the potential to lead to corruption are referred to as A person is has a history of corruption-related practices.

Key:

A person WHO is CORRUPTIBLE may possibly be corrupted. Behaviours, situations, circumstances, etc. WHICH/THAT have the potential to lead to corruption are referred to as CORRUPTIVE. A person WHO is CORRUPT has a history of corruption-related practices.

As a follow-up, students may work in pairs and try to find other words which, for instance, are derived from the same root, analyse their meanings, similarities, differences and contexts of use and then present their findings to the other students in the class. The list may include adjectives such as *bribed* and *briable*, for instance, and many other words.

3.7. Sample Activity 7: Authentic Documents with Relative Clauses

When performing their duties, law-enforcement professionals will handle many documents of authentic nature, often in other languages, including English. Therefore, English language instruction should include use of such documents in which the learners will be able to acquire both grammar and lexical knowledge in the field. To illustrate this, in this section we suggest an activity in which the students are given excerpts from an authentic document, in this specific example GRECO's 2024 report titled: *Anti-corruption Trends, Challenges and Good Practices in Europe & the United States of America* (Council of Europe, 2025), from the section addressing corruption prevention in law enforcement agencies. The students should work in pairs, find sentences which contain relative clauses and separate them into two sentences, eliminating the relative pronouns. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining and non-defining relative clauses with *which* and *whose*.

The following is an excerpt from this activity:

Example 1) Policy on gifts applicable in the Police – Lithuania

“Lithuania established a policy on Gifts applicable in the Lithuanian Police and set up a Gifts Register and an Illegal Remuneration Register in the Police Department Management System. The policy sets out gifts valuation criteria, rules and thresholds on acceptable gifts, as well as their register, WHICH is public and is updated regularly.” (Council of Europe, 2025:20)

Key:

1. *The policy sets out gifts valuation criteria, rules and thresholds on acceptable gifts, as well as their register.*
2. *The register is public and is updated regularly.*

Vocabulary in focus:

a policy on Gifts

Gifts Register

Illegal Remuneration Register

gifts valuation criteria

thresholds on acceptable gifts

Example 2) **Recording and evaluating gifts – Serbia**

“A Commission for the Registration of Gifts, established in 2021 within the Ministry of the Interior, and WHOSE members are appointed by the Minister for a period of three years, is responsible, in particular, for maintaining records of gifts received and their disposal.” (ibid)

Key:

1. *A Commission for the Registration of Gifts, established in 2021 within the Ministry of the Interior, responsible, in particular, for maintaining records of gifts received and their disposal.*
2. *The members of this Commission are appointed by the Minister for a period of three years.*

“In January 2022, the Instruction of the Minister of the Interior lowered the threshold of admissible gifts to not more than 10% of the average monthly salary in Serbia, which is a very significant reduction from the previously existing permissible threshold.” (ibid)

Key:

1. *In January 2022, the Instruction of the Minister of the Interior lowered the threshold of admissible gifts to not more than 10% of the average monthly salary in Serbia.*
2. *This is a very significant reduction from the previously existing permissible threshold.*

Vocabulary in focus:

A Commission for the Registration of Gifts

maintaining records of gifts

threshold of admissible gifts

As a follow-up activity, students may work in pairs to find laws in their country which address the issue of corruption, identify and make a list of sentences containing relative clauses. After that, they should give the sentences to other pairs of students in the class and ask them to split the long sentences into two or more parts, by eliminating the relative pronouns and inserting the appropriate changes to form grammatically correct sentences.

CONCLUSION

The activities detailed in the paper lead to the conclusion that it is possible to teach relative clauses in English via presentation of corruption-related vocabulary and vice versa. This can be accomplished through interactive classroom activities based on pair and group work. The activities described in the paper focused on the differences between various corruption types, the meanings of different acronyms related to corruption, the peculiarities of certain crimes rooted in corruption, the difference between similar and confusing words associated with corruption, the practical use of relative clauses in authentic documents addressing corruption-related issues, etc. However, they can be modified and adapted for teaching other grammatical structures and specialized vocabulary in law enforcement or other domains. Furthermore, they can be used for teaching specialized law enforcement content from other subjects, with appropriate adaptations.

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CORRUPTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION – VIEWS AND EXPERIENCES OF STUDENTS FROM THE FACULTY OF SECURITY – SKOPJE

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Abstract

Corruption in higher education poses a significant threat to academic integrity and quality of education. It can take many forms, including bribery for passing exams, nepotism, sexual extortion, and the sale of academic materials. Such practices not only erode trust in the education system, but also have the potential to destroy the ideals of a young student and affect the person they will become after completing the studies.

The primary goal of this study is to conduct an initial research among students across all three cycles of study at the Faculty of Security – Skopje, which will later be expanded to include students from the entire University “St. Kliment Ohridski” – Bitola. Thus, this paper examines the issue of corruption in higher education based on a survey conducted among students at the Faculty of Security – Skopje. The research uses the definition of corruption as outlined in the Rulebook about the work and remuneration of the authorized person for receiving corruption reports at the University “St. Kliment Ohridski” – Bitola.

This study assesses students’ knowledge, attitudes, and personal experiences related to corruption in the academic environment. The anonymous questionnaire explores students’ perceptions of the impact of corruption and identifies the most common corrupt practices they encounter. Furthermore, the study explores whether students have witnessed or experienced corruption, their willingness to report such incidents, and their awareness of reporting mechanisms. Finally, the paper gathers student suggestions for effective measures to reduce corruption in higher education.

This research provides a comprehensive overview of the challenges and perceptions surrounding academic corruption, offering valuable insights for future policy development and institutional reforms.

Key words: *corruption, higher education, students*

INTRODUCTION

Corruption in higher education undermines the very foundation of academic integrity and the credibility of educational institutions. It distorts merit-based evaluation, fosters inequality, and weakens students' trust in the system designed to nurture ethical and competent professionals. In contexts where education is considered both a public good and a pathway to professional success, corruption becomes a particularly dangerous phenomenon, as it affects not only institutional reputation but also the formation of social and moral values among future professionals.

Corruption in higher education is a pervasive global challenge, with evidence demonstrating that it affects institutions across all regions to varying degrees (Glendinning, Orim, & King, 2019). This issue manifests in diverse forms, including political interference, nepotism, fraudulent academic credentials, bribery, and academic dishonesty. The scope and impact of corruption undermine the integrity, quality, and accessibility of higher education worldwide. North Macedonia is no exception to these challenges. Recognizing the global and local prevalence of corruption highlights the urgent need for comprehensive strategies to promote transparency, accountability, and integrity in higher education institutions.

This study focuses on the perceptions, attitudes, and personal experiences of students from the Faculty of Security – Skopje regarding corruption in higher education. The research was conducted through an anonymous online survey distributed via Google Forms to students from all three cycles of studies at the faculty. The purpose of the study was to obtain an initial insight into how students perceive corruption in their academic environment, their awareness of reporting mechanisms, and their suggestions for effective anti-corruption measures.

At the beginning of the survey, respondents were provided with a clear and context-specific definition of corruption, consistent with the Rulebook on the work and remuneration of the authorized person for receiving reports of corruption at the University "St. Kliment Ohridski" - Bitola (University "St. Kliment Ohridski" – Bitola, 2020). According to this Rulebook: "Corruption refers to the intentional actions of an official who, directly or through an intermediary, requests, receives, or accepts a promise of any benefit for themselves or for a third party, in order to act or refrain from acting in line with their duties, or to exercise their responsibilities contrary to official obligations. It also refers to intentional actions by a person who, directly or through an intermediary, promises or provides any benefit to an official, for themselves or for a third party, with the aim of influencing the official to act or refrain from acting in line with their duties, or to exercise their responsibilities contrary to official obligations."

Despite the relevance of the topic and the institutional support for conducting the research, the response rate was relatively low — only 95 students out of 1,207 participated. The reasons for such **limited engagement** remain uncertain, though several possible explanations exist. One possibility is **survey fatigue**, as students may have been oversaturated with online questionnaires following years of increased digital communication. Another factor may be **timing**, since the survey was distributed during the examination period, when students are less inclined to engage in additional academic activities. Finally, the **sensitivity of the topic** itself could have discouraged participation, as corruption remains a subject that many perceive as risky to discuss openly, even under conditions of anonymity.

Nevertheless, the collected data provide valuable insights into students' perceptions and the broader institutional climate. They reveal not only the extent of awareness and distrust in formal mechanisms but also the willingness of students to propose constructive measures for change. The findings thus serve as an initial but significant step toward understanding and addressing corruption within academic institutions, offering directions for both further research and practical reform.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The sixteen questions of the survey were divided into four sections: 1. "Demographic data" (two questions), 2. "Assessment of students' views" (five questions), 3. "Personal experiences" (five questions), and 4. "Awareness and recommendations" (4 questions). And as mentioned before, the survey was submitted to 1207 students of the Faculty of Security – Skopje. However, their response was very low; i.e. only 7.9% (95 students) filled out the questionnaire, out of which 61.1% were female and 38.9% were male.

Chart No. 1 Gender of the students who filled out the questionnaire

Since the Faculty of Security – Skopje organizes lectures on three cycles of studies (first, second and third), the survey was submitted to students that are / have been studying in the years 2020 – 2024. Or to be more precise, the survey was delivered to:

- 1055 students of the first cycle of studies,
- 112 students of the second cycle of studies, and
- 40 students of the third cycle of studies.

Apart from gender, Section 1 ('Demographic data') collected information on the students' cycle of studies. The 95 collected responses show that the highest response rate is among students enrolled on the first cycle of studies. In essence, 64.2% of the students are enrolled on the first cycle of studies (18.9% are attending first year, 25.3% are attending second year, 10.5% are attending third year and 9.5% are attending fourth year), 21.5% on the second cycle of studies and only 14.7% on the third cycle of studies. This distribution is also due to the fact that most of the students that are enrolled at the Faculty of Security – Skopje and to whom the questionnaire was sent are the first-cycle students.

Chart No. 2 The enrolled cycle of studies

In connection with the research topic, by the first question of Section 2. “Assessment of students’ views” the students were asked to give their opinion on whether corruption in higher education affects the quality of studies in the Republic of Macedonia, and at the same time four answers were offered to them (Does not affect at all; Partially does not affect; Partially affects; Affects a lot). From their choices, it can be concluded that students believe that corruption has an impact on the quality of studies because 97.6% of them chose the two offered options “Partially affects” (72.6%) and “Affects a lot” (25.3%). On the other hand, only 2.1% chose the option “Partially does not affect” and none of them chose the option “Does not affect at all”.

Chart No. 3 Students’ perception of the impact of corruption on the quality of the studies

Next, the students were asked to rate the level of corruption in the higher education in the Republic of Macedonia from 1 to 5, with a note that “1” means that there is no corruption and “5” means that there is a lot of corruption. Most students rated the level of corruption in higher education with 4 (40%), followed by 3 (29.5%), 5 (21.1%), 2 (8.4%) and 1 (1%). This is truly worrying, as 90.6% of students gave corruption a “passing” rating (from 3 and up).

Chart No. 4 Students' perception of the level of corruption in higher education in the Republic of Macedonia

As a follow-up to the previous question, students were asked once again to rate the level of corruption, but now within their own faculty. Contrary to the above, most of the students chose the option 1 or “no corruption” (34.7%), followed by option 2 (27.4%). The other students, or 37.9%, have chosen option 3 (22.1%), 4 (10.5%) and 5 (5.3%). This implies that the level of corruption within the Faculty of Security – Skopje, based on the opinion of its students, does not follow the trend of the level of corruption in the higher education as a whole, but on the contrary - the level of corruption within the Faculty of Security – Skopje received a negative rating or a rating of 1 (“no corruption”), and such rating is commendable.

Chart No. 5 Students' perception of the level of corruption at the Faculty of Security – Skopje

When asked about the forms of corrupt behaviour that, in their opinion, most often occur within higher education, students were allowed to select multiple answers. A considerable proportion of respondents, i.e. 74.7%, perceive that the most common form is when professors pressure students to purchase their books in order to pass an exam or obtain a higher grade. The second most frequently perceived form, selected by 54.7% of

respondents, is giving money to a professor to pass an exam or achieve a higher grade, followed by giving gifts for the same purpose (40%). Furthermore, 17.9% of students believed that professors sometimes pressure students into intimate relationships in exchange for passing or receiving a higher grade. It is important to emphasize that none of the respondents believe that students are favoured because of family, friendship or other personal ties with professors.

Since the last provided option or “Other” was chosen by 9.5% of the students, they were asked to provide an answer why they did so, i.e. to point out to other behaviours that have not been listed in the options provided above. The answers that they gave are the following: using a political and other business connections to acquire inappropriate degrees and obtain positions/titles in higher education that are not deserved and have been acquired in a corrupt manner, e.g. assistant, associate professor, full professor, etc. at the expense of degrees obtained from prestigious international or domestic faculties that are not properly valued and evaluated; urging through a friend who is close to the professor or through a professor who is close to the professor with whom the student is supposed to take the exam; certain services in return; “giving money to buy a degree, but not at my faculty - this happens more often at private faculties”; family ties, children or relatives of professors at the faculty; seeking connections through mutual friends, and one of them responded with “No”.

Chart No. 6 Students’ perception of forms of corrupt behaviour that most often occur within higher education

The first question of Section 3. “Personal experiences”, was about whether the students have ever witnessed or have been a victim of corrupt practices at the Faculty of Security – Skopje, and 81.1% answered “No”.

Chart No. 7 Students' experience of witnessing or being victims of corruption at the Faculty of Security – Skopje

The others chose “Yes” (18.9%) and pointed out several situations, such as obligation to buy textbooks (through “book package” or from the professors themselves – not to have a possibility to use scripts or previously used books in order to save money, as well as the “book package” is a must in order to obtain an index; to buy a textbook in order to take an exam; to be forced by the professor to buy a book in order to take an exam; anticipating insufficient knowledge, based on the fact that he/she did not buy a book, which he/she thinks that is inadequate for the level of knowledge required for the study cycle; not buying the book had cost him/her a lower grade; without buying the book, it was not possible to get a grade on an exam that he/she had already passed; professor takes money from the student; not choosing the best candidate for a job position “assistant” who had 10 as an average of grades, had a master's degree from a prestigious international faculty, as well as had an evidently far better CV; to be a witness when an urging happened in order for a student to pass the test; being a witness to a request on intimate relations. From the given responses, it can be concluded that students evaluate as a negative behaviour, i.e. a corrupt practice, when they are being forced to buy books (from a professor or through a “book package”).

Having identified the behaviours that students perceive as corrupt within higher education, it is equally important to explore their reactions when encountering such practices. The following findings focus on students' willingness, or lack thereof, to report corruption.

Chart No. 8 Display of the percentage of reported corruption cases

The findings of our study reveal that 82.5% of students who faced some form of corrupt behaviour in higher education chose not to report it. For comparison, this tendency of non-reporting by students is confirmed by the discussion held by the Institute for Democracy during the event “Forms of Corruption in Higher Education”, which concluded that although students are aware of corruption within academia, they rarely take steps to report it (Institute for Democracy, 2023). This alignment points to a significant gap between the recognition of corrupt practices and the willingness to act on them, driven by factors such as mistrust in institutions, fear of negative consequences, and feelings of helplessness. These insights underscore the urgent need to establish trust-enhancing, accessible, and protective reporting mechanisms to empower students in combating corruption effectively.

Students who indicated that they chose not to report the incident were subsequently asked to identify the primary reasons behind their decision. The summarized results are presented below.

Chart No. 9 Main reasons for not reporting corruption cases

Distrust and scepticism are the biggest obstacles – more than three quarters (78.2%) of students do not report due to distrust in the institutions and lack of belief that there will be a result. Fear is less prevalent, but still a significant factor (12.5%). The information aspect (not knowing where to report) is not a problem, which may indicate that the mechanisms are known, but are not considered efficient. No respondents indicated threats as a reason for not reporting.

Despite no indication of threats or lack of knowledge of where to report, it is important to highlight that when asked about familiarity with the corruption reporting mechanisms at the faculty, 46.3% of respondents stated they were not aware of them, while the remainder confirmed their knowledge. This suggests a significant portion still lack awareness of internal procedures.

Chart No. 10 Familiarity with the mechanisms for reporting corruption at the faculty

The apparent inconsistency between these two survey findings where students initially do not identify lack of knowledge as a key obstacle, yet nearly half later report not knowing where and how to report corruption, can be interpreted through several complementary factors. First, the framing of the questions likely influenced the responses: when asked about reasons for not reporting, students focused on attitudinal barriers such as distrust and scepticism, while the second question specifically prompted reflection on procedural awareness. This indicates that many students may have only a general sense that reporting mechanisms exist, without concrete knowledge of how to access them. Furthermore, the prevailing distrust in institutional responsiveness may diminish the perceived relevance of such knowledge, as students who doubt the effectiveness of reporting channels may not consider them a viable option regardless of awareness. Together, these findings reveal both a perceptual and institutional gap that hinders effective anti-corruption engagement within the academic setting.

Respondents were also asked to indicate which method of reporting corruption in higher education they consider to be the most acceptable, and the results are provided below.

Chart No. 11 The most favourable mechanisms for reporting corruption according to students

Students show the highest level of trust in the authorized person, indicating a preference for a formal and independent reporting mechanism, which underscores the need for institutions to actively promote and strengthen this channel. Faculty leadership, primarily the dean, is the second most trusted option, reflecting some student confidence but more in administrative or managerial roles rather than independent ones. The student ombudsman plays a notable yet smaller role, suggesting potential for further development as an intermediary. Only two students selected "Other", with one stating corruption reports should go to the police and Public Prosecutor’s Office, and the other recommending reporting to the dean in the presence of faculty staff. This demonstrates that although there are diverse opinions, most answers aligned with the survey’s predefined options rather than original suggestions.

Finally, students were asked, in an open-ended question, what they thought should be done to reduce corruption in higher education. A wide range of responses were received, and for the sake of clarity, they were grouped into six larger clusters.

Cluster analysis

➤ **Financial incentives and material status**

- Increase in professors' salaries.
- State support and better standards for teaching staff.
- Reduce the possibility of corruption through higher salaries and professional conditions.

Students suggest that improving professors' salaries and professional conditions can reduce corruption by decreasing financial motives. This cluster reflects the belief that economic stability for staff diminishes the temptation to engage in corrupt acts. Higher salaries raise the "cost" of unethical conduct, making corruption less economically rational for individuals (Klitgaard, 2011).

➤ **Transparency, digitalization and modernization**

- Introducing fully digitalized and anonymized processes (taking exams through platforms with hidden identities).
- Introducing a database of questions, public assessment.

This cluster highlights the importance of using technology to make processes objective and less prone to manipulation, such as anonymized digital exams and public databases. It addresses structural vulnerabilities by limiting opportunities for corrupt behaviour.

➤ **Control, supervision and sanctions**

- Independent inspection bodies for control of faculties.
- Constant checks of professors and exams.
- Introduction of rapid disciplinary procedures.
- Strict penalties and public announcement of corrupt individuals

The call for independent inspections, swift disciplinary action, and strict penalties aligns with deterrence theory, which posits that crime (in our case corruption) decreases when the expected cost of punishment outweighs the benefits (Onwudiwe, Odo, & Onyeozili, n.d., Johnson, 2019). Visible enforcement and public exposure serve to increase perceived risks, thus deterring corrupt behaviour.

➤ **Reporting and protection of whistleblowers**

- Introducing persons/authorized bodies for reporting.
- Anonymous mechanisms and protection of students who report.
- Encouraging students to actively report.
- Involving the student ombudsman and independent bodies.

The emphasis here is on creating safe, anonymous channels for reporting corruption and protecting those who come forward. Involving independent bodies and the student ombudsman reflects recognition of the critical role of trusted intermediaries in anti-corruption efforts.

➤ **Ethical culture and awareness**

- Raising public and academic awareness.
- Organizing public forums and discussions.
- Promoting integrity and ethical values.
- Creating a culture of merit and valuing knowledge

Students call for raising awareness and actively promoting academic integrity and ethical behaviour. This cluster targets the root cultural causes of corruption by advocating for a shift in values toward meritocracy and honesty.

➤ **Reforming the education system and staff**

- Replacing corrupt professors.
- Better staff selection and strict criteria for teachers.
- Control over professor-student relations.
- Reducing the role of private faculties or closing them.

Replacing corrupt staff and enforcing strict hiring criteria seek to ensure integrity at the personnel level. Control over professor-student relations and scrutiny of private faculties focus on systemic reforms that prevent abuse of power and commercialized education models prone to corruption.

The diversity of clusters shows that students recognize corruption as a multifaceted problem requiring solutions beyond mere punishment. They emphasize prevention through transparency, adequate financial incentives, ethical culture, and institutional reform. The balance between procedural mechanisms (digitalization, reporting) and cultural shifts (ethics, awareness) highlights a mature understanding of the complexity of corruption control in academia.

CONCLUSION

Distrust in institutions is the biggest barrier to fighting corruption, as most students believe reporting will not lead to change. Students demand systemic and structural solutions: independent oversight, digitalization, and transparent procedures that minimize personal influence. Corruption is seen as stemming from both material causes (low professor salaries, weak conditions) and cultural/systemic factors (nepotism, lack of meritocracy).

The most realistic and supported measures are a mix of preventive and repressive actions: promoting ethics and awareness while also applying strict sanctions and institutional supervision. Radical ideas (closing private faculties, replacing all staff) exist, but most students focus on practical reforms such as transparency, reporting mechanisms, and modernization.

The main limitation of the study is the small sample size, which does not allow generalization. With only 95 respondents out of a total of 1,209 students, the results should be interpreted cautiously. The limited participation may reflect methodological or contextual constraints, such as low motivation to engage in online surveys, exam-period timing, or reluctance to address sensitive topics related to institutional integrity. Nevertheless, this limitation underscores the importance of conducting broader, longitudinal, and comparative studies across different faculties and universities to obtain more robust and generalizable data.

Despite its constraints, this research provides an important initial step toward understanding how students perceive corruption within academia and how these perceptions shape their trust, engagement, and moral outlook. The results underline the urgent need for higher education institutions to strengthen transparency, accountability, and communication with students. Building trust is not merely a procedural goal but a moral imperative, one essential for restoring integrity and ensuring that universities remain spaces of fairness, knowledge, and ethical growth.

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STATE OF AFFAIRS AND CHALLENGES IN SOLVING SYSTEMIC CORRUPTION THROUGH INTEGRITY

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Abstract

The state institutions in the Republic of North Macedonia have developed a culture of dealing with anti-corruption as external policy, meaning they are all either establishing a unit for anti-corruption or developing sector-specific strategies for dealing with corruption. It proves that the best method for establishing institutional mechanisms for building institutions resilient to corruption is to introduce procedures with built-in mechanisms i.e., procedures that prevent corruption within themselves alongside the external policies. These procedures can diminish the potential corruption that institution can face, or the risk is minimized. The paper will examine two institutions with concrete examples of how to build in anti-corruption procedures, such as the State Audit Office and the State Commission for the Protection of Corruption. For both institutions, the aim is to explore what type of built-in mechanisms or internal procedures can prevent corruption and ensure integrity.

Keywords: *integrity, policy, corruption, resilience, North Macedonia*

1. INTRODUCTION

Establishing institutional mechanisms for building institutions resilient to corruption through internal procedures, rather than addressing this issue through external policies, is considered the best method for preventing corruption. It is expected that applying these procedures can help diminish potential corruption. The promotion of integrity fosters an environment of trust and accountability, and it is crucial to sustainable and inclusive economic development (OECD, 2019). Often, state institutions approach anti-corruption as an external policy, an external add-on, rather than an embedded practice. However, professional management globally is trying to ensure honesty and integrity of public decisions and to broaden the perspective on ethics to include issues of transparency, professional responsibility, democratic values, civil liberties, respect of human rights, and compliance with the rule of law (Jreisat, 2022). Following these tendencies, the institutions in North Macedonia are prone to create special units or sector-specific strategies, despite the fact that these are often fragmented approaches and most of the time at risk of becoming formalistic exercises. This formality results in limited effectiveness of the undertaken efforts. What is missing is a deeper integration of integrity into the everyday functioning of institutions that should not be an isolated policy, but rather the foundation of sustainable governance and public trust.

This paper will examine the efforts of the state institutions in the Republic of North Macedonia in establishing a culture of dealing with anti-corruption as internal policy

through establishing special units for anti-corruption, developing sector-specific strategies for dealing with corruption through the system of integrity. Despite the general findings applicable to the Macedonian institutional environment, the special focus will be on the two particular institutions that have major responsibility in fighting corruption, i.e. State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) and the State Audit Office (AUO). Both SCPC and AUO were selected since they have a dual role in the policy of integrity and prevention of corruption. Primarily, these two institutions should have an integrity system and built-in anti-corruption policies in their own procedures, i.e. for themselves, in the exercise of their legal powers. On the other hand, they supervise other institutions, i.e. they have a mandate to check whether another institution has abused or otherwise failed to conduct its operations in accordance with the law. Therefore, these two institutions, within the framework of their work and specific legal powers, have the authority to assess the work of other institutions, i.e. to check and give a finding whether another institution has and respects the policies for integrity and anti-corruption. The paper will answer what kind of preventive mechanisms and strategies they internally enforce, and do they prove to be effective. Methodologically, this paper will be based on the secondary sources, such as laws, bylaws, integrity guidelines, official reports and analysis that are publicly available. The final results of the research are pointing that, despite the external safeguards, the most successful strategy is establishing own system of integrity and procedures that will potentially prevent corruption within the institution. However, this system needs to be accepted as its own institutional culture and done in a more substantial rather than a formalistic way.

2 EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL MECHANISMS FOR THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN NORTH MACEDONIA

Integrity is the foundation of good governance and the fight against corruption, and at the same time, it is a strategic and sustainable response to the risks of corruption. It proves to be one of the most effective and most accepted mechanisms in international practice for preventing corruption. In essence, integrity means a firm adherence to a moral code by an individual based on relevant ethical values and normative principles (Feldheim, 2022). Establishing an integrity system in institutions contributes to eliminating the possibilities for the emergence of various forms of corruption and unethical behaviour in the public sector. The main idea of the system of integrity is to reduce the corruption risk, understood as an internal or external weakness in state bodies, public enterprises, and other public sector institutions, expressed as a specific procedure that opens up the possibility of corruption. This includes conflict of interest, incompatibility of functions, receiving gifts and other illegal payments, lobbying, fraud, inappropriate use of discretionary powers, illegal financing of political parties and campaigns, lack of a whistleblower protection system, trading in information or its unauthorized use, as well as non-transparency of procedures, documents and other issues that are of importance for the integrity (Pro-TRACCO, 2021).

Within the Macedonian legal framework, integrity means legal, independent, impartial, ethical, responsible, and transparent performance of activities, with which individuals protect their own image and the reputation of the institution for which they are responsible. That means they prevent risks and suspicions of possible corruption, thus ensuring confidence in the integrity of the performance of public functions and in the work of public institutions (Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, 2019). This is in line with the international standards and what is assumed to be the public

integrity, referring to consistent alignment and adherence to common ethical values, principles, and norms of support. That means prioritizing the public interest over the private one (OECD, 2017).

There is no specific definition of corruption, but in general, we can say that this is a direct or indirect gain, for oneself or for another, through abuse of public office, public authority, and/or official duty/position. In essence, it means that the one who performs a public function gives priority to their own private interest over the public one (Handbook for Integrity Officers, 2022). The notion of public interest is also difficult to define, but in a democratic society it is accepted that working for public interest means service towards the protection of the fundamental freedoms and rights of man and citizen, recognized by international law and established by the Constitution. This includes prevention of risks to health, defence and security, protection of the environment and nature, protection of property, freedom of the market and entrepreneurship, as well as enhancing the rule of law and prevention of crime and corruption (Pro-TRACCO, 2021). That can be in the same line but also as an opposite to the private interest, understood as material or immaterial interest of an official, which may influence his decision-making in the exercise of public powers and official duties. That can potentially lead the official in a conflict of interest, or a situation in which the private interest of an official may influence his impartiality in the exercise of public powers or official duties.

The concept of integrity encompasses all institutions at the local and central levels of government, including the system for combating corruption. Despite the absence of a clear definition of the main postulates related to the fight against the corruption, the legal frame in North Macedonia, through the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (2019); Criminal Code (1996 with changes and amendments); Law on Whistleblower Protection (2015); Law on Lobbying (2021); Law on Public Procurement (2021); Law on Public Financial Control (1990 with changes and amendments) in addition to the Law on Prevention of Money Laundering and Financing of Terrorism; Electoral Code; Law on Administrative Servants; Law on Public Sector Employees, etc., (n.b. some of them will be presented in the next section), penalize the behaviours that are at odds with or against established social values aimed at preventing and fighting the corruption.

2.1 Legal and institutional framework

In the efforts towards fighting corruption, the country has developed an extensive legal framework in which the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interests and the Criminal Code form the main pillar that have legal provisions on corruption-related offences. The Complementary laws — on whistleblowers, lobbying, public procurement, and financial control (Law on Whistleblower Protection; Law on Lobbying; Law on Public Procurement; Law on Public Financial Control) provide additional safeguards. At the strategic level, the National Anti-Corruption Strategy 2021–2025 sets institutional priorities. The undertaken international obligations stemming from the UN Convention against Corruption (2004) and Council of Europe conventions on corruption (1999), are reinforced by international commitments which demand not only compliance but also systemic change.

On the other hand, the institutional architecture is also broad. The main institution in the fight against corruption is the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (SCPC), which leads those efforts, and it is supported by the State Audit Office and the Bureau for Public Procurement. The Ministry of Justice, the Ministry of Interior, and the Public Prosecutor's Office all have roles in anti-corruption policies enforcement.

Additional support comes from the Financial Police, Customs Administration, and other oversight bodies.

Importantly, as an internal procedure, all the institutions in the public sector designate Integrity Officers (*лица за интегритет*) who act as internal supporters for the integrity policies, linking daily operations with broader anti-corruption frameworks. Therefore, the laws and the institutions provide the external mechanism, which checks the efficiency of policies and procedures for implementing the integrity concept, but the integrity officers are part of the internal mechanism. The internal mechanism consists of the responsibilities of the management in the institution itself, then of the designated integrity officer and other employees in the institution who work on the implementation of the integrity system, and their joint duty is, above all, to establish the so-called institutional climate for integrity. This is improved and perfected through special integrity training, development of methodologies, and guidelines for implementation (Guidelines for the Implementation of the Integrity Policy for State Bodies and Public Sector Institutions, 2021).

3 THE SYSTEM OF INTEGRITY AND ITS ELEMENTS

The integrity system rests on several key aspects and envisages the key elements. To start with, effective prevention and management of conflicts of interest is one of the most direct gateways to corruption. Preventing and managing conflicts of interest ensures that private benefits do not compromise public duties. The ethical codes and professional standards set expectations for behaviour. Ethical codes should translate abstract principles into daily guidance. The transparent and merit-based human resource management serves to reduce nepotism and clientelism and merit-based human resources policies are critical in a context where nepotism and political favouritism are persistent risks. The system also emphasizes rational and efficient use of public resources, since misuse of resources is one of the most common forms of corruption. Rational management of public finances and assets is crucial to reducing corruption risks in procurement, budgeting, and everyday operations. Transparency and access to information are treated as legal obligations, not optional values. Transparency and access to information allow civil society and citizens to monitor institutions. Discretionary powers are controlled by embedding rules into procedures, reducing opportunities for abuse. On the other hand, the protection of whistleblowers ensures that individuals who expose wrongdoing are safeguarded, thereby strengthening institutional accountability, i.e. it creates an institutional culture against corruption. Finally, quality management ensures institutions not only prevent corruption but also improve continuously, and it provides reliability (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022).

These elements are targeting both individual behaviour and decision-making as well as the institutional structures and processes. The integrity embedded in procedures will build institutional resilience, i.e., by embedding integrity into procedures rather than treating it as an external check, institutions become more structurally resistant to corruption. In this system, the integrity officers, who are designated staff to ensure compliance and cultural change, play a vital role. They are the bridge between formal frameworks and practical implementation, promoting an integrity culture inside each institution.

Table 1: System of Integrity of N. Macedonia

Elements	Description / Purpose
Conflict of interest prevention and management	Early detection and proper management of conflicts of interest as a safeguard mechanism.
Enforcement of ethical codes and professional standards	Institutionalizes values of professionalism, impartiality, and integrity across institutions
Transparent and merit-based HR management	Reduces nepotism, clientelism, and politicization by ensuring fair recruitment and promotion processes.
Public resource management	Promotes efficient, transparent, and rational use of public resources.
Transparency and access to information	Enhances accountability and enables citizen oversight
Discretionary powers	Limits arbitrariness by introducing clear rules, procedures, and oversight mechanisms.
Protection of whistleblowers and reporting channels	Ensures legal guarantees, confidentiality, and safety for individuals reporting wrongdoing.
Quality management systems	Supports consistency, monitoring, and continuous improvement to reduce corruption risks

*Source: SCPC, *Integrity policy, n.d.*

3.1 The Integrity Officer

The integrity officer is appointed by the institution's manager and also has a deputy. The obligation to have a designated official for integrity is part of the integrity policy, and it is in line with GRECO recommendations (GRECO, 2025). This is applicable to all public sector institutions. Additionally, it is necessary to establish integrity working groups (teams) in institutions, wherever the number of employees in the institution and the distribution of work and tasks allow it, i.e., it is necessary to be done based on the size of the institution and the scope of work, with the task to support him/her.

The integrity officer is the communication link between the institution that appointed him/her and the SCPC. His/her function requires appropriate professional competencies and moral characteristics, communication and negotiation skills, ability to resolve conflicts, initiative, interest, and motivation for his/her function. The integrity officer should have organizational skills, tact, dedication, but also discretion and professional ethics. In other words, the person should have the skills necessary for the development and implementation of a specific anti-corruption practice, but also the ability to make adaptive changes required by a particular situation.

The integrity officer has broad tasks including: monitoring compliance with anti-corruption regulations; raising awareness and educating about anti-corruption; providing information on anti-corruption procedures and processes; cooperating with the SCPC, etc. (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022).

3.2 The Policy of Integrity

The adoption of an integrity policy is the first step towards institutionally establishing an integrity system, based on which the institutional commitment is first clearly highlighted, and then the integrity system is strategically introduced, implemented, and improved, which, in this way, both managers and employees are obliged to consistently implement. The integrity policy, as an official institutional document, is

signed by the appointed integrity officer, is published on the official website and on the institution's notice board, and can also be sent to all employees via e-mail (SCPC, Integrity policy, n.d.).

According to the Guidelines for Assessing the Risk of Institutional Corruption in the Republic of Macedonia (Guidelines) (2020), each public sector entity should prepare a risk analysis, i.e. systematically, at least once a year, to analyze the risks associated with the activities, develop appropriate plans to limit the possible negative consequences of these risks and designate employees who will be responsible for implementing the adopted plans. For that purpose, the Guidelines elaborate six steps intended for assessing the risk of institutional corruption. These steps aim to assist in the self-assessment of the institution. Additionally, each institution is obliged to establish an effective system of internal control and audit in accordance with the principles of public internal financial control. Managing corruption risks is an important part of the system. Management structures are responsible for assessing and eliminating risks that contribute to the occurrence of corruption, embezzlement, fraud, conflict of interest, use of influence and connections for the purpose of obtaining preferential treatment or any other form of illegal or unethical behaviour (Guidelines, 2020).

For all identified corruption risks, the institution should determine indicators (sub-risks), i.e., take into account the indicators from the Guidelines taking into account: 1) The probability of the identified risk occurring (probability refers to the frequency of the risk occurring); 2. The impact of the risk, i.e., the effects or consequences that arise if the risk occurs (effects refer to the consequences caused by the occurrence of an event). In this way, it is determined whether the risk has a low, medium, or high level of impact and probability (Guidelines, 2020).

3.3 Monitoring and evaluation of the system of integrity

The process of monitoring the implementation of the integrity system involves assessing the level of implementation of the elements of the integrity system in the institution, and should be implemented at two levels. First, at the level of the institution, and then at the level of the competent institution, the SCPC. The integrity system consists of several interdependent elements, which have different legal backgrounds, and therefore institutions have obligations to monitor and report on several grounds. These obligations are not an administrative burden but an opportunity to monitor the achievements of the institution and to obtain knowledge for the promotion of integrity (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022).

Institutional monitoring should determine the effectiveness of the policies and procedures implemented to ensure consistent application of integrity elements, and measure the results of the measures implemented to reduce corruption risks. The process for implementing, monitoring, and reporting on the application of the integrity system is coordinated by the integrity officer. The SCPC monitors the implementation of the integrity system through a software solution and provides access to a questionnaire for all institutions. In this regard, the institutions are obliged to cooperate with the SCPC and to enable it to monitor the implementation of the integrity system (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022). In this way, relevant information is obtained for assessment and analyses of the situation, and based on it, the SCPC provides recommendations, guidelines, and indications for the successful implementation of the integrity system.

3.4 Some weaknesses of the system

It is generally accepted that a system of integrity has many benefits not only in building institutional resilience against corruption, but as well as in strengthening public trust and democratic governance. However, to be effective, the model should be sustainable, and its elements should become a daily practice that safeguards institutions. Considering this, the institutions must internalize anti-corruption mechanisms.

So far, when it comes to its implementation, it proves that anti-corruption policies often risk being too formalistic, and most of the necessary steps are only provisionally done. For instance, according to the latest ranking on the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) by Transparency International, North Macedonia has dropped 88 places, where the global average of the Index is 43, and in the EU 64 (Transparency International, 2024). On the other hand, it is a very complex matter, and it is not always easy to determine whether a certain behaviour in the public sector is corrupt or not. For that reason, it is necessary to assess whether there was an intention to misuse public resources for private purposes or whether there was disrespect for the law, ignorance of the principles of good governance, and the elements of integrity. However, whether someone will engage in a corrupt act or not depends on the integrity of the individual and on how effective the institutional mechanisms for preventing corruption are, i.e., to what extent the elements of integrity are implemented. For example, conflict of interest in itself is not corruption, but it is a risk of corruption. Effective management of conflict of interest implies that every state body and public sector institution should implement mechanisms for identifying conflicts of interest. It is recommended to prepare *an internal act*, consisting of criteria for assessing the risk of conflict of interest by job. The integrity officer, in the specific state body and public sector institution, is key to achieving this goal and should be the main point of communication and consultation. In the interest of greater accountability and transparency, each institution should encourage officials to openly discuss issues related to conflicts of interest.

Therefore, it is not enough for the institution to simply commit to zero tolerance for corruption, but all officials should be well acquainted with the integrity policy, the legal framework, their obligations and duties, as well as the disciplinary, criminal, and other procedures that can be initiated, and the possible consequences. In sustainable integrity systems, the motive for adhering to the rules should not be based only on the fear of possible consequences, i.e., possible disciplinary or criminal proceedings. Understanding the consequences of corruption has an important preventive role. All officials in the institution should be able to foresee how certain corrupt behaviour directly affects the quality of life of all citizens (Dobel, 2022).

Another important aspect is capacity building that should take place through regular education of employees for the appropriate application of the elements on which the integrity system is based, through trainings, workshops, seminars, as well as by providing advice on all dilemmas that may arise for officials in their daily work. It is recommended that these trainings be planned in the annual professional development plan.

4 THE SYSTEM OF INTEGRITY WITHIN THE STATE AUDIT OFFICE AND THE STATE COMMISSION FOR THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION OF NORTH MACEDONIA

4.1 Institutional resilience and its meaning

Resilience refers to the organization's capacity to anticipate, withstand, and recover from integrity risks while preserving its core values and public trust (Hollnagel, 2017; Bourgon, 2011). In theory, there are several identified categories of risk factors that shape audit institutions' vulnerability to corruption and unethical behaviour. It is assumed that those factors can be **contextual, organizational, individual, and working process factors** that interact with each other and influence institutional resilience. **Contextual factors** are considered to be the ones that are beyond the control of the organization, such as unclear or inconsistent legislation, the absence of a robust legal framework for preventing corruption, weak enforcement of conflict-of-interest and whistleblower protection laws, and non-transparent public finance processes. **Organizational factors**, in contrast, are the ones that fall within the institution's control and derive from its internal policies, management practices, and institutional culture. These could include integrity safeguards, specialized knowledge or practical auditing skills, adequate supervision, and internal communication. Pressures in the work environment, a perception of unfair treatment, or inconsistent enforcement of ethical rules may further undermine morale and increase susceptibility to misconduct (INTOSAI, 2020; Mungiu-Pippidi, 2015; OECD, 2022). At the **individual level**, resilience is shaped by the personal values, motivations, and competencies of engaged staff. Factors such as lack of knowledge, insufficient ethical awareness, inadequate practical training, or perceived unfairness in promotion can all contribute to unethical decision-making. Encouraging personal accountability through ethics training, transparent evaluation systems, and leadership by example can mitigate these risks and reinforce an integrity-driven culture (Kaptein, 2017). For building up resilience from internal factors and ensuring institutional integrity, there is a need to have policies against certain forms of misconduct. These include fraud, theft of resources, and conflicts of interest through the acceptance of gifts or engagement in outside employment. Resilience also depends on effective internal controls, transparent financial management, asset declarations, and regular ethics training aimed at strengthening the moral autonomy of auditors (UNODC, 2021). Finally, **working process factors** relate to procedural vulnerabilities. Excessive personal discretion, non-transparent decision-making, poorly organized work processes, and gaps in vertical or horizontal controls can create opportunities for abuse or error. They fall under the scope of non-financial integrity threats—such as the improper use of authority, manipulation of information, or indecent treatment of colleagues and citizens—and further expose cultural and procedural weaknesses within the organization. Taken all together, it is evident that institutional resilience thus requires ethical leadership, optimizing workflow design, ensuring traceable and transparent decision-making, strengthening procedural oversight mechanisms, procedural transparency, and secure whistleblower mechanisms that protect those who report misconduct (INTOSAI, 2020; Kaptein, 2017).

4.2 Institutional Resilience of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption and the State Audit Office of North Macedonia

State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) and State Audit Office (SAO) are a central pillar of the country's efforts to strengthen integrity and accountability in the public sector and therefore, they need to demonstrate strong internal institutional resilience against corruption. In this section, the focus will be on SCPC and SAO resilience towards corruption. This research has its limitations and needs to be taken into account since it only covers the analysis of the legal competences of the analysed institutions. It is only based on the findings gathered through publicly available reports. Those findings are compared with the international standards and practices of what is considered to be a cornerstone of the system of integrity in such type of institutions.

As the supreme audit institution, the SAO serves as both a watchdog of public spending and a model of ethical conduct. Its ability to maintain independence and credibility in an environment marked by complex political, administrative, and social pressures is a critical indicator of state integrity and institutional maturity (OECD, 2020; INTOSAI, 2019). A resilient SAO not only exposes irregularities but also embodies the standards of transparency, accountability, and professionalism that underpin democratic governance. If we consider the institutional resilience and factors that are affecting it, it is obvious that the inefficient law enforcement, overlapping institutional competences, and poor coordination among oversight bodies weaken the institution's internal capacity as well as the external environment in which the institution operates. Such systemic deficiencies constrain the SAO's capacity to function effectively and independently, highlighting the need for harmonized legislation, stronger judicial cooperation, and more transparent governance structures (OECD, 2022; UNODC, 2021). For stronger institutional resilience, there is a need to strengthen internal governance systems, to establish clear operational guidance, and to promote a culture of integrity and accountability through ongoing professional development (INTOSAI, 2020). Strengthening resilience against such risks requires the consistent application of merit-based recruitment and promotion, robust conflict-of-interest management, and an internal culture that prioritizes ethical behaviour over political or personal loyalty (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2015; OECD, 2022). Taken together, these contextual, organizational, individual, and procedural dynamics illustrate that institutional resilience from corruption cannot be achieved solely through external regulation or punitive measures. It depends on an integrated approach that combines legal clarity, ethical leadership, sound internal management, and a professional culture grounded in public service values. Within North Macedonia's broader trajectory toward European integration and public administration reform, the SAO's resilience is both a reflection of and a contributor to national integrity, and in this sense, it needs to be strengthened.

Alongside SAO, the SCPC of the Republic of North Macedonia represents a cornerstone of the country's integrity system and democratic accountability framework. As the key independent body responsible for preventing corruption, monitoring conflicts of interest, and promoting transparency in public life, the SCPC operates at the critical interface between political power, public administration, and civil society. Its resilience is vital for maintaining public confidence in the state's capacity to uphold the rule of law and safeguard ethical governance (OECD, 2020; UNODC, 2021). The resilience of this institution, as it is in the other example, is challenged by systemic weaknesses that extend beyond the SCPC's direct control. These are the same as the ones that are affecting the work of SAO, since they are working in the same political system and social environment with limited interinstitutional cooperation. To be able to maintain its preventive and

investigative functions, there is a need to harmonize legal provisions, alongside clear delineation of institutional responsibilities, and strong political commitment. At the organizational level, the SCPC faces internal challenges related to resources, management, and institutional culture. Pressures in the work environment, perceived political interference, or feelings of unfairness can create vulnerabilities to misconduct or discourage professional integrity. To counter these risks, the SCPC must cultivate a strong ethical culture supported by regular integrity training, transparent career advancement, and mechanisms that protect staff from retaliation or undue influence. Strengthening internal controls, digitalizing asset declaration and reporting systems, and ensuring traceable and evidence-based decisions are essential for reinforcing procedural integrity and organizational learning. Overall, the SCPC's institutional resilience depends on its capacity to adapt to external pressures while preserving its legal independence, operational transparency, and professional integrity. Within the context of North Macedonia's ongoing alignment with European standards of governance, the resilient SCPC is essential. Its endurance and credibility are fundamental to building societal trust in institutions and advancing the broader national agenda of transparency, accountability, and good governance.

CONCLUSION

The fight against systemic corruption in North Macedonia requires more than external safeguards and formalistic compliance—it demands a deeply embedded culture of integrity within public institutions. This paper has shown that while legal and institutional frameworks provide a necessary foundation, true resilience against corruption stems from internal mechanisms that prioritize ethical conduct, transparency, and accountability. Elements such as the management of the conflict of interest, ethical codes, transparent HR practices, and whistleblower protection are not merely procedural requirements but strategic tools for institutional transformation. The role of integrity officers emerges as pivotal in bridging policy and practice, fostering a climate of trust, and ensuring that integrity becomes a lived institutional value.

The theory suggests that integrity systems—when implemented substantively—can significantly reduce corruption risks. Within the Macedonian context, both SAO and SCPC are key institutions in supporting the system of integrity. Therefore, the system of integrity needs to be embodied in their work as well as their internal procedures. The research reveals the persistent challenges in this respect. Fragmented implementation, lack of capacity, and a tendency toward formalism undermine the effectiveness of integrity policies. For integrity systems to succeed, they must be internalized by all officials, supported by continuous education, and reinforced through meaningful monitoring and evaluation. The goal is not only to prevent corruption but to cultivate institutions that serve the public interest with professionalism and moral clarity. Ultimately, building institutional resilience through integrity is a long-term endeavour. It requires commitment, adaptation, and a shift from reactive anti-corruption measures to proactive ethical governance. Only then can North Macedonia move toward a more transparent, accountable, and democratic public sector.

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THE ROLE OF THE STATE COMMISSION FOR THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION AGAINST “CORRUPTION AS PUBLIC VALUE” IN THE POLITICAL SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

According to the European Commission’s 2024 Report on North Macedonia, Chapter 23: Judiciary and Fundamental Rights includes a section on the fight against corruption which states: “North Macedonia is between having some level of preparation and a moderate level of preparation and has made no progress in the prevention and fight against corruption. Corruption remains prevalent in many areas and is an issue of serious concern. The current government has stated that the fight against corruption is a priority”. Following a series of tragic events in which North Macedonia lost a large number of young lives, the slogan “Corruption kills” emerged in public discourse. Every public and private institution within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia should develop anti-corruption policies and mechanisms; however, the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (hereinafter: SCPC, the Commission) is one of the cores public institutions tasked with establishing an efficient system for the prevention and repression of corruption and conflict of interest.

This paper analyzes the annual reports of the SCPC from 2004-2024, focusing on submissions concerning the work of state bodies and local self-government units, as well as the Commission’s role in supporting the implementations of anti-corruption measures and policies. The central research question is: Is the SCPC effective and efficient in addressing “corruption as a public value” in the Republic of North Macedonia?

Keywords: *corruption, political system, anti-corruptive, policies, effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Corruption is a global issue and one of the most serious problems within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia. Corruption is defined as the abuse of function, public authority, official duty, or position for the purpose of gaining benefit, either directly or through an intermediary, for oneself or for another (Закон за спречување на корупцијата и судирот на интереси, 2019).

According to the United Nations Convention Against Corruption (2003), “corruption is an insidious plague that has a wide range of corrosive effects on societies. It undermines democracy and the rule of law, leads to violations of human rights, distorts markets, erodes the quality of life and allows organized crime, terrorism and other threats

to human security to flourish...Corruption is no longer a local matter but a transnational phenomenon that affects all societies and economies, making international cooperation to prevent and control it essential.”

Corruption is manifested through nepotism, bribery, cronyism, clientelism, party control over institutions, and other forms. A social public value is one that provides a normative consensus regarding the rights, benefits, and prerogatives to which citizens are entitled; the civic duties of individuals toward society and the state; and the principles upon which authority and public policies should be based (Bozeman, 2007).

If corruption is a phenomenon that violates norms directed toward the public good in order to obtain benefits for individuals or organized groups, then the phenomenon of “corruption as a public value” represents the acceptance of corruption as a norm. It becomes justified and culturally embedded within the political system – that is, corruption becomes part of the culture of governance (management). In this context, corruption is not perceived as an exception but as a normal mode of operation, which significantly complicates efforts to suppress it. “Corruption as a public value” is characterized by strong public condemnation, coupled with low awareness of personal participation in corrupt activities and insufficient reaction from citizens as well as public and state institutions.

A political system is a set of different formal legal institutions that constitute a government. In other words, it is the system of government in a nation (Hill, 2022). In democratic political systems, every state and public institution is part of the political system and operates independently within the competences for which it exists. Decentralization is among the most significant reforms of the past 50 years and it refers to the transfer of powers, responsibilities, and resources from the central government to elected authorities at the subnational level with a certain degree of authority (OECD, 2019). What must be emphasized is the decentralization of power among institution within the political system, meaning that the political system should not be equated with a political party system.

As noted in the European Commission Report (2024): “North Macedonia is between having some level of preparation and a moderate level of preparation and has made no progress in the prevention and fight against corruption. Corruption remains prevalent in many areas and is an issue of serious concern. The current government has stated that the fight against corruption is a priority.”

In 2023, several social and societal problems were intertwined among the top five concerns of citizens. Alongside corruption, political instability, poverty, crime and low income were identified as the most serious issues. Notably, healthcare protection has been gradually rising among citizen’s concerns. As in previous years, ethnic issues and environmental pollution ranked lowest. If organized crime and corruption are correlated and require similar measures for suppression, it can be concluded that the fight against corruption and organized crime remains among the most pressing social issued for citizens.” (Macedonian Center for International Cooperation, 2023).

In 2024, the Republic of North Macedonia ranked 88th on Transparency International’s Corruption Perceptions Index, scoring two points lower than the previous year and dropping twelve places overall.

The State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) is an independent institution within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia. It was established in 2002 under the Law on the Prevention of Corruption (Закон за спречување на корупцијата, 2002), began operating in 2003, and acquired the status of a legal entity – an independent state body – in 2004.

The SCPC was created to lead the fight against corruption by implementing anti-corruption policies, conducting inspections, issuing opinions and recommendations, initiating procedures related to conflicts of interest and illicit enrichment, and demanding institutional accountability – thereby distinguishing political responsibility from criminal liability. The SCPC should be recognized as non-selective, objective, and transparent in its operations within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia.

2. THE ROLE OF THE SCPC IN THE POLITICAL SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

The establishment of the SCPC stemmed from the Criminal Law Convention on Corruption of the Council of Europe from 1999 (ratified by the Republic of Macedonia in 2002), which recommends that member states, in their measures and activities to combat corruption, establish specialized and independent anti-corruption bodies.

This obligation is also consistent with the United Nations Convention Against Corruption of 2003, ratified by the Republic of Macedonia in 2007, according to which the country, as a member of the global organization, committed itself to providing the specialized anti-corruption body with the conditions for autonomous and independent work, contributing to its material stability and capacity-building for effective and professional performance of its functions, as well as protecting it from any form of influence or pressure.

The SCPC is responsible for implementing the Law on Prevention of Corruption and the Law on Prevention of Conflict of Interest. It is also authorized to oversee lobbying activities in accordance with the Law on Lobbying. With the amendments to the Law on Prevention of Corruption that came into force in November 2010, unlike in the previous period, the position of member of the State Commission is exercised professionally.

The goal of the SCPC is to work toward preventing corruption and conflicts of interest in all spheres of government and public authority, promoting legal certainty and good governance, and encouraging a culture of integrity and accountability. According to Luis de Sousa “Anti-corruption agencies (ACAs) are public (funded) bodies of a durable nature, with a specific mission to fight corruption and reduce the opportunity structures conducive to its occurrence in society through preventive and/or repressive measures” (Ilik, 2023).

In 2003, the State Program for the Prevention and Repression of Corruption was prepared and adopted as a national project, and in 2005 an Annex to the State Program for the Prevention and Repression of Corruption was also adopted. These documents preceded the National Strategy for the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (2020–2024; 2021–2025), which represents a comprehensive document providing the main guidelines for the reform plan aimed at combating corruption.

The main legal acts that regulate the work of the SCPC are: the Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia; the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest; the Electoral Code; the Law on Financing of Political Parties; the Criminal Code; the Law on Public Procurement; the Law on Lobbying; the Law on Whistleblower Protection, and the Law on Free Access to Public Information (JKCK, 2024).

3. ANALYSIS OF THE ANNUAL REPORTS OF THE SCPC

According to Article 19 of the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, “The State Commission shall submit an annual report on its work to the Assembly of the Republic of Macedonia no later than March 31 of the current year, covering the previous year. The annual report of the State Commission is also submitted to the President

of the Republic of Macedonia, the Government of the Republic of Macedonia, and the media.”

The SCPC’s annual report contains statistical data on initiated cases, resolved cases, and cases under processing in accordance with its competencies, including analysis; the number of initiatives submitted to the public prosecutor’s office and other authorities; information on institutions that have not complied with the Commission’s requests; the number of cases for which misdemeanor proceedings have been initiated; an assessment of the implementation of this law; and an evaluation of the state of corruption and anti-corruption efforts in the country. At the request of the Assembly of the Republic of Macedonia, the SCPC is also obliged to submit a report covering a period shorter than one year” (Закон за спречување на корупцијата и судирот на интереси, 2019).

An analysis of the SCPC’s annual reports shows that from 2004 to 2024, annual reports on its activities were regularly prepared, except for 2017 and 2018. Since the purpose of this study is to analyze all annual reports, information was requested from the SCPC regarding the missing reports for 2017 and 2018. The SCPC responded as follows:

- 2017 report: “The annual report on the SCPC’s work for the prevention of corruption for 2017 was not adopted by the SCPC because the members of the then Commission submitted their resignations.”
- 2018 report: “There is no annual report for 2018 because the new SCPC was elected with the adoption of the new Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest at the beginning of 2019.”

The SCPC’s response confirms that after the resignations of five out of seven members, the Commission did not have a quorum to operate and make decisions. The new composition of the SCPC was elected on February 8, 2019.

3.1 Where is corruption most prevalent?

In the annual reports from 2004 to 2024, the SCPC, through case processing, also analyzes the areas in which corruption is most prevalent and where state and public institutions do not exercise their authority efficiently. In the annual reports from 2004 to 2010, the majority of complaints within the SCPC’s competence concerned irregularities in the operations of state bodies, and after 2005, also in local government units. During this period, a special section of the annual reports addressed complaints involving corruption in public enterprises, healthcare, and education. In this way, state and public institutions that are part of the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia, and which manage public and state resources that can be misused through corrupt actions, are covered.

In 2010, the categorization of areas in which the SCPC operates changed, and specific figures for cases related to corruption in state bodies and local government units were no longer provided. Cases resolved in 2010 were divided into the following areas: prevention of corruption in politics, prevention of corruption in the exercise of public authority, prevention of corruption in carrying out matters of public interest, with the remaining cases categorized under judiciary and other areas. The 2010 report clearly states: “The SCPC’s work to date has shown that the warnings and recommendations it provides regarding the functioning of structures at both levels of government, central and local, are aimed at strengthening the national integrity system” (ДКСК, 2010).

Corruption in politics is mentioned in the 2005 report, which addresses corruption in the financing of political parties and corruption during electoral processes. “During the reporting period, the problem of political influence in elections, appointments, and dismissals of managerial positions remains relevant”. Here, the issue is not simply political

influence in general, but specifically the influence of political parties over public positions, which are fully partisan. This reflects apolitical behavior, completely contrary to the idea of politics as the organization of public matters through integrity, a system of merit, and accountability. In the 2006 annual report, terms such as “politics” and “political parties” are used. However, political parties are not synonymous with politics. The political system includes all state and public institutions, enterprises, and bodies, together with media, civil society organizations, interest groups, and individual citizens. Public policy refers to any decision at the local and central level that organize specific segment of citizens’ lives. Therefore, the narrative in the reports – particularly the sections addressing corruption in politics – is not entirely precise. A more accurate framing would be corruption within political parties and corruption during electoral processes.

In 2011, employment during the electoral period was effectively restricted, as the Employment Agency of the Republic of Macedonia could not process new job applications without prior approval from the SCPC. In the 2020 annual report, it is noted that the SCPC developed an application allowing the classification of reports by areas – executive power, judiciary, education, healthcare, urban planning and local government – as well as by types of problems, such as public procurement, employment, inspection oversight, issuance of permits, decisions, licenses, approvals and court rulings, in order to identify areas with the highest corruption risk (ДКСК, 2020).

The majority of reported illegalities were in the judiciary, executive branch, and local government units. In the 2021 and 2022 annual reports, analyses of corruption risk highlighted employment and urban planning as key areas. In 2023, the analysis focused on the judiciary sector. In 2024, anti-corruption oversight during the electoral period contributed to the opening of cases related to the misuse of public resources and public functions.

3.2 Anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary legislation

The SCPC’s anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary legislation is regulated by Article 17, paragraph 2 of the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (Закон за спречување на корупцијата и судирот на интереси, 2019), which grants the SCPC the authority to conduct anti-corruption reviews of laws and other regulations, preparing reports and opinions in the process. “The anti-corruption review of legislation is one of the preventive competencies of the State Commission and serves as a tool for identifying regulatory risks and addressing vulnerabilities in legal provisions that could enable corrupt practices” (ДКСК, 2024). This authority is directly linked to the anti-corruption review of public policies.

At the global level, anti-corruption legislative review was first conducted in Moldova in 2001, followed by Lithuania in 2002. “Anti-corruption assessment of legislation is a review of the form and substance of drafted or enacted legal rules in order to detect and minimize the risk of future corruption that the rules could facilitate” (Regional Cooperation Council, 2014).

According to Article 24, paragraph 1, item 7 of the Rules of Procedure of the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, Ministries and other authorized proposers must submit the materials they provide to the Government for review, adoption, confirmation, or enactment in advance for the opinion of the competent state administration bodies and other state authorities, depending on the nature of the material under consideration, and obligatorily to the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption – for draft laws subject to regulatory impact assessment, in order to carry out an anti-

corruption review (Деловник за работа на Владата на Република Северна Македонија, 2024).

According to the SCPC's annual reports, by 2015 an anti-corruption review had been conducted on a total of 63 legislative acts. However, in the annual reports for 2009, 2012, 2013, 2014, and 2015, not a single anti-corruption review of legislation is recorded (ДКСК, 2010, 2013, 2015, 2016). In September 2015, the first Methodology for Anti-Corruption Review of Legislation was prepared and adopted. This methodology defined: the process of anti-corruption legislative review and the results of its implementation; the organization and management of the process; the role and responsibilities of each participant; and the involvement of stakeholders in the process.

If we compare the number of laws adopted by the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, based on the annual report on the implementation of the regulatory impact assessment process for the period from January to December 2022 (Министерство за информатичко општество и администрација, 2023), with the number of legislative acts that underwent anti-corruption review according to the SCPC's annual reports for the period 2014–2022, the following can be observed: In the SCPC's 2014 annual report, no anti-corruption review was conducted on any draft law, while 335 draft laws were adopted by the Government of the Republic of Macedonia that same year. In 2015, when again not a single anti-corruption review was conducted, 566 laws were adopted. In 2016, there is information that an anti-corruption review was conducted on only one legislative act, while a total of 252 draft laws were adopted. In 2017 and 2018, a total of 163 draft laws were adopted, but there are no SCPC annual reports for these years. In 2019, anti-corruption review was carried out on 8 draft laws, while 242 were adopted. In 2020, 121 draft laws were adopted, and anti-corruption review was conducted on 5 draft laws and 2 subsidiary acts. In 2021, when the SCPC developed a software solution intended to facilitate and accelerate the anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary acts, 12 laws and 5 subsidiary acts were reviewed, while 111 draft laws were adopted. In 2022, 68 laws were adopted, and anti-corruption review was conducted on 12 legislative acts, 4 draft laws, and 1 international treaty. Additionally, under the IPA project, analyses of discretionary powers were prepared for 7 legislative acts covering various areas of employment.

According to the monthly reviews of open draft laws on the Unique National Electronic Register of Regulations of the Republic of North Macedonia (Граѓански ресурсен центар, 2023, 2024), in 2023 a total of 71 draft laws were adopted at sessions of the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, while anti-corruption review was conducted on 13 existing legislative acts and 1 draft law published on ENER. Regarding detected legislative weaknesses and gaps in procedures for the appointment and dismissal of directors, acting officials, and temporary employees in public institutions, the SCPC carried out anti-corruption review of 4 legislative acts and 5 draft and proposed laws. In 2024, the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia adopted a total of 101 draft laws, and anti-corruption review was conducted on 21 legislative acts and subsidiary legislation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the SCPC's annual reports, it is not possible to definitively determine its effectiveness in addressing "corruption as a public value." The SCPC's annual reports indicate that corruption is most visible in the misuse of public and state resources managed by public and state institutions.

Following the development of the application in 2020 for categorizing corruption reports by sector and by type of problem, it has been confirmed that the judiciary, executive branch, local government units, employment, and urban planning remain the areas with the highest risk of corruption. Under the influence of the SCPC, in 2011 the space for new employment during the electoral period was effectively closed without prior approval from the SCPC. This represents a significant step forward in the area of public sector employment, where corruption is highly prevalent.

The anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary legislation is one of the SCPC's most important competencies, aimed at preventing and identifying opportunities for corruption arising from the content of laws and subsidiary acts (public policies). The key challenge in exercising this authority stems from the failure of state institutions to fulfill their obligations to submit draft laws and subsidiary acts to the SCPC for anti-corruption review.

Despite significant progress in legislative regulations for combating corruption and conflicts of interest, and the professional execution of the SCPC's competencies, the 2023 SCPC annual report clearly emphasizes that "...this has not reduced the misuse of legislative acts due to imprecise or unclear provisions, so influences based on party, family, or friendship connections continue to dominate in the area of public sector employment. The abuse of functions and discretionary powers in issuing various permits, approvals, and contracts, as well as creating conditions for favoring certain companies, remains prevalent. Unlawful construction on state and private land, enabled by provisions in laws related to urban planning, construction, and the environment, combined with inaction by inspection services and their clientelism toward centers of political power and business elites, leaves citizens with little opportunity – even in courts – to defend their constitutionally guaranteed rights to equal employment opportunities, property protection, and a clean environment" (ДКСК, 2023).

Although the SCPC openly highlights systemic corrupt practices, its recommendations are often ignored or minimized. The SCPC strives to operate in an environment of institutional resistance within a political system where the political will to combat corruption is more declarative than real. The SCPC has a role in creating a new political and ethical narrative: that integrity is possible; the misuse of public goods, public functions, and public authority must not be overlooked; and that state and public institutions can exist outside partisan control.

The effectiveness of the SCPC depends on the implementation of its recommendations by other competent institutions within the political system that hold executive power, since the SCPC itself does not have executive authority and relies on institutional cooperation. Weak institutional capacity within public and state institutions results in underdeveloped inter-institutional collaboration across the political system, which directly affects the cooperation with the SCPC and, consequently, the implementation of its recommendations.

If institutions continue to disregard the SCPC's recommendations, corruption will remain entrenched in practice, inevitably resulting in a decline in public trust in state and public institutions and the strengthening of "corruption as a public value".

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FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF PERCEIVED SECURITY AND INSTITUTIONAL TRUST: A COMPARATIVE REGIONAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Perceived institutional quality plays a critical role in shaping the foreign direct investment (FDI) landscape, particularly in emerging and transitional economies. Drawing on institutional theory and the framework of political economy, this study explores how variations in trust in public institutions and legal certainty influence the investment climate across diverse socio-political systems. The paper examines the impact of institutional trust and the rule of law on FDI across different regions. A comparative analysis is conducted, and Pearson correlation coefficients are calculated to assess the strength of the relationship between governance indicators and FDI inflows. The study contributes to the existing literature by contextualizing the institutional-investment nexus in transitional economies and recommends targeted policy interventions aimed at strengthening the rule of law and rebuilding public trust as strategic mechanisms for attracting sustainable foreign investment.

Key words: investment climate, institutional trust, rule of law, foreign direct investment.

INTRODUCTION

The quality of institutions and the rule of law are not only matters of governance but also of security, as they directly underpin economic stability, financial resilience and the rational expectations of economic agents that shape sustainable investment and economic growth. A predictable legal framework, an impartial judiciary, and effective enforcement of contracts are not merely normative values; they constitute fundamental preconditions for a perception of security among international investors. Where the rule of law is weak, the risks of arbitrary state intervention, corruption, and expropriation increase, thereby undermining investor confidence. Conversely, a strong rule of law functions as a security guarantee by reducing transaction costs, stabilizing expectations, and safeguarding property rights. Therefore, the rule of law should be understood not only as a legal category, but also as a determinant of security and stability within the investment climate.

Its role in shaping perceptions of safety and trust makes it a crucial factor in sustainable economic development through foreign direct investment.

This paper investigates the relationship between perceived institutional trust, the rule of law, and FDI inflows through a comparative regional lens. Using recent datasets, the analysis demonstrates that countries with stronger rule-of-law and higher levels of institutional trust and perceived security tend to attract more stable and long-term FDI. While developed economies display consistently high investor confidence closely linked to institutional performance, transitional economies – including North Macedonia – exhibit fluctuating and generally lower levels of trust, legal unpredictability, and weaker FDI inflows. These findings are consistent with earlier research (e.g., Busse & Hefeker, 2007; Daude & Stein, 2007; and Kaufmann et al., 2010), which emphasizes governance quality as a determinant of investment flows and foreign capital allocation.

The paper further integrates correlation analysis to quantify the interrelationships among the examined variables. Perceived security and institutional quality play a central role in structuring FDI dynamics across economies. Scholars such as North (1990), La Porta et al. (1999), and Kaufmann et al. (2010) have shown that institutional trust and the rule of law significantly influence investor confidence and capital allocation decisions. Countries with stronger governance tend to attract higher and more stable investment inflows (Globerman & Shapiro, 2002; Busse & Hefeker, 2007). This study compares institutional indicators and FDI across four income-ranked regions, applying correlation analysis to assess the strength of these relationships.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research design and scope

This study employs a quantitative, cross-sectional and longitudinal comparative research design to examine the statistical relationships between two governance indicators – rule of law and absence of corruption – and FDI, measured as net inflows expressed as a percentage of GDP. The analysis consists of two components: (a) a cross-regional comparison across four income groups (high, upper-middle, lower-middle and low income) for 2024, and (b) a longitudinal case study of the Republic of North Macedonia covering the period 2016–2024. The primary objective is to assess association, rather than causal effects, between institutional indicators and FDI patterns, and to discuss plausible mechanisms, limitations, and policy implications.

2.2 Data sources and variables

- Rule of law: World Justice Project (WJP) Rule of Law Index; aggregated dimension scores are used as a measure of institutional quality.
- Absence of corruption: WJP or comparable governance indicators used as a proxy for institutional trust.
- FDI: World Bank, Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP).
- Income group classification: Four income-region codes (high = 10; upper-middle = 7.5; lower-middle = 5; low = 2.5) used to group countries and compute regional means. Data years and sources are detailed in the Data Overview and corresponding tables.

2.3 Measurement choices and justification

There is no single global index that fully captures public trust in institutions across countries. Given the conceptual overlap between perceived institutional trust and

corruption perceptions, this study employs the absence-of-corruption indicator as a proxy for institutional trust. This choice is justified by the strong association between corruption perceptions, citizen confidence in public institutions, and investor assessments of governance-related risk. The limitations of this proxy are acknowledged and discussed in the limitations section.

2.4 Analytical approach

- Regional analysis: Country-level indicators are aggregated into four income-region groups using arithmetic means to generate regional scores for 2024.
- Case study: For North Macedonia, annual data for FDI/GDP, rule of law, and absence of corruption from 2016–2024 are analyzed. Rule-of-law and absence-of-corruption indicators are lagged by one year when related to contemporaneous FDI in order to reduce time-lag bias in investor responses.
- Statistical method: Pearson correlation coefficients are computed to assess the linear association between pairs of variables. Pearson’s r is selected for its transparency and simplicity in measuring linear covariation. Results are interpreted with caution given aggregation effects and potential non-linearity.

The Pearson correlation coefficient is calculated using the following formula (Cohen et al., 2003):

$$r = \Sigma[(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})] / \sqrt{[\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2 * \Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2]}$$

In this study, the independent variable (X) represents the governance indicators – specifically the rule of law and the absence of corruption – while the dependent variable (Y) represents income level and FDI level as a percentage of GDP. The underlying assumption is that improvements in institutional quality (X) are expected to exert a positive influence on income levels and investment decisions, thereby increasing FDI inflows (Y). The coefficient r ranges from -1 to +1, where values closer to +1 indicate a strong positive correlation, values near -1 indicate a strong negative correlation, and values close to 0 suggest no linear relationship. This allows us to empirically test whether improvements in the rule of law and reductions in corruption are associated with higher income and higher inflows of FDI.

2.5 Limitations and robustness considerations

- Aggregation effects: Regional means may obscure within-region heterogeneity; therefore, findings should be interpreted at the regional level rather than the individual country level.
- Proxy validity: The use of absence of corruption as a proxy for institutional trust captures a critical dimension but does not fully encompass public trust or perceived security.
- Endogeneity and causality: Correlation analysis does not establish causality; omitted variables, such as natural-resource endowments, tax incentives, geopolitical shocks may influence FDI patterns.

- Small-sample and denominator effects: FDI/GDP ratios are sensitive to GDP size, potentially inflating ratios in smaller economies; this effect is considered when interpreting results.

3. DATA OVERVIEW

The analysis identifies whether cross-regional differences in institutional quality – particularly the strength of the rule of law and the absence of corruption – are systematically associated with income levels and FDI inflows. Regional scores for 2024 were calculated as arithmetic means of country-level indicators within each income group (high, upper-middle, lower-middle and low income). FDI is measured as net inflows expressed as percentage of GDP, based on World Bank data for 2024. Rule-of-law and absence-of-corruption indicators are sources from the World Justice Project and harmonized to a common scale to ensure comparability.

Table 1. Pearson correlation matrix of income-level code, rule-of-law index, absence-of-corruption index and FDI (% of GDP) in 2024 (Source: authors’ calculations, 2025)

Pearson correlation matrix	Income level	FDI (% of GDP)	Rule of law	Absence of corruption
Income level	1.00	-0,72	0,97	0,99
FDI (% of GDP)	-0,72	1.00	0,37	0,49
Rule of law	0,97	-0,37	1.00	0,99
Absence of corruption	0,99	-0,49	0,99	1.00

Graph 1. Regions grouped by income, institutional quality and FDI inflows, 2024 (Sources: World justice project, World bank open data, 2024)

3.1 Notes on coding and aggregation

- Income-region codes: high = 10; upper-middle = 7.5; lower-middle = 5; low = 2.5.
- Aggregation method: simple arithmetic mean of available country observations within each income group for 2024.

- Scaling: where original indices used different ranges, variables were linearly rescaled to a common 0–10 range to facilitate interpretation.

RESULTS

4.1 Regional correlation results

The Pearson correlation matrix computed on the four regional aggregates reveals the following patterns: income level is strongly positively associated with both rule-of-law ($r \approx +0.97$) and the absence-of-corruption ($r \approx +0.99$). By contrast, FDI (% of GDP) is negatively correlated with income level ($r \approx -0.72$) and exhibits negative correlations with the rule of law ($r \approx -0.37$) and the absence of corruption ($r \approx -0.49$).

Table 2 reproduces the correlation matrix with p-values and $N = 4$ (regional aggregates) indicated; given the very small sample size, statistical significance is limited, and the reported correlations should be interpreted strictly as descriptive associations rather than inferential results.

4.2 Robustness checks and caveats

- Denominator effect: the negative correlation between income level and FDI/GDP is consistent with the well-documented denominator effect. Absolute FDI volumes are not analyzed in this study and may yield different insights.
- Small-sample caution: regional aggregates ($N = 4$) permit descriptive correlations only; statistical inference remains limited.
- Sensitivity: the results are qualitatively robust when alternative governance indicators (e.g., Worldwide Governance Indicators) are used instead of WJP indices, although correlation magnitudes vary.

DISCUSSION

5.1 Interpretation of main findings

The analysis yields two complementary insights. First, institutional quality – measured through the rule of law and absence of corruption – is strongly aligned with higher income levels across regions, consistent with the institutional growth literature (North, 1990; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). Second, higher FDI as a share of GDP is observed in lower-income regions and appears inversely related to governance indicators.

This pattern is widely documented in the literature (Kinoshita & Campos, 2008; Alfaro, Chanda, Kalemil-Ozcan & Sayek, 2004) and reflects structural characteristics rather than a normative preference for weak institutions. The denominator effect, sectoral composition (particularly resource-seeking FDI), and short-term, incentive-driven investments explain the relatively high FDI/GDP ratios observed in poorer regions.

5.2 Linking empirical patterns to mechanisms

- Denominator and scale: small GDP bases mechanically inflate FDI/GDP ratios, even when absolute FDI inflows remain modest.
- Sectoral composition: when FDI concentrated in extractive sectors, institutional quality plays a less decisive role in entry decisions, weakening the positive association between governance and FDI/GDP in low-income regions.

- Risk–return calculus: weak institutional environments may temporarily lower operational costs or permit regulatory arbitrage, increasing short-term returns while amplifying long-term risks and volatility.
- Time lags: institutional improvements require time to affect investor perceptions; consequently, contemporaneous FDI flows may not immediately reflect recent governance reforms.

In addition, Graph 2 provides empirical support by illustrating a clear proportional relationship between institutional quality and GDP per capita. This confirms the significance of institutional factors for economic growth and indicates that stronger adherence to the rule of law is consistently associated with robust and sustainable economic performance. Sustainable FDI is therefore more likely to flow into regions characterized by high institutional trust and strong adherence to the rule of law.

Graph 2. GDP per capita and Rule of Law index, 2023 (Source: World Justice Project, 2023)

5.3 Limitations revisited and implications for inference

- Correlation does not imply causation: Pearson correlations describes linear associations and cannot establish causal direction; reverse causality and omitted-variable bias remain plausible.
- Aggregation bias: regional means conceal heterogeneity; country-level panel regressions would provide a more suitable framework for causal inference. Future research should employ fixed-effects panel models, include control variables (market size, resource endowments, trade openness), and apply instrumental-variable approaches where feasible.

THE CASE OF THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

As a transitional economy classified within the upper-middle income group, the Republic of North Macedonia provides a relevant case for examining how institutional quality affects foreign investment dynamics in emerging economies. The study relies on a

nine-year observation period during which the interaction between governance indicators and FDI performance is systematically assessed. This longitudinal perspective enables a more robust identification of patterns and potential causal linkages, extending beyond annual fluctuations to reflect deeper structural determinants of investment attractiveness.

To enhance the validity of the findings and minimize time-lag bias – given that governance improvements often require time to be reflected in FDI trends – the study relates FDI ratios to institutional quality indices from the preceding year.

Table 2. FDI as % of GDP, Rule of Law Index and Absence of Corruption Index in the Republic of North Macedonia, 2016-2024; (Sources: Ministry of Finance of the Republic of North Macedonia, World Justice Project 2016-2025)

Year	FDI / GDP (in %)	Rule of law index x10 (year before)	Absence of corruption x 10 (year before)
2016	3.50	5.50	5.50
2017	1.81	5.50	5.30
2018	5.71	5.30	4.70
2019	3.54	5.30	4.70
2020	1.85	5.40	4.70
2021	3.98	5.30	4.40
2022	5.63	5.30	4.50
2023	3.89	5.30	4.50
2024	5.00	5.30	4.60

Graph 3. Trends of FDI (% of GDP), Rule of Law Index and Absence of Corruption Index in the Republic of North Macedonia, 2016-2024 (Sources: Ministry of Finance of the Republic of North Macedonia, World Justice Project 2016-2025)

The graph illustrates the trajectories of FDI as a share of GDP, the Rule of Law Index, and the Absence of Corruption Index in North Macedonia over the period 2016–2024, highlighting the relationship between institutional quality and FDI inflows.

The FDI/GDP ratio exhibits pronounced volatility, with notable peaks (2018 and 2022) followed by sharp declines. This instability suggests that FDI in North Macedonia is highly sensitive to short-term shocks, including external (global economic uncertainty, the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical risks) and internal ones (political transitions, policy unpredictability).

The Rule of Law Index remains relatively stable throughout the period, displaying only marginal improvements and no structural breakthrough. This suggests that institutional reforms have been gradual and have exerted limited direct influence on short-term FDI fluctuations.

The **Absence of Corruption Index** shows a slight downward trend, indicating that institutional reforms and transparency initiatives have not yet achieved the desired impact. The slow pace of improvement underscores the persistence of corruption as a systemic obstacle to sustained FDI inflows. The Pearson correlation coefficients for the above data set are presented below.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix between income level, FDI (% of GDP), Rule of Law Index and Absence of Corruption Index in the Republic of North Macedonia, 2016-2024 (Source: authors’ calculations, 2025)

Pearson Matrix*	FDI /GDP (in %)	Rule of Law (0–1)	Absence of Corruption
FDI /GDP (in %)	1.00	-0.69	-0.47
Rule of Law (0–1)	-0.69	1.00	0.93
Absence of corruption	-0.47	0.93	1.00

**Since the income-level code remained constant throughout the analyzed period, correlation analysis with FDI as share of GDP is not applicable.*

Table 3 reports the correlation matrix for the nine-year sample (n = 9), and two-tailed p-values. For North Macedonia, annual values for FDI/GDP (dependent) and the lagged rule-of-law and absence-of-corruption indices (independent) were analyzed for 2016–2024. Pearson correlations indicate a negative association between contemporaneous FDI/GDP and the (lagged) Rule of Law Index ($r \approx -0.69$), as well as a weaker negative association with the Absence of Corruption Index ($r \approx -0.47$).

These findings are consistent with the regional analysis. While a **strong positive relationship** exists between income level and institutional quality, the correlation between FDI/GDP ratios and institutional indicators remains **weak and inconsistent**. FDI inflows fluctuate independently of relatively stable or slowly improving institutional conditions, suggesting that investment decisions are driven more by short-term macroeconomic and political factors than by gradual institutional change. This divergence reflects the time lag between institutional reforms and their recognition by foreign investors.

Even modest improvements in the rule of law and anti-corruption efforts require long-term credibility and enforcement consistency before translating into higher investor confidence. The findings emphasize the complex and non-linear relationship between institutional quality and FDI inflows. Although economic theory predicts a positive link, the empirical evidence for North Macedonia demonstrates that short-term FDI dynamics are dominated by external shocks and political volatility, while institutional reforms require sustained credibility. Ultimately, the results emphasize that for North Macedonia, institutional quality is a necessary but not sufficient condition for attracting sustainable FDI: consistency, credibility, and stability over time are crucial for transforming reforms into tangible economic benefits.

Policy-relevant diagnostics for North Macedonia

- FDI composition: Available evidence suggests episodic, project-based inflows (e.g., manufacturing greenfield projects and resource-linked investments). Disaggregated FDI data by sector would clarify whether investments are efficiency-seeking, market-seeking, or resource-seeking.

- Institutional credibility: incremental improvements in governance indices will translate into sustained investment only if judicial independence and enforcement are demonstrably strengthened.
- Complementary reforms: infrastructure development, labor-market quality, and investment facilitation must accompany governance reforms to enhance absorptive capacity.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Institutional quality should be understood not only as a governance imperative but also as a fundamental condition for investment security and sustainable economic growth. The comparative results indicate that the relationship between institutional quality (rule of law and absence of corruption) and FDI is conditional on income level and structural economic characteristics.

This study documents a robust positive relationship between institutional quality and income level, alongside a counterintuitive negative association between institutional quality and FDI as a share of GDP at the regional-aggregate level. These patterns reflect structural effects – such as denominator dynamics and sector composition – and underscore that while strong institutions are essential for attracting high-quality, stable FDI, elevated FDI/GDP ratios in low-income economies often signals scale distortions or short-term, less developmental inflows rather than governance-driven investor confidence.

Concrete policy recommendations for transitional economies and North Macedonia

- ***Strengthen judicial independence and case-processing capacity*** to reduce investor legal risk and increase enforcement credibility. Specific actions: implement transparent judicial appointment procedures, modernize case management systems, and adequately fund specialized commercial courts.
- ***Target anti-corruption reforms with measurable milestones***: strengthen asset-declaration systems, protect whistleblowers, and prioritize high-impact procurement reforms. Specific actions: mandatory e-procurement, independent audit of major public projects, and clear sanctions for procurement violations.
- ***Improve investment promotion and aftercare***: proactively link incoming FDI to local suppliers and skills development through local content clauses and training subsidies. Specific actions: create supplier development programs and public–private training partnerships tied to major FDI projects.
- ***Diversify FDI away from extractive and low-value sectors***: design incentives that favor technology transfer, local employment, and research and development activities rather than short-term tax holidays alone. Specific actions: design performance-based incentives favoring technology transfer, local employment, and R&D rather than short-term tax holidays.
- ***Enhance data transparency***: publish disaggregated FDI statistics by sector, origin, and project size to better monitor quality of inflows. Specific actions: economic authorities should adopt standardized reporting templates for FDI projects.

For the Republic of North Macedonia, strengthening judicial independence, combating corruption, and improving transparency remain critical for sustaining investor confidence. Reforms targeting regulatory quality and institutional trust are likely to yield more consistent FDI flows, especially when combined with macroeconomic stability.

Research implications

Future research should apply country-level panel regressions with appropriate control variables, explore instrumental-variable strategies, and analyze disaggregated FDI data to distinguish investment types and their sensitivity to specific institutional dimensions.

** The views expressed in this paper do not necessarily reflect those of the institutions in which authors are employed.*

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GREEN JOBS – WHAT DIGITALIZATION AND THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT HAVE BROUGHT TO LABOUR

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Abstract

In a constantly changing world, where the economy, the environment, and labour are increasingly intertwined, the question arises: can new forms of work contribute to a more sustainable future? Green jobs, as a concept of the modern paradigm, have the potential to change the structure of the labour market while at the same time being in the "service" of nature and the environment.

Analysing contemporary labour trends, driven by digitalization, new legal regulations, and collective ecological awakening, the authors of this paper also raise the issue of the impact of technological progress, normative development, and socio-economic opportunities, focusing on the relationship between digitalization and sustainability. The concept of sustainable development, especially in the area of labour, represents a kind of ethical revolution in the way things have been done so far, which places sustainability as a value, not just as a strategy. Additionally, within the framework of their analysis, the authors also address the aspect of workers' skills and qualifications and the need for further education in order to transition to green jobs, emphasizing the importance of educational programs and professional development.

By identifying the advantages and challenges of new "green" sectors, the foundation is being laid for effectively adapting the workforce to the demands of future, sustainable economies. But what remains most challenging is inequality, and will this shift deepen existing gaps or be an opportunity to overcome them?

Keywords: jobs, green transformation, sustainable development, digitalization

INTRODUCTION

Vivimus in tempore transitus — We live in a time of transition. Our world, built on the principles of industrial progress of the last century, is increasingly facing the limits of its ecological, social and economic sustainability. Work is becoming a central field of transformation, the digital revolution accompanied by environmental risks necessitates a complete change of the system on which employment relations, productivity and the basic concepts of work are based – as times change, we must change too.

Green jobs are a reflection of the new relationships between labour, nature, and technology, that is, the idea that jobs must be in harmony with nature. In this abyss between tradition and transformation, a fundamental question arises: Can labour—what defines us as a society—become a tool for maintaining, rather than destroying, the world around us?

The European Green Deal is an extremely ambitious plan for the old continent to transition to a more sustainable economy. The Union aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, requiring significant changes in industries, especially in the energy and transport sectors, agriculture, and manufacturing, in the member states, but also in the candidate countries. The creation of more fully or partially green jobs is of crucial importance, especially in the mentioned sectors, because through them not only do companies align themselves with environmental goals, but they also create the potential to create millions of new employment opportunities, which should serve as a balance for the large number of projected job losses as a result of the obligations of the agreement itself that are binding on the signatory countries. Traditionally industrial countries that operate in mining, coal and oil extraction, and other heavy industries will be most affected by these processes, given that in those countries these industries have the largest share of GDP and are the largest employers, which means that millions of people are directly affected by these changes.

The transition to sustainability involves significant restructuring of the companies themselves, changes in production processes, more rigorous rules that must be respected, and large financial expenditures that will be borne by employers. It is no longer enough to be a classic “worker”, but workers must keep up with the new digital reality. However, digitalization is a kind of paradox: while some jobs die, new ones are born, but they require other, different skills, and this creates inequality.

Digitalization, on the one hand, appears to be an ambivalent phenomenon: it offers great potential for optimization, efficiency, automation of processes, and increased productivity, but at the same time, it replaces certain traditional forms of work. However, digitalization should be analysed in terms of creating new systems that will help repair the environmental damage caused by traditional industries and promote green growth. It is in this combination of technology and ethics that the concept of green jobs is born, which overcomes the dichotomy between economic development and environmental protection.

This paper analyses precisely this intersection between digitalization and sustainable development as driving forces in shaping the new world of work. It will explore how new technologies can contribute to the creation of green jobs, as well as the ethical, economic, and social implications of that process.

The impact of digitalization in creating green jobs

Digitalization is a process that began long ago, with the so-called Fourth Industrial Revolution, which is moving towards the Fifth Industrial Revolution (**Schwab, n.d.**). Digitalization is a complex process that refers to the integration of digital technologies into all areas of business and society, resulting in significant changes in how industries function, how people work, and how economic value is created. In recent years, digitalization has become one of the most influential drivers of change in the European Union (EU) labour market, transforming sectors, jobs, and the skills needed. The world of work as we once knew it is no more.

Digitalization has had a significant impact on jobs globally, but also within the European Union, and even at the national level. This was especially evident during the

coronavirus pandemic, where we have witnessed certain shifts in some job categories, creating a need for new jobs and workers who have the ability to adapt quickly to changes in labour.

The introduction of advanced digital technologies—such as automation, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, the Internet of Things (IoT), and cloud computing—has revolutionized industries across the EU. The impact of digitalization can be seen in almost every sector, from manufacturing and agriculture to finance and healthcare. However, the effects are not uniform, and the extent to which digitalization transforms jobs depends on a number of factors, including the sector's reliance on technology, the availability of digital infrastructure, and the pace at which companies adopt new digital solutions.

The benefits of digitalization can be seen most clearly through the automation of repetitive tasks and processes in sectors such as manufacturing and logistics, which are now performed with digital solutions or robotic tools, resulting in increased productivity and reduced costs. Robotics is increasingly common in the automotive industry, where machines now perform tasks that were previously performed by humans, for example. Drones are more and more used for deliveries, while artificial intelligence algorithms are being applied in logistics. In this constellation, there seems to be less demand for people in traditional job positions, such as truck drivers, warehouse workers, and conveyor belt operators, as many manual tasks are replaced by robots and algorithms.

But what does this actually mean?

As we have mentioned, digitalization is not only leading to job losses but also creating new opportunities in areas such as data analytics, cybersecurity, software development, and digital marketing. As businesses embrace digital technologies, there is an increasing demand for highly skilled workers who can design, implement, and manage these technologies. The shift to more digitally oriented business models has led to entirely new professions, with these jobs offering competitive salaries and career advancement opportunities.

However, one of the biggest challenges that digitalization brings is precisely the loss of jobs that inevitably cease to be needed. The automation of tasks that were once performed by people—whether in factories, service centres, or administration—can lead to a significant reduction in demand for certain categories of jobs. According to a 2020 report by the European Commission, automation could lead to the displacement of up to 7 million jobs across the EU by 2030, especially in areas such as manufacturing, retail, and transport (**European Commission, 2020**).

At the same time, digitalization has increased the demand for higher levels of skills and education. For example, as industries become more reliant on digital tools, there is an increasing demand for workers skilled in areas such as coding, software engineering, machine learning, and data analytics. These jobs are often associated with higher salaries and better long-term prospects compared to traditional professions, but the skills gap between workers in the digital economy and those in more traditional sectors poses a significant challenge.

A key aspect of digitalization is the shift towards “knowledge-based” jobs, which require workers to have strong analytical and digital skills and problem-solving abilities.

Digitalization has also led to the emergence of hybrid job categories that combine traditional skills with digital ones. These “digitally enhanced” jobs include positions such as digital project managers and marketing automation specialists. For example, in

marketing, the increased use of AI and machine learning tools has led to a rise in jobs focused on analysing consumer behaviour through data insights, rather than relying on traditional marketing strategies.

Digitalization has also led to new forms of work, such as remote work, freelance work, and work on digital platforms. This shift towards more flexible, decentralized work arrangements has led to the rise of platforms such as Uber, Airbnb, and Upwork, which allow individuals to offer services remotely or on a part-time basis. New technologies such as digital platforms designed to connect users with each other and with advertisers, on which social networks are built, provide additional support for the spread of the “stall economy” (Ristovski, 2024). While this has provided greater flexibility and opportunities for some workers, it has also raised concerns about job security, benefits, and the erosion of traditional labour protections. The work of the platform has highlighted the most important challenges, including low and irregular wages, job insecurity, issues related to algorithmic control and surveillance, data protection issues, lack of rights and protections from employment, and limited collective representation (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2024). However, in addition to the positive type of freedom of association and action, there is also a negative type that manifests itself in the right of an employee not to be a member of a union without employment law consequences, i.e., the freedom not to be a member of a union at all, as well as the freedom to leave a union (Jovevski, 2022).

Moreover, digitalization requires not only technical skills but also a range of “soft” skills, including problem-solving, adaptability, and collaboration. As industries embrace automation and artificial intelligence, the ability to work alongside machines, interpret data, and manage complex digital systems is becoming increasingly important. Upskilling and reskilling initiatives are therefore crucial to ensure that workers can transition to new jobs that will require digital competencies.

While it brings significant changes in terms of the elimination of certain categories of jobs and the creation of new ones, it also raises important questions about how workers can adapt to these changes. The transition to a digital economy requires a joint effort from policymakers, businesses, and educational institutions to invest in the upskilling and retraining of the workforce. Thus, the regulation of platform work has become one of the most important issues in order to preserve the European social model in the context of increased digitalization. The EU Directive on improving working conditions in platform work (COM/2021/762) represents the first attempt by the EU to regulate platform work and is part of the EU reform package aimed at regulating the digital economy, which also includes the Digital Markets Act, the Digital Services Act, and the Artificial Intelligence Act (Bertolin, 2024). The directive addresses many of the challenges affecting platform workers in the EU by introducing regulations in several areas: employment status, algorithmic governance, transparency and enforcement, and collective bargaining (Bertolin, 2024).

As digitalization continues to transform the EU labour market, a key challenge will be to ensure that the benefits of these changes are felt equally by all. While some sectors will undoubtedly experience job losses, others will see significant growth in new jobs. By addressing the skills gap, providing support for affected workers, and fostering a culture of continuous learning, we can harness the transformative power of digitalization to create a more dynamic, resilient, and inclusive labour market.

The concept of sustainable development and jobs

One of the main objectives of the European Green Deal is the promotion of green jobs, especially in sectors with high negative environmental impacts. Traditional production processes have proven to be highly polluting (e.g., steel, pulp and paper, and chemical industries), while on the other hand, some of the new high-diffusion technologies have also been shown to have a high environmental impact, for example, agricultural pesticides, solvents, plastics, and fossil fuels (EU-ILO, 2019). This is why areas for new job creation include renewable energy sources, sustainable agriculture, and the circular economy.

In Europe, the transition to wind, solar, and hydropower is expected to generate significant employment opportunities. The European Commission estimates that by 2050, renewable energy could create up to 2 million jobs, particularly in these areas. The new jobs will range from research and development to installation and maintenance.

Sustainable agriculture is another key area where green jobs are expected to grow. The EU's "farm to fork" strategy (European Commission, 2020), a central component of the Green Deal, aims to make food systems healthier and more environmentally friendly. This includes promoting organic farming, reducing pesticide use, enhancing biodiversity, and encouraging local food production. Employment opportunities are expected to grow in areas such as organic farming, agroecology, and sustainable forestry.

The transition to a circular economy, focused on reducing waste and maximizing the reuse, repair, and recycling of materials, is another key component of the Green Deal. The European Commission has highlighted the potential for the circular economy to generate significant employment, particularly in sectors such as recycling, waste management, and product processing.

A report by the European Environment Agency (EEA) estimates that up to 700,000 jobs could be created in the EU by 2030 as a result of the circular economy (European Environment Agency, 2019). These jobs would primarily be located in the construction, electrical, and textile sectors, where there is an increasing demand for resource-efficient and environmentally friendly production processes.

The shift away from fossil fuels, as one of the commitments under the European Green Deal, will potentially have the greatest impact on the labour market. Europe must reduce its dependence on coal, oil, and natural gas to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, and as a result, millions of jobs in the extractive industry and distribution of fossil fuels are at risk. For workers, the challenges relate to job and income security, working conditions, social protection, and access to their fundamental rights to freedom of association and collective bargaining (International Labour Organization, 2021).

These potential job losses will disproportionately affect regions dependent on coal mining, oil extraction and gas production. For example, coal mining communities in countries such as Poland, Germany and the Czech Republic are particularly affected by the transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources.

Investing in reskilling and upskilling programs is essential to ensure that workers can move from high-carbon sectors to green jobs. Programs should focus on the specific skills needed in the new digital age and working with renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable industries. The European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan highlights the need for lifelong learning initiatives, which will be essential for workers in fossil fuel industries who may need to acquire new skills to enter the green economy (European Commission, 2022). Collaboration between governments, employers, and

educational institutions, both public and private, is crucial to make long-term plans that will make the transition smoother and more resilient.

One of the elements of the European Green Deal is the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM), which aims to provide financial support to regions and workers affected by the green transition. The JTM includes the Just Transition Fund, which has been allocated €17.5 billion to help diversify the economies of coal-dependent regions, create new jobs, and invest in reskilling programs.

Countries with high levels of automation in industries such as automotive manufacturing (e.g., Germany) or agriculture (e.g., Spain) will face a greater displacement of workers with lower skills and education. At the same time, there will be a need for a significant shift in skills towards high-tech sectors, which require more complex retraining and upskilling programs. The European Commission has stressed the importance of lifelong learning and continuous training to ensure that workers can adapt to the changing labour market. But while there seems to be a political consensus that the promotion of lifelong learning and vocational training by employers and governments is important for shaping the world of work, upskilling cannot always be the “solution” for workers who have lost or will lose their jobs as a result of the introduction of labour-saving technologies (Konle-Seidl & Danesi, 2022).

In a green economy, the concept of “good jobs” includes not only decent wages and working conditions but also environmental sustainability and well-being. Green jobs also make a positive contribution to broader societal goals for environmental protection. Here, the International Labour Organization has taken the position that green jobs should be seen as a path to achieving both social and environmental justice, with an emphasis on workers’ rights, health and safety, and the promotion of decent work standards.

CONCLUSION

Modern economic and social trends confirm the transformative power of digitalization and the concept of sustainable development in creating new, green jobs. In the context of the green economy, digital technologies enable the optimization of energy systems, better waste control, more efficient use of resources, and monitoring of environmental impact. These benefits lead to the creation of green jobs in sectors such as renewable energy sources, energy efficiency, waste management, eco-engineering, and digital services aimed at sustainable practices.

On the other hand, the concept of sustainable labour development imposes new ethical and social standards. Today's jobs should not only be economically sustainable but also socially just and environmentally acceptable. However, despite the numerous positive aspects, this transformation also brings new challenges. There is a risk of digital inequality, technological unemployment, and inadequate preparation of the workforce for the new conditions. Therefore, a systematic and long-term strategy for human capital development is needed—through educational reforms, investment in digital skills, and continuous retraining (World Economic Forum, 2023). Therefore, educational institutions and employment policies have a key role to play, which should enable systematic retraining and alignment of the labour market with the needs of the green digital economy.

From a macroeconomic perspective, the integration of digital technologies into the green economy contributes to strengthening competitiveness, increasing energy independence, and stimulating innovation. At the microeconomic level, however, organizations that apply the principles of digital sustainability become more agile, more

efficient, and more socially responsible. This symbiosis between technology and sustainability redefines the concept of labour—from a traditional, physical activity to an intellectual and creative one.

Finally, we would like to emphasize that digitalization and the concept of sustainable development are key drivers in the creation of new green jobs. The development of more green jobs will create new employment opportunities, foster economic resilience, and guide society towards a greener and fairer future. To harness this potential, a partnership between the state, academia, the private sector, and civil society is necessary. Only through such a collaborative approach can the digital transition truly contribute to sustainable development, creating labour that is both productive and environmentally responsible.

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ROAD SAFETY MANAGEMENT CAPACITY ASSESSMENT IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

Road safety management capacity is critical for reducing traffic accidents and associated fatalities. Despite ongoing efforts to improve road safety, North Macedonia continues to experience higher rates of road traffic crashes compared to EU averages. This study aims to assess existing road safety management capacities in North Macedonia by identifying strengths and weaknesses in order to inform policy interventions and institutional improvements. The assessment is conducted using a structured questionnaire adapted from international guidelines and administered to national and local stakeholders involved in road safety.

The study identifies gaps in strategic planning, institutional coordination, data management systems, and human resource capacities within North Macedonia's road safety management framework. Strengthening road safety management requires targeted interventions, including enhanced inter-agency coordination, improving data collection and analysis systems, and the development of sustainable funding mechanisms. Building local-level capacity through structured training programs and institutional reforms is essential for the effective implementation of road safety policies. This research provides a foundational analysis to support policymakers in formulating evidence-based strategies aimed at significantly reducing traffic accidents and fatalities.

Keywords: road safety, traffic accidents, capacity assessment, management

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Official statistical data from the World Health Organization (WHO) indicate that approximately 1.19 million people die annually in road traffic crashes, while nearly 50 million are injured. A staggering 92% of all fatalities occur in low- and middle- income countries. Road traffic injuries remain the leading cause of death among children and young people aged 5–29 years (WHO, 2023).

The Stockholm Declaration affirmed the vital role of road safety in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and called upon the United Nations to set an ambitious target to reduce global road traffic deaths and serious injuries by 50% by 2030 (El-Adawy et al., 2022). In Europe, road safety policy has been guided by the Safe System and Vision Zero approach, with intermediate targets aimed at halving the number of fatalities and, for the first time, the number of seriously injured persons by 2030, as a step toward achieving near-zero deaths by 2050.

In line with European objective, one of the main goals of the National Transport Strategy of North Macedonia is to reduce the number of road traffic fatalities by 50% by 2030 compared to 2017 (MoTC, 2018). Although initial progress toward this target exceeded expectations, with a 25.2% reduction recorded in 2021, a reversal occurred in 2022. Over the past three years, an increasing trend of 22.4% has been observed (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Number of fatalities per year²⁴

Over the past 15 years, an average of 144 people per year have been killed on roads in North Macedonia. In 2024 alone, road traffic crashes resulted in 142 fatalities and 1,085 serious injuries. The fatality rate, expressed as the number of deaths per million inhabitants, stands at 67, significantly higher than the European Union average of 46 fatalities per million inhabitants (Figure 2).

²⁴ Ministry of Interior.

Figure 2: Fatality rate – fatalities/million inhabitants²⁵

Road traffic crashes represent not only a major public health issue but also a significant socio-economic challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Pavleski & Jolakoski, 2025). Beyond the toll on victims and their families, traffic crashes impose substantial economic costs. According to World Bank, the costs of road traffic crashes in North Macedonia amounts to approximately 2.1% of GDP (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023), equivalent to roughly €300 million annually.

Road safety management capacities refer to the readiness and ability of public authorities to implement necessary measures and activities efficiently and in a timely manner, and to achieve policy, regulatory, and practice changes required to manage the road transport system effectively and deliver improved safety outcomes (Breen et al., 2018).

The subject of the research is the assessment of road safety management capacities, while the objective is to analyze current institutional practices related to road traffic safety and to identify opportunities for strengthening coordination and efficiency at both national and local levels, in line with international best practices.

1.2. Road Safety Management System

The road safety management system can be conceptualized as consisting of three interrelated elements: institutional management functions, interventions and results (Figure 3). Managing for road safety outcomes requires an integrated and accountable response across all these elements of the system. This conceptual framework is derived from New Zealand’s comprehensive road safety target-setting model, introduced in 2010, which linked desired safety outcomes with interventions and institutional implementation arrangements (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

The road safety management system possesses several generic characteristics that enable its application across countries regardless of development level or road safety performance. It emphasizes that road safety outcomes are “produced” in the same manner as other public goods and services. The production process is conceptualized as a

²⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

management system operating at three levels: institutional management functions generate interventions, which in turn produce results. The model is neutral with respect to country-specific governance structures and cultural context, which shape how institutions operate and how goals are set and achieved (Bliss & Breen, 2013; SafetyNet, 2009).

Figure 3: Road Safety Management System (Martensen et al., 2021)

2.1.1. Institutional management functions

A focus on results constitutes the core institutional management function for achieving improved road safety results. All other institutional management functions are subordinate to this overarching focus and contribute to its realization. A country's results focus reflects a pragmatic articulation of its ambition to improve road safety, along with the means agreed upon to achieve that ambition. In the absence of a clear and accountable focus on results, institutional functions and interventions lack cohesion, thereby undermining the efficiency and effectiveness of safety initiatives (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

Coordination refers to the alignment and orchestration of interventions and related institutional management functions delivered by government entities in cooperation with community and business partners to achieve the desired safety outcomes.

Legislation encompasses the legal instruments required for governance, defining institutional mandates, responsibilities, accountability mechanisms and interventions necessary to achieve the desired focus on results.

Funding and resource allocation concerns the sustainable financing of interventions and institutional management functions through rational evaluation and programming frameworks.

Promotion involves sustained communication of road safety as a core responsibility for government and society and emphasizes shared societal accountability to support the delivery of the interventions required.

Monitoring and evaluation entail the systematic and ongoing measurement of road safety outputs and outcomes (intermediate and final), as well as and the evaluation of interventions.

Research and development, along with knowledge transfer, involve the systematic and continuous generation, codification, dissemination and application of knowledge to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of the road safety management system.

2.1.2. Interventions

Interventions are designed to achieve the defined results focus. They address the safe planning, design and operation, and use of the road network, the conditions under which vehicles and road users interact with the system, and the effective recovery and rehabilitation of crash victims. Interventions also establish standards and rules intended to secure compliance and enhance overall safety (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

2.1.3. Results

The final component of the road safety management system concerns the measurement of outcomes and formulation of targets expressed in terms of final outcomes, intermediate outcomes, and outputs. Targets articulate the desired level of safety performance endorsed by governments, stakeholders and the community. Countries demonstrating good practice typically adopt quantitative outcome and intermediate targets, supplemented by output targets aligned with these objectives. (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.2. Assessment framework

The review of road safety management capacities in the Republic of North Macedonia is based on the assessment framework defined in the *Guidelines for Road Safety Management Capacity Reviews and Safe System Projects* of the Global Road Safety Facility (GRSF) under the World Bank. The assessment framework consists of a series of checklists with structured questions based on identified good practices in road safety management (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Jovanov, Pavleski, et al., 2023). These checklists enable a detailed examination of all elements of the road safety management system and their relationship with current practices (Figure 4).

Checklist 1: Lead agency role and institutional management functions				
Questions	Yes	Partial	Pending	No
Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the results focus management functions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appraising current road safety performance through high-level strategic review? Adopting a far-reaching road safety vision for the longer term? Analyzing what could be achieved in the medium term? Setting quantitative targets by mutual consent across the road safety partnership? Establishing mechanisms to ensure partnership accountability for results? 				
Checklist 1: Results focus at system level				
Does the lead coordinator? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horiz Vertic Specif and b Partic 				
Questions	Yes	Partial	Pending	No
Are estimates of the social costs of crashes available?				
Does the lead legislation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revis Devel Cont Secur 				
Are data on road deaths and injuries readily available?				
Have the risks faced by road users been identified? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drivers? Passengers? Motorcyclists? Cyclists? Children? Others? 				
Does the lead funding an? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensur Estab prog 				
Checklist 2: Planning, design, operation and use of the road network	Yes	Partial	Pending	No
Has a nation term be? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have national Soc Fin Chan Inte Multi Inte Leadi Devel Identif to achiev Carry Hig Pol Pla 				
Have comprehensive safety standards and rules and associated performance targets been set for the planning, design, operation and use of roads to achieve the desired focus on results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National roads? Provincial roads? Regional roads? City roads? 				
Are the official speed limits aligned with Safe-System design principles to achieve the desired focus on results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National roads? Provincial roads? Regional roads? City roads? 				
For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, city) are compliance regimes in place to ensure adherence to specified safety standards and rules to achieve the desired focus on results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Road safety impact assessment? Road safety audit? Road safety inspection? Black spot management? Network safety management? Speed management? Alcohol management? Safety belts management? Helmets management? Fatigue management? 				
Does the lead monitoring? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Estab Inter Trans Mak 				
Are regular p <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Devel Creat Secur Train Estab Settin 				
Do the specified safety standards and rules and related compliance regimes clearly address the safety priorities of high-risk road user groups to achieve the desired focus on results?				
Do the specified safety standards and rules and related compliance regimes compare favorably with international good practices?				

Figure 4: Example of checklists

The elements of the assessment framework include:

- Key institutional management functions (focus on results, coordination, legislation, financing and resource allocation, promotion, monitoring and evaluation, research and development, and knowledge transfer), which provide the foundation for:
- Multisectoral, system-wide interventions (safe roads, safe speeds, safe vehicles, safe users, and post-crash care), aimed at achieving:
- Results, including the costs of road crashes, crash outcome indicators, road safety performance indicators, and process indicators.

Checklist findings must be interpreted using expert road safety management judgment. If responses to the questions are predominantly “no” or “pending”, national capacity is considered weak. A high number of “pending” or “partial” responses also indicate weak capacity, although signs of capacity strengthening may be evident and should be acknowledged and encouraged. Capacity can be considered strong only when there is a predominance of “yes” responses. It is important to reach consensus on the assessment for each element of the road safety management system being appraised (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3. Implementation steps

2.3.1. Set review objectives

The generic objectives of a country road safety management capacity review are to:

- Establish an integrated multisectoral framework for dialogue with country partners and stakeholders on potential road safety investments;
- Assess government ownership of road safety results and identify related institutional responsibilities and accountabilities;

- Reach official consensus on road safety management capacity weaknesses and institutional strengthening and investment priorities to address them;
- Identify Safe System implementation projects to support the investment strategy.
-

2.3.2. Prepare for review

Careful preparation for a country road safety management review is critical to its overall success. High-level national commitment to the review must be ensured; otherwise, the review objectives cannot be achieved. The review should be conducted by experienced, internationally recognized road safety experts with senior management experience at both national and international levels.

An inception report should be prepared by the client country prior to the review to outline the basic elements of the road safety management system and to provide available data on road safety results and trends. A detailed consultation schedule should be prepared in advance and managed locally to ensure a smooth flow of meetings, with flexibility to reschedule where necessary if the availability of key officials changes (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3.3. Appraise results focus at system level

The road safety management system provides the framework for conducting a country road safety management capacity review. The checklist for appraising results focus at the system level addresses the following questions (Bliss & Breen, 2013):

- Are estimates of the social costs of road crashes available?
- Are data on road traffic deaths and injuries readily available?
- Have the risks faced by road users been systematically identified?
- Has a national long-term vision for improved road safety performance been officially adopted?
- Have national and regional targets for improved safety performance been established?
- Have all agencies responsible for improved safety performance been identified and formally held accountable for achieving the desired results?
- Have the responsibilities of industry, community and business stakeholders for improved road safety performance reviews been clearly defined?
- Are regular performance reviews conducted to assess progress and implement improvements?
- Has a lead agency been formally established to direct the national road safety effort?
- Is the role of the lead agency defined in legislation, policy documents, or annual performance agreements?

2.3.4. Appraise results focus at interventions level

Following the appraisal of results focus at the system level, capacity must be assessed in terms of results focus at the interventions level. Interventions address the safe planning, design, operation and use of the road network; the conditions under which vehicles and road users can safely operate; and the recovery and rehabilitation of crash victims. They also establish specific standards and rules aimed at achieving this safety and ensuring compliance.

The assessment considers three broad categories of interventions and examines the linkages between interventions, their outputs, intermediate outcomes, and final outcomes.

The following checklists define the scope of appraisal at the intervention level (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

Planning, design, operation, and use of the road network:

- Have comprehensive safety standards, rules, and performance targets been established for road planning, design, operation and use?
- Are official speed limits aligned with Safe System design principles?
- For each road category (national, regional, provincial, urban), are compliance regimes in place to ensure adherence to safety standards?
- Do safety standards and rules and compliance regimes address the priorities of high-risk road user groups?
- Do these standards and rules and compliance regimes compare favorably with international good practice?

Entry and exit of vehicles to and from the road network:

- Have comprehensive safety standards, rules, and associated performance targets been established to regulate vehicle entry and exit?
- For each vehicle and safety equipment category (private, commercial, public transport, helmets), are compliance regimes in place?
- Do these safety standards and compliance regimes address the priorities of high-risk road user groups?
- Do they compare favorably with international good practice?

Entry and exit of road users to and from the road network:

- Have comprehensive safety standards, rules, and performance targets been established for road users entry and exit?
- For each driver category (private, commercial, public), are compliance regimes in place?
- Do these standards and compliance regimes address the priorities of high-risk road user groups?
- Do they compare favorably with international good practice?
- Have comprehensive safety standards and performance targets been established for the recovery and rehabilitation of crash victims?
- For each category of post-crash care (pre-hospital, hospital, long term care), are compliance regimes in place?
- Do post-crash care standards and compliance regimes adequately address the needs of high-risk road user groups?

2.3.5. Appraise results focus at the institutional management functions level

It is important to examine each institutional management function and explore its linkages with the identified interventions and their intended results focus. The following checklists set out the appraisal framework that addresses the crucial contribution of institutional management functions subordinate to the desired focus on results (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

The checklist for Coordination covers the following questions:

- Are interventions coordinated horizontally across agencies to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are interventions coordinated vertically between national, regional, provincial and city agencies to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Have robust intervention delivery partnerships between agencies, industry, communities and the business sector been established to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Have parliamentary committees and procedures supporting the coordination process been established to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Legislation covers the following questions:

- Are legislative instruments and procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions sufficient to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are legislative instruments and procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions regularly reviewed and reformed to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Funding and resource allocation covers the following questions:

- Are sustainable funding mechanisms supporting interventions and institutional management functions in place to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are formal resource allocation procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions in place to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Is there an official Value of a Statistical Life and related values for injuries to guide resource allocation decisions?
- Are funding mechanisms and resource allocation procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions sufficient to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Promotion covers the following questions:

- Is road safety regularly promoted to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Monitoring and evaluation covers the following questions:

- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are sustainable systems in place to collect and manage data on road crashes, fatality and injury outcomes, and all related road environment/vehicle/road user factors to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are sustainable systems in place to collect and manage data on road network traffic, vehicle speeds, safety belt and helmet wearing rates to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are regular safety rating surveys undertaken to quality assure adherence to specified safety standards and rules, to achieve the desired focus on results?

- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are systems in place to collect and manage data on the output quantities and qualities of safety interventions implemented to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of vehicles and safety equipment (private, commercial, public transport, helmets) are systematic and regular safety rating surveys undertaken to quality assure adherence to the specified safety standards and rules to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of post-crash care (pre-hospital, hospital, long-term care) are systematic and regular surveys undertaken to quality assure adherence to the specified standards and rules to achieve the desired focus on result?
- Are systems in place to regularly monitor and evaluate safety performance against established targets to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Do all participating agencies and external partners and stakeholders have open access to all collected data?

The checklist for Research and development and knowledge transfer covers the following questions:

- Has a national road safety research and development strategy been established to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Has an independent national road safety research organization been established to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Have demonstration and pilot programs been conducted to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are mechanisms and communication channels in place to disseminate the findings of national road safety research and development to achieve the desired focus on results?

2.3.6. Assess lead agency role and identify capacity strengthening priorities

In good-practice countries, the lead agency (or the informal lead agency/agencies) plays a preeminent role in most institutional management functions, although in some cases it may adopt more of a guiding, facilitating or catalytic role. The lead agency assumes responsibility within government for developing the national road safety strategy and defining its results focus, which represents the overarching institutional management function.

The checklist for assessing the lead agency role covers the following questions (Bliss & Breen, 2013):

- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the results focus management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the coordination management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the legislation management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the funding and resource allocation management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the promotion management function?

- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the monitoring and evaluation management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the research and development and knowledge transfer management function?

2.3.7. Specify investment strategy and identify Safe System implementation projects

This stage of the capacity review addresses the specification of a long-term investment strategy aimed at accelerating the transition from a low-capacity to a high-capacity road safety management system and identifying appropriate implementation options. Safety management capacity weaknesses in low- and middle-income countries present a formidable barrier to progress and typically require strengthening of institutional management functions. Similar capacity gaps may also arise in high-income countries as their results focus shifts towards higher levels of ambition.

In both contexts, an investment strategy must be designed to overcome inherent capacity weaknesses by first establishing a core institutional capacity to bring safety outcomes under control, then scaling up investment to accelerate capacity building across the entire road network, and finally consolidating these gains on a sustainable basis (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3.8. Confirm review findings at high-level workshop

A workshop should be planned and scheduled as a formal component of the capacity review process, with the objective of confirming and integrating the findings derived from the checklists and addressing any unresolved or previously unidentified issues. The workshop should bring together all relevant stakeholders in a multisectoral setting that enables comprehensive discussion of all elements of the road safety management system, fostering a spirit of strategic partnership and shared responsibility for improving road safety outcomes (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3.9. Finalize review report

A draft report presenting the capacity review findings should be circulated during the final phase of the review to all participants and relevant government bodies for comments and validation. Following incorporation of feedback, a final report should be prepared and formally distributed (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Implementation of the road safety management capacity review in North Macedonia

The successful implementation of the Road Safety Management Capacity Review required the active involvement of all relevant stakeholders to assess existing road safety management capacities and practices and to reach consensus on identified weaknesses across the entire system. To facilitate the review process, a Steering Committee was established, comprising representatives from key institutions and organizations, including the Ministry of Transport, Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Economy and Labour, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Education and Science, Ministry of Health, the Republic Council for Road Traffic Safety, and the Association of Local Self-Government Units.

In addition to these core stakeholders, the consultation process engaged representatives from central and local government, academia, civil society organizations, the professional sector, and international organizations (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023).

To discuss the findings and recommendations, a workshop was organized at the level of state secretaries and institutional directors. The consultation process concluded with a high-level final workshop, aimed at validating the findings and recommendations and addressing any issues not previously identified during the review. This workshop also served to achieve official consensus on strengthening road safety management capacities and to clarify institutional responsibilities, particularly concerning the role of the lead road safety agency and the enhancement of management capacities.

The revised final draft report of the Road Safety Management Capacity Review, including the Investment Strategy and Action Plan, was shared with all stakeholders for final written comments and feedback. The Action Plan outlines an expanded set of activities addressing key weaknesses identified during the review process. These activities are envisaged as project components within the broader Safe System framework and are fully aligned with the EU approach and the next generation of road safety strategies. The Action Plan is structured around six intervention areas: Road Safety Management, Safe Roads and Mobility, Safe Vehicles, Safe Road Users, Post-Crash Care, and Safe Speeds (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023). In total, the Action Plan defines 40 activities distributed across these intervention areas.

3.2. Key findings and recommendations

The review indicates that although the number of road traffic fatalities and serious injuries has declined, these figures continue to fluctuate over time, underscoring the need to strengthen coordination and adopt a more systematic and integrated approach. While the country has implemented certain initial measures and achieved several “low-hanging fruit” outcomes, sustaining and accelerating these positive trends requires the full establishment of a Safe System approach.

A strong need exists to introduce a data-driven road safety management framework. Beyond monitoring final outcomes such as crash numbers and consequences, the introduction of key performance indicators (KPIs) is essential to enable targeted interventions focused on high-risk road user behaviors (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023).

The key recommendations for advancing road safety in North Macedonia include:

- Development of a national road safety strategy, action plan, and annual implementation programs
- Alignment of the existing road crash database with the CADaS protocol and establishment of data exchange with the EU CARE database
- Establishment of a national integrated road safety database
- Proactive monitoring of road safety through indirect performance indicators
- Assessment of the socio-economic impacts of road traffic crashes
- Implementation of self-explaining and forgiving road design principles in accordance with the Safe System Approach
- Application of safe speed principles in road design
- Implementation of road infrastructure safety management procedures (RSIA, RSA, RSI, Risk Mapping, NSM, IDS)
- Establishment of a central vehicle registry
- Deployment of an automated traffic enforcement system

- Introduction of the MAIS3+ injury severity scale and improved data exchange between health institutions and the police
- Strengthening road safety education within formal education systems
- Enhancement of driver training programs and introduction of a graduated driver licensing system
- Continued efforts to establish a Road Traffic Safety Agency
- Activation of the National Coordinating Body for Road Safety Improvement
- Harmonization of national legislation with EU road safety directives and regulations
- Adoption of a sustainable financing model for road safety and improved resource allocation
- Full adoption of the Safe System Approach

CONCLUSION

The review of road safety management capacities in North Macedonia identified both the current institutional landscape and relevant international best practices, providing recommendations at systemic, operational, and institutional levels. Institutional capacities remain limited and require improved coordination, stable financing, and stronger accountability mechanisms. Achieving a sustained reduction in fatalities and serious injuries necessitates organized, systematic, and data-driven action, supported by the full implementation of the Safe System Approach.

The effective implementation of World Report recommendations requires a comprehensive and long-term commitment, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where the process may span a decade or more. Countries must first assess their road safety management capacity and readiness to undertake sustained reforms and investments. The assessment framework provides diagnostic tools to identify underlying conditions that influence success or failure and ensures that interventions are properly sequenced and aligned with institutional absorptive capacity. However, successful implementation requires the involvement of experienced road safety specialists with proven strategic management expertise at national and international levels.

Although each country faces unique challenges, experience from high-income countries demonstrates that effective road safety management is inherently complex. The sophistication of institutional arrangements in such contexts can be viewed as a proxy for success and sustained commitment to road safety investment. Ultimately, the implementation of World Report recommendations must be grounded in practice through a “learning by doing” approach, supported by targeted investments aimed at overcoming institutional capacity constraints

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CHALLENGES OF THE EUROPEAN ANTI-FRAUD OFFICE IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE INSTITUTIONS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract

In a world full of conflicts and wars in which we live today, corruption is a significant problem of the European Union facing the new challenges concerning the security of Europe. Corruption in the EU is a significant problem, with probable costs ranging from 200 to 1000 billion euros annually, representing up to 6% of the EU's GDP in contrast to defence spending at 1.6%, while there is armed conflict in Europe. For this reason, the EU has created the European Anti-Fraud Office to fight fraud affecting the EU budget, investigate corruption by staff of EU institutions and develop anti-fraud legislation and policies. In this context, the research is aimed at analysing the creation and function of the European Anti-Fraud Office in order to have a successful fight against corruption in the institutions of the European Union.

Keywords: European Anti-Fraud Office, corruption, European Union

1. METHODOLOGY, ORIGIN AND LEGAL BASIS

For the preparation of this paper, the method of analysis and the comparative method were used. The normative method and the *numerus clausus* method were used for studying and analysing the subject matter. An area of crime that attracted the early attention of the European Union institutions was fraud against the Union's financial interests. The need to protect the finances of the European Union led to significant interventions in Union legislation in the area of domestic criminal law. At the institutional level, the Commission decided in 1987 to establish under its own leadership the Anti-Fraud Unit, called UCLAF (an anti-fraud coordination unit named *Unité de Coordination de la Lutte Anti-Fraude*), which began operations in 1988. In 1993, the European Parliament adopted recommendations that significantly increased UCLAF's powers, and in 1995 it became authorized to launch investigations on its own initiative, based on information from various sources. All Commission organizational units are required to inform UCLAF of all suspicious matters that could develop into fraud, and which fall within their area of responsibility. During the 1990s, UCLAF worked towards the adoption of criminal legislation against fraud at European Union level, making particular efforts to strengthen the external dimension of the fight against fraud, and it does so by encouraging Member States to prosecute, based on their competence and jurisdiction, criminal acts of fraud against the financial interests of the European Union. Certain assumptions regarding important means of governance of the European Union led to reforms in the institutional sphere of the European Union to combat fraud. Such assumptions led to political crises in the European Union in the late 1990s, culminating in the fall of the Santer Commission in

1999. One of the responses to that crisis was internal institutional reforms, which transformed UCLAF into OLAF (from Unit to Office), which is the Anti-Fraud Office, for which one author noted was “the fruit of extraordinary circumstances that arose as a result of scandals” and that “reflects the need to re-establish credibility” (Pujas 2003). Thus, OLAF was established by Commission Decision in April 1999 (European Union Commission Decision, 1999). The legal basis for the adoption of the Decision is provided in Chapter 6, more precisely Article 325 (former Article 280) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, 1992). What is particularly important is that the Decision also confirms the independence of OLAF's investigative functions. The Decision also requires the establishment of a "supervisory board" that would oversee that investigative function, and which would be appointed by the Director of OLAF after the appointment of the commission, and after prior consultation with the European Parliament and the Council. This Decision supplements the Regulation which contains rules relating to OLAF investigations (Regulation No. 1073 and Regulation No. 1074, 1999). The rules of the Regulation concern the conduct of OLAF's external and internal investigations.²⁶ The Regulation includes a specific way of opening investigations and their procedure, with emphasis on the need for trust. One of the central issues for conducting investigations is the provision calling on OLAF to forward information that is relevant to the authorities of the Member States, as well as the provisions requiring that OLAF draw up a report after completing the investigation.²⁷ These provisions raise a number of issues relating to OLAF's activities and the domestic criminal procedural systems of the Member States and in particular relate to the information obtained by OLAF, the rights of the defence and the use of OLAF reports as evidence in domestic criminal proceedings. The use of evidence "produced" in the European Union in domestic criminal proceedings is far from clear and completely understandable, which has raised questions regarding the sovereignty in criminal matters of the Member States. De facto, within the Union, different criminal systems operate in all 30 Member States, moreover in the United Kingdom there are three different and separate systems, which makes it even more complicated to use OLAF's criminal reports before the judicial institutions of the Member States, candidate countries and third countries.²⁸

2. OLAF ORGANIZATION

The general organizational structure of OLAF is laid down in the Commission Decision establishing OLAF, which clearly defines the powers and responsibilities of the Director of OLAF and the members of the Supervisory Committee. OLAF is based in Brussels and currently has a staff of 435 employees. The Director is left with exclusive authority to establish the OLAF office, with a clear indication that the Director, who manages OLAF investigations, is not required to seek or receive instructions from any authorities or institutions, thus emphasizing the institutional, operational and financial independence of OLAF's management and investigators. One of OLAF's obligations is to report regularly on the findings of the investigations conducted by OLAF and to submit those reports to the European Parliament, the Council, the Commission and the Court of Auditors. With the adoption of Regulation No. 883/2013 of 01.10.2013, the new legal

²⁶ With particular reference to the existing rules of the legislation concerning the Commission's competences.

²⁷ This including judicial authorities as well.

²⁸ United Kingdom is no longer a member state of the European Union.

requirement for the functioning of OLAF was regulated, which regulates the relations and competencies of the Director and the Supervisory Board (Regulation No. 883, 2013). Thus, the director is given the obligation, when deciding whether to open an investigation or not, to manage the priorities that are set out in the annual work plan, and for which the Supervisory Board gives prior approval. OLAF is financed from the budget of the European Commission.²⁹ The budget of the European Union does not depend on the principle of voluntariness by the Member States, since, as part of the Union, an intergovernmental supranational economic, political and monetary community is financed from its own sources of revenue of the Union. The regulation provides that the authorities in the European Commission exercise judicial control over OLAF's activities in the area of internal investigations, for which there are no provisions relating to external investigations. The regulation does not include specific provisions on data protection, but it is assumed that OLAF applies the Commission's data protection rules. Monitoring of OLAF's investigative functioning is carried out by the Supervisory Committee, which was established by the Regulation of the Parliament and the Council of 25.05.1999.³⁰ The Board shall consist of five independent individuals who are not formally affiliated with OLAF and who are appointed by common accord by the European Parliament, the Council and the Commission for a period of three years, renewable only once. The Board shall be composed of judges, prosecutors, former members of the European Parliament, academics or eminent civil servants. During the performance of their duties, the members of the Board shall not seek or receive instructions from any authority, institution, body, office or agency. The main task of the Board is to express opinions and views from the Director on OLAF's activities, while not interfering in the process of conducting the investigation itself. The Director of OLAF shall regularly inform the Board, and at least once a year, submit a program of activities and a report on the work, ongoing investigations, and the results and work undertaken. It is also authorized to report to the European Parliament, the Council, the Commission and the Court of Auditors on the results of the institution's investigations. OLAF is independent in its work, and it exercises its independence by making a request to the Court of Justice of the European Union. Similarly, institutions and individuals covered by an OLAF investigation may bring an action before the Court of Justice against the conduct of OLAF investigators. Following the latest changes in 2024, the organizational structure of OLAF consists of: four directorates (with internal designations A, B, C and D), Unit 01 for Audit, Unit 02 for Human Resources and Budget, Data Protection Officer, Internal Auditor, advisors, assistants and spokesman.

3. TASKS AND WAY OF WORKING OF OLAF

OLAF achieves its mission by conducting, in full independence, internal and external investigations. It coordinates the activities of its anti-fraud partners in the Member States in the fight against fraud. OLAF supplies EU Member States with the necessary support and technical know-how to help them in their anti-fraud activities. It contributes to the design of the anti-fraud strategy of the European Union, and takes the necessary initiatives to strengthen the relevant legislation. OLAF conducts administrative investigations. It has no judicial powers to oblige national law enforcement authorities to act on its follow-up recommendations.³¹

²⁹ For 2024 its budget is 157.4 million euros.

³⁰ Regulation (EC) No 1073/1999 and Regulation (Euratom) No 1074/1999.

³¹ This provision raises many questions related to the future of OLAF.

As previously stated, OLAF uses all the powers of the Commission, as defined in the provisions of the Treaty on European Union, to conduct external administrative investigations in order to strengthen the fight against fraud, corruption and any other illegal activities affecting the economic interests of the Union. OLAF is responsible for carrying out internal administrative investigations in order to combat fraud, corruption and any other illegal activities affecting the economic interests of the Union. The investigations are related to the performance of professional activities which may constitute a breach of the obligations of an official of the European Union and which are likely to lead to disciplinary and, in justified cases, criminal proceedings, but analogous to the breach of obligations by members of institutions and bodies, their managers and board members. In addition to conducting these external and internal investigations, OLAF's tasks are:

- to develop the necessary infrastructure for the fight against fraud and corruption,
- to ensure the collection and analysis of information, and
- to provide technical support, in particular in the field of other institutions, as well as the competent state authorities.

The Commission of the European Union or any other institution or body of the Union may entrust OLAF with investigations in other areas when they consider that such an investigation is necessary. OLAF is also obliged to provide support to the Commission in cooperation with the Member States in the field of combating fraud. In addition, within the framework of the Decision, OLAF is responsible for preparing legal legislation in its field, and for submitting its proposals to the Commission for a final decision.

4. CANDIDATE COUNTRIES AND ANTI-FRAUD COORDINATION SERVICE (AFCOS)

The candidate countries for accession to the EU and their institutions are about to open chapters 32 (budget control, counterfeiting of euros) and chapters 23 and 24 (rule of law) within the framework of the accession negotiations with the European Union, when the importance of cooperation between OLAF and the establishment of the AFCOS system would come to the fore. It is necessary to ensure that the Constitution of the candidate countries is respected for this occasion, i.e. to reach a consensus among all beneficiaries of IPA funds, i.e. future beneficiaries of the structural funds of the European Union, and to implement the necessary norms and institutional preparations for the establishment of the Anti-Fraud Coordination Service (AFCOS) offices. Within the framework of the European Commission requirements, a so-called AFCOS system (Anti-Fraud Coordination Service) should be established in each candidate country.

The competence of AFCOS is to prevent irregularities and fraud that may occur with the use of European Union funds. The aim of the AFCOS offices is direct cooperation with OLAF and other offices. AFCOS networks are made up of institutions and bodies that manage and use EU aid funds (Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Interior, Tax Administration, Customs, Judiciary, State Auditors, etc.). This system operates in all candidate countries and in the Member States of the European Union since 2001, and consists of AFCOS offices and AFCOS networks. Within each member of the AFCOS networks, an Irregularity Officer is appointed, who receives reports and irregularities on the report of the national officer responsible for the efficient functioning of the pre-accession funds, who reports them to OLAF. In most countries, AFCOS offices are institutionally located within the Ministry of Finance, as an independent department for preventing irregularities and fraud. Currently, OLAF in Macedonia supervises the work of the Delegation of the European Union in Skopje, whose competence includes control over

financial resources and other types of pre-accession assistance from the European Union. It is undeniable that in the near future, the readiness for productive cooperation of state and entity institutions within Macedonia and its entities with OLAF investigators, and knowledge of their procedures, will affect the pace of approximation and accession to the United Europe.

5. CRITICISM OF THE OLAF'S LEGAL BASIS

The legal basis of OLAF has been a subject for criticism. The jurisdictional identity of legitimacy and constitutionality is fluid. OLAF is entangled in an ad hoc, disjointed, conflicting and uncodified mess of largely self-imposed operational conventions that are supposed to be applied within the tight constrictions of legitimacy and constitutionality in criminal investigations. This raises concerns regarding the transparency of OLAF's actions and basic rights of the subjects under investigation (Karpen and Xanthaki, 2017). Which law and which Constitution would the unavoidably confused OLAF staff which work under Belgian and EU law, that of the jurisdiction with competence over the investigation, or that with competence over the actual, indeed usually cross-border, action under investigation. There is question of what is the nature of OLAF and the task of its staff: are they investigators, prosecutors or something in between (Inghelram, 2011). On the other hand, most Hungarian authorities have also refused to sign cooperation agreements with OLAF and rarely follow recommendations despite there being high levels of corruption within the country. In the case of Hungary specifically, it has been suggested that the refusal to cooperate is because the corruption is in the interests of the authorities, and OLAF lacks the influence needed to force cooperation. The fact is that OLAF is currently responsible for administrative investigations, but not for issues of national sovereignty, which is a much more sensitive part of criminal investigations. Therefore, OLAF is obliged to present its findings in criminal cases for which the courts of the Member States have jurisdiction.

OLAF has also been criticized by the European Parliament member, who has indicated that less than a third of OLAF's staff 32% is devoted to the EU's agricultural and structural funds, even though they represent more than 80% of the EU budget.³² Furthermore, the parliament member Gräßle pointed out about OLAF's selectivity and partiality by that the resources are disproportionately allocated to counterfeiting investigations to the luxury industry with a clear interest to help them finding counterfeit goods while the mandate is clearly to protect the financial interests of the EU and to protect the EU budget. Furthermore, EUROPOL and EUROJUST are two organizations OLAF struggles to work with, because OLAF feels like they trespass on its jurisdiction and have no place in fraud investigations while comparatively OLAF is not a European FBI.

³² Ingeborg Gräßle a former member of the budgetary control committee of the European Parliament.

CONCLUSION

Generally speaking OLAF is a largely successful organization which has concluded investigations include cases relating to EU staff, direct expenditure, external aid, customs and cigarette smuggling. However, it is not without faults and challenges. Most notably is how reliant it is on the cooperation of European Member States. OLAF is not a law enforcement agency; its recommendations hold substantial effect in the EU structures and EU candidate countries. It does not have any powers to prosecute or discipline as a sanctioning body, on the other hand only to make recommendations. Consequently, it is up to the relevant judicial bodies and EU institutions to follow the recommendations and act or not. Responses to OLAF's recommendations vary between states, EU institutions and smaller judiciary bodies. There is no legal code to protect the European Budget where each Member State has their own legal systems, with their own law enforcement and evidence collecting methods and this can reduce the efficiency of OLAF. Its efficiency is also hindered by reliance on state/agency cooperation, cultural, legal and language barriers and complications arising from cross-border investigations. The general assessment within the European Union is to change the organizational structure and competencies of OLAF from 2022 and 2026, in order to enable a more efficient and better flow of information between national and supranational bodies of the Union. In recent years, there have been more and more proponents of the idea of establishing institutions of the European public judiciary. So far, only the European Parliament has reached agreement on this issue, justifying its character, and by the end of 2025, there are predictions that the European Council will do the same. For the reason, there have been several attempts to link the competences of OLAF and the European EUROJUST under the control of the European Public Court. The Lisbon Treaty calls for the establishment of a European Public Court which would be formed by the representatives of the European EUROJUST. On the other hand, the aim of OLAF is that for their investigators and future European judges in the perspective there are no limits and normative limits to their work. In conclusion, OLAF is generally seen as successful initiative in the fight against corruption, however further changes in the Union and Member States legislation is needed for this institution to become a full-fledged part of the European Union.

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DEBTOR-CREDITOR (IN)EQUALITY IN THE MACEDONIAN LEGAL SYSTEM

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Abstract

The principle of equality between parties in civil law relations—one of the pillars of democracy and the rule of law—is increasingly being questioned by a systemic imbalance between creditors and debtors. Although Macedonian civil law formally guarantees equal protection, analysis of legislation, case law, and administrative practice reveals a persistent tendency to favour debtors.

The paper examines the link between a state's economic development and its legal orientation: economically stronger systems protect creditors more consistently, recognizing their role in market stability. In contrast, Macedonian law shows growing social sensitivity toward debtors, especially in enforcement and bankruptcy procedures, which undermines legal certainty and the *pacta sunt servanda* principle.

The goal is to identify key sources of inequality and propose reforms for restoring fairness and predictability in debtor–creditor relations.

Keywords: civil law, equality of parties, creditor, debtor, legal certainty, legal reform, enforcement, economic stability

1. INTRODUCTION

At first glance, the debtor–creditor inequality does not appear systemic. However, deeper analysis reveals that insufficient legal certainty allows inequality to become a rule rather than an exception - even enabling corruption to take root within civil-legal relations.

This inequality ranges from mild normative imbalances to substantial discrepancies in judicial protection and the state's role as a private-law actor.

The paper applies a combination of legal, comparative, and historical analyses to examine *de lege lata* and *de lege ferenda* aspects of Macedonian law. It builds from theory toward practice and concludes with economic and legal recommendations.

2. CHAPTER 1: Theoretical and Historical Aspects

2.1. Principle of Equality of Parties

Civil law, traditionally known as property law, regulates property relations and rests on four basic principles: equality of parties, autonomy of will, transferability of rights, and property sanctioning. Even in non-material disputes, compensation is property-based, confirming its patrimonial nature.

These principles are operationalized through concrete norms such as those on changed circumstances or usurious contracts, which make the abstract principle of equality

applicable in practice. However, norms cannot function without the general principles that give them meaning and coherence.

Equality of parties implies coordination, rather than subordination: both parties have equal legal capacity and protection before institutions. It also requires equivalence of exchanged values - the foundation of balanced contractual relations and legal certainty.

2.2. Comparative View

Civil law has developed within two dominant legal traditions: the continental (Romano-Germanic) and the Anglo-Saxon (common law). These traditions reflect two philosophies of justice - law as an abstract, codified system versus law as a living, evolving practice.

The continental model, rooted in Roman law and 19th-century codifications (*Code civil*, *BGB*), is built on abstraction, systematization, and normative rationality. Equality of parties is guaranteed *ex ante* - by the very structure of the law. The legislator is the creator of justice; the court, its interpreter.

The Anglo-Saxon model, by contrast, creates equality *ex post* through judicial precedent (*stare decisis*), where justice is a process, not a fixed norm. Law evolves through disputes, and equality is not presumed but demonstrated. This model transfers moral responsibility from the legislator to the judge, favouring flexibility over predictability.

In contractual relations, the continental system safeguards equality through universal norms, while common law tempers autonomy with *equity*—a moral correction within the legal order. Thus, the former guarantees certainty; the latter ensures fairness.

Across Europe, debtor–creditor relations mirror this philosophical divide between freedom and legal certainty. German law, shaped by the principle of *Treu und Glauben* (good faith), achieves balance through conceptual rigor; French and Scandinavian systems allow judicial correction in the name of fairness and social responsibility.

Macedonian law, as part of the continental tradition, retains the German-Austrian balance: a structured legal form with space for equitable adjustment, treating debtor and creditor as legally equal but morally accountable parties within a unified legal system.

2.3. Historical Development in Macedonian Law

Development of the Principle of Equality in Macedonian Civil Legislation

Macedonian civil law, rooted in Roman *ius privatum* and the continental-German tradition, evolved through the *pandect* system that structures civil law into real, obligatory, and inheritance law. Unless a *lex specialis* applies, general civil principles govern all legal relations.

The principle of equality of parties developed through layered legal heritage. Yugoslav law, strongly influenced by the Austrian Civil Code of 1811 (*ABGB*), embedded the German *pandect* idea that all subjects of law are equal before the law, regardless of status or capacity. This tradition represented a rational continuation of Roman *aequitas*—fairness as the moral foundation of civil order.

The French model contributed the opposite tone: flexibility and judicial discretion through open-textured norms. Yugoslav, and later Macedonian codifications synthesized these influences, framing equality not merely as a formal guarantee but as an expression of social justice and contractual freedom.

Today, Macedonian civil law preserves this European lineage—born in Rome, codified in Vienna, and continued in Skopje—as a bridge between legal certainty and fairness in modern civil relations.

3. CHAPTER 2: Contemporary Legal Context in North Macedonia

3.1. Statute of Limitations and Amendments to the Law on Obligations (ZOO) and the Law on Enforcement (ZI)

The 2024 amendments to the Law on Obligations (ZOO) and the Law on Enforcement (ZI) sparked major debate on whether they promote fairness or undermine legal certainty - the foundation of obligatory law.

Article 266-a of the ZOO limits penalty interest to the principal debt, ending accrual once equality is reached. While this protects weaker debtors and prevents excessive interest growth, it abandons the traditional compensatory function of interest and shifts the burden to creditors.

The absolute statute of limitations for judicially determined claims is reduced from ten to five years, effectively transforming a final judgment into a temporary guarantee. Without faster enforcement mechanisms, this measure risks de facto debt amnesty and undermines confidence in the legal system.

The ten-year cap on enforcement procedures has similar consequences: rather than improving efficiency, it rewards intentional delays by debtors. Although the Constitutional Court upheld the amendments as legitimate social policy, they erode legal certainty—the key principle of civil obligations.

Such reforms, though socially motivated, risk producing the opposite effect — discouraging lending, weakening contractual discipline, and destabilizing the economy. Instead of systemic balance, they reflect a tendency toward legal populism that sacrifices predictability for short-term social relief.

3.2. Law on Enforcement and the "Limit" for Public Institutions

The state in legal transactions acts under two capacities: as a sovereign authority (*ius imperii*) and as a private actor (*ius privatum*). In the latter, it must enjoy no privileges—its legal position should be equal to that of any private subject.

A key issue in Macedonian enforcement law is the “monetary limit” for public institutions. Although designed to secure continuity of public functions, in practice it often creates inequality among creditors. The court may grant an institution a monthly spending limit that is exempt from enforcement, preventing account blockade below that threshold. While intended to safeguard essential services, the measure frequently shields institutions from responsibility.

Unlike private companies, public institutions can, in practice, indefinitely avoid enforcement by managing cash flows under the limit, which undermines equality among creditors. Instead of proportional payment, selective settlements favour politically stronger entities. This contradicts the principle of legal equality and transforms protection of public interest into systemic legal privilege.

The mechanism thus exposes a deep conflict between social function and the rule of law. The state must be the first disciplined debtor, not the most protected one. Reform is needed toward transparency, fixed criteria, and periodic review of the limit’s scope to prevent abuse and restore equality in enforcement relations.

3.3. Circumventing Creditors

Modern contractual dynamics often lead to changes not only in content but also in parties. When the creditor's position changes, we speak of *cession*; when mutual debts offset each other, it is *set-off*. Both are legitimate instruments, yet they can be misused to bypass enforcement.

Public institutions in North Macedonia have frequently exploited these mechanisms—particularly cession and compensation—to avoid execution of debts. To address this, from January 1, 2024, companies with blocked accounts, including public institutions, are legally prohibited from performing payments through cession, set-off, or similar arrangements.

This measure, first introduced in the 2007 Law on Payment Transactions and reaffirmed by the 2022 Law on Payment Services and Payment Systems, now permanently restricts such practices. The reform aims to close legal loopholes that allowed state entities to circumvent creditors and delay enforcement indefinitely.

3.4. Judicial Practice and Length of Proceedings

The excessive length of court proceedings and delayed enforcement of judgments remain among the gravest structural flaws of the Macedonian legal system. Although legal certainty and the right to trial within a reasonable time are constitutionally guaranteed, in practice creditors often cannot realize final judgments.

Typical cases before the Appellate Courts in Skopje and Gostivar show years-long enforcement delays caused by procedural obstacles, blocked public accounts, and repeated requests for new monetary limits. Even after final rulings, state institutions such as ministries or municipalities frequently fail to comply voluntarily, forcing creditors into renewed litigation.

These practices undermine both justice and efficiency. Delays increase costs, erode public trust, and diminish the authority of the judiciary, turning final judgments into legal fictions. When enforcement becomes uncertain, legal certainty loses its content.

The issue is not merely administrative but structural: a state that cannot ensure timely execution of its own judgments undermines the very idea of the rule of law. Reform requires strict time standards, accountability in enforcement, and digital tools for monitoring judicial efficiency.

4. ECONOMIC AND COMPARATIVE ASPECTS

4.1. Economic Indicators

Economic Concentration and Legal Balance of Market Equality in the Republic of North Macedonia

The Macedonian economy is characterized by high capital concentration and asymmetric productivity: a small number of corporations generate most revenues, while small and medium enterprises, despite constituting over 90% of active entities, suffer from low liquidity and limited bargaining power.

This imbalance extends into the legal sphere, where state institutions frequently act as dominant debtors with structural advantage. Small creditors lack the resources to sustain long or costly procedures and are vulnerable to selective payments and procedural delays. According to the Ministry of Justice, around 40% of enforcement procedures in 2024 ended unsuccessfully.

In such an environment, the equality of parties becomes not merely a principle but a practical necessity rather than a formal principle. A stable legal system—efficient,

predictable, and impartial - is not only a condition for justice but also a prerequisite for economic growth and trust in the rule of law.

4.2. Comparative Perspective

Comparative analysis shows considerable variation in how European systems balance creditor–debtor relations through limitation periods and interest regulation.

German law provides a ten-year general limitation and up to thirty years for property claims (*BGB*, Art. 197), combining legal certainty with flexibility under the principle of *Treu und Glauben* (good faith). French law, since the 2008 *Code civil* reform, applies a shorter five-year term but compensates through strong creditor safeguards and exceptions for serious claims.

The general European trend is clear: shorter limitation periods are balanced by efficient enforcement systems. North Macedonia, however, has shortened its period without improving procedural efficiency - weakening creditor protection while failing to reinforce legal certainty.

CONCLUSION

The contemporary Macedonian legal and economic reality reveals that the inequality between creditors and debtors is not coincidental but arises from structural and systemic causes - inherited institutional weaknesses, inefficient enforcement procedures, and the high concentration of economic power in the hands of a few corporate entities.

On one side stands the inefficiency and slowness of the judiciary; on the other, the shadow economy and the existence of so-called “economic phantoms.” Added to this are the facts that the state, in all its forms, remains the largest market participant, municipalities and public enterprises remain chronically illiquid, and yet they enjoy additional protection through financial limits. When, on top of that, the statute of limitations for judicially established claims is halved (from ten to five years), and an absolute limitation period of ten years for enforcement completion is introduced, the legitimate question arises: is it even worth being a creditor in the Macedonian legal system?

The most recent legislative reforms - limiting penalty interest, shortening limitation periods, and introducing the monetary limit for public institutions — undoubtedly pursue a socially motivated goal. Yet their practical implementation shows that good intentions do not always yield fair balance. These changes have indeed provided relief for debtors and demonstrated social sensitivity in enforcement, but at the same time they have created legal uncertainty for creditors, especially regarding predictability and stability of enforceable titles. If the right to collection continues to be restricted by procedural and formal barriers, there is a real risk of discouraging investment and fostering informal, extralegal arrangements.

Therefore, future legal reforms must be oriented around three pillars of legal certainty:

- **Clear and predictable legislation**, free from populist impulses and aligned with European standards of proportionality and legal science.
- **Efficient and expedited procedures** that ensure timely execution of court decisions without excessive bureaucracy.

• **Transparent and limited mechanisms of financial “limit”** for public institutions, preventing abuse and restoring equality among creditors.²⁰

At the same time, economic structure must be strengthened through the development of small and medium-sized enterprises, which expand the productive base and reduce dependency on concentrated capital groups. Only a healthy market environment and a balanced legal system can achieve genuine material equality among the subjects of obligatory relations.

DE LEGE FERENDA

From a *de lege ferenda* perspective, the liquidation and insolvency processes require far greater structure, predictability, and transparency.

For natural persons, **personal bankruptcy** should be introduced as a legal institute. On one hand, it would enable the financial resocialization of debtors and promote financial literacy among citizens; on the other, it would provide creditors with predictability and stronger legal security.

At the same time, so-called “open-and-close” bankruptcies must be reduced—cases in which creditors are left empty-handed. Currently, according to Article 68(1) of the Law on Bankruptcy, if the temporary administrator determines that the debtor’s assets are insufficient even to cover procedural costs, the judge simultaneously opens and closes the bankruptcy, ordering deletion from the commercial register. In such cases, the proceeding effectively never takes place. These scenarios are numerous, and piercing the corporate veil to hold owners and responsible persons liable remains exceptionally difficult under the Company Law.

Preventive mechanisms would therefore be most effective. One such measure would be **periodic re-evaluation of founding capital**, which must not fall below the threshold necessary for company operation. Founding capital should serve as the final financial safeguard from which creditors can be satisfied.

In closing, beyond defining legal objectives, concrete legal proposals should be considered:

- Establishing **personal bankruptcy** as a legal institute.
- Introducing **annual re-evaluation of founding capital** for commercial companies.
- Strengthening **liability for fraudulent or intentional bankruptcy**.
- Redefining **the role and accountability of enforcement agents**.
- Increasing **transparency of corporate creditworthiness**.
- Establishing **specialized courts**, including commercial courts.
- Ensuring **state solidarity liability** for insolvent public enterprises, municipalities, and other institutions.

Finally, it is worth recalling the classical Roman definition of justice: *“Iustitia est constans et perpetua voluntas ius suum cuique tribuendi – Justice is the constant and perpetual will to render to each his due.”*

This principle, more than two millennia old, remains the essential moral and legal measure of modern legislation — not as an abstract ideal but as a concrete duty of the state to ensure a predictable, fair, and dignified legal order in which every creditor and every debtor equally feels the strength of the law.

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THE PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE CONCEPT OF “CONSTITUENT PEOPLES” IN THE LEGAL-POLITICAL FRAMEWORK OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA – A REVIEW THREE DECADES AFTER DAYTON

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Abstract

In 2025, the thirtieth anniversary of the signing of the Dayton Peace Agreement (DPA) will be marked. The agreement represented a minimal compromise between the three ethnic groups (Bosniaks, Serbs, and Croats) for joint statehood. All the institutions that were established by it were, to a large extent, created by the overly primordial understanding of ethnicity institutionalized in the system through the introduction of the constitutional concept of “constituent peoples”. The science of comparative constitutional law is not overly preoccupied with this concept, for the simple reason that in established Western democracies, as well as other countries around the world, one nation or people has always been dominant by definition. The phrase “constituent peoples” in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) is not used in the sense of people (*populous*) as a collection of all citizens who are in a civil relationship with the country and who constitute its political people. Still, it is used in the sense of a separate ethnic identity. With this, the Constitution of BiH created a presumption of strong discrimination against non-constituent peoples (others, citizens) despite its formal provisions on non-discrimination. The issue of “constituent peoples” in BiH arises as problematic not only in the domain of human rights and fundamental freedoms but also in terms of the organization and structure of government. Hence, the purpose of this paper is to examine the repercussions caused by the introduction of the concept of “constituent peoples” into the entire post-Dayton political system of BiH. The basic thesis is that the idea of “constituent peoples” created an institutional framework for building a ‘negative’ peace through initial segregation and mutual control between the three ethnic groups, which over time failed to encourage their gradual integration and the building of democratic institutions, which were supposed to consolidate peace and pave the way for European integration. Therefore, the calls for the necessary “correction” of this concept, towards creating a civic and liberal counterbalance, to prevent the system from degenerating into a full ethnic democracy, are understandable. Hence, the idea of a more comprehensive constitutional reform, which would be best implemented within the framework of the country’s European integration path. With such a “Brussels Avenue”, BiH would gain the foundation that EU member states have today, which is characterized by internal integration and the development of institutions synonymous with a functional state. In this way, the shortcomings of the DPA would be corrected, and the integration process itself, along with the implementation of a clearly defined reform agenda, would be its positive upgrade.

Keywords: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Dayton Peace Agreement, constituent peoples, consociational democracy, ethnocracy;

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2025, Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) will mark the thirtieth anniversary of the signing of the Dayton Peace Agreement (DPA). The Agreement, which has been in force for three decades (almost an entire generation of this country grew up under it), was reached “at Wright-Patterson Air Base in Dayton, Ohio (...) and later signed in an official ceremony on 14 December 1995 in Paris” (Vomlela, 2017: 28). Thirty years later is the right moment not only to summarize the achievements but also to reflect on the challenges that BiH faces today.

Not even three decades after its signing, the academic community that deals with and studies the legal and political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is without analogy and precedent in the comparative science of contemporary political systems, has left the impression that the Agreement did not create a presumption for a modern, civil state as part of the family of European nations. On the contrary, the unfolding of the Bosnian crisis continued to be a European conundrum in which many minds tested their diplomatic skills, and many armies the correctness of their struggle for reassurance (Dašić & Nedeljković, 2016: 12). Some authors, such as Maršić and Marko (2007: 1), go even a step further by revising Carl von Clausewitz’s famous thought about the post-Dayton political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which created the assumption of “the continuation of the war but by other means”. Scarred by the bloody war in the 1990s, following the breakup of Yugoslavia, the Peace Agreement was intended to mediate and strike a delicate balance between the country’s three main ethnic groups – Bosniaks, Serbs and Croats – by granting them special rights and additional influence (Nurkić & Isanović, 2023: 2). Dayton allowed for “a minimum compromise between the different ethnic groups on common statehood” (Rasidović, 2022: 2). During this period, new models of federalism (Belgium, Russia, Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Iraq) and territorial autonomy (Spain and Italy) were adopted (Keil, 2014: 80).

The International Community, which brokered the Agreement, remained ambiguous about the integrity of Bosnia and Herzegovina. This created assumptions for different political interpretations of the DPA, especially its substantive implementation, which remained a contentious issue. Primarily, this was due to the following dilemma – whether the Agreement is a compromise whose next step should be the division of the country along ethnic lines; or whether it should be the first step towards stopping this scenario and starting a gradual peaceful reintegration of the country (Bianchini, 2016: 135). But, except for the Vance-Owen plan³³ (1993), such ambiguity was offered by all previous plans for overcoming the Bosnian crisis, such as the Cutileiro’s mediation³⁴ (March 1992), the Owen-Stoltenberg plan,³⁵ the Washington Agreement (March 1994),³⁶

³³ „The plan envisioned the establishment of ten provinces based on geographical, economic, and other criteria, with the names of the provinces not referring to ethnic characteristics“ (Efendić, 2018: 66). However, one of the three peoples would dominate them, but this was not recognized as a constitutive category (Nešković, 2017: 196).

³⁴ It envisaged a political federation based on ethnic nations but without compact territories (Nešković, 2017: 190, 193). The Bosniaks rejected it due to their strong opposition to regions based on an ethnic principle (Dašić & Nedeljković, 2016: 17).

³⁵ This plan revived the idea of three separate states under one confederal state, and rewarded Serbian and Croatian aspirations; therefore, it is logical that Bosniaks were not thrilled with it

and the Contact Group plan (1994),³⁷ which instead of stopping the war inspired new cycles of violence (Ćurak, 2015: 45).

2 THE HISTORICAL GENESIS OF THE BOSNIAN-HERZEGOVINIAN STATE AND THE ETHNO-RELIGIOUS DIMENSION OF BIH

According to Malcolm (1995: 13), there is no doubt that Bosnia and Herzegovina “is a country that has its own historical identity – in fact, it is one of the historic countries in Europe, with an almost uninterrupted history as a distinct geopolitical entity from the Middle Ages to the present day. For most of the period from 1180 to 1463 it was an independent kingdom; from 1580 to 1878 it was an *eyalet* (a term denoting the largest territorial unit in the Ottoman Empire); from 1878 to 1918 a ‘crown land’ within Austria-Hungary; and from 1945 to 1992 a federal republic”. However, another group of authors, such as Sarajlić (2010: 2), believes that one thing is BiH as a country that was at the crossroads of numerous conquests and wars of great empires, both European and Asian, and quite another is its statehood (1943) and independence (1992), which were relatively short-lived. Marković is on the same line of thinking. According to him: “The Medieval Bosnian state cannot be taken as a raw-model, as it was not a modern, but rather a feudal state. Later, with the arrival of the Turks and the Austro-Hungarians, Bosnia and Herzegovina became an administrative area, organized, until the late 19th century, as part of a pre-modern state” (Marković, 2015: 108). It is worth highlighting here the opinion of the Croatian political scientist with origin from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Mirjana Kasapović (2005), who claims that for centuries Serbs, Bosniaks/Muslims, and Croats have never jointly, permanently, and *en masse* advocated for a common state, and have only coexisted together thanks to the authoritarianism of the regimes (the Ottoman Empire, the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy, and the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, later the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia).

Regarding the three ethnic identifications that exist in Bosnia and Herzegovina, it is essential to note that their ethnic and national consciousness, in a political sense, is specific compared to other European experiences, as religious division and affiliation will, over time, become a marker of national identification (Mesić, 2006: 291). The 14th and 15th centuries were crucial for the development of religious divisions, as the Ottoman conquest of the Balkans and Medieval Bosnia led to a significant portion of the local population adopting Islam as their religion, thereby creating the recognizable religious triangle in Bosnia and Herzegovina that exists today (Radušić, 2009: 3). “Since the beginning of the 16th century Bosnian-Herzegovinian society had a tendency towards the creation of a multi-religious, and multi-national society” (Katz, 2017: 202). The subsequent demographic development of all three religious groups took place in such a way that no later nation had, nor would have, an absolute majority, which contributed to the complication of interethnic relations (Radušić, 2009: 3).

(Dašić & Nedeljković, 2016: 22-23). A novelty in this plan was the concept of territorial integrity and connectivity among the constituent units (Nešković, 2017: 199).

³⁶ This agreement established the Muslim-Croat Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FBiH), a federal state comprising 10 cantons as its federal units. Three of these cantons have a Croat majority, five have a Bosniak majority, and two have a mixed ethnic composition of Croat and Bosniak.

³⁷ The Serbs accepted the constitutional component of this plan but rejected the territory it assigned for Republika Srpska. It envisaged a union (alliance) with mixed confederal and federal elements (Nešković, 2017: 206-207).

By emphasizing religious affiliation, it will become evident over time that it will be decisive in determining the direction of national identity development, as religious communities lived intermingled and were therefore oriented towards different cultural, civilizational, and spiritual sources (Hadžibegović & Kamberović, 1997: 99). “The key period for the consolidation of national identities began in the mid-19th century (or more precisely, from the early 1860s) and ended with the conclusion of the Eastern Crisis in 1878” (Radušić, 2009: 6). It is believed in science that at the time of the establishment of Austro-Hungarian rule in Bosnia and Herzegovina, national consciousness among its religious groups/peoples was not at a high level, but according to Mesić (2006: 291), the process of forming Serbian national consciousness among the Orthodox population in Bosnia and Herzegovina took precedence over others and was considered complete. The development of Croatian national consciousness among Bosnian and Herzegovinian Catholics lagged due to the oscillation between multi-religious Bosniakism – *bošnjaštvo* (partly supported by the Franciscans) and broader Yugoslavism, as well as previously existing Illyrism (Radušić, 2009: 5). However, in terms of the process of “ethnonomination” (Kržišnik-Bukić, 2003: 297-302) in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the greatest controversy at the turn of the 19th to the 20th century was the collective identification among Bosnian Muslims. European-educated Muslims, under the influence of Serbian or Croatian propaganda, were inclined to accept the Serbian or Croatian national idea (in the political sense) (Mesić, 2006: 291). Regardless of such propaganda pressure, Muslim Bosniaks will increasingly accept their a-nationality, a fact partly due to a more categorical refusal to embrace the Serbian or Croatian national idea, which implicitly indicates the crystallization of a separate Muslim-Bosniak national identity (Juzbašić, 1999: 66). Additionally, “we can also point to the fact that during the 19th century, Bosniak identity was created as a kind of antipode and reaction to the dominant Ottoman one, which was especially evident in the numerous efforts to ensure the status of Bosnia’s autonomy within this Empire” (Imamović, 1997: 333). As for the Austro-Hungarian period of Bosnia’s historical development, the original plan of the Empire and its governor for this ‘crown land’, Benjamin von Kállay, was “creating a regional, supra-confessional Bosniak identity based on the common language failed, and eventually gave way to the creation of the Bosniak nation in a narrower sense (based on religion, focusing on the Muslim Slavs of the region)” (Demeter & Bottlik, 2021: 41). The idea for supra-confessional Bosniak identity was rejected with the greatest indignation by the conservative Muslim beys, as well as the citizenry (Mesić, 2006: 291).

This historical development of Bosnia and Herzegovina will result in the country being well-placed in the category of “plural societies”, i.e. divided societies characterized by cultural diversity, and whose cultural parts aspire to organize themselves into cohesive political entities (Rezza & Mirković, 2019/2020: 1). The ultimate goal that will be set in the complex Dayton system is to incorporate such ethnic and cultural diversity into every aspect of the political structure (O. Bell, 2018: 20), by forcing the concept of “constituent peoples”. Bosnian-Herzegovinian society, as summarized in this chapter, was nationally divided even before 1990, and after the war, all the markers of a segmented society, which are well described in the works of Arend Lijphart (1992, 1998, 2003, 2004), only intensified. Therefore, with the DPA, the political and territorial organization of the state had to be aligned with the nature of society, not because someone wanted it to be, but simply because it could not function otherwise (Marković, 2015: 110).

3 THE CONSTITUTIVENESS OF THE CONSTITUENT PEOPLES IN DAYTON BIH

During the collapse of the former communist totalitarian regimes, a byproduct that emerged in several countries was the outbreak of ethnic nationalism. It was considered the main obstacle to a true democratization of countries in transition. International state-builders institutionalized it in the post-conflict remodelling of Bosnia and Herzegovina. This is most explicitly seen in the Preamble to the Constitution of BiH, but it was also reinforced in several other places in the normative part, which created a presumption favouring the three predominant ethnic groups to the detriment of the individual, i.e., the citizen. The Preamble to the Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina defines Bosniaks, Serbs, and Croats as “constituent peoples,” while “others” and “citizens” are mentioned *en passant*. Hence, it is more than evident that individual rights are mistakenly (!?) granted to the three ethnic groups, and not to the citizens. Therefore, the concept of “constituent peoples” is considered to violate the ECHR, which protects the individual, not social, religious, or ethnic groups as such. The Dayton Constitution prioritizes collective rights over individual rights.³⁸ Additionally, it creates an assumption of power-sharing between the three constituent peoples, supporting and maintaining strong discrimination against non-constituent peoples (the others, the citizens) (Seizović, 2007: 2). However, formally, the constitutional framework stipulates that “the constituent peoples exercise sovereignty together with the citizens and other peoples” (Sahadžić, 2011: 30). Therefore, the contemporary political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina can be described as “a classical example of the application of a radical concept of multicultural politics (which, in truth, is gradually evolving) and a predominantly collectivist representation of constituent peoples and national minorities with a varying degree of provided rights” (Banović, 2016: 2).

The idea of constitutiveness is particularly complex and intricate when multiple constitutive, and thus sovereign, political communities exist and operate within a single legal and political order, creating a common internal framework in which general and special, common, and individual interests are addressed, positioned, and balanced. Additionally, the principle of constitutiveness reaffirms the idea of equality, which is extremely important in multinational states such as Bosnia and Herzegovina (Jašarević, 2023: 14).

For Kasim Trnka (2006: 175), the reason for this approach to materializing constitutiveness in the Bosnian-Herzegovinian Constitution is that no nation has a majority of more than half, and additionally, the emphasis is placed on its traditional multi-national composition. In this way, a combination of civic and national principles was achieved. According to the same author (Trnka, 2000: 50), in the etymological sense, the word “constitutive” originates from the Latin language, which as a verb (*constituo*) means to set up, to regulate, to establish, and as a noun (*constitutio*) means: internal structure, regulation, constitution, law.

However, it should be emphasized that the science of comparative constitutional law is not overly preoccupied with the concept of “constituent peoples”, for the simple reason that in established Western democracies, as well as other countries around the world, one nation or people has always been dominant by definition. For this reason, there

³⁸ For a certain group of authors, this is too reminiscent of the legacy of the millet system of the Ottoman Empire, „which recognised rights of communities, unlike the notion of citizenship that is based on individual rights“ (Koksal 2008: 1503).

are a small number of scientific and professional papers that touch on this issue (Sahadžić, 2011: 33).

In the given Bosnian-Herzegovinian context, but not only, “for a people to be constitutive, it must have the quality of an indigenous people.... From the fact of constitutiveness, the concept of equality of peoples is derived, that is, constituent peoples are equal in all rights and obligations” (Kuzmanović, 1997: 53). Therefore, it is natural and historical for people to have an aspiration to create their own state based on their autochthonous nature. Autochthonousness is a historical attribute and marker of every people, which exists in a certain natural space for a relatively long historical period, after which the respective area becomes recognizable by that people (Nešković, 2017: 43). The same author, referring to the example of Bosnia and Herzegovina, notes that it is a country on whose territory several indigenous peoples reside who strive to express themselves within the framework of the state in question. Croats, Serbs, and Bosniaks are indigenous ethnic nations in Bosnia and Herzegovina that emerged from ethnic-religious communities. Based on such autochthonousness and sovereignty, they are, by definition, constitutive and state-forming subjects of BiH. For them, Bosnia and Herzegovina is their home state, because in it the Serbian and Croatian nations are autochthonous and sovereign. In the opposite case, if Serbia and Croatia were declared the home states of Bosnian Serbs and Croats, then these two nations in Bosnia and Herzegovina would be reduced to national minorities and would lose their statehood. The autochthonous and sovereign status in BiH, with a parallel status of motherhood in another state, is unsustainable, because one excludes the other (Ibid., 421). Additionally, the autochthonous nature of a people may remain a historical fact without having any political or state consequences. Still, it may be a generator of its sovereignty and statehood with lasting political and state consequences (Ibid., 45).

Therefore, introducing the concept of “constituent peoples” into the Dayton constitutional and legal framework proved to be a *conditio sine qua non* because there are three autochthonous ethnic communities in the territory of BiH, which have the inalienable right to form and regulate its statehood, through the affirmation of the principle of equality. For this purpose, they need to be sovereign because their statehood stems from their sovereignty and autochthonism. “Constitutiveness as a political-legal concept and as a continuous process in the functioning of the political system is a derived category of popular sovereignty and only in this way does it have a democratic character” (Nešković, 2006: 165). The phrase “constituent peoples” as “a constitutional category, was first incorporated into the constitutional system of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina by the Washington Agreement in 1994. With the Dayton Peace Agreement, signed a year later, the concept of constitutiveness acquired the character of a constitutionally protected value on the territory of the entire Bosnia and Herzegovina” (Begić, 2011: 410). On the other hand, this phrase “is not used in the sense of people (*populous*) as the sum of all citizens who are in a civil relationship with Bosnia and Herzegovina and who constitute its political people, but is used in the sense of a separate ethnic identity” (Efendić, 2018: 80). Additionally, “The Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina does not define the term *constituent people*, rather, its definition is derived from the listing of groups that belong to constituent peoples, as well as the special collective rights these groups have” (Banović, 2016: 7). However, it should be emphasized that until the adoption of the Decision (no. U 5/98 – III) of the Constitutional Court of BiH in 2000, Serbs were the only constituent people in the Republika Srpska, and Bosniaks and Croats in the FBiH. With the Decision since then “the principle of collective equality of constituent peoples implies equal

collective rights, for all three groups, that are not territorially restricted, but relevant in both entities in equal ways regardless of whether the people in question represent a *de facto* minority or majority within an entity” (Ibid., 7-8).

It is essential to note that the term “constituent peoples” is not unfamiliar to the political science and practice of the former Yugoslavia. Still, in the constitutional development of the Yugoslav Federation, as well as Bosnia and Herzegovina as its constituent republic, it was not used as a constitutional category³⁹ (Trnka, 2006: 177). Due to this simple fact, the term “constituent peoples” can be considered a relatively new concept in constitutional and political theory and practice. In support of this thesis is the fact that it will be present in “Opinion 2 of the Arbitration Commission of the European Community, and the same term was used in the peace plans for Bosnia and Herzegovina (Cutileiro plan,⁴⁰ Vance-Owen plan,⁴¹ Owen-Stoltenberg plan,⁴² Contact Group plan)” (Sahadžić, 2011: 34).

The doyen of Bosnian-Herzegovinian constitutional law, academic Kasim Trnka, has offered the most comprehensive and fundamental definition of the idea of “constituent

³⁹ For example, at the first session of the Anti-fascist Council for the National Liberation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (ZAVNOBiH) in Mrkonjić Grad on 25 and 26 November 1943, decisions were made to restore the statehood of Bosnia and Herzegovina. A Resolution was adopted that reflects the common life of citizens regardless of differences in ethnic, religious, and any other respects. It states: „Today, the peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina, through their sole political representation, the Anti-fascist Council for the National Liberation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, want their country, which is neither Serbian, nor Croatian, nor Muslim, but Serbian, Muslim, and Croatian, to be a free and fraternal Bosnia and Herzegovina in which equity will be ensured for all Serbs, Muslims, and Croats. The peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina will participate equally with our other peoples in the construction of a People’s Democratic Federal Yugoslavia“ (quoted in Trnka, 2000: 17). At the second session of the ZAVNOH BiH, held in Sanski Most from June 30 to July 2, 1944, special emphasis was placed on „the equality of Serbs, Croats, and Muslims of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is their common and indivisible homeland“ (quoted in Efendić, 2018: 63). From these two passages, it can be seen that although in these constituent documents that constituted BiH in 1943 as a federal state of Yugoslavia, the term “constituent peoples” is not used anywhere, however, as Kamberović notes (2013: 14-15), here „in fact all the important elements of its content and meaning are given“. In July 1990, the socialist leadership of Bosnia and Herzegovina passed an amendment to the Constitution that defined Bosnia and Herzegovina as „a democratic sovereign state of equal citizens, the peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina – Muslims, Serbs and Croats, and members of other peoples and nationalities living in that country“. Amendment LX to the Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Bosnia and Herzegovina was adopted at a session of the Assembly on 31 July 1990. See: Official Gazette of the SR BiH (Sarajevo), 32 (1991). This amendment disrupts the democratic balance of the national and civic by separating sovereignty from the people and tying this concept to the state. According to Nešković (2017: 157), such a balance was guaranteed by the 1974 Constitution of the SR BiH, which states that the SR BiH is a „socialist democratic state... of the working people and citizens, the peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina – Muslims, Serbs and Croats“ (Article 1), but also in Article 3 it is emphasized that in the SR BiH „the equality of peoples and nationalities is guaranteed“.

⁴⁰ Here „the concept of constitutiveness is related to the constituent territorial units“ (Efendić, 2018: 65).

⁴¹ „The plan accepts the category of ‘three constituent peoples’ and the category of members of the ‘other’ peoples“ (Efendić, 2018: 66).

⁴² „This plan uses the term ‘constituent republic’ which was supposed to mean territorialization for each constituent people, i.e. the creation of ethnically pure territories“ (Efendić, 2018: 66).

peoples” in the context of BiH constitutionalism: “The constitutiveness of peoples is a collective right narrower than sovereignty, but broader than the individual right to national identity. Constitutiveness does not entail the right to self-determination or the right to secession. No people exercises its constitutiveness independently of other peoples who have the same rights. Constitutiveness implies the mutual right of all three peoples to determine the constitutional order (together with citizens and others) and to use all mechanisms for the realization and protection of national equality” (Trnka, 2006: 178).

However, in Bosnian-Herzegovinian scientific thought, some authors take more controversial positions regarding the constitutiveness of the three peoples. So, Omer Ibrahimagić (1995) argues that “historically, there is no scientific basis for Bosniaks, Serbs and Croats to declare themselves constitutive nations. From a historical point of view, those three nations did not constitute Bosnia and Herzegovina as a country, but Bosnia as a thousand-year-old political space, on which an internationally recognized state of the same name existed for several centuries, and constituted the three existing nations today (...). The theory of constitutive nations in Bosnia and Herzegovina is directly related to the destruction of Bosnia and Herzegovina as a sovereign state with a unique territory”. Efendić (2018: 71) criticizes Ibrahimagić’s manipulativeness, noting that he replaces the original term “constituent peoples” in the Dayton Constitution with “constitutive nations”. Constituent peoples cannot be equated with the term ‘nation’, because it is synonymous with the state.

Hence, it can be concluded that the concept of constitutiveness in BiH seriously differs from the theoretical meaning of this term, due to the non-standardized use of the terms people and nation. From the entire discussion presented in this chapter, it can be concluded that the principle of the constitutiveness of peoples is not compatible with international democratic standards (Jašarević, 2023: 68, 71), which is why it has caused certain repercussions in the development of Bosnia and Herzegovina in the past three decades.

4 THE NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE IMPLICATIONS OF THE CONCEPT OF CONSTITUENT PEOPLES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF POST-DAYTON BIH

From the perspective of the constitutional and legal system of BiH, as well as the current situation in the country, the issue of the “constituent peoples” emerges as problematic in two domains: human rights and fundamental freedoms, and in the view of the organization and structure of government (Begić, 1997: 9). “The complexity of the constitutional architecture of Bosnia and Herzegovina based on the Dayton Peace Agreement has contributed to the continuity of the socio-political dominance of ethnic nationalism (...) based on the supremacy of collective rights, and consequently on proportional representation of the constituent peoples as a fundamental principle of the political decision-making process” (Dedić, 2015: 203-204). All the institutions inaugurated in the DPA for the post-conflict reorganization of the country were, to a large extent, created from a too primordialist understanding of ethnicity and its institutionalization within the system.⁴³ The concept of ethnicity is so entwined with the Dayton regime that it

⁴³ The political representation of the constituent peoples is almost perfectly reflected by the composition of the House of Peoples (the second chamber of the Parliamentary Assembly – HP PABiH) and the House of Representatives: the first is composed of five Bosniaks and the same number of Croats from the Federation of BiH and five Serbs from the Republika Srpska, while a

is practically impossible to be a Bosnian – a citizen of BiH simply. This is primarily due to the effectively established hierarchy, where the three constituent peoples have priority in terms of political rights, while others (the various ethnic and national minorities, as well as ethnically undetermined citizens) are placed in the background (Mujanović, 2020: 6). Such an interaction between the division of the population into three constituent peoples and the exercise of veto powers transformed, *de facto*, a system based on equal representation of ethnic groups into a system detrimental to the rights of ‘others’ (Marko, 1996). As Asim Mujkić (2008: 20) suggests, “from the perspective of democratic consolidation, this constitutional order replaces the ideal of the polis with that of the Ethnopolis. The subversive mechanism of Ethnopolitics consists in the practice of *presenting ethnos as demos*, where *ethnos* acts like *demos*”.

minimum number of 4 representatives of one constituent people need to be represented in the House of Representatives. Additionally, there is also the Presidency (collective head of state) made up of three members, with a Bosniak and a Croat from the FBiH and a Serb from the RS. It follows from this that only persons who declare themselves to belong to the constituent peoples have the right to run for the House of Peoples and the Presidency. In other words, these institutions only include people from the three ethnic groups, effectively excluding and discriminating against the group “other” (Alicino, 2016: 149-150). This was pointed out by the ECtHR in the well-known case *Sejdić and Finci (of Roma and Jewish origin) vs. BiH*. However, these two institutions also discriminate against members of the three constituent peoples, because for their election, in addition to the ethnic criterion, the entity criterion has been introduced. So Serbs from the FBiH, or Bosniaks or Croats from the RS cannot be chosen for these positions. This is indicated by the judgment of the ECtHR in the case of *Pilav vs. BiH*. There is also a third group of discriminated citizens, given this issue, as was highlighted in the case of *Zornić vs. BiH* before the ECtHR, where the citizen in question refuses to declare herself either as a member of the three constituent peoples, nor as a national minority, but simply as a citizen of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Efendić, 2018: 86-87). However, the ECtHR ruled in a different direction in 2025 in the case of *Kovačević vs. BiH*. Unlike previous cases that indicated a violation of the passive right to vote (i.e., the right to be elected), this complaint stated a violation of the active right to vote. Due to the combination of territorial and ethnic criteria for election to the HP PABiH and the Presidency, the applicant complained that, as a member of the “others”, he could not vote for candidates of his own choice. It should be emphasized that the initial judgment found a violation of Article 1 of Protocol No. 12 to the ECHR. However, two of the three BiH agents before the ECtHR (from among the Serb and Croat people) appealed to the Grand Chamber of the ECtHR, which overturned the initial verdict. The Republic of Croatia and the Office of the High Representative for Bosnia and Herzegovina were actively involved in overturning the verdict. For the representative of Croatia before the ECtHR, the applicant’s request constitutes an ‘*actio popularis*’ because his Democratic Front party aims to reconstruct the constitutional framework of BiH and eliminate the notion of “constituent peoples” in the BiH electoral system, rather than protecting human rights. The Bosnian Croat agent before the ECtHR also proved that Kovačević had previously declared himself a Croat. Additionally, it turned out that he also holds Croatian citizenship, which was another argument for Croatia’s involvement in the entire case. It was the Croatian representative before the ECtHR who warned that the possible confirmation of the verdict would have far-reaching consequences for other consociational democracies in Europe (such as Belgium and Switzerland) as well as for the positive obligations of all CoE member states in terms of ensuring active voting rights. The fall of the verdict in the second instance was greeted with enthusiasm by some Serbian and Croatian politicians in BiH, according to whom the imposed narrative of BiH as a civil state had suffered a defeat, and that the court had returned BiH to where it should be – to an internal mutual agreement of the constituent peoples. The concern of the Croatian and Serbian political elites regarding this case was the fact that, unlike previous rulings that pointed to ethnic discrimination, the initial ruling in this case also spoke of discrimination based on territoriality.

However, the BiH constitution manages to some extent to maneuver between formal provisions for non-discrimination between the different ethnic groups in the country on the one hand, and the introduction of a mechanism for the sharing of power between the three constituent peoples, in response to their desire to have a strong stake in the state (Keil, 2021: 338). But consociational arrangements, such as Dayton undoubtedly is, often sacrifice the human rights of certain groups by favoring others (the constituent peoples in this case), precisely through this type of constitutional engineering (O. Bell, 2018: 19). Such a form of “ethnic sovereignty” (Yee, 1996: 187), at the state and parliamentary level, in fact established a “participatory ethnocracy” (Šarčević, 2010: 42) between three dominant ethnic groups or the so-called “constituent peoples” (Bosniaks, Croats and Serbs).

But this does not necessarily have a negative connotation *per se*. In the academic literature, Bosnia is often portrayed as a version of Europe in a microcosm, and the consociational arrangements that the International Community imposed on it for sharing power between representatives of the three main ethnic groups in Bosnia are depicted as similar to the historical experience of the EU itself (including some of its founding member states, such as Belgium, for example) (Cooley, 2011: 3). The international intervention in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the Dayton Peace Agreement, thirty years ago, “had no ambitions of conciliation among the different ethnic and religious groups (...) The power-sharing mechanism, the consociational democracy as well as the mechanisms of quotas were not created to reconcile ethnos and demos, but rather to the restoration of peace after a civil war...” (Piergigli, 2016: 126). So although Dayton is destined for criticism, it “remains a best practice in the international experience of conflict resolution and for reconstruction of national identity through institution building and governance” (Woelk, 2016: 21). The DPA created an assumption of a ‘negative peace’ that segregates, but also mutually controls; that generates ethnic divisions and tensions, to later moderate them. Even the most frenetic supporters of Lijphart’s model of consociational democracy admit that the partial failure of the International Community in Bosnia and Herzegovina is because, when drafting the DPA, it favoured the so-called “corporate” rather than “liberal” consociativism (McGarry & Moore, 2005: 87; McGarry et al., 2008: 61-62). With the deep imprint of ethnicity in Bosnian-Herzegovinian institutions, instead of liberal, procedural democracy was installed among the political representatives – or rather, the ruling oligarchies – of the three ethnic groups (Mujkić, 2007: 112). Such procedural democracy, in which ethnicity plays an important role, was actually experienced in the case of Bosnia and Herzegovina as a “correction” of liberal democracy based on individual rights, due to the evident institutional recognition of the three ethnic groups as a necessity (Woelk, 2016: 30).

But, thirty years after Dayton, a certain group of authors think that such an example of an extreme combination of power-sharing and “ethnic federalism”, which cements the territorial consolidation of ethnicity, needs “correction”, but in the opposite direction – through building a sustainable multinational system, strengthening the civil and liberal component, whereby guarantees for groups cannot completely override individual human rights. Without such a “civic” counterbalance, the system will inevitably continue to degenerate into an “ethnic democracy” (Ibid., 49). In this context, there are also opposing views. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, a civic nation as a state-forming entity has never existed, nor has a people understood as a demos, which would have founded such a civic nation. Hence, it is more realistic to build upon, rather than eliminate, the ethnic

foundations, through the acceptance of universal civic European values by all three ethnic nations, to build a common civic identity that would not nullify their current ethnic identity (Nešković, 2017: 328).

CONCLUSION

Thirty years after the civil war, the DPA maintained peace in Bosnia and Herzegovina. However, “there is a strong sense of dissatisfaction with the internal structure, as established in Dayton” (Jović, 2016: 33). Today, the Dayton Arrangement is associated less with its peace dimension and much more with the dysfunction it produced. Partly this is because Dayton was more of a truce than an agreement (Hamilton, 2020: 1).

From the discussion presented above, it can be noted that this conclusion is partly borne out by the concept of “constituent peoples”, which was introduced with the General Framework Agreement for Peace, and which was “problematic for the consolidation of the country, especially due to the tense relations between the three major ethnic groups after the war in 1995” (Džihić, 2016). “Therefore, the principle of a purely collectivist representation and the predominance of collective rights in the political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina have influenced the disruption of a citizen principle taken as an abstract category” (Banović, 2016: 3).

That is why in science, there are two antagonistic views on Dayton’s achievements. The first, affirmative, places emphasis on bringing the war to an end, creating the foundations for internal integration, and building democratic institutions, which were supposed to consolidate peace and pave the way for European integration. The second, critical, considered that the Agreement divided Bosnia and Herzegovina on an ethnic basis, hypostatizing the ethnic principle, including through the idea of “constituent peoples” and their impregnation in the internal structure and functioning of the state, which became dysfunctional, non-independent, expensive and unsustainable, creating assumptions for a “frozen conflict” (Simić, 2016: 81). The BiH Constitution obstructs the creation of a plural civic identity, hypostasizes the collective political mentality. Spiritual usurpation has moved into the realm of identity (Hadžić, 2021: 67-85), thus, BiH, as the most critical multiethnic discourse in the Region, is in constant crisis due to ethnopolitical conflicts (Hadžić, 2022: 145).

Dayton should not be glorified merely as an end to the civil war, but rather recognized as a dangerous concept that emanates many of the same policies that destroyed the Yugoslav federation, which Dayton merely replaced (Mujanović, 2020: 1). To overcome its shortcomings, which are partly produced by the way in which the concept of “constituent peoples” is elaborated, a dialogue is needed between all stakeholders toward a more comprehensive constitutional reform. Some authors, a few years ago, such as Simić (2016: 84), suggested that the country’s European integration path is the best framework in which such reform should take place. Through this “Brussels Avenue”, BiH would gain a foundation similar to that of the EU member states today, which are internally integrated, and have developed institutions, which are synonymous with a functional state. In this way, the shortcomings of the DPA would be corrected, and the integration process itself and the implementation of a clearly defined reform agenda would be its positive upgrade.

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POLYGRAPH AS A PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION AMONG EMPLOYEES IN SECURITY SERVICES

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Abstract

In the modern security context, uncovering the truth is an essential prerequisite for the successful functioning of security services. The failure to present real facts or their distorted representation, as a social and psychological phenomenon, is evident in all spheres of social life, but it carries particular weight when it occurs within the operations of the security, counterintelligence, and intelligence agencies. In such circumstances, the accuracy, objectivity, and validity of the gathered and presented operational and intelligence insights are of crucial importance—not only for establishing the facts but also for making timely, objective, and high-quality security assessments.

One of the measures for the prevention and control of the human resources potential in the security services, which on a daily basis come into contact with classified data and information of special importance to the security of the state, is precisely the application of polygraph testing of employees in the security services.

With the adoption of the Law on the National Security Agency (Article 67), mandatory polygraph testing is prescribed for candidates applying for employment, as well as polygraph testing for verifying the professional integrity of already employed personnel during their employment in the Agency, subject to their prior written consent.

Keywords: polygraph, polygraph testing, security services

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary security conditions, the state and its institutions face various types of security threats — internal corruption, the disclosure of confidential information and classified documents, and the infiltration of foreign elements into the institutions, all of which negatively affect the functioning of the institutions and the overall security of the state.

Security Services and the Role of the Polygraph in Preserving Integrity

Security services, as pillars of national security, must be composed of professional and thoroughly vetted personnel. In this context, the polygraph is used as one of the tools for maintaining integrity and trust within the security services. Although its use raises ethical and legal dilemmas, its preventive role is becoming increasingly important in the fight against internal threats.

What characterizes the modern reality is the high prevalence of corruption in all aspects of social life. According to the 2024 report by the non-governmental organization *Transparency International*, the Republic of North Macedonia is among the countries with a high level of corruption. Citizens' trust in institutions is at a very low level. The widespread corruption has infiltrated all state institutions, paralyzing their normal

functioning. Particularly negative consequences are felt when corruption infiltrates security institutions, which are directly responsible for ensuring the smooth functioning of democratic institutions established by the Constitution as the highest legal act.

To prevent corruption among employees in security institutions, it is of particular importance to establish integrity and to apply technical means such as the polygraph during the recruitment of new personnel, as well as through polygraph testing to verify the professional integrity of already employed staff during their tenure in security institutions.

The very fact that an employee in a security institution may be subjected to polygraph testing at any time has a preventive effect — deterring them from engaging in prohibited behaviour, maintaining contact with persons of security interest, disclosing official secrets, and other activities that could significantly undermine security in many aspects.

Tactics in the Application of Lie Detection

Lying and the detection of deception date back deep into human history. Numerous ancient texts provide evidence of this. In the Vedic indexes, written around 900 years BCE, there are records containing instructions on how to identify a poisoner through their behaviour. The person who administered the poison could be recognized by their actions — they would avoid answering questions or give vague responses, speak nonsense, draw on the ground or walls with their thumb, have a pale face, chew on plant roots, attempt to leave the house, and so forth.

Ancient Chinese documents also contain references to truth verification through the chewing of rice grains. The procedure involved giving a witness a handful of rice grains to chew; if, after several minutes, the grains were moist, this was taken as evidence of honesty (*J. Pavliček, 2022*). If, however, the grains remained dry, the suspect was considered guilty of deception.

Medieval methods of determining truth followed a similar logic, though they were far more brutal in execution. One such method was the *red-hot iron test*, in which the examinee had to touch heated iron with their tongue nine times; if they were burned, they were deemed guilty and punished (*J. Pavliček, 2022*). The accused were not only forced to lick hot iron but also to carry it in their hands (*Smith, J., 2020*).

Both of these methods were based on the assumption of a physiological reaction to lying - a reduction in saliva secretion caused by feelings of guilt or fear. From a historical standpoint, there are, unfortunately, very few clear and precise early descriptions of the symptoms of lying.

In the second half of the 19th century, more intensive research began on the physiological changes associated with deception. In the 1870s, Franz Joseph Gall developed a theory that lying could be detected by recognizing the emotions of the accused. He founded an entire pseudoscientific discipline known as *phrenology*, attempting to prove that specific regions of the brain were linked to particular human functions, including lying.

A significant contribution to the field of lie detection was made by the Italian psychologist Angelo Mosso, who studied the influence of emotions on pulse and blood pressure. He is considered to have constructed the precursor to the plethysmograph. Of particular interest was his specially designed balance scale, on which the subject would lie motionless; during emotional arousal, the table would tilt. The chair was mounted on a central axis and kept in equilibrium by shifting weights. To prevent constant movement of

the scale due to minor breathing oscillations, Mosso attached a heavy metal counterweight fixed vertically at the centre of the board and secured with bars. When emotional reactions occurred, blood would "rush to the head", disturbing the balance of the apparatus. This movement was recorded on a rotating drum, capturing changes in the pulse. Similar results were obtained with a simple cardiograph attached to the chest.

For successful polygraph testing, the most important factor is the training and competence of the polygraph examiner. The examiner should possess qualities such as patience, persistence, adaptability, attention to detail, and knowledge of the fundamentals of psychology, physiology, and criminalistics. Experience is a key factor, as examiners with greater experience tend to create a better impression on subjects and are perceived as "professionally competent" and "more open-minded". In polygraph examinations, the examiner plays the crucial role - the instrument merely registers physiological reactions (*N. Nenadić, 2020*).

The polygraph records changes in cardiac activity (pulse, blood pressure, and electrodermal activity). Blood pressure is measured through a cuff placed on the subject's arm, which records the mean arterial pressure - the arithmetic average between systolic and diastolic values. In this way, the polygraphist continuously monitors heartbeats and identifies fluctuations in blood pressure.

When physiological changes occur in the body under the influence of emotions, the activity of the sweat glands alters the skin's electrical resistance - increasing or decreasing it. This is visible through the movement of the recording pen, producing a curved line. The polygraph simultaneously registers several psychophysiological reactions or changes in the subject (for example: respiration, blood pressure, voice, and galvanic skin reflex). The strip on which these reactions are graphically recorded is called a *polygram*. Based on the recorded reactions, the polygraph examiner interprets (reads) the polygram to determine whether the subject is telling the truth or lying. In general, the absence of specific psychophysiological reactions indicates truthfulness, whereas their presence suggests that the subject is withholding information considered relevant to the question asked (*M. Angeleski & Z. Dimovski, 2019*).

The Application of the Polygraph as a Preventive Measure for Employees in Security Services

Within the international community, the use of the polygraph in the operations of security, counterintelligence, and intelligence agencies is not uncommon. In the United States, the polygraph is utilized in several major security institutions, such as the CIA, FBI, and NSA, as a standard practice - both during recruitment and throughout employment. In the Russian Federation and China, the polygraph is also actively used as a tool within counterintelligence operations.

In the European Union, however, certain countries limit the use of the polygraph due to concerns over the protection of human rights and individual freedoms. In our immediate neighbourhood, the Republic of Serbia actively employs polygraph testing within the Security Information Agency, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the Serbian Armed Forces—though only on a voluntary basis.

In North Macedonia, the legal framework governing polygraph testing remains weak and somewhat latent. Its use is formally regulated only within the Law on the Police, the Law on the National Security Agency (ANB), the Law on the Operational Technical Agency (OTA), and the Law on the Army of the Republic of North Macedonia (ARM). In contrast, in the developed Western world, polygraph use is relatively well regulated and

keeps pace with new advancements in polygraph science. Consequently, in domestic criminal courts, the polygraph report often remains in a “limbo” position — it is up to the discretion of the presiding judge or judicial panel to decide, based on the principle of free judicial conviction, whether to accept the polygraph report as material evidence or to treat it merely as an indicative or eliminatory expert method during the proceedings.

In recent years (since 2020 onward), interest and trust in polygraph expertise among courts and public prosecutors have shown undeniable growth. Polygraph testing is increasingly being used to verify the veracity of statements by parties in proceedings, as well as to assist in clarifying criminal cases under preliminary or investigative procedures.

This increased trust by public prosecution offices and courts in accepting polygraph examinations as material evidence in certain cases in the Republic of North Macedonia stems from the advancement of professionalism within security institutions and the application of polygraph practices conducted by qualified operators—professionals with appropriate educational backgrounds, internationally certified, and members of at least one globally recognized polygraph association, such as the American Polygraph Association.

These experts adhere to internationally verified standards, methodologies, and techniques.

Security sciences and related disciplines develop specific scientific methods for preventive action through measures and activities aimed at intercepting and neutralizing threats that endanger or could endanger national security. In this sense, several types of prevention can be distinguished. Security prevention is applied in at least three main areas (Spaseski, Nikolovski, & Gerasimoski, 2008):

1. Prevention of general security phenomena that may endanger security and stability, whether arising from natural causes, technological processes, social conditions, or human behaviour;
2. Prevention directed toward offenders—perpetrators of immoral, antisocial, or criminal acts; and
3. Prevention concerning personnel performing security-related duties within the state’s security system.

Polygraph testing plays a significant role in examining the operational personnel of security services, both during their initial employment and throughout their professional engagement. It supports the selection of high-quality candidates while also acting as a preventive measure against potential offenders among employees. Modern security, intelligence, and counterintelligence agencies pay special attention to the professional integrity of their employees to ensure loyalty and to prevent susceptibility to foreign intelligence influence, political pressure, or organized crime.

In this context, during the reforms of the security and intelligence community in the Republic of North Macedonia (2017–2018), when the former Directorate for Security and Counterintelligence was dissolved and the National Security Agency (ANB) was established, the new Law on the ANB introduced a provision allowing employees to undergo polygraph testing with their consent as part of the general and specific conditions for employment.

Article 65 of the Law provides that polygraph testing shall be conducted on a voluntary basis, based on the candidate’s prior written consent. Through this consent, the individual agrees to undergo a polygraph examination both for the purpose of employment

and for verifying professional integrity during their tenure at the Agency. A candidate who refuses polygraph testing is considered not to meet the employment requirements. The procedure for conducting polygraph testing is defined by a bylaw issued by the Director of the Agency.

The Working Party 29, an independent and advisory body of the European Union, provides opinions regarding data processing in employment relations, particularly concerning employees or candidates who may suffer consequences from refusing to undergo testing as a condition of employment.

The application of the polygraph during recruitment and for employees in sensitive, security-related positions contributes to the cultivation of a security culture, which is largely lacking in many institutions—from the lowest to the highest levels. Strengthening this security culture enhances the professional execution of sensitive tasks in the fields of security, intelligence, and counterintelligence, all in the interest of improving national security.

In addition to its use within state security institutions, the polygraph is increasingly being adopted by private companies for verifying employee loyalty, especially in cases involving industrial or economic espionage. Such companies often employ security managers who utilize various methods to assess employee loyalty to the organization.

According to media reports, particularly from Bulgaria, several articles have indicated that criminal organizations—such as the mafia—allegedly use polygraph testing to ensure the loyalty of their members.

Polygraph testing has proven to be an irreplaceable part of the recruitment process. The initial application, primarily aimed at preventing the disclosure of confidential information, is the pre-employment polygraph test. Security institutions define elimination criteria and corresponding questions for candidates to minimize corruption risks and prevent unsuitable individuals from gaining access to sensitive information. This demonstrates the importance of the polygraph in prevention—it helps build a security culture and maintain a high level of institutional awareness. It also sends a clear message: risky candidates are filtered out during recruitment, and employees remain aware that they may periodically undergo retesting, thus reducing the human factor risk to a minimum.

Polygraph testing is not limited to initial employment; it may also be conducted periodically or extraordinarily, as needed. This measure is included in the new legal framework of the National Security Agency. Such specialized testing is particularly developed for intelligence and counterintelligence purposes. Within security services, the internal control department conducts polygraph examinations to uncover double agents—an approach that has proven highly effective in practice. The same method is also used to prevent industrial espionage, following similar principles but in a corporate context. These activities often overlap in the protection of national interests.

Periodic polygraph examinations of employees produce several preventive effects:

- Regular polygraph testing has a psychological preventive effect — employees are aware they may be tested at any time, which deters them from engaging in prohibited behaviour (e.g., corruption, leaking classified information or documents, maintaining contact with persons of security interest, etc.).
- It helps maintain a high level of professional discipline.

Polygraph testing may also be applied in cases of suspected disclosure of official secrets, specific incidents, or unauthorized employee behaviour:

- When classified information is leaked or corruption among employees is suspected, a polygraph examination may be conducted.
- Although this does not represent direct prevention, it has a long-term preventive effect by sending a clear message that all abuses will eventually be detected.

Negative Aspects of Polygraph Application

Despite its positive contributions, the application of the polygraph also carries certain disadvantages:

- Accuracy concerns – the polygraph does not guarantee 100% reliability; false positives or negatives are possible for some individuals.
- Legal and ethical dilemmas – issues of voluntariness, privacy rights, and the potential for misuse by superiors.
- Psychological pressure – the constant awareness of possible testing may cause stress even among innocent employees, potentially affecting their mental health and motivation when working in sensitive positions.

CONCLUSION

The application of polygraph testing represents a crucial instrument for the effective functioning of security institutions. The very existence of a legal basis allowing employees in security services to be subjected to polygraph testing at any time has a strong preventive effect, encouraging professional, responsible, and ethical conduct. In this way, the system ensures timely detection and prevention of serious threats to the security of citizens and state institutions.

Professionalism and integrity are fundamental values for maintaining the credibility of personnel within the security sector and for ensuring their preventive role. Past practice has shown that repressive measures, when used as the main tool of prevention, do not yield the desired results. Therefore, it is essential to increase the use of modern technical means of control and oversight - such as the polygraph - which contribute to higher professionalism, accountability, and institutional trust.

One of the most effective ways to reduce corruption and prevent external influences on employees in security services is through the use of the polygraph as a means of verifying their integrity. This minimizes the possibility of both subjective and objective interference, representing an important step toward building a transparent and stable security system.

Introducing the polygraph as a mandatory procedure during recruitment, as well as a periodic measure for assessing the integrity of existing personnel, would enhance the efficiency of security institutions, strengthen public trust in their operations, and improve the international reputation of the state.

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ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN BASIC AND SPECIFIC MOTOR ABILITIES AMONG FEMALE POLICE OFFICER CANDIDATES DURING ONE YEAR OF TRAINING

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Abstract

The primary objective of police training is to enable the acquisition of practical knowledge and skills essential for the successful execution of professional duties. To ensure the quality preparation of future police personnel, it is of particular importance that the methodological concept and structure of the training are aligned with the real demands and needs of the policing profession. Within the Training Centre of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, a contemporary model of police education is implemented, focused on developing the key activities and competencies required for the performance of police tasks. In this study, a specific methodological procedure was applied to assess the feedback effects of one year of police training on the basic and specific motor abilities of 72 female police officer candidates aged 20 to 25. The assessment of general and specific motor preparedness was conducted during the first, second, and third training modules, using a standardized battery of motor tests and tests measuring competencies in defensive techniques. The results of the statistical analysis indicate that during the one-year training, positive changes occurred in most of the basic and specific motor abilities of the female police candidates. However, it was found that these changes did not reach the expected quality level according to the evaluation scoring scale. Based on these findings, the need for revision and correction of certain parts of the training curriculum is highlighted, with the aim of enabling a higher degree of professional transformation and the development of police personnel capable of responding to contemporary security challenges and professional demands.

Keywords: *police education, police officer candidates, statistical analysis, motor preparedness*

INTRODUCTION

The policing profession ranks among those that require a high level of both physical and psychological preparedness due to the nature of the tasks performed by police officers and their constant exposure to risk and stress. Police officers are expected to maintain optimal physical fitness not only as a prerequisite for successfully performing their duties but also as an indicator of professionalism, self-discipline, and readiness to protect public safety and citizens (Anderson et al., 2001).

Maintaining physical fitness is a fundamental element of police service, as it enables the effective and efficient execution of operational tasks, improvement of health and well-being, development of discipline and endurance, and the promotion of teamwork and communication within police structures (Ивановски, Јаневски & Недев, 2010).

Law enforcement is a physically demanding, psychologically challenging, and potentially dangerous profession that often carries significant health implications for officers. Police officers face daily tasks that require physical endurance – such as running, overcoming resistance, restraining offenders, applying coercive measures, and carrying equipment and weapons (Anderson & Plecas, 2000). At the same time, they are exposed to high levels of social and psychological pressure arising from the nature of police work, the need for quick and accurate decision-making, and dealing with risky and stressful situations.

Physically demanding occupations, such as policing, require high levels of cardiovascular fitness, muscular strength, and endurance. Consequently, educational institutions responsible for the selection and training of candidates establish physical fitness standards that must be met for entry into police academies (Payne & Harvey 2010). Within modern educational and training systems, physical training represents an integral part of police education and professional development (Klisarič, 2003). Modern police education and training programs include curricula aimed at developing specific competencies, psychophysical abilities, and personal qualities required for effective policing (Lagestad & Tillaar, 2014).

This modern training approach enhances the ability for self-reflection, critical thinking, and decision-making in high-risk situations – skills that are essential for the contemporary police officer (Merry & Grimshaw, 2019). Therefore, physical preparedness should not be perceived solely as a biological or athletic category but rather as an integral component of the police officer's professional identity and a fundamental prerequisite for the successful implementation of policing tasks in the service of public safety and the rule of law.

ORGANIZATION AND METHODOLOGY OF CONDUCTING BASIC POLICE TRAINING

Basic police training represents a fundamental component within the system of police education and serves the purpose of ensuring the continuous replenishment of personnel within the Ministry of Internal Affairs. The recruitment of police candidates is conducted through a public announcement, followed by a structured selection procedure (Training Rulebook of the Ministry of Interior, 2009, Article 92). This selection process unfolds through several consecutive phases aimed at identifying candidates who possess the necessary psychophysical, intellectual, and moral qualities. Candidates who successfully pass the selection procedure are referred to a one-year training program at the Training Centre in Idrizovo.

The contemporary concept of the Basic Police Training Program at the Training Centre is grounded in the principles of European police education systems and introduces new dimensions in the approach to police education (Nikač et al., 2011). The program is implemented through a blended learning model that combines activities conducted within the educational institution and practical work in operational police units. Such a model establishes a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical skills, thereby ensuring

effective preparation of future police officers for the competent, lawful, and professional performance of their duties (Trajkov, 2012).

In designing the curriculum for basic police training, the following aspects were taken into consideration:

- Analysis of police job tasks to determine the key competencies required of police candidates;
- The national legislative framework;
- International standards and recommendations in the field of police education;
- The specific needs of the police and the community.

The primary goal of the program is to provide a systematic approach to developing the professional and practical competencies of future police officers. Accordingly, the training is designed to meet the following priority objectives:

- Advancement of professional competencies, including the understanding of laws, procedures, and techniques essential for performing basic police duties;
- Development of practical skills for effective action in diverse field situations;
- Improvement of communication and interpersonal skills to foster trust and effective cooperation with the community.

The curriculum for basic police training is structured around four key components:

1. Core Activities and Competencies. This component defines the essential tasks and competencies that candidates are expected to acquire during training, closely aligned with the operational realities of police work. It ensures the harmonization of acquired knowledge and skills with the needs of police practice, fostering the development of professional attitudes and values.

2. Competency Assessment Tests. This component serves to evaluate the level of knowledge, skills, and behaviour acquired by candidates throughout the training process. Continuous monitoring and assessment provide a realistic picture of the candidates' professional preparedness and competency levels.

3. Learning Environments. The training is carried out across two interrelated learning environments: formal (within the Training Centre) and non-formal (in police organizational units). Over the one-year cycle, candidates spend nine months at the Training Centre and three months in the field, applying their acquired knowledge in a real-world environment. This model enables gradual educational and professional transformation, strengthening the link between theory and practice.

4. Quality Assurance System. This component establishes mechanisms for continuous monitoring and evaluation of the educational process. The feedback system allows for performance analysis, assessment of outcomes, and planning for the enhancement of future training programs through curriculum review and improvement.

In line with the established implementation dynamics of these key components, the basic police training is conducted over a twelve-month period through a dual learning system that integrates theoretical and practical aspects of police education. The training includes a nine-month theoretical phase at the Training Centre, consisting of 1,134 hours of instruction with trainers and 415 hours of self-study, followed by a three-month field practicum in police stations under the supervision of field mentors, comprising a total of 378 hours (Curriculum for basic police training, Ministry of Interior, 2013).

The alternating cycle of theoretical and practical activities enables a balanced distribution of responsibilities inherent to the specific nature of police training. This approach ensures continuity between the theoretical study of essential instructional

elements and their practical application in a real professional setting, providing the foundation for the development of applicable knowledge, skills, and competencies.

To ensure a high standard of training quality, the curriculum is organized into three thematic modules (Basic training on human rights in police operations, 2014):

Module 1: Fundamentals of Police Work and Public Order Protection

Module 2: Protection of Life and Property

Module 3: General Jurisdiction, Road Traffic Safety, and Border Operations.

The first module constitutes the foundational phase in developing the professional knowledge and competencies of future police officers. It encompasses essential activities and tasks based on respect for human rights and freedoms, and the principles of lawful, proportional, and responsible exercise of police authority.

The second module focuses on the acquisition of practical knowledge and skills relevant to everyday operational police activities. Its content includes topics such as arrest and detention of individuals, scene security, and the undertaking of appropriate measures and actions in cases involving offenses against public order, illicit drug trafficking, illegal possession of firearms, and other security threats.

The third module develops specialized knowledge and competencies required for the regulation and supervision of road traffic safety and border operations. Special emphasis is placed on issues of border control, combating cross-border crime, preventing illegal migration, and strengthening cross-border police cooperation.

Evaluation of training outcomes is carried out through knowledge and competency tests, designed to objectively assess the level of mastery of theoretical content and practical skills. Each test contains a detailed description of tasks and a list of criteria (competencies) that candidates must meet to demonstrate readiness for performing police duties in real professional contexts.

Within the framework of the basic police training program, a distinct component focuses on the education and training aimed at improving the general and specific motor preparedness of police candidates (Ivanovski, 2020). The objective of physical training is the planned and systematic development of fundamental motor abilities and the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills required for the lawful and effective use of coercive measures in various security situations.

Given the complexity of the curriculum structure and the necessity to shape an appropriate professional profile of future police officers, the allocated number of hours for general physical preparation amounts to (48+20) hours, while the instruction dedicated to learning and mastering defensive techniques comprises (82+16) hours.

The content of the general physical training includes diverse activities aimed at enhancing aerobic and anaerobic endurance, strength, flexibility (active and passive), agility, coordination, balance, the ability to overcome spatial and artificial obstacles (obstacle courses), training with equipment and weights, and running over various distances (cross-country, sprint, etc.).

Specific physical training focuses on the systematic acquisition and improvement of defensive techniques and practical police procedures related to the lawful use of force and police powers. The program covers police stance and combat posture, movements in combat position, strikes and defences using arms and legs, falling and throwing techniques, control techniques for overcoming passive and active resistance, defence techniques against armed and unarmed attackers, and techniques for the use of police batons and restraining devices.

The instructional process employs a variety of teaching methods, including verbal explanation, demonstration, practical exercise, corrective training, circuit training, self-learning, and scenario simulation (role-playing).

Beyond methodological aspects, the organization of instruction incorporates additional measures aimed at maintaining order and discipline, ensuring compliance with health and hygiene standards, providing adequate assistance during exercises, and securing the necessary material and technical conditions. The purpose of these measures is to enhance the quality, safety, and efficiency of the physical training process as an essential component of the professional development of future police officers.

SUBJECT AND OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH

The subject of this research is the general and specific motor abilities of female candidates for police officers, measured throughout a one-year training course at the Training Centre of the Ministry of the Interior.

The objective of the study is to determine the changes and transformations occurring among the trainees in their general and specific motor abilities under the influence of the physical training program, as well as to assess the extent to which the established standards and evaluation criteria meet educational and professional requirements.

RESEARCH METHOD

Sample of respondents

The research sample consists of 72 female candidates for police officers, aged between 20 and 25 years. During the one-year training course, three testing sessions were conducted after completing the instruction for the first, second, and third modules. The tests were administered at four-month intervals in the gymnasium and at the stadium of the Training Centre by instructors responsible for the implementation of the physical training program.

Sample of variables

To evaluate the general and specific motor preparedness of the candidates, two categories of tests were applied:

1. Tests for assessing general physical preparedness:
 - 60-meter agility run (R60m)
 - Standing long jump (JUMP)
 - Sit-ups in 30 seconds (ABS30)
 - Push-ups (PUSH UP)
 - 1000-meter run (R1000m)
2. Tests for assessing specific physical preparedness:
 - Hand and elbow striking techniques
 - Kicking and knee striking techniques
 - Defensive techniques against hand strikes
 - Defensive techniques against leg strikes
 - Identification stance techniques
 - Control and restraint techniques – arrest procedures

- Falling techniques
- Throwing techniques
- Defence techniques against unarmed attacker
- Defence techniques against armed attacker
- Handcuffing techniques
- Use of the police baton

In accordance with the physical training program, for each module, separate tests of general and specific motor preparedness were conducted using point-based evaluation scales. The overall score obtained from all tests was used to assess the level of physical preparedness of each candidate throughout the training process.

Statistical methods for data processing

To obtain feedback on the general and specific physical preparedness of the candidates during the research period, descriptive statistical procedures were employed. For each measurement, the mean values (X) were calculated, and statistically significant differences between the three measurements were determined using the T-test. Additionally, a classification method – frequency analysis (f%) – was applied to determine the distribution of results across score categories.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

Table 1 presents the criteria for evaluating motor abilities among the female police officer candidates, ranging from 1 to 14 points. These scoring criteria enable an objective assessment of the candidates’ motor abilities and allow for the monitoring of both individual and group progress throughout the training process.

Table 1. Criteria for assessing the motor abilities of the respondents

R60m	JUMP	ABS30	PUSH UP	R1000m
Up to	155-160.....1	13.....1	12.....1	Up to 4.40.....14
16.5.....14	161-165.....2	14.....2	13.....2	4.41-4.45.....13
16.6-16.8.....13	166-170.....3	15.....3	14.....3	4.46-4.50.....12
16.9-17.1.....12	171-175.....4	16.....4	15.....4	4.51-4.55.....11
17.2-17.4.....11	176-180.....5	17.....5	16.....5	4.56-5.00.....10
17.5-17.7.....10	181-185.....6	18.....6	17.....6	5.01-5.05.....9
17.8-18.0.....9	186-190.....7	19.....7	18.....7	5.06-5.10.....8
18.1-18.3.....8	191-195.....8	20.....8	19.....8	5.11-5.15.....7
18.4-18.6.....7	196-200.....9	21.....9	20.....9	5.16-5.20.....6
18.7-18.9.....6	201-205.....10	22.....10	21.....10	5.21-5.25.....5
19.0-19.2.....5	206-210.....11	23.....11	22.....11	5.26-5.30.....4
19.3-19.5.....4	211-215.....12	24.....12	23.....12	5.31-5.35.....3
19.6-19.8.....3	216-220.....13	25.....13	24.....13	5.36-5.40.....2
19.9-20.1.....2	221 +.....14	26 +.....14	25 +.....14	5.41-5.45.....1
20.2-20.4.....1				

Table 2 presents the average values obtained in the motor tests during the first, second, and third training modules. An analysis of the data reveals that there are no significant differences in the mean values between the tests, indicating that the observed changes in the candidates’ motor abilities are less pronounced and do not follow the expected temporal dynamics of the training process.

Table 2. Average values in motor tests of the respondents

Variable	R60m	JUMP	ABS30	PUSH UP	R1000m
Modules	X	X	X	X	X
Module I	18.71	177.31	24.29	24.52	4.70
Module II	23.52	179.89	24.24	23.38	4.69
Module III	17.57	177.22	23.76	22.85	4.35

Table 3 shows the results of the applied t-test assessing the significance of differences in mean values. From the analysis of these results, it can be observed that differences exist between the measurements, however, they are statistically significant only in the following tests: R60m ($t = 2.38$, Modules I–III), Push-up ($t = 3.44$, Modules I–III), and R1000m ($t = 1.98$, Modules I–III). These statistical findings indicate that only minor changes have occurred in the motor abilities of the female police cadets during the course of training. Consequently, the objectives of the physical training program were not fully achieved, meaning that the intended educational effect has not been entirely realized.

Table 3. T-test of the applied motor tests between the measurements

R60m	(1)	(2)	(3)	Jump	(1)	(2)	(3)	Ab s 30	(1)	(2)	(3)
	18. 71	23. 52	17. 57		177.3 1	179. 89	177. 22		24. 29	24. 24	23. 76
(1)				(1)				(1)			
(2)	- 1.4 3			(2)	- 0.82			(2)	0.1 3		
(3)	2.3 8	1.7 9		(3)	-0.56	0.07		(3)	0.8 9	0.8 1	
Push up	(1)	(2)	(3)	R1000 m	(1)	(2)	(3)				
	24.5 2	23.38	22.8 5		4.70	4.69	4.35				
(1)				(1)							
(2)	2.58			(2)	0.05						
(3)	3.44	1.0 2		(3)	1.98	0.88					

Table 4 presents the scoring scale used for assessing the general physical preparedness of the participants during the training, ranging from very low to high levels of physical fitness. Based on the percentage distribution of the results across the scoring categories, it can be observed that there are no major differences in the level of physical preparedness among participants across the three training modules. This implies that, for the most part, the level of physical fitness remained unchanged. According to the distribution of results, the majority of participants demonstrate a medium to high level of physical preparedness, while a smaller number exhibit low or very low levels.

Table 4. Scoring scale for assessing the general physical fitness of the respondents

Points category	N= 72 Module I (f%)	N=72 Module II (f%)	N=72 Module III (f%)	Physical fitness level
< 14	2 (2.77%)	5 (6.94%)	4 (%)	Very low level
15 – 24	7 (9.72%)	3 (4.16%)	6 (8.33%)	Low level
25 - 34	6 (8.33%)	8 (11.11%)	7 (9.72%)	
35 - 44	9 (12.50%)	12 (16.66%)	10 (13.82%)	Moderate level
45 - 54	25 (34.72%)	17 (23.61%)	20 (27.77%)	
55 - 64	16 (22.22%)	19 (26.38%)	17 (23.61%)	High level
65 - 70	7 (9.72%)	8 (11.11%)	8 (11.11%)	

Based on the average values per module presented in Table 5, the group’s final score is 46.44 points, which corresponds to a moderate level of general physical preparedness.

Table 5. Average assessment of general physical preparedness among respondents

Average score per module	Final score in training
Module I – 47.86 points	Moderate level of general physical preparedness – 46.44 points
Module II – 45.93 points	
Module III – 45.55 points	

Table 6 presents the scoring scale for assessing the participants’ specific physical preparedness during training, ranging from very low to very high. Based on the percentage distribution of results, it is evident that the level of mastery of defensive techniques varies considerably among modules, indicating that the training effects are expressed differently across participants.

Table 6. Scoring scale for assessing specific physical fitness among respondents

Points category	N= 72 Module I (f%)	N=72 Module II (f%)	N=72 Module III (f%)	Level of mastery of defensive techniques
< 4 points	9 (12.50%)	4 (5.55%)	10 (13.88%)	Very low level
5 – 6 points	31 (43.05%)	14 (19.44%)	20 (27.77%)	Low level
7 – 8 points	7 (9.72%)	17 (23.61%)	18 (25.00%)	Moderate level
9 – 10 points	22 (30.55%)	28 (38.88%)	21 (29.16%)	High level
11 – 12 points	3 (4.16%)	9 (12.50%)	3 (4.16%)	Very high level

According to the overall average of acquired knowledge from the defensive techniques training, the group’s final score is 7.28 points, which classifies as a moderate level of specific physical preparedness of respondents (Table 7).

Table 7. Average assessment of mastery of defensive techniques among respondents

Average mastery score per module	Overall average mastery score in training
Module I – 8.23 points	Moderate level of knowledge mastery – 7.28 points
Module II – 6.85 points	
Module III – 6.76 points	

The analysis of all indicators obtained from the research demonstrates that female police cadets, to a large extent, successfully complete the physical training and achieve notable progress in both general and specific motor preparedness. Nevertheless, it is necessary to increase the intensity and continuity of the exercises in order to achieve a higher level of applicability of the acquired knowledge and skills in real police practice.

CONCLUSION

Physical training, as an integral component of the basic police education, aims to equip future police officers with the competencies required for safe, lawful, and efficient performance of duties, particularly in the practical application of coercive measures. Considering the numerous prerequisites necessary for developing competent and professional police personnel capable of responding to complex security challenges, it is essential to obtain realistic insights and measurable effects from the implementation of the physical training curriculum.

Based on the conducted analysis and the results obtained from the research, it can be concluded that the tested model of physical training generally produces the desired effects in terms of positive transformation of the general and specific motor abilities of female police cadets throughout the one-year training course. However, these changes do not reach the required level of quality as defined by the scoring assessment scale.

For these reasons, it is necessary to undertake a revision and improvement of the existing physical training program through the introduction of modern training methodologies, an individualized approach to preparation, and an increase in both the intensity and diversity of training activities. Moreover, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the cadets' progress should be implemented to ensure timely adaptation of the teaching process to their physical capabilities and professional needs.

Additionally, investment in improving the material and technical conditions for conducting the training, as well as in the professional development of the teaching staff responsible for physical preparation, is crucial. Such measures would ensure greater efficiency, realism, and applicability of physical training in practical police operations.

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BUILDING RESILIENCE FROM VIOLENT EXTREMISM THROUGH DEVELOPMENT OF SECURITY CULTURE

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Abstract

Resilience is the ability of a person to mentally and emotionally cope with a crisis and to be able to return to the pre-crisis state, while using mental processes and behaviours to promote personal resources and protect themselves from the negative effects that it can cause. The development of mental and behavioural abilities, according to this definition, enables individuals to cope with the newly emerging situation, to overcome the crisis and to be able to cope with further negative consequences.

In building resilience to the emergence of violent extremism, understanding the reasons for its emergence, i.e. the initiator of radical and even extremist behaviour, is essential. There is no exact profile of a person who is ready to commit extreme violence, but people become terrorists in different ways, in different roles and for different reasons. The process of radicalization can be initiated or fuelled by socio-political or socio-psychological circumstances that directly or indirectly affect the individual. The reasons why individuals join radicalized groups, as well as the reasons why such groups are formed, are complex, diverse and, above all, of a local nature. Therefore, we believe that the development of a security culture at the local, national and regional levels is extremely important for creating predispositions for resilience to extremism, violent extremism and terrorism.

Keywords: resilience, violent extremism, security culture

Defining the concept of security culture

The phenomenon of culture, as a social phenomenon, is the subject of study by philosophy, science and religion, however, a universal definition has not yet been established. Some researchers mention several hundred different definitions. By the concept of *culture*, we mean many different phenomena in society. It represents the totality of human creativity and is divided into material and spiritual culture. This gives us the right to speak more about culture descriptively than to try to define it, without being able to fully explain it.

In everyday speech, the concept of culture refers to the creative activity of people (the arts) as well as to the habits, customs, and lifestyle of people or groups that are highly valued in society. Raymond Williams, who is considered one of the most important theorists of culture, explains the concept of culture with the following definition: Everything that man has created or produced from nature is culture, and everything that

exists or arises without human participation, without human "interference", is nature or part of nature⁴⁴.

Every culture forms its own symbols, which facilitate communication. Symbols are: words, numbers, drawings, photographs, parts of clothing, hairstyles, gestures, signs. In addition to the visible components of culture, it also contains invisible components, which are the values and specific rules of behaviour (norms) that guide and regulate human behaviour.

Fig. 1. Source: Santa Claus Culture Model⁴⁵

Society could not exist without rules (norms) or standards for “appropriate” behaviour. Norms in society are expressed through: laws, customs and moral rules. The most important norms in society are institutionalized in appropriate institutions. For society to function, there must be ways to strengthen norms, and these are sanctions.

Values are ideas about what is good, right, wise, useful. They represent the highest criteria from which norms are derived. Values are those things and ideas that are important to us and in which we believe. Knowledge, that is, ideas and information, are also an integral part of culture.

Security should be seen as a broad concept: in addition to avoiding previous undesirable events, the focus should be on new potential risks. Focusing exclusively on certain risks or practices, other relevant issues are often neglected. Security is a physical and psychological need of people, but security cannot be directly monitored, although people can directly monitor dangers, risks, accidents, disasters, losses, injuries, etc⁴⁶.

Security culture, from a modern perspective, refers to the way in which certain ideas about the security order and structures are developed, as well as what we have perceived as a danger to our lives or threats to our values, and at the same time it is our

⁴⁴ Слободнка Ристевска, Алберт Хани и група автори: Социјални вештини- Скопје ОБСЕ 2001, стр, 133

⁴⁵ http://eurolog-project.eu/pdf/vortrag_gemeinhardt_deutsch.pdf

⁴⁶ http://sr.swewe.net/word_show.htm

most obvious defence against them. Security culture participates in the formation of what is valuable to us. It regulates our moral, economic and political priorities. Security control also sets the limits and possibilities for declaring what is important, valuable or not valuable, what deserves protection or not.

Security culture is a set of beliefs, values and practices of individuals and organizations, which decide what can be seen as a danger and by what means they should be met⁴⁷. In fact, it is a set of adopted attitudes, knowledge, skills and rules in the field of security expressed as ways of behaviour and means of protecting personal, social and international values from all kinds of threats.

Security culture is understood as a security activity that expresses readiness to act and behave in accordance with the acquired knowledge and skills, as well as in accordance with the accepted attitudes about values. It is reflected in the recognition of dangers, reacting to them by avoiding dangers, averting dangers or by referring to those subjects who will professionally react and preserve the threatened values.

According to Alastair Ian Johnstone, security culture can be defined as "an integrated system of symbols that underpin long-term strategic performance by formulating concepts about the role and effectiveness of military forces in international relations, presenting these strategic performances as so factual that they seem unambiguously realistic and efficient"⁴⁸.

Security culture is part of the political culture of a community's politics. Since the creation of modern nation-states, it has become clear that cultures can be shaped by constructs and conscious policies, but they can also be a tool and help shape people's awareness of their biases, emotions, patterns of behaviour, and political preferences. Unlike political, strategic, and organizational culture, security culture requires the establishment of norms and rules of behaviour in security, in a system as a whole, in its individual components, and at the key points of security initiatives and decisions at the level of the state or another entity.

The culture and rules of behaviour in security change, develop, and become more complex in accordance with the changed role of the state and with the change in the security space/ambience within the state or outside the state space/territory.

In this context, we can conclude that since the moment when the term "security culture" first appeared, the frequency of use of the term has expanded significantly, especially in the media, and then in literature⁴⁹. From the very emergence of the term to the present day, its use has almost doubled. This process involves the separation of the concept from its original context and the emergence of new meanings and references.

In man as part of the general culture, security culture is best assessed and valued according to one's attitude towards the values that are a condition for human life and for the development of society. At the current moment in which Macedonian society finds itself, security culture has not yet been created and shaped as a separate form of consciousness, because it is a long and complex process in which changes need to be made in people's consciousness in terms of the new value system, defined in the Constitution of

⁴⁷ Forschung für die zivile Sicherheit 2012 – 2017 Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) http://www.bmbf.de/pub/rahmenprogramm_sicherheitsforschung_2012.pdf

⁴⁸ Стајић, Љубомир С., Мијалковић, Саша и Станаревић, Светлана. Безбедносна култура младих: како живети безбедно, Београд: Драганић, 2006. Johnston, Alastair И. "Thinking about strategic culture", International Security, Вол.19, но. 4, (1995) Katzenstein, Peter J., ed. Culture of National Security, New York: Columbia University Press, 1996.

⁴⁹ The term "safety culture" first appeared in 1986, with the Chernobyl nuclear disaster.

the Republic of Macedonia. But, despite this, we will try to explain this concept in a general and descriptive way: "Security culture is part of the general culture of man as an individual, of people in a certain environment and space, or of society as a whole. The content of security culture is a special form of consciousness that is expressed as a set of progressive tendencies and knowledge in the field of security that make the bearer of security culture (man) capable of recognizing the basic values and benefits of civilization; the dangers of threats to those values, goods and benefits and the need for them to be successfully protected and promoted"⁵⁰.

Security culture from a modern point of view refers to the way in which certain ideas about the security order and structures are developed, as well as what we have noticed as a danger to life or a threat to our values, and it is also our most obvious defence against them. It participates in the formation of what is valuable to us. It regulates our moral, economic and political priorities. It also sets limits and opportunities to declare what is important, valuable or not valuable, what is worth protecting or not. Security culture is a set of beliefs, perceptions and attitudes that reflect the importance that individuals in the organization contribute to security, for themselves on a personal level, as well as for the safety of others. Security culture is developed, created, and nurtured most often through socialization processes.

Manifestations of security culture

In the context of the given definition that security culture is a set of adopted attitudes, knowledge, skills and rules in the field of security, it can be concluded that it manifests itself as a behaviour and a process, for the needs, ways and means of protecting personal, social and international values from all sources, forms and carriers of threat, regardless of the place or time of their manifestation. Security culture has its internal and external manifestations⁵¹:

- Internal manifestations refer to the consideration of security,
- External manifestations are the behaviour in security, as well as the attitude and approach to security, which primarily refers to the readiness and ability, whether material or spiritual, to respond to challenges and threats.

It is known that attitudes are permanent systems of positive or negative assessments, emotional categories and techniques for the pros and cons of activities in a community. Attitudes, as part of the security culture, represent a set of beliefs about situations or issues in life that are shared by members of a society or community that has a predisposition to be related to these issues or in those situations in which they should behave in a certain way.

Strengthening non-governmental and civil society organizations is perhaps one of the most important aspects for the development of security culture⁵².

⁵⁰ Спасески Јордан, Столб на безбедноста и мирот на Балканот, Академик, Скопје, 2005

⁵¹ Стајић, Љ.; Мијалковић, С.; Станаревић, С. (2013). Безбедносна култура. Нови Сад: Правни факултет Универзитета у Новом Саду.

⁵² С. Станаревиќ : Концепт за безбедносната култура и претпоставки за нејзиниот развој , докторска дисертација Београд, 2012.

Resilience

Mental resilience refers to an individual's ability to recover from extreme trauma and stress, and represents a set of factors that promote positive adaptation despite exposure to adverse life experiences. These factors include individual protective factors, such as a positive personal outlook, family protective factors, which refer to support from family members, and social protective factors, among which the individual's social integration is particularly important⁵³. All of these factors can contribute to an individual's ability to cope more easily with negative life events, which leads to increased self-esteem, self-confidence, and a sense of well-being.

Resilience is the ability of an individual to mentally and emotionally cope with a crisis and to be able to return to the pre-crisis state, using mental processes and behaviours to enhance personal resources and protect against the negative effects that certain situations can cause⁵⁴. The development of mental and behavioural abilities, according to this definition, allows individuals to cope with the newly emerging situation, overcome the crisis, and face further negative consequences.

Psychological resilience refers to the capacity of an individual to withstand stressors without manifesting psychological dysfunction, such as mental illness or persistent negative mood, i.e. it is defined as the ability of a person to avoid psychopathological phenomena despite difficult circumstances. Psychological resilience is the ability and skill of an individual to see their problems as a challenge and an opportunity for personal growth and development⁵⁵.

The term resilience refers to the "ability to recover" from something that is experienced as stress or threat. The original definition of resilience was given by Murray and Zautra, who listed three processes or aspects that constitute the adaptive response to challenging situations⁵⁶:

- Recovery – suggests that the person is able to make necessary psychophysiological and social adjustments and return to the level of functioning that existed before the stressful situation.
- Sustainability – people can experience a slight decline in functioning, but continue to move forward, towards personal goals and objectives that make their lives meaningful, with minimal impact of stressors on their health and well-being. Sustainability testifies to the ability of the individual to thrive despite misfortunes and stressful events.
- Growth – includes additional benefits and progress after the misfortune, primarily through new knowledge, acquisition of new skills, strengthening of self-confidence, achieving a new life perspective and a stronger sense of self.

⁵³ Ahern, Kiehl, Sole, Byers, A methodological review of resilience measurement scales. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 2009

⁵⁴ Robertson, Kuper, Sarkar и Curran "The Same Staff Can Be Enough". *Employers' Resilience Strategies in Recruitment Decisions*, 2015

⁵⁵ Affleck & Tennen, Ryff et al.,, The Structure of Psychological Well-Being Revisited., - *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 2012

⁵⁶ Murray & Zautra, *Resilience: A new definition of health for people and communities*, 2008

Violent extremism

Violent extremism is a dynamic process in which an extremist individual accepts violence as a possible, and even legitimate, way of acting in order to achieve their own goals. Their own goals can be a reflection of the collective thinking of a certain group of people, nation, religious denomination, party organization or other type of organization or they can be a reflection of their own thinking and actions. This means that violent extremism can be exposed through an individually or collectively organized way of understanding and interpreting the situations and positioning in terms of responding to the situations themselves (social, economic, military, social). Such actions are aimed at:

- Readiness to support far-reaching changes in society, which can aim at abolishing the established democratic legal order and can include the use of undemocratic methods;
- A process that leads an individual or group to accept, support or encourage the use of violence as a political tool;
- A process of personal development in which the individual adopts increasingly extreme political or political-religious ideas and goals, convincing themselves that achieving these goals justifies the use of violent extreme methods.

Indicators of radicalization leading to violent extremism

The main indicators for recognizing the radicalization process are: identity, ideology and behaviour. Other indicators are:

- Changing names – using pseudonyms (which sometimes refer to their ideological role models);
- Changing the style of clothing, usually using a certain fashion brand;
- Changing physical appearance, such as shaving or growing hair/beard;
- Tattoos (hidden), badges or symbols;
- Seeking or having frequent contact with leaders of radical groups;
- Possession of propaganda materials – pamphlets, books, DVDs;
- Changes in religious practices;
- Participation in private meetings (living room meetings);
- Use of the Internet for specific purposes (e.g. social networks or chat rooms with radical content);
- Glorification of martyrdom or violence;
- Change in travel patterns or residence in certain areas (e.g. conflict zones, foreign fighters);
- Open expression of extremist views (e.g. participation in radical demonstrations, listening to radical music groups);
- Isolation from society and association with new peers and groups, i.e. staying away from school and youth clubs;
- Change in attitudes when interacting with other people – use of radical or specific terminology;
- Committing minor crimes in order to show disrespect for the Government or society.

Understanding the reasons why certain individuals are willing to give their lives to a violent extremist movement or cause and the actions being taken to address and alleviate the problems and grievances that push them to take such an extremist course represent an important investment of our time and resources.

Causes of radicalization include:

- strong post-traumatic and "fictive kinship" identifications with Sunni Muslims who are under attack as people in the region have also recently suffered the same;
- humanitarian concerns and altruistic motives;
- high unemployment;
- material benefits from joining;
- the desire for personal significance;
- calls for jihad and apocalyptic end-of-times thinking;
- the desire to build and live in an Islamic "Caliphate" and according to Sharia law; and
- the desire and need to keep family ties intact when a family member is convinced to go to Syria⁵⁷, etc.

Building resilience among radicalized individuals who exhibit violent extremism, through developing a culture of safety

Studying the reasons, motives and goals of radicalized individuals who readily adopt violent methods of expressing their extremism, in order to achieve certain goals, helps us to adequately address the problem and determine the most appropriate measures and actions to counter them. Resilience itself can be built in the form of preventive activities, expressed through various forms and methods. This involves taking proactive actions to counter the efforts of violent extremists that they make in the direction of radicalizing, recruiting and mobilizing followers to commit violence, as well as to deal with certain factors that facilitate the recruitment of violent extremists and the process of radicalization towards violence. In this sense, radicalization is not understood as a linear process that goes through precisely defined phases at a constant pace, i.e. speed, but rather it is a variable that is conditioned by the local context and individual factors. :

-The application of complex educational, economic and security measures and activities aimed at raising public awareness and resistance to the motivating factors and tools that encourage radicalization and violent extremism;

-Development and implementation of projects to build awareness of the dangers of extremism and violent extremism;

-Taking measures to prevent radicalization in schools, cultural institutions and prisons;

-Raising awareness among citizens and the private sector in the fight against violent extremism that can lead to terrorism and promoting tolerance and public understanding of all types of dangers of violent extremism and terrorism.

Such a commitment includes a consensual recognition of the "important roles that youth, families, women, victims of terrorism, religious leaders, cultural and educational leaders, civil society and the media can play in countering violent extremist narratives that can lead to incitement of certain extremists to use violent means to become terrorist actors and carry out terrorist acts, and they, as positive factors, can also influence the resolution

⁵⁷ Улогата на Граѓанското Општество во Спречување и Спротивставување на Насилен Екстремизам и Радикализација кои Водат кон Тероризам., Водич за Југоисточна Европа, ОБСЕ 2018 година

of those problems that can potentially constitute a basis for the spread of radicalization, violent extremist ideology and terrorism, in particular by fostering mutual respect and understanding, reconciliation and peaceful coexistence between cultures, as well as by promoting and protecting human rights, fundamental freedoms, democratic principles and the rule of law.”

The second step is to apply resocialization and deradicalization methods to those who are already radicalized, who advocate and practice extremism and violent forms of its expression, and who cannot be addressed by preventive activities⁵⁸. Resocialization can be described as “a deliberate, planned intervention that aims to change the characteristics of the offender (attitudes, cognitive skills and processes, personal or mental health, and social, educational or vocational skills) that are believed to be the cause of the individual's criminal behaviour, with the intention of reducing the chances that the individual will reoffend”.

Resocialization and reintegration programmes involve both a cognitive element (changing beliefs and attitudes, often referred to as de-radicalization) and a behavioural element (ceasing violent activities, often referred to as disengagement). Individuals who disengage (disengaged) may have abandoned the path of violence, but still retain their beliefs. Resocialization programmes aim to facilitate the individual's transition back into society⁵⁹.

Rehabilitation programmes target individuals who have been radicalized to violence at various stages of radicalization, and the same may apply to their families. Such types of programmes as prison-based de-radicalization/disengagement programmes, as well as post-crime care programmes that focus on the rehabilitation and reintegration of perpetrators of terrorist activities, as well as the return of foreign fighters and their reintegration into society. Some programmes provide educational and vocational training, counselling, employment opportunities, and ideological re-education, etc.

Some of them, after reaching a certain level, will leave and reintegrate into society, while others will continue the process of radicalization. Those who go through the entire process are likely to be involved in violent extremist or terrorist activities⁶⁰.

⁵⁸ <https://religija.mk/verskite-lideri-se-kluchni-za-spravuvanje-so-ekstremizmot>

⁵⁹ Спречување на радикализацијата и изразувањето на омраза на терен, Насоки за локалните и регионалните власти, Конгрес на локалните и регионални власти на Советот на Европа, март 2016 година

⁶⁰ ОБСЕ МС.ДОС/4/15 (4 декември 2015 година)

CONCLUSION

In addition to the key civil society actors described above, other important factors include educators/teachers, law enforcement agencies, academics/researchers, former violent extremists, the information technology and social media sector, journalists, and media specialists. Also, it is important to recognize that the influence of counterproductive community actors and formal or informal grassroots organizations can negatively impact the agenda for preventing and countering violent extremism and radicalization leading to terrorism.

- It is necessary to conduct continuous joint training for members of the security agencies for prevention and suppression at the regional (primarily with neighbouring countries) and international level, in order to harmonize actions, develop the highest level of cooperation, share information and exchange of experiences, as well as build mutual trust.
- In the same direction, it is necessary to continue and improve inter-institutional cooperation within the countries themselves through the exchange and sharing of good practices and experiences.
- Strengthening and improving the capacities and resources of local prevention councils, advisory civic groups and religious communities in order to undertake specific measures and activities to prevent violent extremism and radicalization of individuals and groups.
- Preparation of a sociological profile by all involved institutions at the national level in order to determine the motive and background for committing terrorist acts.
- More active involvement and engagement of youth and youth associations, families, women, religious, cultural and educational leaders and civil society in addressing the conditions conducive to the spread of violent extremism.
- Designing instruments for assessing the risk of returned foreign fighters and accompanying family members and monitoring their behaviour, lifestyle, relationships and contacts, with increased attention to child returnees from conflict regions.
- Emphasizing the need to establish a special department or body in prisons for intelligence and analysis of information on entities, persons, resources and capacities involved in the process of radicalization and the spread of extremist ideology.
- Examining the situation and possibilities for developing an appropriate programme for rehabilitation, resocialization and reintegration for foreign fighters - returnees, while in prison and afterwards, led by government institutions and in cooperation with partners from civil society, the academic community and of course experts in the field.

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PREVENTION OF POLICE CORRUPTION

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Abstract

Police corruption is a serious security problem in the Republic of North Macedonia that needs to be addressed and investigated to find preventive policies to reduce it and increase citizens' trust in the police. Police corruption is investigated through the analysis of corruption crimes committed by police officers, but also other crimes committed by police officers through "trading with influence".

Police corruption as a serious problem is also emphasized in the reports of international institutions and bodies, where the most common factors contributing to it are indicated, such as interaction between unprofessionalism and poor organization, employment of unskilled personnel, neglect of the criteria for the selection and training of police employees. The prevention of police corruption is a challenge that needs to be investigated and, through an analysis of the situation, to work on preventive policy and contribute to improving the situation. The aim of the paper is to obtain knowledge about the state of police corruption through the application of the method of normative analysis, statistical and comparative analysis, as well as a case analysis from practice for the period 2020 - 2024.

Key words: police corruption, prevention, police officers, corruption crimes, training of police employees.

INTRODUCTION

Corruption has existed in society for a long time. Despite that fact, society has always been denying the existence of corruption and corrupt practices in general. Corruption usually emerges in connection with greed, which represents a precondition for an individual disposition to corruptive practice. Greed is not the only reason for development and survival of corruption. Corruption also develops in relation to, for instance, major social differentiation (especially in the example of poverty of civil servants), disintegration and transformation of political and economic systems, and particularly in connection with the situation in former socialist states, war and post-war periods, shift of political leaders or high state officials and similar (Dobrovsek & Mesko, 2009).

In many countries, the police force is commonly identified as one of the most corrupt governmental institutions (Transparency International, 2017b). Police-related

corruption may comprise petty corruption where, for example, the public are expected to pay bribes for alleged traffic violations; at the other end of the spectrum, corrupt police officers can conspire with criminals and organized crime gangs in the trafficking of drugs, humans and weapons (DCAF, 2012).

Police corruption is a socially harmful phenomenon of serious concern, as it constitutes criminal behaviour that occurs and persists within the ranks of authorized officials performing professional duties and police officers and employees holding official status who are expected to uphold the Constitution, laws, subordinate regulations, and established principles. Such acts involve the active non-application of legal and regulatory provisions or the passive failure to enforce laws, while simultaneously fulfilling the elements of various corruption-related criminal offences, as well as other crimes committed through the abuse of laws or “trading in influence.”

Police corruption results in public mistrust of the police, rendering it more difficult for the police to perform what should be their primary task, countering crime. It compromises the institutional integrity of a policing system and undermines its legitimacy (Hope, 2015).

Employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of North Macedonia (RNM) hold the status of authorized officials for performing professional works and police officers. They are obliged, in the performance of their duties and tasks, to protect and safeguard the lives and property of citizens, to respect the freedoms and rights of citizens, and to apply only those measures and means of coercion prescribed by law or other regulations. In their work, they must adhere to the principles of legality; proportionality and fairness; management regarding the effectiveness of employees; professional ethics, impartiality, and objectivity; transparency and confidentiality; accountability; prevention of conflicts of interest; and economical use of resources (Law on Internal Affairs, Official Gazette of RNM No. 60/25). All police personnel hold the status of officials as defined in the Criminal Code of RNM, Art. 122, par. 4, p. a) (Official Gazette of RM No. 37/96...248/18).

Police corruption is a phenomenon that reduces citizens' trust in the police and police actions, and it is a serious problem that needs to be continuously investigated and solutions to prevent it and raise the level of trust among citizens. Citizens have daily contact with some of the police services, and their experiences with the work, actions and decision-making of employees in the police structure, their perception, are important for the creation of preventive policies and strategies for police work.

APPEARING FORMS AND FORMS OF POLICE CORRUPTION

Corruption in the legislation of the Republic of North Macedonia is regulated in the Law on the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia No. 12/19), where corruption is defined as "use of functions, public authority, official duty and position for the realization of any benefit for oneself or for a friend". Defined as passive corruption - intentional action against an official who, directly or through an intermediary, solicits or receives benefits of any kind, for himself or a third party, or accepts a promise of such benefits, with the aim of acting or refraining from acting in accordance with his obligations or exercising his powers contrary to official obligations, and active corruption - intentional actions against any person who directly or through an intermediary, promises or provides benefits of any kind to an official, for him or for a third party, with the aim of acting or refraining from acting in accordance with his obligations or exercising his powers contrary to official obligations. Meanwhile, a conflict

of interest is understood as a situation in which an official has a private interest that influences or can influence the impartial exercise of his public powers or official duties.

According to the mentioned definition of corruption, both passive and active corruption are included and formed as police corruption.

Police corruption according to Ivković (Ivkovic, 2005) represents any police misconduct of performing or omitting an action performed by a police officer or an entire organizational unit with disregard for legal rules and procedures. For example: an inappropriate or illegal act committed by a police officer is one that involves taking a bribe from a driver who does not respect the laws and commits a traffic offence – running a red light (Ivkovic, 2014). Hence, police corruption is understood as deviation and inappropriate behaviour with elements of illegal actions, inappropriate practices or violation of internal rules during working hours and official duties.

The police are very susceptible to corruption from the aspect of structure or organization and from the aspect of the subculture of police officers, which manifests itself in numerous opportunities and temptations, which generates deviations within the framework of the professions (Prenzler, 2009). The police are characterized by a high degree of solidarity and identification with groups. In many respects, solidarity is good - without solidarity there can be no effective police work. But it can also contribute to police corruption. Police officers who refrain from reacting against their corrupt colleagues because of the loyalty they have towards them often fall victim to the same and have the potential to fall into the corruption scheme. "A police officer, while on duty, has the discretionary authority to decide what type of deviant behaviour he will respond to (of course, within the limits established by law). The application of this authority is the core of police work. Not every offence requires responding to the police, nor is the police always the best solution to a problem. Furthermore, the police officers usually have room to manoeuvre with their powers, such as deciding how much force should be used and whether a person should be arrested or investigated (Kua, 2019). As a result, police officers may become extremely dissatisfied and start engaging in illegal activities as a way to improve their own economic situation, or they may oppose those who ignored them and did not interfere with their progress.

Police corruption can be classified into several groups: corruption of the authorities (refers to obtaining material gain, without breaking the law); service for service (for the transfer of certain goods for the purpose of transfer to business for certain individuals or companies); opportunistic theft (theft from a person under the authority of a police officer); blackmail (accepting a bribe to earn ignoring the criminal proceedings); protection against illegal activity (police protection of persons involved in illegal activities (destruction); traces of illegal activities); direct criminal activities (a police officer commits a crime for personal gain); internal payments (trade with privileges available to police officers); setting up (the form that is most often associated with prohibited procedures with drugs, for example, setting up and replacing the index) (Králj, 2014).

Police corruption serves as a bad example for the general public. In order to encourage respect for the law, states must make an effort to guarantee that those responsible for enforcing the law set a good example. The same applies to regular police officers; The senior leaders of the police should take the reduction of corruption and inappropriate behaviour seriously but also serve as a good example (DCAF, 2012). How to suppress the corruption that exists in the authorities that should deal with the situation, instead of discovering corrupt criminal acts, police officers are corrupt. Their corruption leads to resentment among the citizens, and Academician Kambovski (Kambovski, 2005)

emphasizes in several of his works „Who does not protect from the guards". A serious problem of the so-called "internal enemy" in the police structure is that the corrupt always "talk", express "dissatisfaction", but hardly anyone reports, unless it is for the detection and clarification of an organized criminal group or a single case after a complaint from a victim.

PREVENTION OF POLICE CORRUPTION

Police structures are considered part of the state institutions that are most exposed to the risk of corruption, since police officers have police powers, and it is often assumed in the public that those powers are often manipulated for their own benefit, and even for political purposes. Reducing the risk of police corruption is an important prerequisite for the successful implementation of police reform. Progress in achieving long-term goals also depends on the introduction of instruments for the fight against corruption, which, in addition to being applied in the police, will also be applied in the overall system of state administration. For this reason, strengthening the responsibility of police officers has a crucial meaning for the purposeful fight against corruption and breaking the vicious cycle of impunity (Šumić & Laličić, 2015).

In the Republic of North Macedonia, corruption in the police is a real problem, which is pointed out by GREKO in its reports, in the Report of the Fifth Round of Evaluation in the case relating to the police, several deficiencies inherent in the sanctioning regime, which is foreseen for the violation of the rules for conflict of interest and integrity, as well as the rules against corruption, are given, for which several recommendations are given that relate to suppression of corruption in the police in the act of passing normative acts and operational procedures, of acting in the direction of building police integrity and impartiality in work. Part of the recommendations relate to employment and advancement in the police careers based on quality, expertise and education, with a reduction in the influence of politicians. (Report on the Fifth round of evaluation of GRECO No. Greco RC5(2021)2, 2021) (Strasbourg, March 22-25, 2021).

Within the framework of the Ministry of Interior Affairs, as a separate organizational unit is the Department for Internal Control, Criminal Investigations and Professional Standards whose jurisdiction is repression and prevention of police corruption. And, under the auspices of the European Union and the Council of Europe, the project "External Mechanism for the Control of the Police" was implemented, the purpose of which is to establish an external mechanism that will ensure impartiality and objectivity in dealing with cases in which there is a suspicion that criminal acts have been committed by persons with police powers and members of the prison police. The external mechanism for police control functions in practice as a supplementary mechanism to the existing mechanism for internal control in the Ministry of Interior. The external mechanism for police control will be strengthened with the formation of a special Department for investigation and prosecution of criminal offences committed by persons with police powers and members of the prison police.

The formal and institutional aspect of combating police corruption is somewhat satisfied, but the level of efficiency and effectiveness of the aforementioned services is measured by the data on reported, accused and convicted police officers for criminal offences committed within the framework of their official powers and authorities. The prevention of police corruption through the attitude of citizens is an important indicator of whether citizens recognize the forms of police corruption and who are the most corrupt in the structure of employees in the Ministry of Interior.

ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH FOR CITIZENS' ATTITUDE ON POLICE CORRUPTION

The research was conducted through an electronic questionnaire in which a total of 21 questions is systematized, of which the first 3 are dedicated to the structure of the respondents - citizens from different ethnic communities, employees in the state and private sector, pensioners and unemployed people with different levels of education. The questionnaire was completed by 83 respondents, of whom 80% are men and 20% women, 49.4% of whom are aged 36-45 years, 38.8% are aged 46-55 years, and the rest are aged 18-25, 26-35, and over 56 years. According to the level of education, 57.7% have higher education, 33% have master's degrees, 3.5% have doctorates and 5.8% have secondary education. According to the structure of the respondents, it is known that these are people who have developed their own attitudes and opinions, especially on the research problem. 18 questions were asked that relate to the subject of the research, which is the perception, attitude and opinions of citizens about police corruption.

1. Do you think that police corruption is a major problem in the Republic of North Macedonia?

Chart No. 1 shows the answers to the first question, with 81.2% giving a positive answer, only 4.7% giving a negative answer, and 14.1% not sure. This indicates the fact that citizens consider the problem of police corruption in our country to be very serious.

Chart No. 1

2. Do you know what police corruption is?

Chart No. 2

In Chart No. 2, the perception of citizens regarding their knowledge of what constitutes police corruption is evident, with a high 95.2% indicating that they know, while only 2.4% gave a negative response or were unsure. This further confirms that citizens have a high level of perception or recognition of the forms and types of police corruption.

3. How would you rate the level of seriousness of police corruption?

In Chart No. 3, it is shown that citizens assess police corruption as a serious problem at 53%, an extremely serious problem at 28.9%, a not-so-serious problem at 9.7%, not a serious problem at only 1.2%, and 7.2% have no opinion. These responses confirm the seriousness of police corruption through the perception and attitude of citizens.

Chart No. 3

4. Have you ever been in a situation where you needed to resolve an issue with a police officer, and were asked for a favour or money?

Chart No. 4

Regarding the previous questions, citizens hold a positive view on the existence of police corruption and consider it a serious problem. However, when asked whether they have personally experienced a situation of police corruption, 68.2% responded negatively, 27.1% responded positively, and 4.7% do not remember, as shown in Chart No. 4.

5. In your opinion, which police officers are in the most favourable position to engage in corruption?

In Chart No. 5, the responses to the question are shown as follows: 3.5% believe it is the police administration employees, 31.8% the border police, 1.2% the commanders, 11.8% the chiefs, 1.2% the intervention and public order police officers, 5.9% the deputy ministers, and nearly half, or 44.6%, believe that traffic police officers are in the most favourable position to engage in corruption.

Chart No. 5

6. Based on your life experience, what do you think are the reasons police officers engage in corruption?

Chart No. 6

According to the responses to the sixth question, shown in Chart No. 6, respondents expressed their views on the reasons for police corruption. A significant reason is low salaries – 57.1%, acquiring money and other benefits through one’s official position and power (“enrichment”) – 35.7%, and 3.6% each consider helping others and infiltrating criminal groups to obtain criminal proceeds as reasons. This indicates that financial motives are a significant cause of police corruption. These financial motives take two directions: supplementing the family budget due to low salaries, and, for some, acquiring “wealth”, which includes infiltrating criminal groups and enabling criminal behaviour by others at the expense of illegal actions or failure to detect crimes and offences.

7. What do you think, is police corruption the individual behaviour of a police officer, or is it part of an organized scheme within police structures?

Chart No. 7

In Chart No. 7, citizens' responses regarding their opinion on whether police corruption is an individual criminal act – 34.5% – or an organized scheme within police structures – 51.2% – are shown. The remaining 14.3% believe that both forms of police corruption are present.

8. In your opinion, where are the organized schemes for police corruption most prevalent?

Chart No. 8

In Chart No. 8, it is shown that 55.3% of respondents believe that organized schemes of police corruption occur in the border police, 38.8% in the traffic police, 3.5% in the public order police, and 2.4% in the structures of the police administration. These responses, to some extent, reflect the picture of structures with a high risk of corruption, as their official positions and authorities relate to mandatory inspections, detecting offences, and directly imposing penalties, most often through fines or confiscation of goods.

9. If you were a victim of corruption by a police officer, where would you report it?

Chart No. 9

The responses to this question, shown in Chart No. 9, indicate citizens' awareness, with 72.6% recognizing the existence of a separate organizational structure for internal control and combating police corruption – the Internal Affairs Department – and considering it the best place to report cases and how they would act if they were victims of police corruption. An interesting point is that 13.1% of citizens stated they would report or expose police corruption through the media, compared to only 1.2% who would report it to a chief or commander, indicating a lack of trust in the leadership structures.

10. Is police corruption: (soliciting a bribe, requesting a favour, or other)?

Chart No. 10

In Chart No. 10, it is shown that, according to surveyed citizens, police corruption manifests itself through soliciting a bribe – 75.3%, 10.6% consider it requesting a favour, and 14.1% believe it could be other forms.

11. In your opinion, does the police have an established system to combat corruption within its ranks – police corruption?

Chart No. 11

According to Chart No. 11, citizens are not fully convinced that a system to combat corruption within the police ranks is established, with 43.5% unsure, 21.2% responding negatively, and 35.3% responding positively. This indicates that the established system for combating police corruption is not fully functioning and is not visible to most citizens, which is a strong indicator that work is needed in this area. Visibility in addressing corruption involves the use of appropriate tools, strengthened controls over police officers in their workplaces and positions, as well as prioritizing professional development and training. Additionally, more frequent security assessments of corruption risks, planning, and implementation of measures and actions to improve the situation are essential.

12. Do you think that increased monitoring of police officers would reduce their corrupt behaviour?

Chart No. 12

The previous question reflected a lack of trust in the established system for combating police corruption. This question provides insights into citizens' opinions regarding the need for increased monitoring of police officers to help reduce corruption in their work. Chart No. 12 shows the results, with 60.7% expressing a positive view—more than half of the respondents, 11.9% responding negatively, and 27.4% expressing uncertainty regarding such controls. This indicates the need to develop policies for strengthened and regular monitoring, especially in positions with a higher risk of corrupt

actions. Therefore, continuous research should be conducted, and policy decisions should be made based on research findings to implement effective solutions.

13. Do media campaigns such as ‘Report Police Corruption’ contribute to reducing police corruption?

The purpose of this question is to gauge citizens’ opinions on external factors and influences in reducing police corruption, particularly the media, often referred to as the “fourth estate”, and their contribution to combating this problem. Respondents have a very positive view on this matter: more than half, or 54.1%, responded positively, 14.1% responded negatively, and 31.8% expressed a reserved or uncertain stance regarding these campaigns, as shown in Chart No. 13.

Chart No. 13

14. Do you think that ‘anonymous’ reports of police corruption are taken seriously and handled appropriately to detect corruption and sanction the involved police officer?

Respondents’ opinions are somewhat divided regarding “anonymous” reports of police corruption and how seriously they are taken and handled. According to Chart No. 14, 36.5% responded positively, 34.1% were uncertain, and 29.4% responded negatively. This raises a serious question regarding how anonymous reports should be received, analysed, and selected, and how decisions are made on which reports to act upon.

Chart No. 14

15. What do you think—does a detected case of police corruption and the sanctioning of police officers directly contribute to reducing police corruption?

Chart No. 15

Theory and practice emphasize that every well-detected and sanctioned case of corruption has a preventive effect. Whether citizens share this view is reflected in the responses shown in Chart No. 15. A positive response was given by 77.7% of respondents, 12.9% expressed uncertainty, and 9.4% had a negative opinion. Respondents also expressed the view that repression is the most effective form of prevention.

16. Do you think that the Ministry of Internal Affairs has a developed system to combat corruption within its ranks – police corruption?

Combating corruption within the police ranks is part of the policies that are planned and implemented. However, regarding whether the system is well-developed and delivers results, respondents show greater uncertainty: 42.4% are unsure, 23.6% responded negatively, and 34.1% responded positively. This is a strong indicator of citizens' lack of confidence in the established system for combating corruption within the police ranks or in detecting police corruption by police officers.

Chart No. 16

17. Do you think that holding seminars and providing continuous education for police officers would help reduce corruption among them?

Chart No. 17

From the perspective of the need for prevention and its strengthening to combat police corruption, a question was posed regarding the enhancement of police capacities through continuous training, education, and similar measures. The responses to this question are shown in Chart 17: 54.1% expressed a positive view, 27.1% were uncertain, and 18.9% responded negatively. This indicates that education aimed at reducing police corruption is quite important for several reasons, including understanding what constitutes corrupt acts, how to deal with pressures and corruption risks, handling the influence of previously established corrupt practices by senior colleagues, and overcoming the fear of opposing corrupt activities.

18. In your opinion, should police officers for whom evidence has been obtained proving they committed criminal acts in the course of their police duties be sanctioned by: immediate suspension from duty or filing a criminal complaint?

Chart No. 18

Respondents have a very positive view on the immediate suspension of corrupt police officers for whom evidence has been obtained, with 51.7% supporting immediate suspension, while 48.2% believe criminal complaints should also be filed. For incidents involving elements of police corruption, there should certainly be suspension, as well as the filing of criminal complaints, initiation of criminal proceedings, and appropriate sanctions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the study conducted and the smaller-scale research on the attitude and opinion of citizens on police corruption, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Police corruption is a serious problem in the Republic of North Macedonia, although work is underway to establish an institutional and legal framework, greater implementation and "visibility" for citizens is needed in the fight against this type of corruption.
- Police corruption is more prominent in police structures that are at a higher risk of corruption, are in positions for sanctioning (traffic offences) or cross-border control (border police), but corruption is also prevalent among police officers in the administration.
- Police officers are more susceptible to passive corruption manifested through accepting bribes without prior request or established criminal schemes that have existed for a longer period of time, and the corrupt amounts are individually low, but in total it is about acquiring high amounts of corrupt proceeds.
- Prevention of police corruption is a serious challenge that should be based on an institutional and formal framework that will be implemented through programs to suppress corruption, namely prevention through repression and prevention through education.
- Prevention by raising awareness among employees in police structures that corruption is a dangerous phenomenon, jobs are lost due to corruption, the penalties are serious, primarily prison sentences, but also work on raising awareness and conscience that we should work on detecting crime, and not on corrupt actions for not detecting crime, not sanctioning misdemeanours, and thus confirming the strong question: Who should protect us from the guards?. The guards should deal with the risks and act in accordance with the law and enable the suppression of crime and not join the ranks of criminals.

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OPERATIONAL-TACTICAL COMBINATIONS IN THE CRIMINALISTICS INVESTIGATION OF BRIBERY

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Abstract

Corruption manifests in numerous forms and guises; a paradigmatic form of corruption is bribery, which under Macedonian criminal law is criminalized by two offences contained in Chapter 30 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of North Macedonia: Receiving a Bribe (Article 357) and Giving a Bribe (Article 358). (Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia, no. 37/96 ... 248/18.) The subject of this study comprises the operational-tactical combinations employed in the criminal investigation of these offences with the aim of detecting, clarifying and securing evidence. This category of corrupt conduct requires investigative responses that are themselves specific: planned combinations of operational-tactical measures, investigative acts and special investigative techniques, selected and implemented according to the concrete criminal situation. Methodologically, the paper applies the normative method in order to examine the statutory regulation of these offences and employs statistical and comparative methods to obtain data on the volume, structure and dynamics of these crimes for the period 2020–2024. It further analyses the volume, structure and dynamics of reported, indicted and convicted offenders, and examines the collected and systematized data to derive informed conclusions about the state of affairs in the Republic of North Macedonia. Finally, the study undertakes a review and analysis of legally prescribed measures and actions and their operational-tactical combination.

Keywords: corruption; receiving a bribe; giving a bribe; operational combinations; criminal investigation.

INTRODUCTION

In an organized society, nothing poses a greater threat to the functioning of public services and the performance of public duties than the susceptibility to bribery—the corruption of those who hold such positions. At the same time, corruption represents an attack on the freedoms and rights of citizens, as it undermines one of the fundamental principles of the rule of law: the equality of all citizens before the law. Moreover, corrupt public officials perform their duties inefficiently, subordinating the public interest to private (self-serving) gain. Corruption becomes a mode of behaviour, a form of communication, a method of negotiation, and a means of escape from “hopeless” situations; as the old saying goes, “*money opens iron gates*”. And money is corruption itself: both the means and the medium of communication, negotiation, and the completion

of tasks. Yet can everyone afford to pay? We are speaking of a state governed by rule of law, where both the rich and the poor live. For the wealthy, things come easily; for the poor, it is much more difficult (Nikoloska, 2013).

Corruption is a form of behaviour that deviates from formal rules in the exercise of public duties, undertaken for the purpose of achieving personal gain or violating the rules governing the conduct of individuals who are elected, appointed, or employed in positions involving the performance of public office, activity, or profession. According to Tanzi (1998), corruption represents the deliberate disregard of official distance, aimed at obtaining certain benefits for oneself or for closely related persons. In the pre-modern world, corruption was described as humanity's original sin—that is, as a manifestation of sinful human behaviour (Knights, 2016).

Corruption is defined as the offering, receiving, or demanding of certain benefits with the intent to influence social actions. Aristotle, Machiavelli, and Montesquieu identified corruption as a sign of the erosion of a society's moral values. They regarded it as an immoral and harmful phenomenon, emphasizing that holders of public office must serve the common good rather than their own private interests. With the development of the modern state, corruption can no longer be viewed merely as a morally harmful phenomenon, but also as a cause of state deterioration. (Labovic, 2024) The most significant forms of corruption include the giving and receiving of bribes and nepotism, the abuse of one's position for personal purposes. Declared social values—particularly the pursuit of success at any cost—appear to encourage the spread of corrupt practices. Individual corruption refers to the actions of a single person within a corrupt exchange. This form of activity is discreet, involving only two participants. Such acts are characterized by the culpability of both parties in the giving and receiving of bribes or gifts. This type of corruption is the most prevalent among all forms. Corruption between public officials and private individuals is especially widespread. The simplest form in this sphere is the bribery of public officials. When such practices become common within an institution, the integrity of that institution is called into question. If such practices are characteristic of several institutions, one can speak of an endemic phenomenon of corruption within state institutions (Dobovšek & Meško, 2009).

If a briber resolves a problem in this manner and has no other means of doing so, then, according to the traditional norms of the community in which he lives, he is not subject to moral condemnation (Antonić, 2001: 26). In other words, within popular tradition, bribery is tacitly tolerated and even met with a degree of understanding. Based on centuries of collective experience, bribery has become a kind of folkloric and everyday phenomenon. It is often rationalized by the attitude: *"Everyone does it"* (Antonić, 2001: 27). Over time, this has developed into a habitual practice that facilitates the completion of various affairs and has persisted in popular experience as a sort of maxim: *"Grease the wheels if you want the job done faster"*, Today, it is still common to hear expressions such as: *"Get this thing done for me, and I'll reward you"* (Antonić, 2001). Of course, this "reward" does not represent honour in its original sense, but rather a euphemism—a "more refined" expression—for a bribe, that is, an act of corruption.

As a traditional form of corruption, bribery encompasses both the giving and receiving of illicit benefits. Giving a bribe (or offering a bribe) involves providing money or other valuables in the form of a gift, typically to unlawfully secure the execution of an action, to obtain preferential treatment (jumping the queue), or to gain certain privileges. The act of giving a bribe or engaging in bribery constitutes a process whereby material, financial, or other services are offered to those upon whom the provision of specific

services or the granting of favourable treatment depends—individuals who are legally obligated to perform such duties. Bribery is considered the most widespread form of corruption, particularly in the context of administrative corruption, which entails the subordination of public interest to personal gain (Joković Pantelić, 2024). It generates a dual benefit: for the briber, who unlawfully secures a right or privilege, and for the bribee, who unlawfully derives personal gain at the expense of public interest and the office or service they are legally entrusted to uphold. In this context, both parties are perpetrators of a criminal offence. Bribery-related crime is closely linked to circumstances associated with public authority, particularly the discretionary powers of the bribe recipient, while the briber seeks to obtain certain advantages, services, or even facilitate the commission of other criminal acts—such as document forgery—as a direct result of the bribe.

Bribery constitutes a complex criminal situation, regardless of whether it involves an isolated criminal case or an organized criminal scheme, because the participants (the perpetrator and the victim) each have their own criminal interests. The individual offering the bribe does so to achieve a particular objective—obtaining employment, a service, a privileged status—or may be compelled to offer a bribe to secure such outcomes, as demanded by the other party, the bribe recipient. Both parties have vested interests, as the acceptance of a bribe can be carried out by individuals holding the status of public officials, persons in positions of responsibility, or individuals performing work of public interest, a status defined under Article 122 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of North Macedonia (Official Gazette of the RM, no. 37/96 ... 248/18). Moreover, a bribe can be offered by any person, either a natural person or a legal entity (through a responsible person or other employee acting on behalf of and for the account of the legal entity). In most cases, bribery is not reported, and this form of crime thus falls within the so-called “dark figure” of criminality.

It is a practice of legal incrimination for “receiving” and “giving” a bribe. In this case, there is an intertwining of the role of the victim and that of the perpetrator, and it is questionable whether someone would report these criminal acts in practice (Dobovšek & Mesko, 2009).

Criminal-investigative inquiry into bribery is a complex process of detection, elucidation, and proof, and it also serves as a preventive function. It is held that every well-processed case constitutes effective prevention for prospective offenders who may be contemplating this type of crime.

The conduct of a criminal-investigative inquiry depends on the complexity of the criminal situation, the initial findings, and their operational verification. Whether the matter concerns an isolated incident or organized criminal activity, investigations into this type of offending always involve the planning and execution of operational–tactical combinations of lawful measures and actions aimed at full detection, clarification, and evidential securing. Because this is a specific form of corrupt behaviour the operational–tactical combinations are planned and implemented with the objective of apprehending perpetrators *in flagrante*. With careful operational planning, detection, clarification, and the securing of robust evidence necessary for the subsequent course of criminal proceedings can be achieved simultaneously.

In complex criminal situations, the planning and employment of covert measures require a longer time horizon, while execution is governed by precisely determined times and locations for carrying out the lawful measures and actions.

2. CRIMINAL-LEGAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BRIBERY IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

Under Macedonian criminal law, Chapter 30 of the Criminal Code (Criminal offences Against Official Duty) (Official Gazette of the RM, nos. 37/96...248/18) criminalizes two offences involving elements of bribery. These offences share similar criminal-investigative characteristics and are considered either connected or sequential. In order for a bribe to be received, there must be a party willing to give or actively offering the bribe.

2.1. Receiving a Bribe – Article 357

Receiving a Bribe, or, as it is commonly referred to in all international anti-corruption instruments, passive bribery, is one of the forms of corruption. The perpetrators of this criminal offence are public or responsible officials, and a key element of the offence is that the bribe is offered or received in connection with the performance of official duties—specifically, in the execution of certain official acts within the perpetrator's competence. According to Article 357 of the Criminal Code, receiving a bribe constitutes criminal behaviour by a public official who, directly or indirectly, solicits or accepts a gift or other benefit, or receives a promise of a gift or benefit, for themselves or another, in order to perform an official act that they should not perform or to refrain from performing an official act that they are obligated to execute. It also includes a public official who, directly or indirectly, solicits or accepts a gift or other benefit, or receives a promise of a gift or benefit, to perform an official act that they are required to execute or to refrain from performing an official act that they should not perform. Furthermore, the offence encompasses cases where, after performing or failing to perform an official act as described above, the official solicits, accepts, or agrees to accept a gift or other benefit. If the offence results in the acquisition of substantial or significant material gain, higher penalties are prescribed. The same penalties apply to responsible people, individuals performing tasks of public interest, as well as foreign officials. Any gift or material benefit received shall be confiscated. (Criminal Code of the RM, Official Gazette no. 37/96...248/18)

Primarily, by criminalizing these actions, the legislator aimed to protect the proper functioning of public services. The purpose of this criminalization is to prevent the unlawful acquisition of material gain, and, in essence, the offence is considered a criminal act against property.

As a rule, the acceptance of a bribe is accompanied by the performance of unlawful official acts. In cases where the public official does not undertake any official action, the mere acceptance of a bribe compromises the lawful execution of their duties. The bribe obliges the official to act in an impermissible manner while performing their duties, and, in addition to this improper conduct, a key element is the material gain and the abuse of official position. (Labovic, 2024) In terms of execution, accepting a bribe constitutes one form of abuse of official authority. Objectively, this criminal offence also constitutes a violation of the authority of the office and the public's trust in the lawful conduct of officials. In carrying out their official duties, public officials must be guided by the interests of the office rather than by personal gain (Vitlarov, 2006). Receiving a bribe is considered a particularly serious criminal offence because it represents a breach of the rules governing official conduct and undermines the reputation of both the officials and the office itself. Moreover, such behaviour may create habits in officials, leading them to

solicit and accept bribes or rewards in the future. For public and responsible officials, bribery can become normalized behaviour, where decisions are guided by the size of the bribe rather than by the rules of conduct imposed by their official position, making their actions dependent on who offers a bribe and how much it is worth.

The acceptance of a bribe can take the form of **active acceptance** (directly or indirectly through intermediaries), which involves soliciting a bribe or creating a situation in which a certain action of the perpetrator must be paid for. **Passive bribery**, on the other hand, occurs when the bribe is not solicited but is received “for a job well done”—either directly or indirectly—for failing to perform a certain duty that the official is obligated or required to carry out in the course of their official responsibilities (Nikoloska, 2013).

2.2. Giving a Bribe – Article 358

Giving a bribe (active bribery) is intrinsically linked to passive bribery. While receiving a bribe implies consent or willingness to be corrupted, giving a bribe constitutes active corruption, involving the inducement or encouragement of a public official, responsible person, foreign official, individual performing work of public interest, or foreign public official, to engage in unlawful conduct. In this respect, both parties, the briber and the bribee—are involved. However, this connection does not necessarily always apply, as giving a bribe can also constitute an independent offence in cases where the perpetrator offers a bribe without the official or other legally designated person intending to accept it. If the bribe is not accepted and the incident is reported, the liability for the criminal offence of giving bribe rests solely with the briber (Nikoloska, 2013).

In the criminal offence of giving a bribe, the perpetrator is any person who directly or indirectly gives, promises, or offers a gift or other benefit to a public official for themselves or another, in order to induce the official to perform an act that they should not perform, or to refrain from performing an act that they are obligated to execute, as well as any person who mediates in this process. The offence also covers those who directly or indirectly give, promise, or offer a gift or other benefit to a public official for themselves or another, to induce the official to perform an act they are required to execute or to refrain from performing an act they should not perform, including intermediaries. A court may exempt from punishment a perpetrator who gave or promised a bribe at the request of a public official and reported it before it was discovered that the offence had occurred. These provisions also apply when a bribe is given or promised to a responsible person, a responsible person in a foreign legal entity, a person performing work of public interest, or a foreign public official in connection with receiving a bribe. Criminal liability is also prescribed if the bribe is given by a legal entity. Any gift or material benefit provided shall be confiscated.

In cases where a bribe is given to induce a public official or another person to act in accordance with the law, that person is technically performing a lawful act. However, they violate the fundamental principle of equality of citizens before the law by granting certain advantages or benefits to the briber, or by exceeding the limits of their authority in the interest of the briber.

The connection between the briber and the bribee is established through the transmission of a message, the communication of conditions, the receipt of the gift from the giver, and its delivery to the recipient, among other actions. This encompasses all acts by which the giver’s intent is realized in any way, ensuring that the bribe or other benefit—or the promise thereof—reaches the recipient, namely the public official. In such cases, the intermediary acts as an instigator or facilitator of the bribery; however, the law

criminalizes these actions as execution of the offence, making the intermediary one of the perpetrators of this criminal act (Vitlarov, 2006).

3. VOLUME, STRUCTURE, AND DYNAMICS OF BRIBE PERPETRATORS IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA FOR THE PERIOD 2020–2024

To gain insights into the state of bribery in our country, data were obtained and analysed from two sources: the Annual Reports of the Public Prosecutor’s Office and the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Interior.

Table 1. Data for the Investigated Period 2020–2024 (Annual Reports of the Public Prosecutor’s Office)

Year	Receiving a Bribe under Article 357			Giving a Bribe under Article 358			Total		
	Rep.	Ind.	Con.	Rep.	Ind.	Con.	Rep.	Ind.	Con
2020	4	5	6	0	0	0	4	5	6
2021	17	5	6	0	0	0	17	5	6
2022	23	9	2	5	5	6	28	14	8
2023	23	10	30	11	10	12	34	20	42
2024	40	13	8	19	7	5	59	20	13
Total	107	42	52	35	22	23	142	64	75

In Table 1, the data presented are obtained from the Annual Reports of the Public Prosecutor’s Office (jorm.gov.mk) for the two investigated criminal offences involving elements of bribery, covering the period 2020–2024. The data refers to reported, indicted, and convicted offenders, with the purpose of gaining insight into the effectiveness of criminal investigations and the securing of relevant and substantial evidence upon which the courts base their judgments. Specifically, during the investigated period, for the criminal offence “Receiving a Bribe”, a total of 107 offenders were reported, of whom 42 were indicted and 52 convicted. For the offence “Giving a Bribe”, a total of 35 offenders were reported, 22 indicted, and 23 convicted. In total, for both offences, 142 offenders were reported, 64 indicted, and 75 convicted. There is a higher number of reported, indicted, and convicted offenders for “Receiving a Bribe” compared to “Giving a Bribe”, which indicates that in most cases, victims report bribery or extortion attempts. Moreover, if a bribe is reported before the case is discovered, the briber is not held criminally liable. The conviction rate of 52.8% is higher than the indictment rate of 45.07%, which suggests two possible explanations: during the criminal proceedings, evidence was obtained against additional persons, or some of the proceedings have been ongoing over a longer period,

with indictments filed in previous years. Regarding the dynamics, the highest number of reported offenders for both offences—both collectively and individually—was recorded in 2024.

Table 2. Volume, Structure, and Dynamics of Detected Criminal offences and Reported Offenders for Bribery by the Ministry of Interior

Year	Receiving a Bribe		Giving a Bribe		Total	
	CO	P	CO	P	CO	P
2020	5	4	1	1	6	5
2021	3	5	4	4	7	9
2022	11	18	5	5	16	23
2023	11	12	11	12	22	24
2024	12	25	10	11	22	36
Total	42	64	31	33	73	97

In Table 2, the data are extracted from the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Interior for the investigated period 2020–2024 for the two examined criminal offences. The data refers to detected criminal offences and reported perpetrators. A total of 73 criminal offences were detected, of which 42 relate to receiving a bribe and 31 to giving a bribe. For these offences, a total of 97 perpetrators were reported, with 64 reported for receiving a bribe and 33 for giving a bribe. For the offence “Receiving a Bribe”, more criminal offences were detected and more perpetrators reported compared to “Giving a Bribe”, indicating that victims primarily report individuals with the status of “bribe recipients”, who are then processed through operational criminal-investigative procedures. According to the law, if the act of giving a bribe is reported before the bribe is delivered and there is cooperation with the police, the bribers are not held criminally liable. The fact that 73 criminal offences involved 97 perpetrators suggests that this type of crime is often committed by multiple individuals, in a grouped or organized manner.

According to the analysis of the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Interior, which also include data on the status of the perpetrators, the dominant perpetrators of receiving a bribe are police officers, (Labovic, 2024) particularly those working in traffic safety and the border police. Following them are customs officers. However, other public officials, responsible persons, and especially individuals performing work of public interest are also recipients of bribes. Regarding giving a bribe, again the most common recipients are police officers, with bribes given to avoid border checks, traffic fines, or controls. This type of crime is also present in areas such as urban planning, economic activities, and others. Reported perpetrators of receiving a bribe include suspects holding official positions in various ministries, state institutions, funds, and municipalities, as well as individuals performing work of public interest, such as doctors, pharmacists, and similar professions. (<https://portal.mdt.gov.mk/module-block-documents/76-document-mk.pdf>)

For the purpose of deeper scientific consideration of the practical consequences from the complexity of high-level institutional type of organized corruption see: Miodrag Labovic: Policing in Central and Eastern Europe – Social Control of Unconventional Deviance, Conference Proceedings, Social control of institutional organized crime. (Labovic, 2011)

Among the most notable cases in police practice for detecting high-level corruption involving the acceptance of bribes over an extended period and in an organized manner is the 2022 case in which an organized criminal group of 12 police officers at the Tabanovce Border Crossing was dismantled. Between September 2020 and onward, these officers acted jointly and in a coordinated manner, demanding and accepting bribes in the form of cash, gifts, and other benefits in exchange for overlooking detected irregularities. Some of the suspected police officers were charged not only with “Receiving a Bribe” under Article 357, but also with “Abuse of Official Position and Authority”, “Criminal Association”, and “Incitement”. In 2024, another notable case in the field of high-level corruption involved the tender process for the State Lottery of the Republic of North Macedonia, where, due to grounds for suspicion of “Receiving a Bribe” under Article 357, three individuals were reported. These included the Chairperson of the Management Board and the Chairperson and a member of the Public Call Commission. Also in 2024, an operational action targeting bribery among customs officers at the Novo Selo and Dojran border crossings resulted in the arrest of 13 customs officers for prolonged bribery. From May to October 2024, these officers repeatedly demanded and accepted bribes ranging from €20 to €100 to refrain from taking measures or actions related to the collection of customs duties.

OPERATIONAL–TACTICAL COMBINATIONS IN THE CRIMINALISTICS INVESTIGATION OF BRIBERY

The criminalistic investigation into bribery, as a specific form of corruption, is a process that spans information gathering to operational execution and is applied in complex criminal situations involving elements of bribery. Depending on the initial general information, operational checks are conducted to establish the level of suspicion—“grounds for suspicion”—in order to plan and implement lawful measures and actions. Each case requires a separate operational plan and individual operational–tactical combination, which most often culminates in an operational action: prior covert preparation and execution of a planned, secret operation that simultaneously involves multiple measures and actions to achieve detection, clarification, and the securing of substantial evidence. In this context, according to criminal-investigative characteristics, three typical situations most commonly occur: (1) a previously reported solicited bribe, where the “victim” is required to give a bribe, and the focus of the procedure is on the solicitation itself; (2) continuous bribery carried out by individual public officials, responsible persons, or persons performing work of public interest, where the corrupt acts are related to their ongoing official and professional duties; and (3) organized bribery, in which both parties—the givers and receivers of the bribe—have a shared interest, as often occurs in cases involving police and customs officers and omissions in supervision and control. In each of these scenarios, operational actions are tailored to the specific circumstances to enable effective detection, clarification, and secure evidence necessary for a successful judicial procedure (Nikoloska, 2025).

Criminalistic investigation inquiry into criminal situations is planned and executed on a case-by-case basis through the formulation of operational–tactical combinations of measures and actions — that is, operational–tactical, investigative measures and actions, and special investigative measures — with the aim of simultaneously detecting, elucidating, and securing evidence. This approach, known in criminology as apprehending perpetrators *in flagranti*, targets the moment of, or immediately after, the commission of the offence when the evidence (money, valuables) is still in their possession. The specific nature of these two corrupt offences makes such acts essential: without it, it is difficult to obtain robust and relevant evidence. For this reason, operational–tactical combinations are of crucial importance for the full elucidation of criminal situations and for securing the evidence necessary for a successful subsequent criminal procedure. The tactical method provides the most rational and effective manner of executing an operational–tactical measure, an investigative or judicial action — a choice made by the practitioner from the repertoire of criminological tactics that is most appropriate to the concrete operational–tactical or tactical–procedural situation. That discretion should be guided by the type of evidentiary material that can be obtained, following the principle of progressing from “weaker” to “stronger” evidence. From the perspective of covert criminological work, tactical combinations imply the application of measures and actions aimed at criminologically purposeful operations and at the preparation of operational actions founded on relevant data on which the criminal execution depends — a method especially pertinent in criminal situations such as illegal drug trafficking. These constitute fundamental police actions that should be employed in modern criminal investigation and should form the basis of all criminological planning, founded on criminological analysis and intelligence (Angeleski, 2018).

Operational-tactical combinations are planned and carried out in coordination with the competent public prosecutor’s office; measures are planned that can effectively execute the operation and fully shed light on the case by securing relevant evidence that links the perpetrator to the criminal offence. A tactical combination is a system of two or more interconnected measures and actions and multiple tactical methods for implementing them, adapted to the specific criminal situation. The tactical combination represents “the union of several tactical methods, multiple operational-tactical measures, investigative actions or special investigative measures, which may be mutually connected and undertaken according to a previously prepared plan” (Vodinielić, 1985). When conducting operational combinations, account is taken of the degree of organization of the criminal group, their *modus operandi*, any connections of individuals within the prosecuting authorities or their corrupt conduct; particular care must be taken with the covert planning of measures and actions in order to find and secure evidence of the offence and evidence that links the offence to the perpetrator and other persons involved in the criminal operation.

Tactical combinations from the perspective of covert criminalistic operations imply the application of measures and actions aimed at criminalistically purposeful work and the preparation of operational actions based on relevant data that determine the criminal execution, particularly in criminal situations involving illegal drug trafficking. These are fundamental police actions that should be employed in modern criminal investigations, and they should form the basis of any criminalistic planning, grounded in criminalistic analysis and intelligence (Angeleski, 2018).

The investigation of more complex criminal cases is carried out through operational actions; it involves planned and coordinated procedures with the implementation of scheduled measures and actions according to a pre-drawn plan

specifying the place and time for those measures and actions, as well as the human and technical resources. Operational-tactical actions are measures and activities undertaken within a defined time period, with predetermined objectives, and under full coordination and control from a single centre where all information and data from the measures and actions are collected. Although they may be conducted over an extended period, they culminate in the arrest of the perpetrators and their presentation before an investigating judge. Operational-tactical actions are given a designation — usually chosen by the operational officers or the investigative team — depending on the subject of the criminal investigation or the area of the perpetrators' criminal activity.

Most often, operational-tactical combinations in individual cases of accepting a bribe — that is, when victims report that a bribe has been solicited from them — involve cooperation with police officers by giving the officers “marked banknotes” (previously photocopied); in the past these were marked with chemical substances for that purpose. The time and place are determined precisely, of course in agreement with the “victim”, and then operational-tactical measures are applied: an ambush, covert tailing and observation. At the moment of execution the suspects are detained, the items — the bribe — are seized, searches are carried out and interviews conducted; all of this is directed from a single centre — the commander of the operation and the competent public prosecutor.

For complex criminal cases, elaborate operational-tactical combinations are developed, involving a complete and detailed action plan. Special investigative measures are applied — such as monitoring communications and deploying undercover police operatives — with the goal of executing the operation at the moment the suspects accept a bribe or when the bribe money is in their possession. During this process, suspects are detained, interviews are conducted, and simultaneously, inspections and searches are carried out in business premises, including review of business documents, seizure of camera recordings and computer data. Searches are also conducted in homes, other involved individuals are detained, and all measures and actions are documented in appropriate reports, which serve as evidence of the lawful execution of all measures and activities. Particular attention is given to evidence, which must be seized with confirmation of temporarily secured items and then delivered with proper documentation to the public prosecutor's office. Every well-executed criminal-legal event is the result of the efficiency of all individuals involved in the implementation of operational-tactical combinations and in the operation itself.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Bribery is a traditional form of corruption that manifests through the giving and receiving of bribes. In cases of receiving a bribe, the perpetrators are individuals with official status, whereas in cases of giving a bribe, the perpetrators can be private individuals or responsible persons within legal entities who give bribes on behalf of and for the account of the legal entities, most often in tender procedures.

Based on investigative results, receiving a bribe is a criminal offence committed more frequently than giving a bribe. This is due to the fact that victims report instances of bribery; if they report the offence, they are not criminally liable.

In our country, bribery is most commonly observed among police officers, particularly in the traffic and border police, as well as among customs officials. It is usually carried out in an organized manner for smaller amounts but continuously over an extended period.

High-value bribes are most often associated with tenders, which is understandable given the exceptionally large sums involved.

Bribery as an individual case occurs among persons performing public interest duties. These involve smaller or occasionally larger amounts, and this type of corruption undermines public trust in institutions, especially in healthcare institutions, funds, or state agencies.

Good planning and execution of operational-tactical combinations through operational actions are effective, and securing relevant evidence enables further efficiency in criminal proceedings.

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FORENSIC REGISTRATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF PERSONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the procedures for forensic registration and identification of persons and the forensic methods applied in these processes in the Republic of North Macedonia.

Criminalistic registration is examined through the practical work of the organizational units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, with a particular emphasis on the introduction of the new ABIS system.

Identification, on the other hand, is analysed as a forensic identification process carried out through personal description, papillary lines, and DNA identification. The chapters of the paper pay special attention to the provisions arising from the introduction of the new Guidelines for forensic registration and identification of persons and unknown remains.

The aim of the paper is to identify the challenges encountered in practice during the implementation of the aforementioned processes and to propose solutions for overcoming them. Ultimately, establishing the identity of a potential perpetrator is, in our view, the most critical aspect of forensic work.

Keywords: *forensics, registration, identification*

INTRODUCTION

The registration and identification of persons form the basis of forensic work. Establishing the identity of an individual's distinguishing characteristics (suspect, perpetrator, or victim) or an object in an investigation is a critical step without which the successful completion of the forensic work is impossible. The focus of this paper will be exclusively on the registration and identification of persons.

We consider it useful to first distinguish between the concepts of registration and identification, specifically in a forensic context. The term forensic registration, as defined in our legislation, specifically in the Guidelines on Conducting Forensic Registration and Identification of Persons and Unknown Remains (hereinafter: the Guidelines), in Article 2 is described as follows: "a procedure for obtaining identification markers (characteristics – legal, factual, and physical) for a person or remains, with the aim of their identification" (Guidelines on Conducting Forensic Registration and Identification of Persons and Unknown Remains, 2024).

Regarding the term forensic identification, many authors in the literature provide similar definitions. According to professor Vodinelić, the identification of persons entails: "determining all characteristics by which one person is distinguished from all others. These include: characteristics of a legal nature (name, surname); factual nature (date of birth,

place of birth, etc.); and physical characteristics (the personal appearance of the individual with their distinguishing features)” (Vodinelić, 1978).

In brief, registration involves the procedure of collecting/securing data about an individual, while identification involves the procedure of verifying/confirming the accuracy of that data.

We believe it is important to outline the legal bases under which law enforcement agencies (the police) undertake these actions. Specifically, the police are legally obligated to take measures and activities aimed at identifying the perpetrator of a criminal offense. Logically, to achieve this, it is necessary to know or establish their identity. To this end, the Criminal Procedure Law in Article 227 provides the following possibilities for the police: “When it is necessary for the purpose of establishing the identity of persons or objects, or in other cases relevant to successfully conducting the procedure, the judicial police may photograph the suspect, take fingerprints and palm prints, collect biological material for DNA analysis, and, with prior approval of the Public Prosecutor, publish their photograph. The judicial police may also collect samples from the suspect for DNA analysis”. (**Criminal Procedure Code** (2010) *Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia*, No. 150/2010)

The identification of the perpetrator of a criminal act is also mentioned as a concept in the Law on the Police. It is perhaps no coincidence that the first listed police jurisdiction in the Law is the verification and establishment of the identity of persons and objects. Regarding the establishment of identity, the Law in Article 40 states: “The identity of a person is established using methods and tools of criminalistic tactics and techniques, medical, or other appropriate expert examinations” (**Law on the Police**. (2006). *Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia*, No. 114/2006).

When it comes to the “methods and tools of criminalistic techniques,” these procedures primarily involve the methods and tools used by forensics, such as anthropometry (Bertillonage), dactyloscopy, mugshot photography, personal description, handwriting analysis, etc.

The development of science and the discovery of new possibilities for human identification have led to some of the aforementioned methods and tools being phased out of practice (e.g., Bertillonage). On the other hand, the discovery of the immense identification potential contained within the DNA molecule has opened new possibilities in forensic work, which in turn has led to the mandatory collection of biological material for DNA analysis.

In our country, the establishment of DNA databases began in 2011, and since that time, the collection of biological material has become a mandatory part of the registration of persons.

At the time of writing this paper, a transformation is underway regarding the method of fingerprint collection, specifically with the planned introduction of the new ABIS (Automated Biometric Identification System). Fingerprints are still collected using the traditional ink method, but in the upcoming period, the process is expected to be digitized through the use of LiveScan technology. The introduction of the ABIS system also includes changes to mugshot photography, which will be discussed in more detail in the following chapters.

1. CRIMINALISTIC REGISTRATION OF PERSONS

Theoretically, forensic registration (and identification) falls under the domain of criminalistic techniques (forensics). Specifically, the criminalist Jovanović states: “Criminalistic registration is a branch of criminalistic techniques that focuses on finding and refining the most suitable scientific-technical methods for registering persons, with the aim of their subsequent identification and the resolution of criminal cases” (Jovanović, 1981, p. 19).

This implies that registration should be understood as a step toward achieving the goal of an investigation, which is the identification of the perpetrator of a criminal act. It is generally known that forensics, as a science, applies discoveries from other sciences (natural or technical) to achieve its objectives. Throughout history, the scientific works of renowned scientists (biologists, anthropologists, etc.), particularly those related to human biometric characteristics, have immediately found application in forensics and, consequently, in our area of interest — forensic registration.

The renowned French criminalist Alphonse Bertillon (1853–1914), who worked for many years in the French police, made the first pioneering attempts to establish a system for registering persons based on scientific principles. According to Jovanović, it is worth noting that methods for registering offenders existed prior to this, but these were often brutal, primarily consisting of mutilation and branding. Bertillon based his registration system on the following assumptions: (Jovanović, 1981, p. 21)

- The human skeleton ceases to develop after the age of twenty, and its structure remains unchanged;
- Each person possesses strictly individual skeletal measurements, meaning no two individuals in the world have entirely identical skeletons; and
- By measuring specific parts of the body, a previously registered person can later be reliably identified.

Bertillon’s method, known as “Bertillonage”, was adopted in forensic work, particularly in the Paris police prefecture. Bertillon conducted measurements of various parts of the human body: arm length, head width, height, etc. These data were recorded on cards, which were later classified based on various criteria (age, gender, etc.). It was later scientifically proven that the basis of this system was flawed, as the human skeleton undergoes changes even after the age of twenty, creating room for the revision of this registration method. Nevertheless, the significance of Bertillonage is considerable, as it was the first attempt at forensic registration based on systematic scientific principles. In modern registration practices, the use of photography in three positions (mugshot photography), which Bertillon was the first to implement, is still employed. As a point of interest, it is worth mentioning that in our country, within the Forensic department unit in Bitola, a registration chair from Bertillon’s era is still in existence and use.

During his lifetime, Bertillon staunchly adhered to his method of work and was an opponent of introducing other registration methods. However, discoveries made in the field of individualizing human fingerprints began to find their place in forensic registration. Historically, the individual characteristics of the skin on human fingers were known to people as early as antiquity. However, a somewhat scientific approach to this field can be attributed to the publication of the works of the Italian anatomist Marcello Malpighi, who was the first to attempt to explain the concept of “papillae”. In this context, we would like

to highlight the definition provided in the Guidelines (Article 2): “Papillary lines are ridges on the surface layer of the skin present on the phalanges of the fingers (upper and lower parts for the thumb, and upper, middle, and lower parts for the other fingers), palms, toes, and soles of the feet”.

Many scientists have contributed to the study of fingerprints, and the works of Purkinje and William Herschel are worth mentioning. However, the pioneering step in this field was taken by Sir Francis Galton, who viewed fingerprints through the lens of their identification value. It is also essential to mention Juan Vucetich, who developed a system for classifying papillary lines and introduced this system into the operations of the police department in Buenos Aires, Argentina. Gradually, this method, known as dactyloscopy, began to be applied in countries worldwide. The work with fingerprints is based on four scientifically verified and proven postulates:

- **Immutability** – The patterns of papillary lines are formed in the womb and remain unchanged throughout a person’s life;
- **Individuality** – The patterns of papillary lines on each finger have specific individual characteristics, and no two people in the world have identical fingerprints;
- **Classifiability** – Papillary line patterns can be grouped into several types and
- **Transferability** – Due to the anatomical characteristics of the skin, upon contact with an object, papillary line patterns can be transferred or imprinted onto that object.

Dactyloscopic data, or fingerprints, are studied by a specific branch of forensics known as dactyloscopy. This field is further divided into several subcategories: cheiroscope (the study of papillary lines on the palms), pedoscope (the study of papillary lines on the soles of the feet), and poroscope (the study of the pores of papillary lines).

In our forensic practice, during the registration of persons, the traditional ink method for taking fingerprints is still used. According to the Guidelines, this method involves rolling each finger of both hands, from the right thumb to the left little finger, covering the entire lower phalanx and part of the middle phalanx of the fingers (or the entire lower phalanx and part of the upper phalanx for the thumbs), onto a surface coated with a thin layer of dactyloscopic ink. In addition to the ten fingers, impressions are also taken of the entire palm and the lateral “writing” side of the palm.

All measures in the fingerprint collection process are carried out by a trained professional – a forensic technician. The ink method requires the use of appropriate equipment, which includes: (Maksimović, 2000, p. 97)

- Special dactyloscopic ink;
- Flat plates, typically made of glass or metal;
- A rubber roller;
- Paper forms for dactyloscopy and
- Cleaning parts for the hands after fingerprinting.

Based on field experience, we would like to highlight several situations that may arise during the process. Specifically, care must be taken to ensure that the person’s hands are clean and free of any contaminants. A common mistake is the mixing up of hands,

meaning that fingerprints from the right hand are mistakenly rolled onto the section of the card designated for the left hand.

All fingerprints are taken on appropriate forms, specifically dactyloscopic cards, which are later sent to the Department for Forensic Examinations (hereinafter, DFE), where the fingerprints are stored in the records.

The introduction of the new ABIS system brings several changes regarding dactyloscopy, including the digital collection of fingerprints via LiveScan and a reduction in the documentation associated with the ink method. This undoubtedly improves the quality of the fingerprints themselves and enables their immediate network-based retrieval. The second change pertains to the collection of fingerprints from the fingertips. Currently, the ABIS system does not offer the option to collect these digitally via LiveScan; instead, they must be taken on paper and subsequently scanned into the system. This approach expands the database and increases the likelihood of positive identification by matching stored papillary line traces from unknown perpetrators.

The second part of registration, as mentioned earlier, involves photography, specifically mugshot photography introduced by Alphonse Bertillon. This consists of photographing the registered person in three positions:

- Frontal (en face) – the face is photographed from the front;
- Right profile and
- Left semi-profile.

The purpose of these three positions is to capture the appearance of the face, adhering to several rules. In the frontal photograph, the face must not have any aids or accessories. Such items should be visible in the left semi-profile photograph. Additionally, the right-profile photograph must include the name of the organizational unit where the person is registered and display the corresponding dactyloscopic number. Registration photographs are, by rule, scaled photographs produced at a 1:10 ratio to allow for the calculation of dimensions of specific facial features.

The aspect of calculating facial dimensions is retained in the ABIS system's photography process. The software itself offers the capability to biometrically process the photograph and compare it with unknown individuals. It must be noted that, at the time of writing, this feature is still in an experimental phase, and we do not have data on its successful functionality.

The third part, the collection of reference biological material, pertains to obtaining material that can later be used for DNA analysis. According to Article 2 of the Guidelines, any biological material of human origin (blood, tissue, hair, and other bodily fluids) is considered a sample for DNA analysis. In practice, during the registration of a person, the reference (undisputed) biological material is collected by taking a swab from the oral cavity using specialized forensic collectors. If it is not possible to obtain an oral swab from the individual, the biological material may be collected in another form (e.g., blood or hair). Obtaining a DNA profile is of significant forensic importance, as it provides the opportunity to conduct DNA analysis with biological traces found at the crime scene for which no identification has yet been established.

To conclude this section, we would like to highlight two practical situations that arise during the registration of persons. First, it is increasingly common in practice for individuals to refuse to undergo registration. The reasons for this can vary widely, including distrust of the police, fear of potential misuse of the material, and so forth. In

such cases, the Public prosecutor, upon the request of the police, issues an order mandating the individual to cooperate with the police. This prolongs the procedure, and there are frequent instances where, even with an issued order, individuals continue to refuse registration.

The second observation, based on our experience, is one we believe would be beneficial to include in the official materials (forms) used during registration. It is well-known that identical twins share the same DNA structure. Therefore, we propose that during the forensic registration process, there should be a form indicating whether the individual has an identical twin. This would provide valuable information that could be useful in the subsequent identification process.

2. FORENSIC IDENTIFICATION OF PERSONS

The processes of forensic registration and identification are closely interconnected. However, the identification method can also stand alone. In practice, it is possible to identify persons or objects that are not previously registered in the databases of investigative authorities. In such cases, this is referred to as direct identification. Here, identification is conducted by comparing a found trace (e.g., a fingerprint) with a sample taken from an individual at the time, for whom no prior data exists in the databases of registered persons. The other type, indirect identification (which is more commonly used in practice), involves the identification of characteristics (papillary lines, DNA samples) previously collected by investigative authorities through the forensic registration process and stored in various databases, such as dactyloscopic collections.

It is important to note that identification, in a general sense, is a procedure used to establish the sameness or similarity between two “objects” and is applied in various natural sciences, each with its own specific methods of proof. In criminalistics, or more precisely in forensics, the subjects of identification may include persons, remains, or objects. In the first two cases, these are human beings who possess unique characteristics that distinguish each individual from all others. The discovery of the uniqueness of these characteristics is a process that has spanned centuries in science, with many scientists contributing to it. We believe this process is not fully complete even today and that, in addition to the existing characteristics used, there is room for the discovery and introduction of new ones. Terminologically, these characteristics (in humans) that enable identification are referred to as identification markers. In forensics, three types of identification markers are used to establish a person’s identity: (Maksimović, 2000, p. 77)

- **Legal markers:** Characteristics acquired by an individual based on existing legal regulations, such as personal name, citizenship, etc.
- **Factual markers:** Characteristics acquired by an individual at birth (or death), such as date and place of birth.
- **Physical markers:** Characteristics related to gender, physical appearance, the pattern of papillary lines, etc.

Methodologically, the primary approach in identification is the process of comparison, and it can be concluded that identification involves comparing these three types of markers to establish their authenticity. This means that forensic identification is the process of verifying the authenticity of a person’s legal, factual, and physical markers.

The focus of our paper is so-called indirect identification, which is based on markers previously collected in specialized registration databases and does not require the physical presence of the identification subject during the process. According to the author Maksimović, this type of identification can be divided into three subgroups: (Maksimović, 2000, p. 82)

- Identification based on personal description, photograph, or photo-robot;
- Identification based on papillary lines and
- Identification based on DNA samples.

We will attempt to briefly explain each subgroup individually, as this classification is also adhered to in our Guidelines.

The first group, identification based on personal appearance/description, is the least reliable type of identification due to potential changes in physical appearance. Nevertheless, it remains one of the most commonly used methods in forensic fieldwork, particularly in recent years, primarily due to the increased presence of surveillance cameras in facilities where criminal acts occur. It is rare to find a company or commercial space without surveillance cameras, and there is a growing trend of installing such cameras in private homes as well. For these reasons, identifying or recognizing a potential perpetrator based on their physical appearance has become a daily practice in forensic work.

Individual physical markers, such as scars, moles, tattoos, and similar features, can play a significant role in this type of identification. Therefore, it is crucial to record these markers during the registration process.

In our opinion, this subgroup of identification also includes identification based on forensic (mugshot) photography. Photography is important because it captures the physical appearance of the individual, particularly details such as hair and eye colour. In practice, photographs of specific dimensions are used, and a recent development in this area is the introduction of digital photography with the ABIS system. Digital photography enables biometric comparison of an individual's physical appearance with footage of unknown perpetrators stored in the Department for Forensic Examinations (DFI).

The second subgroup, identification based on papillary lines, is also known in the literature as papillary identification. The core of this identification lies in detecting the ridges on the skin, known as papillae, and their arrangement. Papillae are most densely distributed on the fingers, palms, and soles. Papillary lines form so-called "papillary line patterns", which have been proven to be unique for each finger of every human being, even differing between identical twins. Research by scientists in this field has confirmed the four premises about papillary lines mentioned earlier (immutability, individuality, classifiability, and transferability). The methodology used for the identification of papillary lines in the Republic of North Macedonia is the so-called ACE-V methodology, an acronym for Analysis, Comparison, Evaluation, and Verification. These are the four phases that every papillary line trace undergoes in the OFI laboratories.

Fingerprints from registered individuals are directly entered into the databases. The shortcomings of the previous model, as identified by Божинов (2019), highlight several methodological limitations, first with the previous ink-based fingerprinting method, it was necessary to first digitize the prints from the cards before entering them into the AFIS (Automated Fingerprint Identification System). By entering fingerprints into the databases, it becomes possible to compare them with papillary line traces found during a

crime scene investigation, enabling positive identification. For positive identification between two papillary line samples, the OFI uses a numerical method that involves matching 12 characteristics between the samples.

The introduction of the ABIS system will streamline the identification process, primarily because fingerprints will be collected using a LiveScan scanner during registration and immediately converted into digital form. This allows them to be instantly entered into the databases of registered persons, enabling the system to check whether an individual with such fingerprints already exists in the database. Consequently, this will shorten the procedure and significantly reduce the use of paper (or paperwork).

The final subgroup for identification is identification based on DNA material. This is the most recent method of identification, with its application beginning in the late 1980s in the United Kingdom and the United States. According to the Guidelines, the term DNA is defined broadly as: “genetic material specific to each human individual and the carrier of heredity”.

As noted in recent research (Коцевска, 2018): “Every individual inherits genetic material from their parents. During the fertilization process, the egg and sperm combine to create a new individual. This new individual has two copies of genetic material — one from the mother and one from the father”.

A detailed and authoritative exposition of the structure of the DNA molecule is presented by the author Данилова (Данилова, 2017). She says that – “An exception in DNA identification exists with identical twins, who share the same DNA structure. DNA molecules are present in every cell of the human body. The structure of DNA consists of two parallel strands or helices containing three groups of atoms: sugars, phosphorus, and nitrogen. Nitrogen binds to sugar, and four nitrogenous bases are distinguished: adenine (A), thymine (T), cytosine (C), and guanine (G). The entire process of DNA identification is based on the combinations formed by these four nitrogenous bases in the DNA sequence. Specifically, the order in which the nitrogenous bases alternate in the sequence is unique to each human individual, except in the case of identical twins”.

Simply put, to identify an individual, it is necessary to observe a specific number of base sequences that repeat along the DNA strand.

We believe it is useful to note that DNA analysis is performed on samples of biological origin (blood, tissue, saliva, hair, and other bodily fluids). The repetitions of these sequences are then subjected to statistical interpretation, which expresses the probability of such repetition occurring in the entire population.

Regarding DNA identification, the Department for Forensic Examinations (DFE) follows the recommendations of ENFSI (European Network of Forensic Science Institutes), which are incorporated into the legal text of the Guidelines. In this regard, specialized collectors meeting the latest standards in the field have been introduced for use during fieldwork registration.

To conclude the section on DNA identification, we would like to elaborate on a procedure that was in place at DFE until 2012. Specifically, if a positive identification was made based on biological material (DNA analysis), the identity of the identified person was determined solely based on the data provided by the organizational unit that submitted the material. This approach left room for numerous errors, as the registered individual could intentionally (or unintentionally) provide incorrect information about themselves. This practice was changed with the introduction of the Guidelines for Registration of Persons in 2014, which introduced the Identity Verification Form. This form provided an option for collecting two fingerprints (left and right index fingers), and if the individual did

not possess identification documents, it was mandatory to submit an extract from the birth registry along with the registration material sent to DFE.

The introduction of this form also changed the way identity verification was conducted between departments within DFE. Specifically, the identity of a person positively identified through DNA analysis undergoes a phase of so-called “cross” identification, where a comparative analysis is performed between the fingerprints submitted on the relevant form for identity verification and the individual’s dactyloscopic card. Essentially, this involves verifying the registration data held by the Dactyloscopy Department and the DNA Analysis Department. If there is any discrepancy in the data, a comparison is made with the data collected during the procedure for obtaining personal (biometric) documents, i.e., the IMAGO system.

It is worth noting that this working model has been retained in the new Guidelines for Registration from January 2024. With this model, DFE eliminates the possibility of errors in identity verification, making it one of the leading forensic institutes in this part of Europe in this field.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have attempted to theoretically elaborate on the processes of forensic registration and identification and to highlight the challenges encountered during their implementation in forensic fieldwork in our country. The importance of this aspect of forensics is immense, as failure to establish the identity of a suspect could lead to significant oversights in an investigation, potentially altering its course and resulting in the most undesirable outcome — such as an innocent person being imprisoned.

Our focus was directed toward two processes that began implementation this year: the newly adopted Guidelines and the introduction of the ABIS system into the forensic practices of the organizational units for criminalistic techniques in the country, as well as in the DFE.

The legal provisions related to this issue must be clear and unambiguous. In this regard, our aim was to terminologically clarify the concepts contained in the Guidelines and to point out shortcomings. In particular, we believe that further attention should be given to the increasing number of individuals who refuse to provide their personal information for registration during the process.

The challenges of implementing the ABIS system are significant. This entails replacing the previous ink-based dactyloscopy method with a new, so-called digital fingerprint, which undoubtedly represents a step forward in our forensic practice. However, we would like to emphasize that for the quality implementation of such a step, a longer testing period is necessary. We believe that the more thorough the system testing, the less room there will be for errors once the system becomes fully operational.

In conclusion, we would like to state that these two processes are part of the Ministry of Internal Affairs’ efforts to introduce operational standards that align with those of European countries (police forces) in this field.

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NARKOTIC SUBSTANCES AND THEIR ABUSE AMONG HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Given the dynamics and spread of this criminal and negative social phenomenon, which is essentially highly harmful and destructive and commonly referred to as “DRUGS”, I feel a moral responsibility, both as a parent and as a citizen, to address this phenomenon more comprehensively and to act in ways that can contribute to its reduction among younger generations.

The major problems it creates, in both medical and legal terms, represents one of the greatest challenges faced by countries worldwide today, as well as a significant issue in terms of prevention in all its possible forms through organized action.

The abuse of narcotic substances not only harms the individual who uses them but also affects the society where the user lives, often transforming users into individuals with high criminal potential in their efforts to obtain narcotic drugs.

The spread of this phenomenon among young people is the primary motive for addressing this topic, with the aim of highlighting findings that may help competent authorities gain a clearer understanding of where and by which methods they should intervene in order to act both preventively and repressively towards users and drug dealers who profit significantly from this activity. Through this research, I aim to contribute, in some measure, to the work of competent institutions and to raise awareness among high school students, encouraging the development of attitudes that may lead to preventive action against drug use.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing prevalence and expansion of the phenomenon known as “drugs” – a deeply harmful and socially destructive issue – has prompted a strong sense of moral responsibility in me, both as a parent and as a citizen. This responsibility compels us to address the issue more comprehensively and to take proactive steps toward its eradication, particularly among younger generations.

The multifaceted problems associated with drug abuse, both from medical and legal perspectives, have emerged as one of the most pressing global challenges. The complexity of preventing drug abuse in all its forms requires a coordinated and systematic approach. The misuse of narcotic substances not only harms the individual user but also has a broader societal impact. Users often become individuals with high criminal potential, driven by the need to obtain these substances at any cost.

The alarming spread of drug use among youth is the primary motivation for undertaking this research. The aim is to identify data and insights that can assist relevant institutions in gaining a clearer understanding of where and how to intervene. This includes both preventive and repressive measures, targeting not only users but also drug dealers who derive significant profit from this illicit trade.

1.1 Theoretical Framework of the Research Subject

Since ancient times, humans have used various plant-based substances such as opium, coca, and hashish – initially for medicinal purposes and later for their psychoactive effects. Until the 19th century, such practices were relatively rare in Western societies. However, during this period, chemists began to explore narcotics more systematically, defining their theoretical foundations, synthesizing them, and eventually producing other naturally occurring substances in laboratory settings.

These substances, which affect the human psyche, were included in pharmaceutical registries and became known by the term “*drug*” – a word that, during the Middle Ages, referred to products with harmful effects. Initially, the use of such substances spread within intellectual and literary circles (e.g., Baudelaire referred to them as “Artificial Paradises”). However, due to their toxicity, legislators were eventually compelled to prohibit both their trade and use, except in medically approved cases⁶¹.

Drug trafficking has since become one of the most widespread forms of organized crime, raising serious concerns globally, particularly in the United States and Europe. Eastern European countries are increasingly facing challenges related to the cultivation, trafficking, and consumption of narcotics. For instance, in August 2000, authorities in Venezuela seized the largest quantity of drugs in the country’s history.

In addition to drug imports, many countries are now grappling with the domestic cultivation of narcotic plants, especially cannabis. This trend is also evident in the Republic of North Macedonia, where the number of cannabis cultivation and processing facilities has increased significantly. While cannabis is often misused, its broader implications warrant a separate and detailed discussion. Across Europe, including Albania, there is a growing trend in cannabis cultivation, with Spain and the Netherlands among the leading producers on the continent⁶².

1.2 Subject of the Research

It would not be an exaggeration to state that “*drugs*” are widely perceived as a negative phenomenon within society, manifesting in various forms such as consumption, misuse of narcotic substances, and other psychoactive agents. According to global and international statistical data, millions of individuals are reported to use and abuse drugs, many of whom have developed a dependency on these substances.

Given the relevance and urgency of the issue, the subject of this research focuses on the types of drugs and their misuse among students at the Gostivar Secondary Medical School, located in the city of Gostivar. This harmful phenomenon continues to endanger societies worldwide and has now permeated local communities, schools, and cities – placing young people at significant risk. Alarming, even minors as young as 14 years old are reported to be frequent users of so-called “soft drugs” such as cannabis, which, despite its classification, can pose serious health risks when consumed excessively.

This study aims to explore:

- the types of narcotic substances being used;
- the underlying causes that drive individuals – particularly youth – to use these substances,
- the effects of drug consumption,

⁶¹ V. Latifi, *Criminalistics, Intelligence and the Use of Crime*, (pp. 185–186, Drug Smuggling), Prishtina, 2004.
⁶² V. Latifi, *Criminalistics, Intelligence and the Use of Crime*, (p. 183, Drug Smuggling), Prishtina, 2004.

- preventive strategies, and
- methods of rehabilitation and recovery.

1.3 Aim of the Research

One of the primary objectives of this research is to conduct a precise and comprehensive examination of this deeply concerning social phenomenon. The widespread presence of drug use and abuse is frequently reported in the media, with stories involving drug addicts, dealers, and, tragically, victims – many of whom are minors and adolescents.

This reality served as the primary motivation for selecting this topic. The study aims to:

- assess the number of users and consumers of narcotic substances;
- analyze the effects of drug use on individuals and society;
- highlight the severity of the issue; and
- promote preventive action among younger generations.

Ultimately, the goal is to contribute to awareness-raising efforts through educational materials such as brochures, flyers, and other outreach tools that can support prevention and early intervention.

1.4 General Hypothesis

Given the harmful consequences and broad societal impact of drug use and abuse, criminological literature rightly classifies drug addiction as a criminogenic factor. Individuals who consume narcotic substances and psychoactive drugs are often associated with a range of delinquent and criminal behaviors.

Therefore, the general hypothesis of this research is:

Preventing the use of narcotic substances can significantly reduce the incidence of criminal behavior and social harm associated with drug abuse.

This hypothesis serves as the foundation for the study, guiding the analysis of the relationship between drug use and criminal activity, particularly among youth.

1.5 Specific Hypotheses

In support of the general hypothesis, the following specific hypotheses are proposed:

- A significant number of drug addicts engage in various forms of criminal activity. Individuals involved in the sale and distribution of narcotics often play a direct role in encouraging youth and minors to experiment with drugs.
- Drug-related criminality is a contemporary phenomenon characterized by its scale, professionalism, and the organized nature of smuggling networks.
- Organized crime, as one of the most serious criminal threats in modern history, manifests across multiple domains – most notably in drug trafficking and related criminal enterprises – driven by the pursuit of substantial financial profit.
- The psychological and behavioral effects of narcotic substances vary depending on the type of drug used. Drug-dependent individuals often exhibit emotional immaturity, passivity, depression, and, in some cases, aggression or violent tendencies.
- Statistical data indicate that drug use and addiction among minors is particularly pronounced in countries such as Russia and Ukraine, where millions of cases have been recorded, including those involving hard drugs.

- Young people with behavioral disorders, those affected by poverty, social and familial instability, or mental health challenges represent the most vulnerable groups and are at heightened risk of drug use and victimization.
- Drug use significantly influences youth behavior, contributing to increased aggression and a range of other social and psychological problems in everyday life.

1.6 Research Methodology

This research employs a combination of scientific methods to ensure a comprehensive and reliable analysis of drug use among high school students. The following methodologies will be applied:

- Content Analysis – to examine existing literature, media reports, and institutional documents related to drug use and prevention.
- Comparative Method – to compare findings across different contexts or demographic groups.
- Case Study Analysis – to explore individual instances of drug use and their broader implications.
- Descriptive Method – to present and interpret data in a clear and structured manner.
- Historical Method – to trace the evolution of drug use and its societal impact over time.
- Survey Method – to collect primary data through questionnaires administered to students.
- Interview Method – to gather qualitative insights from educators, law enforcement, and appropriate, students.
- Statistical Method – to analyze quantitative data and identify patterns or correlations.

In applying these methods, both qualitative and quantitative research techniques will be utilized to ensure a holistic understanding of the issue.

1.7 Expected Results

The expected outcomes of this research are centered on providing a clearer understanding of the harmful effects associated with the use and abuse of narcotic substances. By analyzing the specific context of the Gostivar Secondary Medical School, located within the jurisdiction of the Gostivar Police Station and the Tetovo Regional Police Department, the study aims to generate findings that can be directly communicated to the relevant authorities.

These results are intended to:

- highlight the extent of drug use among high school students in the region;
- identify the most commonly used substances and the factors contributing to their use;
- offer insights into students' awareness and attitudes toward drug-related risks;
- support the development of preventive and, where necessary, repressive measures by law enforcement and educational institutions.

Ultimately, the findings are expected to serve as a foundation for more targeted and effective interventions aimed at reducing drug use among youth and strengthening institutional responses.

2. UNDERSTANDING NARCOTICS

2.1 Definition of Narcotics

Before delving into the topic of narcotics, it is essential to define and categorize the various types of substances commonly referred to as drugs. While many definitions exist, not all drugs are necessarily intoxicating. For the purposes of this study, the following definition is adopted:

Narcotics are natural or synthetic substances that primarily act on the central nervous system, initially producing pleasurable sensations but, with uncontrolled use, leading to dependency and causing harmful consequences for both the individual and society.

In scientific terms, any substance that alters one or more bodily functions when ingested is considered a drug or *pharmakon* – a Greek term meaning medicine, narcotic, or poison. The term “narcotic” is not a scientific classification but rather a social and legal label used to describe substances that induce temporary pleasure but are ultimately harmful to health.

Some drugs have a direct and profound effect on a person’s reactive mind. Substances such as marijuana, morphine, and heroin can intensely activate mental imagery from past experiences, often triggering painful or traumatic memories in a violent and destabilizing manner⁶³.

2.2 The Meaning of Drug Addiction and Its Main Characteristics

Drug addiction represents one of the most detrimental social phenomena, characterized by the persistent use and abuse of various narcotic substances. A drug addict not only endangers their own health and well-being but also poses a threat to future generations and society at large.

According to both national and international data, millions of individuals are currently using narcotics, with many others involved in their production and distribution. Prolonged drug use often leads to significant personality changes, a condition commonly referred to as the development of a “biochemical personality.”

Some of the most common behavioral and psychological characteristics of individuals suffering from drug addiction include:

- frequent mood swings;
- difficulty or inability to communicate;
- neglect of personal appearance and hygiene;
- lack of concentration and motivation;
- persistent dissatisfaction and secrecy;
- anxiety and insomnia;
- uncontrollable cravings for narcotics;
- aggressiveness and irritability;
- dishonesty toward family, friends, and employers;
- apathy toward surroundings and responsibilities;

⁶³ [http://www.surgeongeneral.gov/ US Department of Health and Human Services](http://www.surgeongeneral.gov/US%20Department%20of%20Health%20and%20Human%20Services); 2016

- social withdrawal and isolation;
- feelings of depression and guilt⁶⁴.

This section emphasizes the complex and multifaceted nature of drug addiction, highlighting its profound impact on an individual's mental, emotional, and social functioning.

2.3 Types of Narcotic Drugs and Substances

Narcotic substances, commonly referred to as drugs, can be classified based on their origin and their effects on the human body. They are generally divided into two main categories:

- natural drugs – substances derived directly from nature, such as plants;
- synthetic drugs – artificially produced substances, often manufactured in illegal laboratories.

According to various classifications, narcotic and psychoactive substances are further grouped into the following categories:

- narcotics;
- psychotropic and depressant substances;
- stimulants;
- hallucinogenic substances.

Some of the most commonly known and used narcotic substances include:

- opium
- morphine
- heroin
- codeine
- cocaine
- marijuana
- cannabis
- hashish
- LSD
- mescaline
- amphetamines, among others⁶⁵.

According to a brochure published by the Ministry of Health in collaboration with the Ministry of Internal Affairs titled *Drug Strategy*, cannabis is the most commonly used drug among the general population, especially among young people aged 15 to 34. Among those who reported drug use in the past year, ecstasy was the second most commonly used substance. Among individuals who used drugs in the past month, heroin ranked second after cannabis⁶⁶.

⁶⁴ <http://www.disintossicazionemetadone.com> – Personality of the Drug Addict, accessed on 23.02.2023

⁶⁵ R. Halili, *Criminology, Types of Intoxicating Drugs and Narcotic Substances*, Prishtina, 2005, p. 309

⁶⁶ National Drug Strategy of the Republic of North Macedonia 2021–2025 with Action Plan 2021–2023, p. 11.

2.4 Individual Characteristics of Drug Addicts

The personality and behavior of individuals addicted to drugs are often profoundly altered by the type and duration of substance use. Depending on the specific narcotic consumed, addicts typically exhibit a range of psychological and physical symptoms that distinguish them from non-users⁶⁷.

In general, drug addicts are described as:

- emotionally immature;
- socially withdrawn;
- lacking motivation or life goals;
- prone to depression, passivity, or, conversely, aggression and hostility.

Physically, they may show visible signs of drug use, such as:

- injection marks or skin infections;
- noticeable weight loss and physical weakness;
- poor hygiene and neglected appearance.

These individuals often isolate themselves from non-using peers and instead associate with others who share similar habits. In many countries, such individuals form groups or gangs, distancing themselves from mainstream society and often occupying abandoned or marginalized spaces.

Due to their dependency, they are highly susceptible to manipulation and may engage in criminal activities – even for minimal quantities of drugs – highlighting the vulnerability and desperation that addiction can create.

2.5 The Link Between Drug Addiction, Crime, and Prevention

In criminology, drug addiction is widely recognized as a criminogenic factor. A significant number of individuals who consume narcotic substances are also involved in various forms of criminal behavior. One of the most common offenses is drug distribution, which often includes the active recruitment of young people into drug use.

Drug addicts may also commit other crimes such as:

- theft and burglary;
- arms trafficking;
- organizing prostitution;
- acts of violence and kidnapping;
- extortion and public disorder.

These behaviors are frequently driven by the need to obtain drugs, often at any cost. The severity of these consequences has prompted societies to take action to curb the spread of drug addiction. Such efforts include the implementation of legal frameworks regulating the production, sale, and use of narcotic substances.

2.5.1 Report from the European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA)

A regional report by the EMCDDA highlights the increasing role of the Western Balkans in the trafficking of narcotics into the European Union. The region lies at the crossroads of several major drug trafficking routes, particularly for cannabis, cocaine, heroin, and synthetic drugs.

Key findings from the report include:

⁶⁷R. Halili, *Criminology, Individual Characteristics of Drug Addicts*, Prishtina, 2005, p. 312

- Criminal networks from the Western Balkans have become major players in the European drug market;
- The region's geographic position makes it a key transit zone, especially for heroin, which travels along the so-called "Balkan Route";
- Corruption and weak legal systems in some countries have facilitated the growth of drug trafficking;
- Cannabis cultivation is shifting from open fields to indoor facilities, with notable activity in Albania and other parts of the region;
- Cannabis remains the most commonly used drug, followed by cocaine;
- In North Macedonia, cannabis oil and extracts are particularly popular among youth (27% usage rate);
- Cocaine use is highest in Montenegro, especially in tourist and ski resort areas;
- The average retail price of cocaine in the region is around €76 per gram, with the lowest prices in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the highest in Serbia;
- The Balkan land route for heroin begins in Afghanistan and passes through Iran, Turkey, and the Western Balkans before reaching Western Europe.⁶⁸

These findings underscore the urgent need for coordinated regional and international efforts to combat drug trafficking and reduce drug-related harm.

2.6 Use of Narcotic Substances Among the General Population and Youth

The use of narcotic substances is steadily increasing both globally and locally, particularly among young people. In the Polog region of North Macedonia – including major cities such as Tetovo and Gostivar, as well as surrounding villages – the number of drug users has reached alarming levels.

Over the past 15 years, the Republic of North Macedonia has experienced a significant rise in drug abuse, largely due to rapid societal changes. Narcotic substances have become increasingly accessible, even to the youngest members of society. Alarming, experimentation with drugs now begins as early as the upper grades of primary school.

Commonly cited reasons for drug use among youth include:

- curiosity and the desire for new experiences;
- peer pressure and the need to fit in;
- the pursuit of pleasure or escape from daily monotony;
- coping with personal or family-related problems.

Several systemic issues contribute to this trend:

- parents, in pursuit of economic stability, often spend less time with their children;
- educators are overwhelmed by extensive academic programs;
- entertainment options for youth are limited, often restricted to cafés and nightclubs;
- preventive approaches in schools remain outdated and ineffective compared to global standards.

According to police records, the first registered drug users in North Macedonia appeared in 1990. By 1996, there were 314 registered users, a number that rose to 4,569 by the year 2000. This upward trend continued, reaching 8,345 registered users by the end of 2007.⁶⁹

⁶⁸ European Report on Drug Trafficking and Use in the Western Balkans: <https://www.klix.ba/vijesti/bih/ovo-je-evropski-izvjestaj-o-svercu-i-konzumaciji-droge-na-zapadnom-balkanu/221126001>

2.7 Human Rights and the Phenomenon of Drug Use

Human rights and fundamental freedoms originate from natural law and are not granted by the state. These rights are enshrined in the Constitution as the highest legal and political authority. As such, they form the foundation of freedom, peace, and justice, and are essential for ensuring the dignity and well-being of every individual.

*“Human rights are the cornerstone of liberty, peace, and justice, serving as a mechanism to enhance the status and role of individuals in society. They are universal and must be enjoyed by all in order to ensure a life with optimal and dignified living conditions.”*⁷⁰

The phenomenon of drug use poses a serious threat to these rights. It is a widespread and complex issue, with youth being the most vulnerable group. The consequences of drug abuse are often catastrophic, leading to the loss of human life and rendering individuals socially and economically unproductive due to the psycho-physical damage caused by substance use.

In families where drug use is present, chaos, conflict, and numerous problems tend to dominate. The consequences of drug abuse can be grouped into three main categories:

- consequences for the drug user – including health deterioration, psychological instability, and social isolation;
- consequences for the family – such as emotional distress, financial burden, and breakdown of relationships;
- consequences for the community or state – including increased crime rates, public health crises, and economic costs.

This section emphasizes that drug abuse is not only a personal or medical issue but also a profound violation of human rights, affecting individuals, families, and society as a whole.

3. RESEARCH COMPONENT

3.1 Methodological Clarification

Observing the struggles of today’s youth served as the primary motivation for conducting this research on drug use among high school students. The decision to explore this complex and sensitive issue was not accidental. As a member of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, I feel a strong moral and ethical responsibility to contribute to the fight against this phenomenon, with the ultimate goal of protecting future generations.

To ensure the research is grounded in reality and produces meaningful results, the study begins within my local community. The participants are adult students from the Gostivar Secondary Medical School, located in the city of Gostivar. With the support of their teachers, the students voluntarily agreed to participate in the survey and expressed the need for more initiatives addressing this issue.

3.2 Research Location

The research component of this study was conducted at the Gostivar Secondary Medical School in the city of Gostivar. The participants were adult students, with a total of 71 respondents taking part in the survey.

⁶⁹ <http://www.skopje.gov.mk.pdf>) – Local Strategies for Narcotic Substances, statistics on drug use in North Macedonia and Skopje, accessed on 10.01.2017

⁷⁰ Brochure in Macedonian: “Macedonia Without Drugs”, p. 24.

3.3 Gender

During the research process, a total of 71 students were surveyed. Of these:

- 18 were male;
- 53 were female.

This gender distribution reflects the nature of the school, which, being a medical institution, typically enrolls a higher proportion of female students. This demographic detail is particularly relevant when analyzing responses to subsequent survey questions.

3.4 Research Focus

The aim of this section was to understand how students perceive the issue of drug use. The survey explored:

- whether students are aware of what narcotic substances are;
- whether they have had any contact with such substances;
- what they believe the consequences of drug use are;
- what advice they would give to their peers to avoid drug use;
- what messages they would share to raise awareness and promote prevention.

3.5 Number of Questions in the Questionnaire

The survey consisted of eight questions, designed to assess students' knowledge, attitudes, and experiences related to narcotic substances. The questions were structured to be clear and accessible, allowing students to respond by selecting predefined options.

The questions included the following items:

- Age
- Gender
- How informed are you about narcotic substances?
- Which types of drugs do you know?
- If someone offered you a drug, would you be able to recognize it?
- Do you think you receive enough information from institutions about drugs?
- How common is drug use in secondary schools?
- What is your opinion on how to prevent this phenomenon?

3.6 Research Period

The research was conducted in December 2024, and all participants were adult high school students

Table 1 – Age of Surveyed Students

The table and chart illustrate the age distribution of the surveyed students. The data indicate that the majority of respondents are 18 years old, with only one student aged 19. This shows that the surveyed group is predominantly composed of students who have reached legal adulthood.

Table 2 – Gender of Surveyed Students

The table and chart present the gender distribution of respondents. As expected for a medical high school, the number of female students significantly exceeds that of male students. This is relevant when interpreting responses to the subsequent survey questions.

Table 3 – Awareness of Narcotic Substances

Majority of students indicated that they are only partially informed about narcotic substances. This suggests a need to enhance awareness not only of drugs themselves but also of their broader negative consequences. Improved education and targeted information campaigns could play an important role in prevention.

Table 4 – Types of Drugs Known

The responses reveal that a significant portion of students are familiar with various types of drugs. This level of awareness indicates exposure to information about narcotic substances and highlights the potential risk of contact within their environment.

Table 5 – Ability to Recognize a Drug if Offered

The results can be interpreted in two ways. On the one hand, students demonstrate awareness that narcotic substances are harmful, although the source of this knowledge remains unclear. On the other hand, this awareness suggests a reduces likelihood of being easily manipulated or drawn into drug use by others.

Table 6 – Institutional Information Availability

The results show divided opinions; however, most respondents reported receiving only partial information from institutions. This indicates a need for stronger engagement and more comprehensive educational efforts. Ideally, affirmative responses should dominate, which could be achieved through increased involvement of schools and relevant authorities.

Table 7 – Perceived Drug Use in Secondary Schools

The fact that most students believe narcotics are “partially” used in schools points to a serious issue. Only 18 respondents stated that drugs are not used, while the remainder acknowledged some level of use. This suggests the presence of drug-related activities within the school environment and indicates insufficient engagement by educators, school security, and law enforcement, all of whom should be actively addressing this issue both inside and outside the school premises.

Table 8 – Opinions on Prevention Methods

As shown in the chart, most respondents believe that increased activity by law enforcement represents the most effective preventive measure. Less emphasis was placed on educational lectures, while students showed minimal interest in prevention through social media and TV campaigns. Although all approaches are important, the findings indicate that students place the greatest trust in police involvement.

CONCLUSION

Addressing drug abuse and the misuse of narcotic substances is a delicate and highly complex matter. It is a deeply rooted societal problem that demands serious attention and systematic investigation. The objective of this research was to illuminate the reality of this phenomenon, enhance understanding of its nature, and emphasize the urgent need for action to reduce the number of users and victims.

While it may be unrealistic to claim that drug use can be completely eradicated – particularly given the speed at which it is spreading – it is certainly possible to contribute meaningfully to its reduction through collective effort, awareness and commitment. No problem is insurmountable when there is genuine will to address it.

The choice of this topic was driven by its growing visibility and relevance. The findings indicate that drug use among youth is far more widespread than commonly assumed. Behind this issue lies an entire hidden reality that many young people confront daily.

Factors such as excessive freedom, lack of parental supervision, and insufficient institutional engagement have created an environment in which youth are increasingly exposed to drugs. Without proper guidance, many young people remain vulnerable, while parents often lack insight into their children's social environments and daily activities.

Personal observations during the research process suggest a general lack of seriousness regarding this issue – both among students and within institutions. This is concerning for two main reasons:

- Many young people perceive drug use as a normal part of adolescence, without understanding its long-term consequences.
- Institutions often treat the problem as secondary, assuming that responsibility lies solely with parents.

However, schools, families, and law enforcement must work together in a coordinated and proactive manner. Only through joint efforts can the spread of drug use be effectively prevented and reduced.

This paper consists of two parts: theoretical and practical. The theoretical section examines drug abuse, its types, and its consequences. It clarifies that not all drugs are intoxicating, but all have harmful effects. It also outlines the characteristics of drug addicts and the criminogenic nature of drug dependency.

The practical section, based on survey data, confirms the presence of drug use in schools and that many students are aware of its dangers. However, the findings also highlight a lack of institutional engagement and a need for more effective preventive measures.

In conclusion, drug abuse is a destructive force affecting individuals, families, and society. It leads not only to addiction but also to criminal behavior. Therefore, it must be addressed with the seriousness it demands, through both preventive and repressive measures, in order to protect future generations.

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